

INTEGRATED CULTURAL RESOURCES MANAGEMENT PLAN 2017-2021

FORT BLISS

This Page Intentionally Blank

APPROVAL

MIKE HESTER
COL, AR
Commanding

9 Oct 17

Date

FOREWORD

This plan was prepared by the Fort Bliss Directorate of Public Works - Environmental Division, Conservation Branch. Contributors included Brian Knight, Former Chief of Conservation Branch, Sue Sitton, Archaeologist, Belinda Mollard, Archaeologist, Martha Yduarte, Archaeologist/Curator and Charlene Brown, Historical Architect. Major General Robert White is the Commanding General of Fort Bliss; Colonel Michael Hester is the Garrison Commander; and Vicki G. Hamilton is the Chief of the Environmental Division.

I. Table of Contents

FOREWORD	I
I. TABLE OF CONTENTS.....	II
II. LIST OF FIGURES.....	VI
III. LIST OF TABLES.....	VII
1.0 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	1
1.1 GENERAL INFORMATION.....	1
1.2 LEGAL FOUNDATION AND METHODS FOR ICRMP	2
1.3 ICRMP GOALS	3
1.4 STIPULATIONS.....	5
1.5 CULTURAL RESOURCES INVENTORY	6
1.6 IMPLEMENTING THE ICRMP	6
1.6.1 ICRMP ACTION PLAN.....	7
2.0 GENERAL INFORMATION	9
2.1 INTRODUCTION	9
2.2 GOALS AND OBJECTIVES.....	9
2.3 LOCATION.....	10
2.4 GEOGRAPHIC OVERVIEW	11
2.4.1 PHYSIOGRAPHY	11
2.4.2 STRATIGRAPHY.....	11
2.4.3 SOILS.....	13
2.4.4 CLIMATE.....	14
2.4.5 FAUNAL AND FLORAL COMMUNITIES	15
2.4.6 WATER RESOURCES.....	17
2.5 HISTORIC OVERVIEW	18
2.5.1 PREHISTORIC	18
2.5.2 PROTOHISTORIC (A.D. 1450 – 1659).....	26
2.5.3 HISTORIC.....	31
2.6 MISSION STATEMENT.....	44
2.6.1 PRESENT MISSION(S).....	44
2.7 MISSION ACTIVITIES THAT MAY AFFECT CULTURAL RESOURCES.....	45
2.7.1 ACTIVITIES LIKELY TO AFFECT ARCHAEOLOGICAL SITES	45
2.7.2 ACTIVITIES LIKELY TO AFFECT ARCHITECTURAL PROPERTIES.....	45
2.8 PROGRAM RESPONSIBILITIES	46
2.9 INSTALLATION COMMANDER AND CULTURAL RESOURCES MANAGER.....	46
2.9.1 GARRISON COMMANDER.....	46
2.9.2 CULTURAL RESOURCES MANAGER (CRM).....	46
2.10 USER GROUPS.....	46
2.10.1 1 ST ARMORED DIVISION	47
2.10.2 31 ST COMBAT SUPPORT HOSPITAL	47
2.10.3 32 ND ARMY AIR AND MISSILE DEFENSE COMMAND.....	47
2.10.4 402 ND FIELD ARTILLERY BRIGADE.....	47
2.10.5 5 TH ARMORED BRIGADE.....	47
2.10.6 93 RD MILITARY POLICE BATTALION.....	47
2.10.7 BRIGADE MODERNIZATION COMMAND.....	47
2.10.8 DIRECTORATE OF MOBILIZATION AND DEPLOYMENT	48

2.10.9	INSPECTOR GENERAL’S OFFICE.....	48
2.10.10	JOINT TASK FORCE NORTH.....	48
2.10.11	MARINE CORPS DETACHMENT	48
2.10.12	UNITED STATES ARMY SERGEANTS MAJOR ACADEMY	48
2.10.13	WILLIAM BEAUMONT ARMY MEDICAL CENTER	48
2.10.14	GARRISON COMMAND	49
2.10.15	DIRECTORATE OF HUMAN RESOURCES	49
2.10.16	DIRECTORATE OF LOGISTICS.....	49
2.10.17	DIRECTORATE OF MORALE, WELFARE AND RECREATION.....	49
2.10.18	DIRECTORATE OF PLANS, TRAINING, MOBILIZATION AND SECURITY	49
2.10.19	DIRECTORATE OF PUBLIC WORKS.....	49
2.10.20	NETWORK ENTERPRISE CENTER	50
2.10.21	EQUAL EMPLOYMENT OPPORTUNITY.....	50
2.10.22	PUBLIC AFFAIRS OFFICE	50
2.10.23	MISSION INSTALLATION CONTRACTING COMMAND	50
2.10.24	OFFICE OF THE CHAPLAIN.....	50
2.10.25	OFFICE OF THE STAFF JUDGE ADVOCATE	50
2.10.26	SAFETY OFFICE.....	51
2.10.27	ARMY AND AIR FORCE EXCHANGE SERVICE	51
2.10.28	BANKING AND CREDIT UNION FACILITIES	51
2.10.29	UNITED STATES CUSTOMS AND BORDER PROTECTION	51
2.10.30	UNITED STATES POSTAL SERVICE.....	51
2.10.31	UNITED STATE VETERAN’S ADMINISTRATION.....	51
2.10.32	FEDERAL PRISON	51
2.10.33	FORT BLISS MUSEUM AND STUDY CENTER	52
2.10.34	EL PASO INDEPENDENT SCHOOL DISTRICT	52
2.10.35	GERMAN AIR FORCE AIR DEFENSE SCHOOL.....	52
2.10.36	BALFOUR BEATTY MILITARY HOUSING.....	52
2.11	INTERESTED PARTIES	52
2.11.1	ADVISORY COUNCIL ON HISTORIC PRESERVATION.....	53
2.11.2	BUREAU OF LAND MANAGEMENT	53
2.11.3	EL PASO COUNTY HISTORICAL COMMISSION	53
2.11.4	EL PASO COUNTY HISTORICAL SOCIETY, INC.....	53
2.11.5	EL PASO HISTORICAL LANDMARK COMMISSION	54
2.11.6	EL PASO PRESERVATION ALLIANCE.....	54
2.11.7	COMANCHE NATION OF OKLAHOMA.....	54
2.11.8	FORT SILL APACHE TRIBE OF OKLAHOMA.....	54
2.11.9	PUEBLO OF ISLETA.....	54
2.11.10	KIOWA TRIBE OF OKLAHOMA.....	54
2.11.11	YSLETA DEL SUR PUEBLO (TIGUA).....	55
2.11.12	MESCALERO APACHE TRIBE.....	55
2.11.14	PRESERVATION TEXAS.....	55
2.11.15	STATE HISTORIC PRESERVATION OFFICER.....	55
2.11.16	UNITED STATES DEPARTMENT OF AGRICULTURE-FOREST SERVICE.....	55
2.11.17	NEW MEXICO HERITAGE PRESERVATION ALLIANCE.....	56
3.0	LEGAL FOUNDATION AND METHODS FOR ICRMP	58

3.1 FEDERAL CULTURAL RESOURCES LAWS (WITH ACTION ITEMS) 58

 3.1.1 NATIONAL HISTORIC PRESERVATION ACT OF 1966, AS AMENDED. 58

 3.1.2 THE NATIVE AMERICAN GRAVES PROTECTION AND REPATRIATION ACT OF 1990..... 63

 3.1.3 THE ARCHAEOLOGICAL RESOURCES PROTECTION ACT OF 1979 64

 3.1.4 36 CFR PART 79 CURATION OF FEDERALLY-OWNED AND ADMINISTERED
 ARCHAEOLOGICAL COLLECTIONS..... 65

4.0 STANDARD OPERATING PROCEDURES 67

4.1 STANDARD OPERATING PROCEDURE #1: COMPLIANCE WITH ARCHAEOLOGICAL RESOURCES
 PROTECTION ACT OF 1979 68

 4.1.1 APPLICABILITY 68

 4.1.2 OBJECTIVE..... 68

 4.1.3 POLICY 68

 4.1.4 IMPLEMENTING PROCEDURES 68

4.2 STANDARD OPERATING PROCEDURE #2: COMPLIANCE WITH THE NATIVE AMERICAN GRAVES
 PROTECTION AND REPATRIATION ACT OF 1990 (THIS SOP IS SUBJECT TO REVISION PENDING
 COMPLETED COMPREHENSIVE AGREEMENT)..... 76

 4.2.1 APPLICABILITY AND OBJECTIVE 76

 4.2.2 DEFINITIONS..... 76

 4.2.3 POLICY 78

 4.2.4 IMPLEMENTING PROCEDURES 78

 4.2.5 DISPOSITION PLAN..... 83

 4.2.6 NOTICE OF DISPOSITION 86

4.3 STANDARD OPERATING PROCEDURE #3: NATIVE AMERICAN CONSULTATION UNDER THE
 NATIONAL HISTORIC PRESERVATION ACT (THIS SOP IS SUBJECT TO REVISION PENDING
 COMPLETION OF A TRIBAL MEMORANDUM OF AGREEMENT- IN DRAFT AND CONSULTATION
 AT THE TIME OF THIS ICRMP) 88

 4.3.1 APPLICABILITY 88

 4.3.2 OBJECTIVE..... 88

 4.3.3 POLICY 88

 4.3.4 IMPLEMENTING PROCEDURES 90

4.4 STANDARD OPERATING PROCEDURE #4: IDENTIFYING CONSULTING PARTIES..... 96

 4.4.1 APPLICABILITY 96

 4.4.2 OBJECTIVE..... 96

 4.4.3 POLICY 96

 4.4.4 IMPLEMENTING PROCEDURES 96

4.5 STANDARD OPERATING PROCEDURE #5: CURATORIAL AND COLLECTION MANAGEMENT OF
 ARCHAEOLOGICAL AND HISTORICAL COLLECTIONS AND ASSOCIATED RECORDS..... 98

 4.5.1 APPLICABILITY 98

 4.5.2 OBJECTIVE..... 98

 4.5.3 COLLECTION POLICY 99

 4.5.4 IMPLEMENTING PROCEDURES 100

5.0 CULTURAL RESOURCES INVENTORY 110

5.1 LITERATURE REVIEW 110

 5.1.1 SUMMARY OF INVESTIGATIONS 110

 5.1.2 PUBLISHED INVESTIGATIONS 113

5.2 ARCHAEOLOGICAL SITES 113

5.2.1 ARCHAEOLOGICAL SITE PROTECTION MEASURES 121

5.3 HISTORIC SITES..... 126

6.0 IMPLEMENTING THE ICRMP..... 132

6.1 THE GARRISON COMMANDER’S ROLE 132

6.1.1 ANNUAL REVIEW OF THE ICRMP..... 132

6.2 CULTURAL RESOURCES MANAGER’S ROLE 133

6.2.1 NHPA TITLE 54 U.S.C. 306101 THROUGH 306114 (FORMERLY SECTION 110) 133

6.2.2 NHPA SECTION 106..... 133

6.2.3 CONSULTATION WITH NATIVE AMERICANS 133

6.2.4 CULTURAL RESOURCES EDUCATION PROGRAM..... 134

6.2.5 MANAGEMENT RESPONSIBILITIES..... 134

6.3 ICRMP ACTION PLAN 134

6.3.1 ICRMP GOALS..... 134

6.3.2 ACTION PLAN SCHEDULE 136

7.0 REFERENCES CITED 155

APPENDIX A: PROGRAMMATIC AGREEMENT A-1

APPENDIX B: ACRONYMS AND DEFINITIONS B-1

APPENDIX C: EXEMPTED UNDERTAKINGS C-1

APPENDIX D: IDENTIFYING AND EVALUATING PROPERTIES D-1

APPENDIX E: RECORD OF HISTORIC PROPERTIES CONSIDERATION..... E-1

APPENDIX F: AREA OF POTENTIAL EFFECT..... F-1

APPENDIX G: FLOWCHART – INADVERTENT DISCOVERY PROCEDURES..... G-1

APPENDIX H: STANDARD MITIGATION MEASURES..... H-1

APPENDIX I: ARCHAEOLOGICAL REPORT LISTING I-1

APPENDIX J: HISTORIC PROPERTIES: TABLES AND MAPS J-1

II. List of Figures

FIGURE 1.1: CAPTAIN GEORGE RUHLEN, QUARTERMASTER CORPS, SUPERVISED THE CONSTRUCTION OF FORT BLISS IN 1889.	1
FIGURE 1.2: FORT BLISS IN 1929.	10
FIGURE 2.1: AERIAL PHOTO OF MADERA QUEMADA PUEBLO, DOÑA ANA RANGE, FORT BLISS, NEW MEXICO.	25
FIGURE 2.2: POSSIBLE DEFENSIVE WALL.	30
(FROM SEYMOUR 2002)	30
FIGURE 2.3: BUNKHOUSE AT DON LEE’S RANCH.	33
FIGURE 2.4: OFFICERS’ ROW ALONG PRESENT DAY SHERIDAN ROAD, LATE 1880S.	38
FIGURE 2.5: PANCHO VILLA (CENTER) WITH GENERAL PERSHING (RIGHT) 1914.	39
FIGURE 2.6: CAMP COTTON 1916.	39
FIGURE 2.7: AERIAL OF FORT BLISS, 1934.	41
FIGURE 2.8: NIKE TRAINING, LATE 1950S.	43
FIGURE 2.9: BUILDING 1094. ELIGIBLE FOR INCLUSION IN THE NRHP AS THE UNIVERSAL MISSILE TRAINING BUILDING, SAFEGUARD CENTRAL TRAINING FACILITY (1973-1975) ALONG WITH THE SILOS LOCATED ADJACENT, TO THE RIGHT.	44
FIGURE 5.1: ENTRANCE TO CEREMONIAL CAVE, FORT BLISS, TEXAS.	116
FIGURE 5.2: PICTOGRAPH OF STEPPED CLOUD AND MASK AT PICTURE CAVE, FORT BLISS, TEXAS.	117
FIGURE 5.3: RESULTS OF THE GROUND PENETRATING RADAR (GPR) AND MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY SURVEYS AT ESCONDIDA PUEBLO (FROM 2006 LUKOWSKI ET AL., <i>GROUND-TRUTHING REMOTE SENSING DATA AT THE ESCONDIDA SITE (LA 458), OTERO COUNTY, NEW MEXICO</i>).	117
FIGURE 5.4: CERRO ROJO SITE (FROM 2002 SEYMOUR, <i>CONQUEST AND CONCEALMENT</i>), FORT BLISS, TEXAS.	118
FIGURE 5.5: HOT WELL PUEBLO, AREA 1 (FROM 2005 LOWRY, <i>ARCHAEOLOGICAL INVESTIGATIONS OF THE HOT WELL AND SGT. DOYLE SITES, FORT BLISS, TEXAS</i>) FORT BLISS, TEXAS.	119
FIGURE 5.6: AERIAL PHOTO OF MADERA QUEMADA PUEBLO, DOÑA ANA RANGE, FORT BLISS, NEW MEXICO.	120
FIGURE 5.7: AERIAL PHOTO OF SACRAMENTO PUEBLO, OTERO COUNTY, FORT BLISS, NEW MEXICO.	121
FIGURE 5.8: OFF LIMITS AND LIMITED USE AREAS ACROSS THE NORTHERN MANEUVER AREAS, FORT BLISS.	123
FIGURE 5.9: OFF LIMITS AND LIMITED USE AREAS ACROSS THE SOUTHERN MANEUVER AREAS, FORT BLISS.	124
FIGURE 5.10: OFF LIMITS AND LIMITED USE AREAS ON MCGREGOR RANGE, FORT BLISS.	125
FIGURE 5.11: FORT BLISS MAIN POST HISTORIC DISTRICT WITH EARLY COLD WAR GUIDED MISSILE INSTRUCTION HISTORIC DISTRICT AREA A AND AREA B AND ASSOCIATED VIEW SHEDS	128

III. List of Tables

TABLE 1.1 CULTURAL RESOURCES LAWS, REGULATIONS, EXECUTIVE ORDERS AND GUIDELINES	2
TABLE 2.1 COMMON FLORA OF THE FORT BLISS AREA.....	15
TABLE 2.2 COMMON PREHISTORIC AND MODERN FAUNA OF FORT BLISS	17
TABLE 2.3 REGIONAL CULTURAL PERIODS AND ASSOCIATED DATES	18
TABLE 5.1 SIGNIFICANT ARCHAEOLOGICAL SITES ON FORT BLISS	114
TABLE 6.1 ACTION ITEM 16, PROJECTED COSTS FOR INVENTORY/SURVEY/EVALUATE, 2016-2020 (IN \$1000).....	140
TABLE 6.2 ACTION ITEM 17, PROJECTED PROJECT COSTS FOR MAINTENANCE, REPAIR, NEW CONSTRUCTION, AND RENOVATION OF HISTORIC PROPERTIES, 2016-2020.....	143
TABLE 6.3 ACTION ITEM 18, PROJECTED PROJECT COSTS FOR MONITORING/EDITING ICRMP/PA, 2016-2020 (IN \$1000).....	144
TABLE 6.4 ACTION ITEM 19, PROJECTED PROJECT COSTS FOR MITIGATION OF HISTORIC PROPERTIES, 2016-2020 (IN \$1000)	145
TABLE 6.5 ACTION ITEM 20, PROJECTED TRAINING COSTS FOR CULTURAL RESOURCES STAFF, 2016-2020 (IN \$1000).....	146
TABLE 6.6 ACTION ITEM 29, PROJECTED PROJECT COSTS FOR TRIBAL CONSULTATION, 2016-2020 (IN \$1000).....	148
TABLE 6.7 ACTION ITEM 32, PROJECTED PROJECT COSTS FOR CURATION, 2016-2020 (IN \$1000)	152

1.0 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The executive summary provides an overview of the Integrated Cultural Resources Management Plan (ICRMP) for Fort Bliss, Texas. It summarizes each section, explaining its purpose and how it relates to the cultural resources program, and provides an understanding of how the ICRMP works. The ICRMP has been prepared to meet requirements set by Army Regulation 200-1, Environmental Protection and Enhancement (AR 200-1) and Department of Defense Instruction (DoDI) 4715.16, Cultural Resource Management.

1.1 General Information

Fort Bliss and its surrounding area represent a landscape shaped by various forces over thousands of years. These include the erosional forces of climatic change, vegetational shifts, and the effects of human habitation. Evidence of this habitation includes prehistoric hunting camps and short and long-term residences, ranches, railroads and trails, late 19th century buildings, World War II buildings and structures, and Cold War buildings and structures. Human activities continue to shape the landscape through the various missions of Fort Bliss. These activities leave records on the landscape for future generations to manage. These records collectively form the present cultural landscape.

Prehistoric habitation of Fort Bliss began about 10,000 years ago and ended about 500 years ago. While there is speculation over a Pre-Clovis period (50,000 - 10,000 B.C.), prehistoric occupations in the area are known to include Paleoindian (10,000 – 6,000 B.C.), Archaic (6,000 B.C. – A.D. 200), Formative (A.D. 200 – 1450), Precontact (A.D. 1450 - 1581) and Protohistoric (A.D. 1580 – 1659) periods. The historic period began with the arrival of the Spanish in A.D.

Figure 1.1: Captain George Ruhlen, Quartermaster Corps, supervised the construction of Fort Bliss in 1889.

1581. The Spanish ruled the region from 1581 to 1821, when Mexico won its independence. The United States acquired the region from Mexico following the Mexican American War (1846-1848) through the 1853 Gadsden Purchase. Although El Paso del Norte became a commercial hub and halfway point along the Camino Real between Mexico City and Santa Fe, it was not until after the United States purchase that settlement expanded northward into the Tularosa Basin out of the Rio Grande drainage. The Army established its first post in the region in 1849 and moved to its present location on La Noria Mesa in 1893. The arrival of the railroads in 1881 marked an increase in El Paso's population. A few ranchers had moved into the region by the late 1860s and early 1870s, but the main ranches were formed shortly after the arrival of the railroads.

Mining has a long history in the region with the first mines recorded in the 1840s, although there are rumors of earlier lost Spanish mines. It was not until the settlement of the Mescalero Apache tribe on their reservation and the Wheeler Survey that mining activities

increased (late 1870s through the 1930s). Cultural resources reflecting these significant activities and periods have been recorded on lands managed by Fort Bliss. The present Fort Bliss landscape reflects influences of its initial establishment, the Punitive Expedition, the establishment of the Fort as a Cavalry post following the Punitive Expedition, World War II, as an air defense training facility, the Cold War, and its latest transformation into the home of the 1st Armored Division.

A body of laws has been passed to protect and preserve historic properties under the jurisdiction of Federal agencies. It is the Garrison Commander’s (GC) responsibility to ensure compliance with these laws and to implement the ICRMP. The GC will, through his appointed Cultural Resources Manager (CRM), coordinate activities with this ICRMP. It is the CRM’s responsibility to coordinate with users and interested parties to ensure compliance with cultural resources laws and regulations on Fort Bliss. The body of laws specifically addressed in this ICRMP is listed in the table below.

TABLE 1.1 CULTURAL RESOURCES LAWS, REGULATIONS, EXECUTIVE ORDERS AND GUIDELINES

Public Law 89-665	National Historic Preservation Act of 1966 (as amended)
Public Law 96-95	Archaeological Resources Protection Act of 1979
Public Law 101-601	Native American Graves Protection and Repatriation Act of 1990
32 CFR Part 229	Protection of Archaeological Resources
36 CFR Part 60	National Register of Historic Places
36 CFR Part 68	The Secretary of the Interior’s Standards for Preservation Projects
36 CFR Part 79	Curation of Federally-owned Archaeological Resources
36 CFR Part 800	Protection of Historic and Cultural Properties
43 CFR Part 10	Native American Graves Protection and Repatriation Regulations
48 CFR Part 44716	Archaeology and Historic Preservation: Secretary of the Interior’s Standards and Guidelines.
Executive Order 11593	Protection and Enhancement of the Cultural Environment (1971)
Executive Order 12555	Protection of Cultural Resources (1986)
Executive Order 13007	Indian Sacred Sites (1996)
Executive Order 13084	Consultation and Coordination with Indian Tribal Governments (1998)
Executive Order 13287	Preserve America (2003)
AR 200-1	Environmental Protection and Enhancement

1.2 Legal Foundation and Methods for ICRMP

Pursuant to AR 200-1, the GC is responsible for compliance with cultural resources laws on Fort Bliss. This section reviews the preservation laws applicable to Fort Bliss. It provides an analysis of Fort Bliss’ current preservation program with respect to these laws. This is the legal foundation for the ICRMP and a basis for establishing the action plan for the ICRMP.

The National Historic Preservation Act (NHPA) establishes a national program for historic preservation. Regulations and guidelines in this Act include Federal agency responsibilities and

consideration of effects of Federal undertakings on historic properties. These are outlined in Section 110 and Section 106 of the NHPA, respectively. The Native American Graves Protection and Repatriation Act (NAGPRA) provides for the disposition of Native American human remains, associated and unassociated funerary objects, and sacred objects and objects of cultural patrimony removed from Federal and tribal lands. NAGPRA requires consultation with Native American tribal entities with respect to disposition of cultural items discovered on Federal and tribal lands. The Archaeological Resources Protection Act (ARPA) protects archaeological resources that are 100 years of age or older on public lands. ARPA defines illegal activities and prescribes civil and criminal penalties for each infraction, establishes a permitting process for removal of archaeological resources from public lands and provides for the confidentiality of archaeological site location information.

Analysis of the current cultural resources management program on Fort Bliss shows that a number of actions must be taken during 2016-2020 to address concerns associated with each of the above laws. Action plans have been established to assist the GC in addressing these concerns and achieving compliance with the above laws. These are found in Section 6.3 ICRMP Action Plan.

Achieving and maintaining compliance with cultural resources laws requires an understanding of how to follow various cultural resources guidelines, carry out certain preservation activities, and meet specific requirements. Section 3.0 Legal Foundation and Methodology provides guidance on how to implement the action plan provided in Section 1.6 and carry out preservation activities required by stipulations and standard operating procedures (SOPs) provided in Section 4.0. The CRM will use this guidance to ensure compliance with cultural resources laws and regulations.

1.3 ICRMP Goals

DoDI 4715.16, Enclosure 6(1)(i), establishes procedures for compliance with Federal laws, regulations, and executive orders requiring the protection and/or management of cultural resources with the least possible effect on military training and mission support activities. During the life of this ICRMP, the following goals will direct the cultural resources program at Fort Bliss:

- Integrate cultural resources compliance requirements with other installation plans, including but not limited to the installation master plan, the facilities maintenance plan, training and range area management plans, natural resources management plans, mobilization and deployment plans, and information management systems.
- Maintain the historic fabric and character of buildings and landscapes contributing to the Fort Bliss historic districts.
- Seek ways to avoid, minimize and/or mitigate adverse effects on Historic Properties in concert with the execution of military training and support activities.
- Conduct data recoveries on National Register eligible properties under the attached Programmatic Agreement (PA), eliminating the necessity for an individual Memorandum of Agreement (MOA) on each project.

- Continue development of project manuals and handbooks for guiding treatment of historic buildings, structures and landscapes; and regular, systematic inventory and evaluation of these properties.
- Set priorities based on currently available information for the inventory and evaluation of cultural resources: (1) survey and NRHP evaluation of archaeological sites for eligibility to the National Register in all areas where military training has or is expected to have the greatest impact; (2) evaluation of any site with “undetermined” eligibility; and (3) identify mitigation methods for unavoidable adverse effects to historic properties.
- Give top priority to management of properties most at risk for adverse effects by the military mission.
- Use a system of internal controls for review of routine and mission-critical undertakings.
- Exempt from review undertakings that do not or are not likely to adversely affect cultural resources.
- Enforce Federal laws prohibiting the vandalism of cultural resources or illegal collection of archaeological materials on Fort Bliss and strengthen that effort with continued training and additional staff (as funding is available).
- Implement the existing plan to ensure management of archaeological collections relevant to cultural resources at Fort Bliss in compliance with 36 Code of Federal Regulations (CFR) Part 79.
- Make collections available for research by professionals, interested Indian tribes, and other members of the public at the Fort Bliss curatorial facility during normal duty hours.
- Establish and implement a management plan for currently endangered paper collections relating to historic structures, archaeology, cultural landscapes, and objects on Fort Bliss.
- Implement and enhance the public awareness program, including maintaining a mailing list and sending out brochures to interested parties detailing the findings of recently completed projects addressing cultural resources.
- Maintain cultural resources training opportunities for military and civilian personnel whose jobs or building occupancies have an influence on cultural resources.
- Establish realistic budgetary goals based on ongoing and future projects and available industry data.
- Ensure staff responsible for cultural resource management meet the Secretary of the Interior’s *Standards and Guidelines for Archeology and Historic Preservation*, (*Federal Register* Vol. 48, No. 190, pp. 44717–44742) and receive continuing training.
- Through the implementation of this ICRMP, develop an innovative program that may serve as a model for other Federal facilities; demonstrate the value of cultural resources management programs; and publicize and promote the commitment of Fort Bliss to programs.

1.4 Stipulations

Most cultural resources management activities can be carried out using a routine set of procedures. The Stipulations in Section 4.0 have been developed for such activities. Each Stipulation, SOP, or other guidance document identifies responsible parties, participants, and procedures. It is the GC's responsibility to ensure that all military and nonmilitary organizations on Fort Bliss coordinate their actions with the CRM to ensure compliance with NHPA, NAGPRA, ARPA and other applicable preservation laws. Twelve stipulations are addressed in a Programmatic Agreement (PA) among the Fort Bliss Garrison Command, the Advisory Council on Historic Preservation, and the New Mexico and Texas State Historic Preservation Offices (Appendix A). Additionally, there are seven (7) appendices to the PA that address exempted undertakings, identify and evaluate properties, and provide standard mitigation measures. These Stipulations and Appendices are listed below.

- Stipulation I: Project Review
- Stipulation II: Updates to the Significance Standards
- Stipulation III: Reporting Damage to Cultural Resources
- Stipulation IV: Notification and Involvement of Institutions and Interested Members of the Public
- Stipulation V: Broader Fort Bliss Outreach
- Stipulation VI: Inadvertent Discovery of Archaeological Sites
- Stipulation VII: Dispute Resolution
- Stipulation VIII: Annual Report
- Stipulation IX: Fiscal Requirement and Sources
- Stipulation X: Amendment
- Stipulation XI: Termination
- Stipulation XII: Duration of this PA
- Appendix A: Acronyms and Definitions
- Appendix B: Exempted Undertakings
- Appendix C: Identifying and Evaluating Properties
- Appendix D: Record of Historic Properties Consideration
- Appendix E: Map of the Area of Potential Effect
- Appendix F: Flowchart-Inadvertent Discovery Procedures
- Appendix G: Standard Mitigation Measures

These Stipulations will be distributed on Fort Bliss as the GC's Policy. In addition to the Stipulations provided in the PA, the following SOPs and guidance documents addressing other preservation laws and regulations are implemented by this ICRMP.

SOP #1:	Compliance with the Archaeological Resources Protection Act of 1979
SOP #5	Curatorial and Collection Management of Archaeological and Historical Collections and Associated Records
Draft MOA	MOA for Government-to-Government Consultation among Fort Bliss Garrison Command and the Federally-recognized Tribes with interests in lands managed by Fort Bliss in New Mexico and Texas

Draft CA Comprehensive agreement regarding inadvertent discovery and intentional excavation of Native American human remains and cultural items

1.5 Cultural Resources Inventory

To manage a resource successfully, it is first necessary to know the resource. The historic overview, presented in Section 2.5, provides a general summary of Fort Bliss' histories and an understanding of what cultural resources exist or might be found on the installation. This section provides an overview of investigations that have been completed, literature generated by the investigations, and the inventory of cultural resources resulting from such investigations. As of November 2015, there were over 20,600 archaeological sites and approximately 4,340 buildings and structures identified on Fort Bliss. Properties identified in this inventory listed in the National Register of Historic Places (NRHP) or eligible for listing in the NRHP consist of 3,567 archaeological sites and 507 eligible buildings and structures. An additional 55 historic buildings and structures have been determined noncontributing properties of the Fort Bliss Main Cantonment Historic District. One-hundred and fifty buildings and structures are located within historic view sheds. Properties listed in the National Register, determined eligible for listing in the National Register, or remain undetermined for the NRHP are subject to the historic preservation laws and this ICRMP.

1.6 Implementing the ICRMP

To implement this ICRMP the GC will complete the following actions:

- Initiate a review of the ICRMP with interested parties.
- Sign the ICRMP after comments have been addressed.

After the ICRMP has been reviewed and approved, the GC will take the following actions to ensure implementation:

- Designate a government employee and subject matter expert in cultural resources, as Cultural Resources Manager (CRM) (AR 200-1, 6-4(a)(3)) to ensure that:
 - Efforts to identify, evaluate, and treat historic properties consider the Secretary of the Interior's Standards and Guidelines for Archeology and Historic Preservation
 - Are conducted under the supervision of personnel who meet applicable professional qualifications for undertaking such work (AR200-1, 6-4(b)(5))
 - Provisions are made for enforcement of cultural resource laws and regulations by professionally trained personnel (DoDI 4715.16, Enclosure 6(2)(p));
- Continue the current process that requires installation staff, tenants, contractors, users and interested parties to coordinate with the CRM early in the planning of

projects and activities to ensure compliance with Section 106 of the National Historic Preservation Act and this ICRMP;

- Continue to prioritize funding and program funds for cultural resources compliance and management activities;
- Provide for the annual review of the ICRMP and initiate revision of the ICRMP if the annual review indicates a need for such revision.

The CRM will play a primary role in implementation of this ICRMP. In this role the CRM will coordinate compliance with cultural resources laws and Army regulations on behalf of the GC. The CRM will coordinate with users, interested parties and the public to ensure compliance with Sections 106, 110, 112 of the NHPA, the NAGPRA) and the ARPA. Additionally, the CRM will coordinate consultation with interested parties to address management concerns that affect the ability of Fort Bliss to comply with cultural resources laws and regulations.

1.6.1 ICRMP Action Plan

The action plan for the ICRMP is presented in Section 6.0 Implementing the ICRMP. Costs associated with implementing the ICRMP are also found in Section 6.0.

NOTES

2.0 GENERAL INFORMATION

2.1 Introduction

The Fort Bliss area represents a landscape that has been and continues to be shaped by various forces. The earliest human occupations in the region (Paleo Indian) occurred during an interglacial span of the Late Pleistocene (13,000-9000 B.C.) when much of the landscape was represented by forests of white pine, pinon and fir, particularly in the lower elevations of the surrounding mountains. By the Early Archaic period, the Early Holocene (9000-6000 B.C.) environment experienced temperature fluctuations changing the biotic communities to xeric juniper woodlands with grasslands along the basin floor. The present day Chihuahuan Desert environment was becoming established by the Middle Holocene period (6900-2000 B.C.) which corresponds with Early and Middle Archaic occupations in the region. Late Holocene (2000 B.C.-present) was essentially the same as modern day climates which occurred during the end of the Middle Archaic period through to modern day occupations. Today the landscape reflects a myriad of human activities from the early pueblo settlements through ranching to establishment of the fort. Changes to the landscape continue to occur through both natural actions, as well as through the training of soldiers. These changes will leave records on the landscape for future generations to manage. These natural and cultural records collectively form the present landscape.

Management of these cultural landscapes requires an understanding of what resources make up the cultural landscape and the agents that have affected them and those that have the potential to affect them in the future. This section presents these agents and what cultural resources may have resulted from them. The section provides information on user groups that may affect the landscape as well as parties interested in seeing that management is conducted in a sound manner consistent with local, state, and national interests. This section also defines the role and responsibilities the Installation Commanders and the CRM have in managing this non-renewable resource.

2.2 Goals and Objectives

Goal: The goal of cultural resources management on Fort Bliss is to manage historically significant resources in support of Fort Bliss' missions.

Objectives:

- Comply with Federal laws and regulations governing the treatment of cultural resources while causing the least disturbance to the military mission as required to support undertakings
- Inventory and evaluate cultural resources for eligibility for inclusion on the National Register of Historic Places

- Avoid or minimize adverse effects on cultural resources that meet criteria for eligibility on the National Register of Historic Places
- Continue to implement efficient management procedures that streamline consultation and focus on significant cultural resources
- Enforce Federal laws that prohibit vandalism of cultural resources on Federal properties through law enforcement, monitoring, and public awareness
- Consider outside interests, including but not be limited to, local governments and public groups
- Continue active curation program
- Develop a meaningful public education program presenting historic resources on Fort Bliss
- Continue to engage Federally-recognized Tribes in the management of resources of interest to them
 - Sign a Comprehensive Agreement with the Tribes to streamline NAGPRA compliance
 - Sign a Memorandum of Agreement with the Tribes to establish government-to-government consultation procedures

The overall purpose behind these management objectives is the integration of legal requirements for preservation into the everyday operations of Fort Bliss' military mission and support activities. This ICRMP incorporates guidelines, schedules and SOPs for cultural resources management into a single document to more efficiently fulfill management responsibilities.

2.3 Location

Fort Bliss is located in the Tularosa Basin in western Texas and south-central New Mexico. It is adjacent to El Paso, Texas (population ca. 833,487 as of July 2014; US Census Bureau) with Ciudad Juarez, Mexico (population ca. 1.4 million in 2010) directly across the Rio Grande from El Paso. Fort Bliss consists of a cantonment, an air field, and three base camps (Doña Ana, McGregor, and Orogrande) that service training areas in New Mexico. Fort Bliss training lands abuts White Sands Missile Range in New Mexico. The Fort totals approximately 1.1 million acres.

Figure 1.2: Fort Bliss in 1929.

2.4 Geographic Overview

Understanding the geography of the region around Fort Bliss is important to understanding why and where cultural resources exist, and how they came into being. The prehistoric peopling of the region occurred because geographic conditions were right for it. The existence of these conditions into historic times has encouraged continued use of the region. An explanation of the region's geography is presented here.

2.4.1 Physiography

Fort Bliss lies within the Basin and Range physiographic province. Extension of the crust throughout the province during the past 30 million years has produced characteristic short, linear mountain ranges separated by intervening valleys. Superimposed along the eastern side of the Basin and Range is a peculiar physiographic feature that extends from western Texas and northern Mexico northward through central New Mexico. This feature, the Rio Grande Rift Valley, extends northward into the Southern Rocky Mountains physiographic province of southern Colorado and northern New Mexico. From Albuquerque, NM the northward trending Rio Grande Rift Valley is a relatively distinct continuous physiographic feature containing numerous basins. South of Albuquerque, the rift broadens and encompasses several valleys and small, linear mountain ranges. At about the latitude of El Paso, Texas, the Rio Grande Rift Valley turns abruptly to the southeast.

Much of Fort Bliss lies in the Tularosa Basin and Hueco Bolson. The contiguous basins are about 100 miles long and 60 miles wide. It is one of the largest valleys in the Rio Grande rift. The Tularosa Basin merges with the Hueco Bolson (valley) at, and south of, El Paso, Texas. The Hueco Bolson is about 16 miles wide and extends into western Texas and Mexico. From south to north along the east side of Fort Bliss are the Hueco Mountains, Otero Mesa and Sacramento Mountains. The Hueco Mountains form the western edge of the Diablo Plateau, which extends far into southeast New Mexico and Texas. The Otero Mesa is continuous with the Diablo Plateau. Approximately 163,000 of the 1.2 million acres of Otero Mesa and 17,000 acres of the Sacramento Mountains foothills are located in the Fort Bliss Training Complex. The Sacramento Mountains rise steeply from Otero Mesa and the Tularosa Basin north of Fort Bliss. Along the southwest side of Fort Bliss are the Franklin Mountains. Several miles north of the Franklin Mountains are the narrow, steep-sided Organ Mountains. The Organ Mountains are continuous northward with the San Andres Mountains and, together, form an unbroken 100-mile-long mountain range. A short distance north of the central part of Fort Bliss are the Jarilla Mountains, a small, circular cluster of hills rising from the Tularosa Basin.

2.4.2 Stratigraphy

The oldest rocks near Fort Bliss are exposed in the Organ and Franklin mountains. These mostly granite, schist and gneiss rocks are the deep crustal roots of ranges that extended across much of western North America more than 1.3 billion years ago. During the next several hundred million years, these mountains were eroded by glaciers, rivers and storms into a remarkably flat surface close to sea level.

Beginning about 550 million years ago, a sea lying west of the Fort Bliss region began advancing eastward across the eroded plain. Later, the seas retreated westward in response to gentle uplift of the crust and the carbonate deposits left by prior seas were partially or completely eroded before the seas again advanced across the region.

The character of sedimentation changed over time from carbonate to silts and clays. These deposits are represented today by black, non-fossiliferous shale that contains abundant pyrite. Middle and late Mississippian rocks preserve a record of deep basins in which black, calcareous muds accumulated. These basins were eventually filled in, the region was uplifted, and the sea retreated southward to about the location of El Paso, Texas. From El Paso southward, deposition was continuous from the Mississippian to Pennsylvanian (sub-periods of the Carboniferous Period, about 360 – 300 mya). The cyclical nature of carbonate deposits during the Pennsylvanian sub-period may reflect changes in sea level that have been correlated with glaciations elsewhere in the world. These relatively stable marine conditions were interrupted on occasion by influxes of coarse sand and pebbles eroded from the broad Pedernal Uplift 100 miles east of the Fort Bliss area. As the Pedernal Uplift grew in elevation, a large oval-shaped basin (the Orogrande Basin) developed along the uplift's west side.

In the southern part of the Fort Bliss area, the shoreline between the coarse debris flowing in from the north and the marine waters of the Orogrande Basin, advanced and retreated many times, depositing gypsiferous sand and silt and carbonate muds (the Yeso and San Andres Formations). The rock record in the Fort Bliss area from the late Permian to the early Jurassic period (about 260 mya – 180 mya) is missing. Sediments were either not deposited during this time span or, if deposited, were eroded away prior to deposition in the Cretaceous Period (about 140 – 72 mya).

Early Cretaceous sands (such as the Dakota Sandstones) are overlain by mudstone and shale (the Mancos Shale). The abundance of sands and silts in the late Cretaceous seas were early indicators of major and widespread uplifts that occurred throughout the region. This period of mountain building, referred to as the Laramide Orogeny, lasted for some 50 million years (late Cretaceous time to early Tertiary time [about 100 – 6 mya]). Large masses of molten rock were injected into the subsurface, and some are exposed today in the Organ, Jarilla and Hueco mountains. Coarse debris eroded from the Laramide uplifts is preserved in various Early Tertiary rocks (i.e., the Love Ranch Formation). Beginning at the end of Cretaceous time approximately 80 million years ago, and continuing intermittently into the present, the Laramide Orogeny affected much of the Rocky Mountain region from Wyoming south to New Mexico. Large blocks of the crust were uplifted, exposing Precambrian rocks that had been eroded flat in the Precambrian time. These crustal blocks trended largely northward and were flanked by steep faults and folds. In the El Paso area however, some of the Laramide uplifts trend northwestward, paralleling the trend of the Cordilleran orogenic belt. The Cordilleran belt extends southward from Alaska, through western Canada and the western United States. Near Las Vegas, Nevada, the belt abruptly changes to a southeasterly direction and continues through southern Arizona and southwestern New Mexico. The belt continues into west Texas near El Paso and then southeastward through Mexico. Some of the major faults in the Franklin and Organ mountains developed during this time and may be related to compressional stresses that developed at the intersection of the Laramide and Cordilleran belts. Many other Laramide structures however, are hidden beneath younger rocks in present-day valleys and are known only through geophysical

surveys and drilling. Many of these buried Laramide structures have been further obscured by younger deformation associated with the development of the basin and range and the Rio Grande Rift.

The middle Tertiary period (about 4 mya) marks the beginning of extensive igneous activity in south-central New Mexico and West Texas. In the Organ Mountains, rhyolitic eruptions from the Organ caldera are more than 10,000 feet thick. Intrusive igneous rocks were emplaced in early Tertiary time in the Organ, Hueco, Jarilla, and Sacramento mountains. This phase of igneous activity was followed by deposition of conglomerate, sandstone, caliche, shale, and gypsum. During the Oligocene Epoch (about 34 – 28 mya), the Rio Grande Rift began to develop and by about 17 million years ago, the broader basin and range began to develop. The present-day mountains in the Fort Bliss region began developing about 10 million years ago.

The Tularosa Basin and Hueco Bolson contain thick deposits of Cenozoic Era (about 66 mya to present) debris eroded from the adjacent mountains. Basaltic lava flows extruded throughout the Fort Bliss area, with remnants preserved north of the Jarilla Mountains and east of the Organ Mountains. During the Pleistocene Epoch (2.5 – 0.1 mya), Lake Otero occupied the present-day White Sands National Monument. As this lake evaporated, the broad areas of gypsum-bearing sediments in today's Tularosa Basin were deposited.

2.4.3 Soils

The majority of soils in the Fort Bliss area are classified as either aridisols or entisols, although a few mollisols are also found. Aridisols are soils with well-developed pedogenic horizons, which developed under conditions of low moisture. There is very little water leaching through its profile. Consequently, some of these soils have lime-cemented hardpans (caliche). Entisols, young soils with little or no development of soil horizons, are located in areas where the soil is actively eroding (slopes) or receiving new deposits of soil materials (alluvial fans, flood plains, and eolian sand dunes). A few mollisols occur in the mountains of the Fort Bliss area. These soils are distinguished by a deep, dark-colored surface horizon, rich in organic matter and saturated with bases.

Soils in the Fort Bliss area generally consist of sandy, silty and gravelly loams, and fine sands and silts. The soils are alkaline and calcareous, having developed from the weathering of gypsum, sandstone, limestone, igneous, and metamorphic rocks. Windblown sediments from exposed lakebeds occur widely. Wind is an important soil forming agent in the Fort Bliss area. Wind-blown sand is common, with the greatest accumulations forming dunes in the basins.

Fort Bliss area soils can be separated into two general categories based on the following physiographic positions: valleys and basin floors, mountains, mountain foot slopes, and escarpments. Soils in valleys and basins are shallow to deep, nearly level to very steep, well-drained to excessively drained soils that formed in alluvium, alluvium modified by wind, and eolian material. Most of the basin floors are covered by coppice dunes (eolian deposits trapped by mesquite thickets) and eolian sheet deposits. These soils are found mainly in the Tularosa Basin and Hueco Bolson. Major soil units in this category include Bluepoint, Caliz-Bluepoint-Yturbide, Pajarito-Onite-Pintura, Pintura-Wink, Berino-Doña Ana, Mimbres-Stellar, Nickel-

Upton, Tome-Mimbres, Philder-Armesa-Reyab, Nickel-Tencee, Bluepoint-Onite-Wink, and Pintura-Doña Ana, Hueco-Wink and Turney-Berino.

Land surfaces on mountains, mountain foot slopes, and escarpment are rock outcrops or shallow to deep, well-drained and nearly level to extremely steep soils that formed in alluvium and colluviums, mostly derived from limestone. These soils are found mainly in the Sacramento, Hueco and Organ mountains, and on Otero Mesa. Major soil units in this category include: Rock outcrop-Torriorthents, Deama-Tortugas-Rock outcrop, Ector-Rock outcrop, Delnorte-Canutio and Lozier-Rock outcrop.

Wind and water erosion are currently the most significant processes affecting soils in the Fort Bliss area. Soils unprotected by vegetation are susceptible to erosion from wind and water runoff. Gullying is the most prevalent form of erosion, but sheet and rill erosion from water and wind erosion are processes that can also significantly affect soil movement.

2.4.4 Climate

The present climate of the El Paso area and surrounding Chihuahua desert is a semiarid mesothermal regime characterized by hot daytime temperatures, relatively cooler nights and low humidity. Mean monthly temperatures range from a January low of 44° F to a July high of 83° F, although summer temperatures often exceed 100° F and freezing temperatures may occur during the late winter months. Relative humidity in the area is quite low, averaging from 10-14 percent during the winter and spring and 22-24 percent in the fall months. The average growing season for El Paso is approximately 241 days. This is measured as the average interval between the last killing frost of spring (March 8) and the initial killing frost of autumn (November 12). However, the agricultural and biomass productivity of the regional environment is primarily tied to moisture availability rather than growing season temperatures.

The average annual rainfall in the area ranges between 8 to 11 inches. Precipitation in the region comes from two major seasonal movements of air masses. Winter moisture is associated with the southerly deflection of Polar Pacific air which delivers a generally prolonged, low intensity winter precipitation to the area. During the summer months, beginning at the end of May and lasting through mid-October, convective cells are formed by the intersection of moist tropical air from the Gulf of Mexico with local air masses uplifted by intense surface heating. The resulting summer precipitation is localized and generally concentrated in short, high intensity thunderstorms in the mid-afternoon and evening that often produce substantial runoff water in arroyo drainages and standing pools of water in playa depressions. Over 50 percent of the total annual precipitation in the El Paso area is from the north in winter, west-southwest in spring, and the south during the summer. Relatively strong winds often accompany steep cold fronts or frontal storm lines moving across the mountains; although a year-round occurrence, they reach their greatest frequency during the climax of the dry season from March to May. Consequently, spring is the season with the highest mean wind velocities and when dust storms are most frequent.

2.4.5 Faunal and Floral Communities

The modern vegetation is typical of the Lower Sonora Life Zone. Common plant species of this area are listed in Table 2.1. Local vegetation of the central Hueco Bolson landform consists of the signature Chihuahuan Desert xerophytic shrub community composed predominantly of honey mesquite (*Prosopis glandulosa*), creosotebush (*Larrea tridentata*), and broom snakeweed (*Gutierrezia sarothrae*; also known as *Zanthocephalum sarothrae*). Other common plants in the project area include four-winged saltbush (*Atriplex canescens*), soap-tree yucca (*Yucca elata*), Mormon tea (*Ephedra* sp.), sunflower (*Helianthus petiolaris*) and assorted range grasses, forbs and seasonal herbaceous plants. Many of the local plant taxa are of ethnographically documented importance among historic Native American groups of the southwest United States and northern Mexico and were undoubtedly exploited for food, fuel and medicinal treatments by the prehistoric inhabitants of the area.

Scientific Name	Common Name
<i>Acacia constricta</i>	Whitethorn acacia
<i>Agave lechuguilla</i>	Lechuguilla
<i>Artemisia filifolia</i>	Sandsage
<i>Ambrosia artemisifolia</i>	Ambrosia
<i>Apodanthera undulate</i>	Gourd
<i>Astragalus</i> sp.	Milvetch
<i>Atriplex canescens</i>	Four-wing saltbush
<i>Bahia absinthifolia</i>	Bahia
<i>Baileya multiradiata</i>	Desert marigold
<i>Boerhaavia erecta</i>	Boerhaavia
<i>Bouteloua barbata</i>	Six weeks grama
<i>Chilopsis linearis</i>	Desert willow
<i>Datura metaloides</i>	Jimson weed
<i>Dasyllirion wheeleri</i>	Sotol
<i>Descurainia pinnata</i>	Tansymustard
<i>Dithyrea wislizenii</i>	Spectacle pod
<i>Echinocereus triglochidiatus</i>	Claret cup cactus
<i>Ephedra</i> sp.	Mormon tea
<i>Euphorbia albomarginata</i>	Forb
<i>Ferocactus wislizenii</i>	Barrel cactus
<i>Flourensia cernua</i>	Tarbush
<i>Fouquieria splendens</i>	Ocotillo
<i>Gutierrezia sarothrae</i>	Broom snakeweed
<i>Helianthus petiolaris</i>	Sunflower
<i>Kallstroemia parviflora</i>	Caltrop
<i>Larrea tridentata</i>	Creosotebush
<i>Lepidium</i> sp.	Pepperweed

TABLE 2.1 COMMON FLORA OF THE FORT BLISS AREA (CONCLUDED)

Scientific Name	Common Name
<i>Mammillaria sp.</i>	Unident. Mammillaria
<i>Muhlenbergia porteri</i>	Bushy muhly
<i>Platyopuntia sp.</i>	Prickly pear
<i>Parthenium incanum</i>	Mariola
<i>Pectis angustifolia</i>	Lemonweed
<i>Proboscidia sp.</i>	Devil's claw
<i>Prosopis glandulosa</i>	Honey mesquite
<i>Rumex hymenosepalus</i>	Rue
<i>Salsola kali</i>	Tumbleweed
<i>Sporobolus contractus</i>	Spike dropseed
<i>Tidestromia lanulosa</i>	Tidestromia
<i>Verbesina encelioides</i>	Verbesina
<i>Yucca baccata</i>	Banana yucca, datil
<i>Yucca elata</i>	Soap-tree yucca
<i>Yucca torreyi</i>	Torrey yucca, Spanish dagger

While the vegetation of the area appears rather homogeneous to the casual observer, substantial topographic and environmental variation exists across the landscape. There are 22 distinct plant associations on Fort Bliss. Vegetation communities are conditioned by the depth of the local soils, their capacity for water retention, and their proportions of constituent gravels, as well as elevation and exposure. Mesquite, numerous grasses and forbs, and herbaceous annuals such as cheno-ams, sunflower, Tansy mustard, and purslane, thrive in low-lying areas where water accumulates, such as the playa depression at Nations East Well. Soap-tree yucca, acacia and sunflowers are also found along the toeslope of the Hueco Mountain alluvial fan. Communities of mesquite, acacia, desert willow, and prickly pear are abundant along the larger washes leading from the Hueco Mountains. The rocky and calcareous soils of the alluvial fans, canyons, and foothills of the Hueco Mountains support communities of cacti, leaf succulents, and other species of known importance to prehistoric subsistence economies, including lechuguilla, stool, datil, prickly pear and various species of *Echinocactus sp.* and *Mammillaria sp.*

Several studies have provided evidence of substantial transitions in regional vegetation from Pleistocene to historic times. These studies have identified cyclical periods of increased or diminished precipitation which resulted in the expansion of grassland or desert shrub communities. This phenomenon has been demonstrated in historic times, as overgrazing and drought during the latter part of the nineteenth and early twentieth centuries resulted in severe soil degradation and radically altered vegetation patterns throughout much of west Texas and southern New Mexico; the most visible change being the widespread expansion of mesquite shrub communities. Prehistoric vegetation patterns in the project area undoubtedly differed in some respects from present conditions, most likely in the relative proportions of grasses and desert shrubs present across the central basin landforms.

A variety of fauna are present in the northern Chihuahuan Desert, many of which were hunted and trapped by the prehistoric inhabitants of the region. A partial list of mammals common to Fort Bliss is listed below in Table 2.2. Species diversity is higher in mountain regions and the lowest in the bolson areas. Large ungulates include mule deer and white-tailed deer, pronghorn antelope, and occasional bighorn sheep that would have been encountered in the canyons and plains. Other available animal species would have included small lagomorphs (desert cottontail and black-tailed jackrabbits), javelina, coyote, badgers, and a variety of small rodents, reptiles, and birds. These animal resources may have provided a variety of uses for prehistoric peoples, including meat, hide and sinew for clothing and coverings, bone for tools, and marrow for grease.

TABLE 2.2 COMMON PREHISTORIC AND MODERN FAUNA OF FORT BLISS	
Scientific Name	Common name
<i>Sylvilagus audobonii</i>	Desert cottontail
<i>Lepus californicus</i>	Black-tailed jackrabbit
<i>Odocoileus hemionus</i>	Mule deer
<i>Odocoileus virginianus</i>	White-tailed deer
<i>Antilocapra Americana</i>	Pronghorn antelope
<i>Dicotyles tajacu</i>	Collared peccary (javelina)
<i>Dipodomys sp.</i>	Kangaroo rat
<i>Neotoma sp.</i>	Woodrat
<i>Perognathus sp.</i>	Pocket mouse
<i>Canis latrans</i>	Coyote
<i>Crotalus sp.</i>	Rattlesnake
<i>Geococcyx californianus</i>	Roadrunner
<i>Spilogale gracilis</i>	Western spotted skunk
<i>Taxidea taxus</i>	Badger
<i>Vulpus macrotis</i>	Desert fox

2.4.6 Water Resources

Permanent water sources presently do not exist on Fort Bliss. Historically documented springs are known in the Franklin, Organ, San Andres, and Sacramento mountains, but no such reference to springs or seeps in the Hueco Mountains has been found. Eroded depressions in syenite and limestone outcrops, called huecos, often held pooled water for some period of time after a rainfall, and thus provided an intermittent water source. Otherwise, in prehistoric and modern times, excess rainfall runoff flowed through canyons and down alluvial fans and emptied into playas distributed along the confluence of the alluvial piedmont and basin floor or as ephemeral flow concentrated in shallow, transient drainages across the medial and distal ends of alluvial fans. Whether or not these water sources were more frequent and stable during prehistoric times is difficult to ascertain and the frequency and duration of water ponding in the playa depressions cannot be determined with any degree of certainty. The macro botanical study of plant remains recovered from prehistoric features offer an important clue. Charred spike rush (*Eleocharis sp.*)

seeds were recovered from hearth features. Spike rush grows along shoreline environments in the presence of shallow, still, ponded waters, and thus suggest the presence of a relatively stable water-filled playa. This finding indicates that periods of high precipitation combined with lower temperatures and reduced evaporation rates must have occurred during the prehistoric time intervals.

2.5 Historic Overview

2.5.1 Prehistoric

The prehistory of the Jornada Mogollon region encompasses several cultural historic periods and phases (Table 2.3). Archaeological investigations throughout the central basin landform of the greater Hueco Bolson and Tularosa Basin have encountered sites spanning the range of cultural/temporal periods from Paleo Indian through Protohistoric occupations.

TABLE 2.3 REGIONAL CULTURAL PERIODS AND ASSOCIATED DATES*

<u>Cultural Period/Phase</u>	<u>Associated Dates</u>	<u>Reference</u>
Pre-Clovis	Ca. 50,000 – 10,000 B.C.	MacNeish 1993a; MacNeish and Libby 2003
Paleo Indian	Ca. 10,000 – 6000 B.C.	Carmichael 1986; Miller and Kenmotsu 2004
Clovis	Ca. 10,000 – 9000 B.C.	Miller and Kenmotsu 2004
Folsom	9000 – 8200 B.C.	Amick 1994a
Plano/Cody	8200 – 6000 B.C.	Miller and Kenmotsu 2004, Mallouf 1985
Archaic	6000 B.C. - A.D. 200	Carmichael 1986; Anderson 1993
Early	6000/4000 – 3000 B.C.	Carmichael 1986
Gardner Springs	6000 – 4000 B.C.	MacNeish 1993b; Anderson 1993
Middle	4000/3000 – 1200 B.C.	Carmichael 1986
Keystone	4000 – 2500 B.C.	MacNeish 1993b; Anderson 1993
Fresnel	2500 - 900 B.C.	MacNeish 1993b; Anderson 1993
Late	1200 B.C. - A.D. 200	Carmichael 1986
Hueco	900 B.C. - A.D. 250	MacNeish 1993b; Anderson 1993
Formative	A.D. 200 - 1450	Lehmer 1948; Hard 1983a; Carmichael 1986; Whalen 1994
Mesilla	A.D. 200 - 1100	Carmichael 1986
Early	A.D. 200/400 - 1000	Miller and Kenmotsu 2004
Doña Ana	A.D. 1100 - 1200	Lehmer 1948; Carmichael 1986
Transitional	A.D. 1200 - 1300	Miller and Kenmotsu 2004
El Paso	A.D. 1300 - 1450	Whalen 1977, 1978; Carmichael 1986
Late	A.D. 1250/1300 - 1450	Miller and Kenmotsu 2004
Precontact	A.D. 1450 - 1581	Beckett and Corbett 1992; Sale 1991
Protohistoric	A.D. 1581 - 1659	Wimberly et al. 1979; Peter and Mbutu 1997; Miller 2001; Seymour 2001
Historic	A.D. 1650 - present	Peterson and Brown 1992

* From Lowry, et al., 2004, National Register of Historic Places Eligibility Evaluations of 150 Prehistoric Sites for Fort Bliss Project 9202 in the Tularosa Basin and Otero Mesa, Otero County, New Mexico (as amended)

2.5.1.1 Pre-Clovis (ca. 50,000 – 10,000 B.C.)

Since Alex Krieger first suggested that Pre-Clovis traditions existed in Texas and elsewhere in the United States, the existence of a Pre-Clovis occupation in North America has been met with considerable debate (Krieger 1962, 1964). Claims of a pre-Clovis occupation in the Jornada Mogollon region have been largely fueled by Chrisman et al. (1996) in which they discuss the presence of 12,000 to 35,000 year-old human fingerprint and skin imprints at the Pendejo Cave site. Richard MacNeish, based on his excavations at Pendejo Cave, has proposed the existence of a Pre-Clovis tradition in the American Southwest.

Pendejo Cave is a deeply stratified rockshelter located on McGregor Guided Missile Range east of Oro Grande, New Mexico (MacNeish 1993a, MacNeish et al. 1993; Chrisman et al. 1996). During his excavations, MacNeish claimed to have a well-stratified sequence of radiocarbon dates ranging from between approximately 12,000 and 50,000 year old which contained large quantities of Pleistocene fauna and flora, and other eco-facts purportedly in direct association with hearths, stone artifacts, and human modified animals bones. Additionally, and perhaps more interestingly, MacNeish claimed to have human skin impressions and hair.

While an Early to Late Archaic occupation of the shelter is not in dispute, arguments for a late Pleistocene occupation prior to 10,000 B.C. is based on substantially less conclusive findings. This earlier occupation is based primarily on a small quantity of crudely manufactured stone artifacts, a small number of bones with marks suggesting human modification, hearth features constructed of stones differing petrologically and chemically from the limestone formations comprising the natural cave setting, and the aforementioned hair and skin imprints claimed to be of human origin.

Much of the material used to assign this component to Pendejo cave remains under speculation. Researchers have examined the small amount of bone and stone artifacts, the majority of which have commented that the tools are extremely crude in nature and do not have any of the attributes of known chipped stone artifacts. Harris (1995) did a detailed study of the 36,000 faunal specimens and found no evidence of human modification of the assemblage. Harris commented that other than the widespread occurrence of burned bone that “the sample appears no different than natural, non-human-related cave accumulations that have been examined elsewhere.” He further concludes that “[a]t least some of the burning seems consistent with burning or smoldering of strata post depositionally, as also seen elsewhere.”

The presence of human friction prints was met with a great deal of controversy. Fort Bliss retains a copy of the original study conducted by the Ontario Provincial Police Forensics Laboratory stating that no evidence of sweat pores could be detected among the imprints and that they could not exclude the possibility that the prints were made by a non-human agent.

Finally, a reexamination of the stratigraphic layers in Pendejo cave indicated alternating layers of uncharred and charred organic material sealed in discrete stratigraphic units, which may represent natural depositional episodes exposed to varying levels of heat during major fires inside the cave. This suggests that the sediments may represent a complex depositional sequence in which bioturbation and burning has played a significant role and would require a much higher resolution to truly characterize the stratigraphic sequence.

In sum, a great deal more work will need to be conducted to verify the presence of a Pre-Clovis occupation in this region. At present, there is no strong evidence to support the argument for an occupation in the area predating the Paleo Indian period.

2.5.1.2 Paleo Indian (10,000 – 6000 B.C)

The earliest securely documented presence in the Jornada Mogollon region is the Paleo Indian Period from 10,000 to 6000 B.C. Paleo Indian groups were highly mobile bands with a subsistence economy based on big game hunting including Pleistocene megafauna. Most Paleo Indian sites are represented by isolated projectile point finds and by open-air sites located in the Tularosa Basin. One radiocarbon date from a small hearth feature has been radiocarbon dated to the Paleo Indian period on Fort Bliss; most of these older sites are dated using relative means such as a projectile point type. Significant numbers of Paleo Indian artifacts have been documented in the region, but they pale in comparison to artifacts from later periods. In this area, the Paleo Indian period is divided into three subperiods including the Clovis, Folsom, and Plano/Cody complexes. Over 500 Paleo Indian components have been identified on Fort Bliss sites.

2.5.1.3 Clovis (10,000-9000 B.C.)

Most Clovis occupations are represented in this area by isolated Clovis points. Clovis points are a distinctive form of fluted projectile point which has been found elsewhere in direct association with the skeletal remains of Pleistocene mammoth. Although documented throughout much of North America, Clovis remains are relatively rare in the local area. Habitation sites are known from Rhodes Canyon and Mockingbird Gap in the northern Tularosa area.

2.5.1.4 Folsom (9000 – 8200 B.C)

Folsom occupations are better represented in the region. Several sites in the region have Folsom materials. Many of the Folsom site components are mixed with later occupations, making inferences concerning Folsom adaptation tentative. Folsom materials are dominated by isolated projectile points, lithic fragments and formal stone tools, suggesting highly mobile and dispersed hunting activities. Raw material studies indicate assemblages focusing on fine quality cherts and obsidians. Source areas for these materials are sometimes up to 459 km away from the Tularosa Basin.

In the southern Plains area, Folsom subsistence economy is focused on bison hunting. However, a study conducted by Amick (1991, 1994) suggests that Folsom sites in this region may have been residential or “home base” localities oriented towards hunting game animals other than bison. Like other Paleo Indian subperiods, the Folsom in the Jornada region is still poorly understood.

2.5.1.5 Plano/Cody (8200 – 6000 B.C.)

The Plano and Cody occupations are well documented with several different projectile point types noted. Plano/Cody components are found in a variety of topographic zones however, the majority of the sites have been found near reliable water sources such as playa basins and major

and minor drainages, and the margins of the Rio Grande Valley. While big game hunting was likely still a major subsistence activity, changes in the environment at this time likely affected human adaptation with an increase in use of plant foods, changes in settlement patterns, and technology leading to Archaic period adaptations.

In addition to distinctive projectile point types, Plano/Cody assemblages also have transverse end scrapers, side scrapers, and bifaces. Some of the sites from this period tend to be more similar to Early Archaic occupations, and likely represent a gradual transition to Archaic lifeways.

2.5.1.6 Archaic Period (6000 – A.D/ 200)

The Archaic period represents the longest span of human occupation in the Jornada region. This period is better represented than the Paleo Indian period, with an impressive array of evidence from rock shelters and open sites found in all environmental zones.

Notable developments during the Archaic period include the first archaeological evidence for agriculture, the habitation of residential pit house or hut structures, and the widespread use of rock or caliche in the construction and use of thermal features. An increase in the range of plant materials utilized, as well as technological changes reflecting the processing of these foods indicate a greater diversification of subsistence practices over the preceding Paleoindian period.

Information obtained through archaeological surveys in the Hueco Bolson and Tularosa Basin, excavations at cave locales and open-air site excavations characterize the Archaic period as an adaptation based on seasonally mobile, broad spectrum hunting and gathering. There is evidence of increasing sedentism during certain periods of the year during the Late Archaic period. The population is thought to have increased throughout the period, leading to increasingly restricted home range territories and ultimately the adoption of agriculture.

The 6,000-year interval of the Archaic period has been conventionally divided into the Early (6000/4000-3000 B.C.), Middle (4000/3000 – 1200 B.C.) and Late (1200 B.C. – A.D. 200) sub-periods that have been defined based on projectile point styles and stratigraphic data from rock shelters.

Over 2,000 Archaic components have been recorded on sites across the installation, usually through a diagnostic projectile point type. However, some of the many sites containing only non-diagnostic stone artifacts may date to this period.

2.5.1.7 Early Archaic (6000/4000 – 3000 B.C.)

The Early Archaic sub-period is one of the least understood time periods of the entire Jornada prehistoric sequence. Early Archaic occupants have been defined primarily on the basis of projectile point styles and a few insubstantial deposits or features. The overall number of projectile points does not greatly outnumber those of the preceding Paleo Indian period. Few firmly dated Early Archaic contexts have been identified in the Jornada, and have primarily involved deeply buried features or rock shelter deposits. These deposits have yielded little data concerning subsistence, settlement, and technology.

Projectile technology emphasizes a change from the lanceolate forms of the preceding Paleo Indian period to stemmed forms such as Jay, Bajada, and Uvalde. Along with the adoption of these stemmed projectile point forms comes a noticeable change in the use of coarser-grained raw materials for the manufacture of projectiles. Additional technological changes include the utilization of rock or caliche for heating elements in thermal features and the use of ground stone. The factors causing such changes are still unknown, although they may be related to changes in prey selection and hunting practices, restricted home ranges that caused an increase in local raw material use, reduced emphasis on tool maintenance and an increase in tool reliability, or a combination of these factors. Though speculative, the settlement and subsistence of the Early Archaic can be characterized by an absence of structures, use of larger burned rock features on the alluvial fans, use of artifacts, and other hearth features in all environmental zones, and changes in projectile point technology and raw material utilization. The data suggest an adaptation of seasonally mobile, small band hunter-gathers.

2.5.1.8 Middle Archaic (4000/3000 – B.C.)

Fundamental subsistence, settlement, and technological adaptations established in the Early Archaic tend to be maintained through the middle Archaic, although they may have become intensified throughout the latter part of this 2,000-year-long interval. This inferred intensification of subsistence and settlement adaptations is based on an overall increase in the number of sites and an increase in feature use based on a significant increase in the number of radiocarbon dates available for this period. Fifty-one radiocarbon dates are known from sites of this time period in the Jornada area; the majority of these are from open sites located in the central Hueco, Tularosa, and Mesilla Bolson. Middle Archaic sites also tend to be found along drainages, are generally larger, and contain more features than Early Archaic sites. Such sites also have more substantial artifact assemblages and clustered radiocarbon dates suggestive of larger social groups.

More recently, several Middle Archaic occupations have been identified along the Rio Grande Valley terrace in east El Paso and at several sites near Old Coe Lake Playa. The topographic setting of these sites supports the view that Middle Archaic settlements were tethered to permanent and semi-permanent water sources.

House structures are noted for the first time in the Middle Archaic. House structures were found at Keystone Dam, which has an occupation spanning the period between 2500 and 1800 B.C. These structures were small, shallow brush structures or “huts”. They are shallow (15 cm to 20 cm), circular (less than two square meters), and have unprepared floors and few internal features, suggesting a short-term occupation. The presence of thermal features and ground stone artifacts at Middle Archaic sites suggests a focus on plant foods in addition to hunting.

2.5.1.9 Later Archaic (1200 B.C. – A.D. 200)

In terms of settlement, subsistence, and technological adaptations, the Late Archaic represents a true break in the long Archaic sequence of the previous 4,000 years. Several technological innovations and changes in settlement adaptations characteristic of this period presage developments during the Formative period.

An important aspect of Late Archaic settlement is the dramatic increase in sites, features, and material culture attributable to this period. Basin landforms experience a peak in use intensity, although Late Archaic sites are found in all environmental zones. The diversity and quantity of Late Archaic period artifacts increase greatly compared to preceding periods, and include the common presence of such items as nets, basketry, atlatl, wood implements, and hide containers. Small circular structures are also common during this period. Projectile points change to corner-notched and side-notched forms in the latter half of this sub-period. They also become significantly smaller, marking the introduction of the bow and arrow.

Among the most important developments during the Late Archaic in the Jornada region is the first conclusive evidence for the use of cultigens, with inception of cultigens at 2500 B.C. based on corn pollen found at Keystone Dam. This date should be considered provisional due to the poor preservation of the pollen and the wide range of carbon 14 (¹⁴C) dates for the same strata. More conclusive evidence of cultigens comes from Tornillo Shelter where a date of 2030-830 B.C. was recovered from corn, and from Fresnel Shelter which revealed a suite of dates ranging from 1390-940 B.C. to 1200 B.C.-A.D. 600. The causal factors for the adoption of cultigens are still poorly understood. The prevailing view in the Jornada Mogollon region is that domesticates were part of a large and diverse subsistence base during the Late Archaic and that its addition provided a stable and predictable resource. Measures of agricultural dependence provided contradictory data with rock shelters containing abundant evidence of cultigens, while open sites contain no evidence of cultigens. Analyses on human bones indicate no evidence of a high maize diet. The apparent difference in rock shelter versus open sites may be a function of preservation or due to seasonal differences in site occupation. Hunting is still a very important subsistence factor in the Late Archaic diet with rock shelter locations near or in the mountains containing large amounts of large mammal bone, while other locales are dominated by rabbit species.

Causal factors underlying the adoption of corn, beans, and other cultigens during the Late Archaic period are not well known, and the origins of agriculture in the Jornada Mogollon region are best viewed within the larger perspective of developments across the Southwest. Many view the use of cultigens as part of an increasing diversification and range of plant foods exploited during the Late Archaic times, one which also provided additional stability, buffering, and /or predictability to the subsistence base. Whether or not this process may have been a cause or effect of increasing population levels, and in turn, reduced territories available for population movements, is not well understood.

2.5.1.10 Jornada Mogollon (A.D. 200 – 1450)

The Formative period is represented in this area by the Jornada Mogollon culture, which encompasses several important transitions in settlement adaptations. These include a relatively rapid succession of changes in architectural form, settlement structure, subsistence, and technology, including a trend of decreasing mobility coupled with increasing agricultural dependence and specialization that culminated in Puebloan occupation between A.D. 1300 and 1450. These developments have almost universally been perceived in terms of increasing agricultural dependence. However, evidence from the Jornada region also suggests that prehistoric populations may have become more agriculturally specialized between A.D. 1300

and 1450. About 3,100 Formative period sites have been recorded on Fort Bliss (often based solely on the presence of unpainted El Paso brownware ceramics). Sites that have been dated to the more refined phase sequences that follow are included at the end of each section.

The Jornada Mogollon includes three phases: the Mesilla phase (A.D. 200/400 – 1000), the Doña Ana phase (A.D. 1000-1300), and the El Paso phase (A.D. 1300 – 1450).

2.5.1.11 Mesilla Phase (A.D. 200/400 – 1100)

The Mesilla phase is characterized by the appearance of the El Paso brownware ceramic tradition. Intrusive ceramics (predominantly Mimbres white wares and other Mogollon wares) appeared in the region after A.D. 600, but usually were not common. Painted pottery (El Paso Bichrome) also made its first appearance late in this phase. Pit houses were constructed during this period, but were generally similar to the huts of the Archaic period. Structures become increasingly formal after A.D. 600. Sites generally are larger and more numerous, and contain more artifacts than sites from the earlier Archaic period.

Mesilla phase sites for all environmental zones show a slight association between sites and playas in the central basin. Because all types of sites are found in all zones, it is believed that the subsistence practices of the Mesilla phase were based primarily on hunting and foraging supplemented by agriculture and that occupation of the bolson was residential in nature.

Some see the Mesilla phase as a continuation of the subsistence and settlement practices of the Late Archaic. They believe that the basins of the region could not have been the whole area utilized by prehistoric groups. These basin areas were non-residential in nature rather than being used by sedentary peoples. Residential sites were probably located outside of the basins, most likely near the Rio Grande and were defined as sites containing trash middens.

Another settlement-subsistence model has been proposed where differences in environment influenced choices for seasonal rounds and activities. This model has winter and spring sites located on the mountain alluvial fans, while the central basin was used for foraging. The summer and fall seasons saw the central basin used for temporary residences. Recent work suggests that Mesilla phase peoples may be characterized as residential foragers. The central basin and alluvial fans are thought to have been components in a residential foraging strategy in which groups lived throughout the region as hunter-gathers. After A.D. 600, feature-related activities in the central basin drastically decreased. This may indicate a shift in the settlement and subsistence practices of prehistoric groups to a less intensive, logistical use of the central basin. Around 2,000 Mesilla phase components have been identified, usually through the presence of El Paso Brown ceramics.

2.5.1.12 Doña Ana Phase (A.D. 1100 – 1300)

Doña Ana phase sites are characterized by the presence of El Paso Bichrome and El Paso Polychrome pottery, sometimes associated with adobe surface construction. There is debate about the ability to distinguish Doña Ana occupations within the archaeological record. Early Doña Ana phase occupations have been described at the Gobernadora, Ojasen, and North Hills sites. These have informal pit houses and burned rock activity areas. Data indicates the use of

deep, square-shaped, formal pit houses and the utilization of discrete trash middens, suggesting a more sedentary existence than earlier time periods. Cultigens such as corn, squash, and beans as well as rabbit bone are found in these sites. Another site from this phase contained evidence of formal pit-structures with plastered hearths, as well as evidence for changing social organization defined by the presence of a very large pit-structure believed to be a communal house. Research indicates that this period is characterized by increasing population levels and a shift of settlement areas to runoff zones located on lower alluvial fans of the Franklin, Hueco, and Organ Mountains.

Overall, the changes that occurred during the Doña Ana phase include the introduction of polychrome pottery, rapid population increase, artifact changes that included larger manos and metates, decreased projectile point sizes (with larger forms still in use), and changes in intrusive ceramic types from Mimbres to Chupadero and Chihuahuan wares. Increasingly formal pit structures eventually led to later pueblo architecture of the El Paso phase. Another crucial change that occurred during this time was the shift from a general use of all areas within the region to concentrated use of specific environmental zones. These areas included the Rio Grande and the distal alluvial fans of local mountain ranges that are notable for their abundance of water and arable land for growing cultigens. Over 1,000 Doña Ana phase components have been identified on sites across the installation, usually through the presence of El Paso Bichrome/El Paso Decorated, or a combination of local and nonlocal ceramic types.

2.5.1.13 El Paso Phase (A.D. 1300 – 1450)

The final and most intensive prehistoric use of the region occurred during the El Paso phase. This phase is characterized by an increase in the number of large and small residential sites, increased artifact densities, and a clustered settlement pattern, as well as the introduction of small triangular projectile point forms. Larger projectile point styles are regularly found on the floors of rooms, indicating the possible continuing use of the atlatl in conjunction with the bow and arrow.

Several excavated El Paso phase sites provide data on subsistence and settlement. Varied settlement patterns and different structure types are suggested by data from Hot Well Pueblo, a 100-plus room village located near the eastern edge of the Hueco Bolson, others located near the Rio Grande and on the alluvial fans of the Franklin Mountains, and still others throughout the region. Additionally, individual surface room structures are a common feature of El Paso phase settlements (Figure 2.1).

Hueco Bolson survey data outline important changes that occurred during the El Paso phase. Data suggests that a shift in settlement patterns from earlier phases may indicate increased use of the lower alluvial fans for farming activities. Similar areas in the northern Hueco Bolson

Figure 2.1: Aerial photo of Madera Quemada Pueblo, Doña Ana Range, Fort Bliss, New Mexico.

suggest they were established during the Doña Ana phase as part of a larger regional exchange network related to Casas Grandes in Mexico.

Another settlement-subsistence model for the El Paso phase assumes more dependence on agriculture. This model suggests a division between primary villages and secondary villages. Primary village locations were near reliable water sources on mountain slopes but populations and intensity of use fluctuated during the year. Subsistence at these sites was based primarily on agriculture. Secondary villages, which were located on both mountain slopes and in the central basin near playas, were associated with late summer residential occupations based on hunting and foraging. Small sites are not included in this or other models of settlement and subsistence for the region. The debate over the role of agriculture and its importance to subsistence for this period is unresolved, as is the degree of sedentism.

The El Paso phase is characterized by peak population levels and diverse artifact assemblages, use of pit structures, individual surface rooms, and above-ground pueblos; and dependence on agriculture, but not to the exclusion of hunting and foraging. Residential permanency at sites during wet years and seasonal movement during periods of dry or lean years is postulated. Alternatively, a seasonal sedentary lifestyle alternating between the desert floor, alluvial fan, and riverine habitation may have been the norm. Over 2,000 Paso phase components have been identified on Fort Bliss, often through the presence of El Paso Polychrome ceramics and/or a combination of local and nonlocal ceramics.

2.5.2 Protohistoric (A.D. 1450 – 1659)

Various groups inhabited the Rio Grande Valley before the Spanish arrived in the area (Baugh and Sechrist 2001). These groups included the Jumanos, Suma, Manso, and others. Their territory encompassed the Rio Grande Valley from El Paso and downstream as far as the confluence of the Rio Grande and the Mexican Rio Conchos.

The Manso and Suma Indians were primarily nomadic with limited horticulture supplementing their food subsistence. Both groups relied on fishing, hunting deer and bison, gathering shellfish and a variety of plants. The primary cultigen for the Manso and Suma, however, was corn. The Jumano Indians lived east of the El Paso area. These people were also hunters and gatherers with one band living and farming at La Junta. La Junta was near the confluence of the Rio Grande River and Rio Conchos. Because the Suma were very similar to the Jumano in language and culture, it is believed that the Suma of the Rio Grande in the seventeenth century were the northern people who belonged to the Jumano of the lower Conchos.

Other groups were also noted to inhabit areas surrounding Manso territory. For example, the Apaches del Perillo occupied areas north of the Mansos and east and southeast of the Piro Pueblos. In the Tularosa Basin, Apaches were dominant. The Apache group that ranged over southeastern New Mexico and extreme western Texas were the Mescalero. They were recognized in Spanish records of the seventeenth century as a separate Tribe. These semi-nomadic people were also hunters and gatherers who seasonally hunted bison. The Spanish name “Mescalero” refers to crowns of the agave (or mescal), which the Indians collected for food.

The earliest interaction between Europeans and Native Americans of the lower Rio Grande Valley occurred in about A.D. 1535 when Alvar Nuñez Cabeza de Vaca traveled through the area. By 1581, the expedition by Fray Agustin Rodriguez and Captain Francisco Sanchez Chamuscado explored the El Paso/Juarez area for nine days. The following year, Antonio de Espejo led another expedition through the same area and camped for several days just south of present-day El Paso. By 1597, Juan de Oñate and his colonizing expedition reached present-day San Elizario. Oñate's group camped for several days taking advantage of the abundance of fish and game. Oñate claimed for Spain the entire region drained by the Rio Grande. From there, Oñate's party traveled up the Rio Grande. De Vaca provided brief descriptions of the Indian nations encountered.

There are very few verified Protohistoric components on Fort Bliss, less than 20 have been identified: a few by radiocarbon dates within range, one with possible Protohistoric ceramics, and a few by feature types. The majority of these sites are possibly early Apache.

2.5.2.1 Jumano Indians

The Jumano are believed to be peripheral members of the southwest Puebloan culture. Indirect evidence, through linguistic affiliations, associates them with a Uto-Aztecan language. The Jumano are the least culturally known of all Texas natives.

The Jumano culture is believed to be made up of two geographically distinct groups, one with bison hunting and the other an agricultural mode of production. One group, the Patarbueye, was a sedentary, agriculturally-based culture located in the valleys of the Rio Grande and the lower Rio Conchos. The other group, the Jumano, primarily hunted beyond the Chisos and Davis Mountains on the southernmost plains of west Texas. This group hunted throughout the summer and came down to the valley settlements to visit, trade, and wait for the next hunting season. This indicates that the Jumano either practiced a mixed economy, similar to the Pawnee and Wichita of the Central and Southern Plains, or were divided into two separate ethnic groups engaged in different economic pursuits. A mixed economy implies that people, who viewed themselves as belonging to the same ethnic group, were participating in a single economic system based on both hunting and farming. By postulating two independent modes of production, the second position maintains that these ethnically distinct groups, although tethered by trade mechanisms, were engaged in entirely separate, yet complementary, activities.

When the Spanish returned to the region at the beginning of the eighteenth century, the Jumanos were found to be allied with their former enemies, the Apaches. The Jumanos became known as a branch of the Apache and were referred to as the "Apaches Jumanos." Throughout the sixteenth century, the Jumanos had been increasingly exposed to Spanish-Mexican culture therefore decreasing their traditional Indian culture. With their cultural integrity weakened, the Jumano were unable to put up either a physical or moral barrier against Spanish or Apache encroachment. Some Jumanos became wage workers, as they were attracted to the mines and haciendas of Mexico. These Jumanos would be assimilated into the general Mexican populace. Those that stayed in the remaining ancestral homes also lost their cultural identity as these communities became bi-cultural. No known Jumano sites have been recorded on Fort Bliss.

2.5.2.2 Suma Indians

It is difficult to separate Suma and Jumano Indian culture given that both groups were described simultaneously and were believed to be culturally similar. It was believed that in the seventeenth century the Suma were the northern people who belonged to the Jumano of lower Conchos. Further, the Suma belonged to the Uto-Aztecan language group, based on only four words and several recorded personal names.

In the 1600s the Suma occupied territory southeast of El Paso along the Rio Grande, extending south to Jumano territory at La Junta, and southwest to the Rio Santa Maria. They were both agriculturalist and hunter-gatherers. In 1659, the San Francisco mission was built for the Suma Indians.

Throughout the seventeenth century the Suma, Jano, Jacome and Manso were troublesome to the Spanish. Some Indians were known to occupy the eastern frontier of the Pimeria Alta south of the Apache. After years of short-lived uprisings many of the peoples of Suma, Jano, and Jcome settled into the mission communities along the Rio Grande. The remaining bands were assimilated by the Apache.

Towards the end of the eighteenth century the Sumas were believed to have died out due to a smallpox epidemic in 1780. Archaeological evidence may indicate that Suma and Apache winter camps may have existed along the Rio Grande between El Paso and Presidio. No known Suma sites have been recorded on Fort Bliss (but see Seymour 2002).

2.5.2.3 Manso Indians

Manso territory began just north of El Paso along the Rio Grande and extended towards the Las Cruces area. From the sixteenth through the eighteenth centuries however, Manso territory included the El Paso area. The Franklin and Organ Mountains were known as the Sierra de los Mansos, extending from El Paso north to Hatch, New Mexico, and west near the Florida Mountains. In addition, the Manso language has an unknown linguistic affiliation.

The Spanish described the Mansos as untrustworthy and prone to harassing travelers without adequate escorts. This attitude may have been warranted, since the Mansos experienced many injustices and slave raids at the hands of the Spanish explorers.

The Nuestra Señora de Guadalupe de los Manso del Paso del Norte was built for the Manso Indians. By the late seventeenth century the Manso led several uprisings against the Spaniards. A few Mansos from the Mission revolted against Spanish brutality in 1684. As the Manso leaders were fleeing possible arrest, the Suma and Jano of La Soledad, Santa Gertrudis and San Francisco de Toma missions revolted. The Jacome and Chinarra Indians also joined the uprisings. Although the Manso leaders were caught and hanged, violent skirmishes lasted until 1698.

Spanish records from 1711 document the Mansos as an independent group. However, by 1751 the Manso history is mixed with other Indian groups, but still listed on the Guadalupe mission documents. In 1728, two distinct Indian groups were associated with the Guadalupe mission.

The Pueblo Arriba or Pueblo de los Mansos and the Pueblo Abajo or Pueblo de los Piros, would later merge after a devastating epidemic killed many in 1748. By the 1760s, the few Mansos that lived in the Guadalupe mission area lost their tribal organization. Many were also assimilated into the multi-cultural community. A few Mansos left the El Paso area and migrated to the Las Cruces area. These Manso and other Indians from Senecū and Ysleta del Sur would become known as the Tortuga Indians.

Some archaeologists believe the Manso Indians are descended from the El Paso phase of the Jornada Mogollon. Historically, Manso territory encompassed an area within the geographical distribution of the Jornada Mogollon. Researchers contend that because the Manso lived in permanent structures, some El Paso phase pueblo sites might have actually been occupied by Manso Indians. Some archaeologists believe that the Jornada Mogollon area was abandoned during the El Paso phase. Others argue that this theory is based only on ceramic cross-dating and that discounting known late radiocarbon, archaeomagnetic, obsidian hydration, and thermoluminescence dates from brown ware sites is wrong. They further argue that ecological changes caused by climatic fluctuations altered habitation and subsistence patterns, although complete abandonment did not happen. No known Manso sites have been recorded on Fort Bliss (but see Seymour 2002).

2.5.2.4 Apache Indians

Anthropologists recognize Apaches as the southernmost extent of the Athabascan language family. Northern Athabascans historically occupied much of interior Alaska and western Canada. Linguistic analysis indicates that the separation of southern Athabascans from the northern Athabascans occurred relatively recently. The Spanish observed two groups of bison hunters on the southern Plains in 1541. Querechos occupied territory north of the Canadian River and the Teyas occupied the south side. The Querechos are widely accepted as being southern Athabascan, while the Teyas probably represented the Plains Jumano. Plains Apaches around 1600 were called Vaquero Apache and hunted bison and traded with the more sedentary residents to the east and west.

In the Tularosa Basin, Apaches were dominant. Apache social organization however, makes it difficult to determine how different groups were related to each other or their origins. Confusing the matter further, a multitude of names, many obsolete, were applied to the Apaches by Spanish explorers and colonist.

The Apaches del Perrillo occupied areas north of the Mansos and east and southeast of the Piro Pueblos. During the Spanish expedition of 1598, a small dog had discovered a water spring in the Jornada del Muerto. Therefore, the spring and the Apaches of the area were named Perrillo. In addition, the Apaches del Perrillo may have been composed of bands later identified as Mescalero Apache and may have become known later as the Sierra Blanca Apaches.

**Figure 2.2: Possible Defensive Wall
(from Seymour 2002)**

The Mescalero Apache ranged over southeastern New Mexico and extreme western Texas. They were recognized in Spanish records of the seventeenth century as a separate Tribe. These semi-nomadic people were also hunters and gatherers who seasonally hunted bison. During the 1650s Mescalero Apaches became more prominent in the Tularosa Basin and Hueco Bolson. In response to Spanish attacks, the Mescalero Apaches raided pueblos under Spanish protection. West of the Organ Mountains, the Apaches attacked settlements of Doña Ana (just north of modern Las Cruces) and Mesilla, and then retreated through the San Augustine Pass, taking refuge in Soledad Canyon or the Sacramento Mountains.

Conflicts continued between the Puebloan people and the Spanish settlers on one side and the Apaches on the other. In the 1600s Apache raiders attacked from strongholds located in the mountains surrounding the Tularosa Basin. Raiding increased during the Pueblo Revolt. As the pueblos were abandoned, the Apaches most likely migrated north. By the early eighteenth century the Comanche began to encroach on Apache territory, thus straining natural resources. The Apaches, in turn, raided the ever expanding and struggling El Paso settlements. By the mid- to late-eighteenth century, Spanish military from the Albuquerque/Santa Fe area and the Comanche from the east pressured the Apaches. By late 1777, the Mescalero Apaches in the Sierra Blanca, Sacramento, and Organ mountains wanted peace with the El Paso settlements. The Spanish signed a treaty with them in 1810, agreeing to supply rations and recognizing their right to inhabit land extending from the El Paso region north to the Sacramento Mountains. During the 1850s, travel through the Jornada del Muerto was extremely dangerous. Mexican towns along the Rio Grande organized themselves against Apache attacks. Other towns were simply abandoned. The last Apache battles occurred in 1880, in Dog Canyon on the western slopes of the Sacramento Mountains and Hembrillo Canyon in the San Andres Mountains. There are a few sites that are postulated as having Apache components based on Seymour 2002 and the “Cerro Rojo Complex”.

2.5.3 Historic

The Fort Bliss region has experienced more than 450 years of Euroamerican exploration, settlement and use including ranching, mining, oil and gas exploration, and military activities. This era is represented on Fort Bliss by both archaeological and architectural resources, beginning with the establishment of the Salt Trail by Spanish explorers in the mid-17th century and extending to 20th century Cold War military activities. The region fell under Spanish rule from 1581 to 1821 when Mexico won its independence. Mexico ruled the region from 1821 to 1848 when it was acquired by the United States through the 1853 Gadsden Purchase. Nine hundred and seventy-five (975) sites with at least one historic component have been recorded on the installation. The vast majority are undated trash dumps/artifact scatters, followed by some type of water feature (for example, tanks, aqueducts, cisterns, dams). Other site types include historic and military camps, military features, firing ranges and firing towers, and ranches and homesteads. The following provides the historic contexts under these three periods.

2.5.3.1 Spanish Exploration and Settlement

(See Faunce 1997, Timmons 1990, Metz 1993)

The Chamuscado-Rodriquez expedition under Captain Francisco Sanchez Chamuscado was the first Spanish entry into the El Paso region in 1581. This expedition crossed through the Rio Grande pass between the Franklin Mountains and the Sierra de Juárez on their way up the Rio Grande. The route that the expedition followed became the Camino Real, connecting Mexico City with Santa Fe, New Mexico. The pass between the Franklin Mountains and the Sierra de Juárez became known as the El Paso del Norte (Pass of the North). Two Franciscan friars with the expedition continued onward after the expedition turned to return home.

The next Spanish expedition to enter the El Paso region was the Espejo expedition in 1582, consisting of Don Antonio de Espejo, two priests and fifteen soldiers. The purpose of this expedition was in part to rescue the earlier expedition's Franciscans. The Espejo expedition followed the Rio Grande north from El Paso del Norte. Learning that the Franciscans had been killed, the expedition continued on into what is now Arizona, looking for mineral wealth. Both these expeditions provide descriptions of the indigenous peoples they encountered.

No further expeditions were sent into the El Paso region until 1598 when an expedition was formed under the leadership of Don Juan de Oñate. The intent of this expedition was to formally claim areas to counter England's interests in North America and to establish a settlement in New Mexico. Oñate held a formal ceremony on April 30, 1598 at a site near present day San Elizario taking possession of the entire territory drained by the Rio del Norte (present day Rio Grande). A few days later, the expedition crossed the Rio del Norte with Oñate naming where they forded "El Paso del Rio del Norte." The expedition continued up the river establishing his capital at San Juan Pueblo, 25 miles north of Santa Fe. Don Pedro de Peralto founded the city of Santa Fe and became the capital in 1610. Caravans were formed to supply Santa Fe following the Camino Real from Mexico City. It took the caravans six months to travel the 1,500 mile trip, with El Paso del Norte the halfway point.

In 1647, the Salt Trail was established by the Spanish. This trail ran from the mining districts in Durango, Mexico, through El Paso del Norte along the eastern slope of the Organ Mountains to

Lake Lucero where salt deposits were being mined. Two more salt deposits were discovered in 1691 in the eastern Tularosa Basin. These deposits supplied huge quantities of salt that was shipped down the Camino Real to the silver mines. This trail and mining of the salt represents the first known excursions by the Spanish into the Tularosa Basin.

Two friars established the Mission Nuestra Señora de Guadalupe at El Paso del Rio del Norte in 1656. It was abandoned two years later but reestablished as a permanent mission in 1659. The mission attracted Spanish settlers, Jumanos, Sumas, Tanos, Mansos, and Apaches to settle around it. By 1680, it became a civilian Spanish community under the jurisdiction of Nueva Vizcaya. In 1665, the mission San Francisco de los Sumas was established near where Oñate had taken possession of the region in 1598. A third mission, Nuestra Señora de la Soledad was established at Janos near Casas Grandes. These three missions accounted for the Spanish settlements in the El Paso del Norte region in 1680.

In 1680, the Pueblo Indians of northern New Mexico revolted against the Spanish. This resulted in forcing the Spanish population out of the region and relocating to El Paso del Norte. As part of this relocation, the Tigua were brought to El Paso del Norte with the Spanish exodus, first in 1680 and then again in 1682 (Gerald 2000). This population relocation spurred the establishment of new missions and communities. By 1682, five settlements had been founded; El Paso del Norte, San Lorenzo, Senecú, Ysleta and Socorro, in a chain along the right bank of the Rio Grande. The missions consisted of Guadalupe, Santísimo Sacramento de la Ysleta, Senecú, Santa Gertrudis de los Sumas and San Francisco de los Sumas.

There was an outbreak of Indian hostilities in 1684 along the Rio Grande. It was not until a year later that peace was restored. The outbreak emphasized the need for a more compact arrangement of Spanish settlements. By the eighteenth century, only El Paso del Norte, San Lorenzo, Senecú, Ysleta and Socorro remained. Not only had the settlements decreased in number, the 1684 census identified a population of 1,051 people living in the settlements, down approximately 50% from the 1680 census. In spite of all the problems and cost in maintaining the El Paso settlements, Spain's fear of possible French intrusion into New Mexico made abandonment of these settlements unthinkable.

Spanish presence in the region increased in the eighteenth century. Irrigation ditches were constructed to stimulate agriculture along the river. Vineyards and orchards were planted along with grains. As agriculture grew, so did the population and its ability to be self-supporting. By 1760, the population had grown to over 4,700 people. It also became a hub of trade between Santa Fe and Chihuahua. With this increase however, came an increase in raids of Spanish settlements and pueblos under Spanish protection since the 1650s, by the Gilénos, Mescalero and Natagés Apaches. These raids resulted in a series of expeditions sent into the region that continued through Mexico's independence from Spain in 1821. In the 1750s, the Apaches destroyed approximately four million pesos worth of property within a 200 mile radius of Chihuahua. Apache raids in northern Mexico between 1771 and 1776 killed over 1,900 people, captured over 150 others, made off with over 68,000 head of cattle, sheep, and goats and caused the abandonment of 116 haciendas and ranches. With the exception of the Salt Trail and expeditions sent against the Apache, little attention was given to the Tularosa Basin by the Spanish. This disinterest was due to the lack of water in the basin as well as the presence of the

Mescalero Apache. Portions of the Salt Trail are extant on Fort Bliss. No other cultural resources are known to be extant that represents Spanish activities on Fort Bliss. By Mexico's independence from Spain in 1821, the population around El Paso del Norte was approximately 8,000. The economic activities, agriculture, stock raising, and commerce continued to flourish, increasing the regions self-sufficiency. Emphasis was placed on colonizing the area around El Paso del Norte. In spite of granting a number of land grants, attempts to increase the settlements failed partly due to continuing Apache raids. Expansion of American interests into Mexican territory followed the Louisiana Purchase in 1803. It finally reached a head in 1846 when Mexico and the United States went to war over the expansionism and entry of Texas into the Union. With the end of the war in 1848, the territory that would become Arizona, New Mexico and California became possessions of the United States. No known cultural resources representing the Mexican period (1821-1848) are known to be extant on Fort Bliss.

2.5.3.2 United States Period

Following the acquisition of the territory in 1848, the United States began to establish military posts, explore and map the region, and report on natural resources and favorable routes to and through it. The region saw an influx of settlers and expansion into the Tularosa Basin. The arrival of the railroad had great impacts on El Paso and later establishment of permanent Fort Bliss began reshaping the landscape to that of the present. This period for purposes of understanding Fort Bliss' history is addressed in five sub-contexts of: 1) ranching, 2) railroad, 3) mining, 4) oil and gas exploration, and 5) United States military.

Ranches (see Faunce 1997)

Due to the lack of water and the threat of Apache attacks, the southern Tularosa Basin attracted few settlers before the 1860s. A few ranchers moved into the area in the late 1860s and the early 1870s, but the main ranches were established in the 1880s. Reasons for this vary, but the improvements in acquiring water and the Apaches being moved to reservations played a major role in the settlement of the basin and surrounding areas. Approximately 200 historical sites associated with ranching and homesteading have been identified on Fort Bliss. Many of the ranchers and homesteaders were involved in various types of land and water speculation and many were involved with mining and oil exploration. However, the need for and lack of water greatly influenced the way the land was used. The majority of the ranch and homestead sites have been determined eligible for listing in the National Register of Historic Places under Criterion A – association with development of ranching in the basin, Criterion B – identifying ranchers as significant individuals in the region's history of ranching, and Criterion D for the information that these sites are likely to yield in understanding this period of history. Also see Kenneth Faunce's *The Fort Bliss Preacquisition Project: A History of the Southern Tularosa Basin* pages 51-100 for a discussion of the early ranches and ranchers. And see Komulainen-Dillenburg and Perez (2013),

Figure 2.3: Bunkhouse at Don Lee's Ranch.

the *NRHP Evaluation, under Criterion D, of Eight Historic Properties: Development and Implementation of a New Historic Context, Fort Bliss Military Installation, Otero County, New Mexico*.

Railroads (see Faunce 1997 and Faunce 2005)

The railroads played an extremely important role in the settlement and development of large areas of the frontier west. They provided greater access to a wider range of markets and impacted society by bringing new ideas and standards, and a large influx of people to the various frontier regions. The Tularosa Basin and El Paso region experienced significant changes in economy, society, and growth of local communities as a result of the arrival of the railroads. The railroad also had a great impact on Fort Bliss, prompting its relocation closer to the rail line, and its advancement to a permanent post.

Railroad construction in the Tularosa Basin and El Paso region was part of the drive to construct a second transcontinental railroad. The Southern Pacific laid the first tracks into El Paso in 1881, working eastward from California in competition with the Texas and Pacific Railroad that was constructing a line from east to west. The Texas and Pacific Railroad ceased to run as a railroad in 1885, with Southern Pacific becoming the major rail line through El Paso. Properties associated with this route are not present on Fort Bliss. In 1924, Southern Pacific acquired the assets of the El Paso and Southwestern Railroad (see below). There are two historic archaeological sites associated with Southern Pacific's running of the later line on Fort Bliss.

Following the discovery of gold and coal deposits near Carrizozo, the White Oaks Railroad began planning to build a route along the eastern slope of the Organ Mountains from El Paso to San Augustine, White Sands, Tularosa, Carrizozo and White Oaks. By 1887, only five miles of roadbed had been constructed when the El Paso and Northeastern Railroad took it over. The Kansas City, El Paso and Mexican Railroad Company was formed in 1888 and took title to the short-lived El Paso and Northeastern Railroad. In 1897, with the route still not completed, the Kansas City, El Paso and Mexican Railroad Company went into receivership and was acquired by Charles Eddy. He changed the name of the line back to El Paso and Northeastern. By 1898, the rail was completed from El Paso to Alamogordo and shortly continued on to Carrizozo. Portions of this route can be found within the borders of Fort Bliss. There are five known historic archaeological sites on Fort Bliss associated with the El Paso and Northeastern Railroad.

Phelps Dodge founded the El Paso and Southwestern Railroad in 1900 to take over properties of the Arizona and Southeastern Railroad. The railroad continued building from the Arizona and Southeastern Railroad established rail beds eastward from Douglas, Arizona to Deming, New Mexico and finally reaching El Paso by late 1902. In 1905, the El Paso and Southwestern Railroad acquired the El Paso and Northeastern Railroad, adding its assets under the control of Phelps Dodge. In 1924, the Southern Pacific acquired the assets of the El Paso and Southwestern Railroad. A FY14 project, Evaluate Railroad Sites, was completed in the fall of 2015; a historic context on railroad-related sites on Fort Bliss was submitted as a deliverable. As of 2016, there are only nine (9) known historic archaeological sites or features on Fort Bliss associated with the early railroads.

Mining (see Faunce 1997)

Mining was a major industry in the mountains around the Tularosa Basin. Twenty-one historic archaeological sites have been identified representing some mining activities on Fort Bliss. The following is a discussion of mining activities by mountain range.

Organ Mountains

Mining in the Organ Mountains possibly started at an earlier date than other areas of the region. Although there have been tales of Spanish mining activities in the Organ Mountains, no indications of Spanish activities have been recorded. The Padre La Rue Mine is the most famous of the lost Spanish mines in the Organ Mountains. Reportedly, this mine existed in Soledad Canyon between Espiritu Santo Springs and La Gueva de las Vegas. People have been searching for this mine without any success.

Silver deposits were first reported in the Organ Mountains at the beginning of the nineteenth century. It was not however, until the 1840s that mining in the area became important. Two mines, the Refugion silver mine and the nearby Mariano Barela mine existed at this time. The general location of these two mines put them in the present Fort Bliss boundary however, neither has been found. Additional mines were established after the United States' purchase of the region. A large silver vein was discovered in 1849 north of Fillmore Canyon that was worked by numerous owners over the next four decades. Although not within the Fort Bliss boundaries, this discovery brought more interest in the Organ Mountains. In 1853, a claim for the Santa Susana mine, near the Refugion mine, was filed. This was followed by the Las Cruces mine. These mines produced silver, copper, and lead and were possibly within the Fort Bliss boundaries. These have not been found. Mining continued in the Organ Mountains through the 1850s and 1860s, but it was not until the settlement of the Mescalero Apache and the arrival of the railroad to El Paso that mining activities increased.

Hundreds of mining claims were filed in the 1880s for the Texas Canyon area of the Organ Mountains, the Black Mountain, and Cottonwood Canyon areas of the San Andres Mountains. In 1882, the Organ Mountain Mining and Smelting Association produced a promotional pamphlet that is a perfect example of the high hopes for these areas. Most of the mines in the Organ Mountains were not on land that became part of Fort Bliss. L.W. Lenoir filed a claim in October 1883 on the Soleda Mine south of Soledad Canyon and later built a mill near the claim. Soledad Canyon became the location of several mining claims throughout the 1880s. Mines located within Fort Bliss boundaries were small producers or prospect holes. None of these claim sites have been located. Mining and prospecting continued until the acquisition by the United States Government of the land area presently in the Fort Bliss boundary.

Hueco Mountains

Little is known about mining activities in the Hueco Mountains. One mining site has been recorded within the Fort Bliss boundaries, but who developed the claim is unknown. There are indications that prospecting occurred throughout the area but did not result in finding any large deposits.

Jarilla Mountains

The Jarilla Mountains are outside the boundaries of Fort Bliss but the mining boom in these mountains had a significant impact on the area. The boom brought in more settlers, increased use of the railroad, and led to the expansion of the water control systems in the area. Also, many ranchers and homesteaders became involved in various mining activities in the mountains.

Franklin Mountains

A smelter opened in El Paso in 1887 due to the increased mining activity in the Franklin Mountains and the surrounding area. There are five (5) recorded mine sites in that portion of the Franklin Mountains that fall within the Fort Bliss boundaries. Overall historic mining context for the Franklin Mountains appears to be lacking. Dates when the five mine sites were established as well as the owners are unknown.

Sacramento Mountains

Although several claims were filed in the Sacramento Mountains and homesteaders tried their luck, no large mines were established and no rich lodes were found. The boom in the Jarilla Mountains may have caused a flurry of claims in the Sacramento Mountains in 1909. No recorded mining sites in the Sacramento Mountains are within the Fort Bliss boundaries.

Oil and Gas Exploration (see Faunce 1997)

An oil and gas exploration craze swept through the Tularosa Basin in 1919. At the beginning of 1919, fossils were recovered in the Sacramento Mountains and the Tularosa Basin that indicated the Tularosa Basin was part of the Pennsylvania series, which contained extensive oil deposits in other parts of the world. Geologists also located porous sands 200 feet thick in the basin, which indicated to the people of the area that large amounts of oil were beneath the Tularosa Basin. By April of 1919, the land office in Santa Fe was buried in thousands of mineral claims for oil and gas exploration. Mineral patents for that month alone totaled more than 200,000 acres of land in New Mexico. Oil companies were created quickly, and oil promoters were in the area in force seeking investors. Many state officials warned people that investing in the oil companies would be hazardous to their financial future. One company advertised that it had asked for approximately two million acres of land for oil leases, selling stock in its venture at ever increasing prices while the company had never leased even one acre of land and had never drilled a single test well. Many of the basin's ranchers, homesteaders, miners, and railroad employees ventured into the craze. The W. W. Cox Oil Company, formed by W.W. Cox and his family and considered one of the more financially stable oil companies in New Mexico, established the Cox State well in November 1919. The company never struck oil and Cox went bankrupt.

The oil craze lasted throughout 1920 but the basin did not develop into the rich oil fields that were predicted. Most of the oil ventures and partnerships had failed by the early 1920s. No major wells were discovered and not one struck it rich. In spite of this, the oil boom had a significant impact on the region. Large amounts of time and money were invested in the oil craze, and oil played a role in the failure of several ranches and business. More than 2,300 oil

and gas claims were filed within the boundaries of Fort Bliss. Approximately 39 historic archaeological sites have been identified representing oil and gas exploration activities on Fort Bliss. Much of this is identified based on lands filed as oil and gas claims.

United States Military

The Army's history in the El Paso region began in 1848. The first of a series of five forts that led to the present Fort Bliss location was established in 1849. The history of Fort Bliss from that date to present can be addressed in 11 historic contexts with some further divided into sub-contexts. These historic contexts are 1) Early, 2) the Formative Years, 3) Spanish-American War/Philippine Insurrection Period, 4) Early New Army Period, 5) The Mexican Revolution, 6) World War I, 7) Creation of a Permanent Cavalry Post, 8) Fort Bliss in the 1920s, 9) Fort Bliss in the 1930s, 10) World War II, and 11) Cold War Era. The following provides a brief discussion of these periods along with the number of extant buildings constructed during the periods that have been determined eligible for inclusion in the National Register of Historic Places.

Early

Two factors, geography and diplomacy, were the principal elements in the decision by the United States Army to establish a fort at the "Pass of the North," the site of present-day El Paso. The United States government established its international boundary with Mexico after the Treaty of Guadalupe Hidalgo that ended the Mexican War was signed in 1848 and the Gadsden Purchase was completed in 1853. In 1854, the second site of Fort Bliss was built near the small settlement of Magoffinsville. Initially, it served as one of a chain of southwestern forts that protected Americans heading to California in the 1850s gold rushes.

This post was abandoned by union forces when Texas seceded from the Union in 1861. It was re-occupied by the confederates shortly after its abandonment. The confederate forces burned the fort as they abandoned it in 1862 following their defeat in northern New Mexico and their subsequent evacuation of New Mexico and Texas.

The post was rebuilt in 1865 only to be abandoned again in 1868 when a new post was constructed three miles north of the Rio Grande. The new location was selected to escape periodic flooding of the old fort located along the Rio Grande. The garrison was transferred out of the region in 1877, which led once again to abandonment of the fort. In 1878, troops were moved back into the area and yet another fort was built at Hart's Mill on the banks of the Rio Grande. Here it remained until it was moved to its present location in 1893. No properties from this time period are represented on Fort Bliss.

The Formative Years (1890-1898) (see Jameison 1993)

The Formative Years represent the first decade of the establishment of present day Fort Bliss. This period saw the move of Fort Bliss from Hart's Mill to the La Noria mesa. This period saw Fort Bliss become and expand as a permanent regimental post along the border. Twenty-seven (27) buildings and a parade ground are extant from this period on Fort Bliss and contribute to the Fort Bliss Main Post Historic District.

Figure 2.4: Officers' Row along present day Sheridan Road, late 1880s.

Spanish-American War/Philippine Insurrection Period (1898-1902)

In April 1898, the United States declared war on Spain and the Spanish-American War broke out. It was over a short five (5) months later, with the United States defeating the Spanish Pacific Fleet in Manila Bay and its Atlantic Fleet at Santiago, Cuba. As an outcome of this war, the United States acquired the Philippines, Guam, and Puerto Rico from Spain and annexed Hawaii. Shortly after the end of the Spanish-American War, United States control of the Philippines was challenged by the Philippine Insurrection that lasted until 1902.

The Spanish-American War confirmed the United States' new expansionist foreign policy and launched the nation into world affairs. In mobilizing for its first foreign war since 1848, weaknesses were revealed in the organization and administration of the United States Army. More than 2,500 soldiers died of disease while only 345 were killed in battle during the Spanish-American War and 5,500 died of disease with approximately 1,500 killed in battle during the Philippine Insurrection. This period saw the United States move beyond its continental interests and began to experience the difficulties that accompany involvement in foreign affairs. For the first time, the military had personnel stationed overseas.

During this period, Fort Bliss had only a skeletal garrison, containing never more than 100 soldiers. Its permanent garrison was deployed in Puerto Rico and the Philippines. It was not until 1902 and the end of the Philippine Insurrection that Fort Bliss was once again to its full complement of troops. There was no construction on Fort Bliss during this period and no extant buildings achieved significance under this context.

Early New Army Period (1902-1910) (see Jameison 1993)

This period witnessed the development of a new, twentieth-century United States Army. The army underwent several reorganizations with service schools strengthened as well a movement to create a professional officer corps. Twentieth-century technology produced the machine gun, the airplane, improved artillery, and motorized forms of transportation.

Fort Bliss had fallen into disrepair since the previous period. Although still a quiet, small post on a distant frontier, it underwent major renovation during 1905 and 1906. These two years are seen as a turning point for Fort Bliss in that it was recognized as having a future in the Army's

plans. It was also believed that the fort would take on more importance in regard to border issues. This period represents the last lull in Fort Bliss' history. Six extant buildings have been identified as being constructed during this period. These contribute to the Fort Bliss Main Post Historic District.

Punitive Expedition and the Mexican Revolution (1910-1917) (see Jameison 1993)

The Mexican Revolution led to Fort Bliss becoming a major horse cavalry post. Fighting in northern Mexico spilled across the Rio Grande. Border violations, violence, and arms smuggling made an increased American police presence along the border necessary.

During the Mexican Revolution, Fort Bliss played a significant role in local, regional, and national history for the first time. Also, because of its strategic border location, the fort became important in the international confrontations that occurred during the revolution. The Punitive Expedition and the Zimmerman Telegram affair kept international attention focused on the border during this period.

Figure 2.5: Pancho Villa (center) with General Pershing (right) 1914.

Figure 2.6: Camp Cotton 1916.

The Punitive Expedition is the best-known episode of American involvement in the Mexican Revolution. The expedition represented a turning point in American military history. It was the first major test of the new American Army of the twentieth century. Airplanes were used for the first time in a field operation and other new transport systems and logistical techniques were tested. It provided a training school for the American Army for World War I. Fort Bliss served a number of strategic and

logistical functions. Its most important role was as a base camp for patrol operations. These patrol operations culminated in the Punitive Expedition. Contemporaneous with this, a ring of base camps were built around Fort Bliss to house newly mobilized National Guard troops. Troops operating from Fort Bliss attempted to control the flow of weapons into Mexico and escorted Mexican troops back across the border. The post played an additional role as a reception center for Mexican refugees, the wounded, and prisoners. Finally, Fort Bliss served as a supply point for American troops in the Southwest.

Fifty (50) extant buildings have been identified as having been constructed during this period and contribute to the Fort Bliss Main Post Historic district.

World War I (1917-1919) (see Jameison 1993)

World War I brought increased involvement by the United States in European and world affairs. The American Expeditionary Force (AEF) was the largest force mobilized in the 142 years of American military history. By September 1918, the AEF was more than five (5) times the size

of the largest Civil War armies. The contributions of Fort Bliss to the American war effort are important and the years 1917 to 1919 are important in the post's history.

Fort Bliss contributed to the American war effort in a variety of ways, none of which however, appear to be unique or unusual. By the time the United States entered World War I, the Mexican Revolution had made Fort Bliss a major military installation. Fort Bliss's first service to the war effort was as an enlistment post. During the war years, Fort Bliss was surrounded by a ring of auxiliary camps where support units were stationed and troops were mobilized for the European war. Several training schools such as the Fort Bliss Cavalry School and Southern Department Machine Gun School were also established. Many units passed through Fort Bliss on their way to the Western Front. After the war, the post served as a demobilization area. Department Base Hospital No. 2, organized in 1916 during the Punitive Expedition, became a United States Base Hospital during WWI. Auxiliary camps that ringed Fort Bliss during WWI included camps Boyd, Courchesne, Newton D. Baker, Stewart and Bierne (established during the Mexican War period). These auxiliary camps were not intended to be more than temporary encampments and were removed once the war ended. In addition, Fort Bliss had its own cavalry camp to accommodate the influx of troops.

Extant buildings constructed during this period are included in the previous period. Although it is known that 50 (fifty) extant buildings were associated with the Mexican Revolution, no studies have been undertaken to determine if any surviving buildings were constructed to meet the mission requirements during World War I.

Creation of a Permanent Cavalry Post (1916-1920) (see Jameison 1993)

The extensive use of trenches, barbed wire, and defensive artillery had thrown the front lines of many WWI battlefields into a perpetual stalemate. This tactical deadlock was resolved by introducing airplanes and tanks, the weapons of the future. As a result of these major advancements in warfare technology, cavalry had little to no engagement opportunities during WWI. Incongruously, Fort Bliss became a major horse cavalry installation as the cavalry arm of the Army was in decline. Several general causes contributed to the fort's increased dependence on cavalry: the Mexican Revolution and the strategic border location of Fort Bliss; superior control and agility of horse cavalry to wheeled-vehicles over the rocky and uneven terrain; and the post's proximity to El Paso's extensive railroad network. By 1921, the 1st Cavalry Division had been established at the fort and the appropriate facilities had been constructed to support the division.

Ten (10) extant buildings constructed during this time have been identified to have direct associations with Fort Bliss's transition to permanent Cavalry post. These buildings are all contributing resources to the Fort Bliss Main Post Historic District.

Fort Bliss in the 1920s (see Jameison 1993)

In the 1920s, Fort Bliss emerged as a major cavalry installation. Its strategic mission was to safeguard the Southwest border. World War I left most Americans war weary and resistant toward further involvement in European affairs. The Federal administration pursued an isolationist foreign policy and reduced the army to peacetime strength, cutting army manpower

from about 227,000 to 146,000. The War Department's spending fell from 48.8% of Federal outlays in 1919 to 13.6% by 1929.

In spite of these cut-backs, Fort Bliss remained important for its strategic border location, proximity to a railroad center, and potential for training and expansion. During this period, the development of the airplane raised the possibility that air communication might become as important as railroad communication. Fort Bliss was on one of the best coast-to-coast air routes in light of its mild winters. The 1920s saw major expansion of the fort not only in its building stock but in acquiring new lands to expand its training capabilities for both the cavalry and field artillery. That expansion included Biggs Field, Castner Range, and William Beaumont General Hospital. Forty-two (42) extant buildings contributing either to the Fort Bliss Main Post Historic District or the William Beaumont Hospital District (2 of the 42) were constructed during this period.

Fort Bliss in the 1930s (see Jameison 1993)

The 1920s expansion caused a housing shortage on Fort Bliss that was not resolved until the 1930s. The 1930s were shaped by the Great Depression caused by the Great Stock Market Crash of 1929. Roosevelt's administration placed its efforts on ending the depression. Conservative spending that marked the 1920s was reversed in an effort to put Americans back to work and end the depression. Fort Bliss benefited from the national funding programs to address its housing shortages. Through funding provided by the Works Program Administration (WPA) and the National Industrial Recovery Act (NIRA) as well as military funding, Fort Bliss witnessed a construction boom. This period saw the construction of not only housing but also barracks. All contracts were let to local contractors to provide local employment opportunities.

Figure 2.7: Aerial of Fort Bliss, 1934.

Fort Bliss was also involved in the Civilian Conservation Corps (CCC), a New Deal agency that employed young men to work on park development and conservation projects. The 1st Cavalry Division assumed operation of the Arizona-New Mexico CCC District, providing manpower and headquarters for CCC companies that at one time numbered more than 62,500 men.

One hundred ninety-seven extant buildings have been identified as having been constructed during this period and all contribute to the Fort Bliss Main Post Historic District.

World War II (see Jameison 1993)

Fort Bliss entered World War II as a Cavalry installation and by the end of the war had become the country's anti-aircraft artillery center, home to the Anti-Aircraft Artillery School and the Anti-Aircraft Artillery Board. Troops were trained here for posting throughout the war effort, manning anti-aircraft artillery. Biggs Army Airfield became a hub of training activity for B-17, B-24 and B-29 crews.

Most buildings constructed during World War II were wood frame, temporary structures. A nationwide Programmatic Memorandum of Agreement (PMOA) signed in 1993, removes World War II Temporary buildings from further Section 106 consultation regarding demolition; any other actions will go through the regular 106 procedures. Nineteen buildings are managed under this PMOA. See Appendix J for Table.

Cold War Era

The end of World War II left the United States and the Union of Soviet Socialist Republics (U.S.S.R or Soviets) as the world's dominant military powers. During the war the two nations were allied. Within a very short time after the war a multidimensional conflict ensued between the two superpowers. Known as the Cold War, the hostile confrontation began without any formal declaration of war but defined international politics and superpower military strategies for over four decades.

At the core of the Cold War, was an ideological battle between the competing economic and political systems of democratic capitalism and totalitarian communism. Each side saw the other's system as a potentially mortal threat. The Cold War involved worldwide geopolitical strategies, as each side sought alliances in Europe and in the developing world. The initial tensions occurred in Europe, where the danger of escalation from standoff to full-scale superpower battle was very high. Over the years, limited proxy wars occurred outside that arena in Korea, Vietnam, and Afghanistan. The United States and the Soviets did not engage one another in a direct hot war, although military planners on both sides always prepared for that contingency. Part of that preparation involved creating and sustaining a large military-industrial complex. With the advent of nuclear weapons and the systems for delivering them, technology itself became a critical front in the Cold War.

The Cold War's dates are approximate. Winston Churchill's well-known 1946 Iron Curtain speech generally marks the Cold War's onset while the official dissolution of the U.S.S.R. in 1991 marks its close. Alternatively some sources use 1989 and the fall of the Berlin wall as the close of the Cold War. Stretching over the forty-five year period, the conflict went through several phases as outlined below.

Onset and Containment (1946-1953)

The first instances of "onset and containment" began during the Truman administration between 1946 and 1952. By 1947, the administration established the Truman Doctrine, a containment policy to limit growth of communist spheres of influence with implicit and explicit military threats. This formalization of containment was paired with the Marshall Plan, and economic development program for at-risk nations in post-war Europe. The Berlin airlift of 1948 was the first major military application of containment, followed by the Korean War from 1950 to 1953. During this period, Biggs Army Airfield was turned over to the newly formed United States Air Force and became the Biggs Air Force Base under the Strategic Air Command (SAC). The SAC base used the existing field and infrastructure to support its missions. Fort Bliss continued to provide training and testing support for Air Defense.

Seventy-seven (77) extant buildings constructed during this time period have been identified eligible for listing in the National Register of Historic Places. Four (6) consists of the replica of Old Fort Bliss built in 1948. The later are identified as contributing elements to the Fort Bliss Main Post Historic District.

Massive Retaliation (1953-1960)

The second period corresponds to the Eisenhower years between 1953 and 1960. “Massive retaliation” formed the major strategic policy of the United States during this period. Any communist aggression against United States allies worldwide would be met with nuclear response directed at the Soviets itself. The United States focused its military resources in this direction, rather than into maintaining large, expensive ground forces. At the same time, the technological landscape was changing. Soviet scientists unexpectedly exploded an atomic device in the fall of 1949, well before the Americans had estimated they could do so. A technological arms race was underway. During 1952 and 1953, both the United States and the Soviets developed nuclear fusion devices, and both nations achieved intercontinental ballistic missile capability only five years later.

Figure 2.8: Nike Training, late 1950s.

This period marks a large building program on Biggs Air Force Base to replace the World War II era buildings. Ninety six (96) properties have been identified and evaluated and one has been found individually eligible on Biggs Army Airfield. This period also saw a major building program throughout Fort Bliss, not only to replace World War II era buildings but to accommodate changing needs brought on by the Fort’s missions. A total of 128 buildings constructed during this phase have been determined eligible for listing on the National Register of Historic Places. The majority of these buildings are directly associated with missile programs, the Unaccompanied Personnel Housing (UPH) development on the Cantonment, and the three (3) range base camps. This period also saw the Capehart/Wherry housing programs to provide family housing on Post. This UPH and Capehart/Wherry housing, however, have been removed from further Section 106 review by a Program Comment for Cold War Era UPH (1946-1974) and Program Comment for Wherry and Capehart Era Army Family Housing and Associated Structures and Landscape Features (1949-1962).

Flexible Response (1961-1968)

A third phase of the Cold War took place during the Kennedy and Johnson administrations from 1961 through 1968. Some military leaders had been advocating for “flexible response,” believing that massive retaliation limited American options. Flexible response focused more resources on conventional capabilities and on options for limited warfare. In 1962, the Cuban Missile Crisis occurred when the Soviets placed intermediate-range ballistic missiles in Cuba, triggering a standoff with the Kennedy administration which nearly led to nuclear war. Following this crisis, the two superpowers avoided direct confrontation in each other’s

Figure 2.9: Building 1094. Eligible for inclusion in the NRHP as the Universal Missile Training Building, SAFEGUARD Central Training Facility (1973-1975) along with the silos located adjacent, to the right.

immediate spheres of influence, and the Cold War battleground moved primarily into the Third World.

During this phase, American involvement in the Vietnam conflict escalated to its highest levels. Thirty two (32) properties that were constructed during this period have been identified as eligible for inclusion on the National Register of Historic Places. They are equally divided between properties directly associated with various missile programs and UPH. This UPH however, have been removed from further Section

106 review through a Program Comment for Cold War Era UPH (1946-1974). Fort Bliss properties have been evaluated under the entire phase and are documented in a NRHP Multiple Property Documentation Form.

Détente (1969-1979)

In the fourth phase, beginning in 1969, the Cold War took another turn. Starting with the first Nixon administration, the United States practiced policies of détente, or peaceful co-existence with the Soviets. Under the surface, the superpower relationship continued to be hostile, but the two sides began to address issues such as nuclear arms control. By 1979, détente had collapsed and a renewed Cold War emerged in the next decade. Fort Bliss properties have been evaluated under this phase and are documented in a NRHP Multiple Property Documentation Form.

Reagan and Glasnost (1980-1991)

Internal politics within the U.S.S.R. and the East bloc countries gradually led to the collapse of satellite communist governments and to the dissolution of the U.S.S.R. in 1991, marking the end of the Cold War. Fort Bliss properties have not been evaluated under this phase.

2.6 Mission Statement

2.6.1 Present Mission(s)

The present mission is to train, sustain, mobilize and deploy members of the joint team to conduct global, full spectrum operations in support of the national military strategy, while providing for the well-being of the regional military community (see <https://www.bliss.army.mil/>).

2.7 Mission Activities that May Affect Cultural Resources

2.7.1 Activities Likely to Affect Archaeological Sites

- **Excavation:** Excavation and ground disturbing activities associated with military training activities can damage or destroy archaeological sites. Common training activities requiring excavation and ground disturbance may include but are not limited to trenches, bombing, artillery fire, foxholes, bivouacs, and tank traps. Engineering units train to provide infrastructure to combat units during combat situations. This training includes digging trenches to lay pipes and other utilities.
- **Off-Road Maneuver:** Various types of off road maneuver exercises will occur on Fort Bliss. These include use of tracked vehicles, a variety of truck types, troop carriers, and smaller four-wheel drive vehicles.
- **Construction:** Mission requirements may make construction of new facilities necessary. The excavations for building foundations, utilities, and roads, along with development of new ranges or upgrading existing ranges can disturb or destroy archaeological sites.
- **Static Positions:** Areas that will experience a concentration of troops and/or vehicles or other equipment for a variety of purposes.

NOTE: Any standing structure in the maneuver areas has been surrounded by off-limits signs and is periodically monitored for unauthorized intrusions. Other historic buildings are found only in the Cantonment and are not subject to maneuver or other range-type activities.

2.7.2 Activities likely to Affect Architectural Properties

- **Demolition:** Demolition of historic properties should be done where absolutely required to support Fort Bliss' mission. Army Regulations (AR) 200-1 requires building demolition address the demolition and removal of unsafe buildings and structures at facilities or sites that are or were owned by, leased to, or otherwise possessed by the United States and under the jurisdiction of the DOD. In lieu of demolition, Fort Bliss will consider alternatives for historic properties, including adaptive reuse.
- **Construction:** Mission requirements may make construction of new facilities necessary. Construction of new facilities has the potential to affect view sheds of Historic Districts and are evaluated for impacts before approval.
- **Landscaping:** Landscaping not consistent with a historic property's landscape during its period of significance can diminish the property's historic integrity.
- **Maintenance and Renovation:** Maintenance activities can destroy or alter features of a historic property that qualify it for inclusion in the National Register of Historic Places. Replacement of doors or windows with a new type can alter the historic character of a building. Painting with colors inconsistent with those in use during a building's period of significance can also have an adverse effect on a historic property.
- **No Action:** Avoidance and neglect of historic buildings and structures can result in the deterioration and loss of integrity. A decision not to maintain a historic

property is considered an undertaking and subject to the Programmatic Agreement (Appendix A).

2.8 Program Responsibilities

Fort Bliss is responsible for managing cultural resources on approximately 1.12 million acres in accordance with applicable Federal laws, regulations and guidelines (see Table 1.1) and this ICRMP is in compliance with those laws. AR 200-1 “Environmental Protection and Enhancement” outlines responsibilities at all levels, as well as specific Cultural Resources Program goals and requirements.

Management of cultural resources on Fort Bliss is an ongoing process. It is the responsibility of anyone who may initiate or undertake a project or activity on the fort that could affect a historic property. The Cultural Resources Manager (CRM) is responsible for coordinating compliance with cultural resources laws and regulations and administering the ICRMP on behalf of the Installation Commander

2.9 Installation Commander and Cultural Resources Manager

2.9.1 Garrison Commander

It is the GC’s responsibility to implement this plan and through his appointed Cultural Resources Manager (CRM), coordinate activities with this plan. Section 6.0, Implementing the ICRMP, more clearly identifies the responsibilities of the GC with respect to cultural resources management.

2.9.2 Cultural Resources Manager (CRM)

The CRM, designated by the GC and delegated authority per AR 200-1, is the expert in cultural resources and the administrator of the ICRMP. The CRM acts on behalf of the GC to coordinate compliance with this ICRMP. The CRM will meet the qualifications under the Secretary of Interior’s “Archaeology and Historic Preservation: Secretary of the Interior’s Standards and Guidelines (as amended and annotated)” (36 CFR 61). Section 6.0 Implementing the ICRMP identifies the responsibilities of the CRM. The CRM is located in the Directorate of Public Works - Environmental Division. As the individual responsible for the administration of this ICRMP, the CRM coordinates with users and interested parties to ensure compliance with cultural resources laws and regulations on Fort Bliss.

2.10 User Groups

Numerous organizations use Fort Bliss under host-tenant agreements. Other organizations arrive periodically to use the facilities under temporary agreements. Any of these users have the potential to affect the cultural resources on Fort Bliss and they must be made aware of laws and

regulations governing cultural resources and ensure their missions are in compliance with this ICRMP. Activities undertaken by the users that may affect cultural resources must be coordinated with the CRM as outlined in Section 4.0, Stipulations and Standard Operating Procedures. The following identifies key users of Fort Bliss.

2.10.1 1st Armored Division

Following BRAC and relocation to Fort Bliss, the 1st Armored Division has been reorganized under a modular design, including a Division Headquarters, 1/1 Stryker Brigade Combat Team (BCT), 2/1 Armored BCT, 3/1 Armored BCT, 1st Armored Division (AD) Combat Aviation Brigade (CAB), 1st AD Division Artillery (DIVARTY, and 15th Sustainment Brigade (SUS). Each BCT has supporting elements, including infantry, cavalry, field artillery, brigade support and brigade engineers. The CAB, DIVARTY and SUS also have support elements.

2.10.2 31st Combat Support Hospital

The 31st Combat Support Hospital provides Level III Health Service Support (as defined in Army doctrine) in combat zones, as well as worldwide contingency operations.

2.10.3 32nd Army Air and Missile Defense Command

The Army Air Missile Defense Command conducts air and missile defense planning, integration, coordination and execution. One brigade, the 11th Air Defense Artillery Brigade, is stationed at Fort Bliss the 11th Brigade has six subordinate units: 1-43, 2-43, 3-43, 5-52, A-2 Terminal High Altitude Area Defense (THAAD) and A-4 THAAD.

2.10.4 402nd Field Artillery Brigade

The 402nd Field Artillery Brigade is a training brigade, especially for Reserve and National Guards units, and includes live fire and detainee operations training.

2.10.5 5th Armored Brigade

The 5th Armored Brigade is a training brigade with supporting Regiments, especially for Reserve and National Guard units preparing for deployment.

2.10.6 93rd Military Police Battalion

The 93rd Military Police (MP) Battalion is stationed at Fort Bliss and is supported by six units: 202 MP, 212 MP, 591 MP, 978 MP, 72 Law and Order (L&O) MP, and 513 MP.

2.10.7 Brigade Modernization Command

The Future Force Integration Directorate was recently re-designated the Brigade Modernization Command. Their mission is to synchronize the delivery, preparation, and evaluation of all Future Combat Systems-related products.

2.10.8 Directorate of Mobilization and Deployment

The Directorate of Mobilization and Deployment supports all active, reserve, and guard units with mobilization and demobilization requirements.

2.10.9 Inspector General's Office

The Inspector General's (IG) Office is tasked to provide assistance for solving problems on an area basis for commanders, soldiers, family members, civilian employees, and retirees who seek help with problems as related to the United States Army. The IG Office also conducts inspections as prescribed by law or regulation and reports results to the directing authority, identifying root causes, and recommending solutions for implementation. It also conducts inquiries and investigations when tasked by the Commanding General.

2.10.10 Joint Task Force North

Joint Task Force-North is a joint-services command that supports all Federal law enforcement agencies in the identification and interdiction of suspected trans-national threats within and along the approaches to the continental United States.

2.10.11 Marine Corps Detachment

The Marine Corps Detachment at Fort Bliss is home to the Marine Corps' Low Altitude Air Defense Gunner Course.

2.10.12 United States Army Sergeants Major Academy

The mission of the United States Army Sergeants Major Academy is to develop agile and adaptive non-commissioned officers and enlisted soldiers through professional military education opportunities that meet the challenges of unified land operations in an area of persistent conflict.

2.10.13 William Beaumont Army Medical Center

William Beaumont Army Medical Center's (WBAMC) mission is to provide innovative, life-saving care to the largest power project platform in the Army in support of any mission, anytime, anywhere, to promote a safe environment of care to support a system for health and fitness for their community, and to cultivate talented medical professionals into tomorrow's medical leaders through education and cutting-edge research. The medical center also has a variety of clinics, as well as the Warrior Transition Battalion (WTB). The WTB provides command and control, primary medical management, risk mitigation, and comprehensive transition planning which facilitates the medical, social, and professional rehabilitation of Warriors back to the force or as productive veterans.

2.10.14 Garrison Command

The Garrison Command falls under the Installation Management Command (IMCOM) and is responsible for all base operations support for the installation.

2.10.15 Directorate of Human Resources

The Mission of the Directorate of Human Resources is to provide transition services to military personnel. This includes unit personnel readiness, force projection support, mobilization support, in- and out-processing, promotion, and retirement processing. The Civilian Personnel Advisory Center and the Adjunct General are also a part of DHR.

2.10.16 Directorate of Logistics

The Directorate of Logistics is responsible for providing logistical support to all DOD activities at Fort Bliss.

2.10.17 Directorate of Morale, Welfare and Recreation

The Directorate of Morale, Welfare, and Recreation (MWR) is a comprehensive network of support and leisure services designed to enhance the lives of soldiers (Active, Reserve, and Guard), their families, civilian employees, military retirees and other eligible participants. MWR employees worldwide strive to deliver the highest quality programs and services at each installation -- from family, child and youth programs to recreation, sports, entertainment, travel and leisure activities. Their mission is to serve the needs, interests and responsibilities of each individual in the Army community. MWR contributes to the Army's strength and readiness by offering services that reduce stress, build skills and self-confidence and foster strong *esprit de corps*.

2.10.18 Directorate of Plans, Training, Mobilization and Security

The Directorate of Plans, Training, Mobilization and Security (DPTMS) performs planning and operations functions for military training activities on Fort Bliss; DPTMS also manages and maintains all ranges. Through performance of its mission DPTSM controls all military training activities on the fort.

2.10.19 Directorate of Public Works

The Directorate of Public Works performs a variety of functions that include property management, engineering, housing, fire prevention, facilities maintenance and operation, grounds maintenance, refuse, and utilities. The Directorate of Public Works – Environmental Division performs a variety of functions including, but not limited to, environmental issues, natural resources management, and cultural resources management. The directorate has two branches, the Conservation Branch and the Compliance Branch.

2.10.20 Network Enterprise Center

Network Enterprise Center is responsible for and supports all aspects of information management at Fort Bliss, Texas to include management of telecommunications, automation, files and records, printing and publications, correspondence, forms, postal, and the Freedom of Information Act.

2.10.21 Equal Employment Opportunity

The goal of the Equal Employment Opportunity Office (EEO) is to manage workforce diversity and to maintain a discrimination-free workplace. The EEO at Fort Bliss ensures equal opportunity for civilians under Title VII of the Civil Rights Act of 1964. The primary purpose is to eliminate and prevent discrimination, to correct the effects of discrimination and achieve the goal of a representative workforce.

2.10.22 Public Affairs Office

The Public Affairs Office plays two major roles. It establishes and maintains good community relations between Fort Bliss and the local community through events, concerts, tours and publications. Secondly, it is responsible for telling the Army's story. *The Monitor*, published weekly by PAO, is the command's medium for disseminating news and information to local, state and national media. The PAO also coordinates important community events, such as the Amigo Airshow and Armed Forces Day.

2.10.23 Mission Installation Contracting Command

The Mission Installation Contracting Command plans, integrates, awards and administers contracting throughout the deployment cycle and supports the Army commands.

2.10.24 Office of the Chaplain

The mission of the Fort Bliss Chaplain's Office is to develop, coordinate, and execute a comprehensive Command Master Religious Program in support of Commanders, Unit Ministry Teams, and the Total Army Community at Fort Bliss through Worship Opportunities, Pastoral Care, Family Enrichment Programs, Religious Education, Community Outreach Programs, and Ministry of Presence.

2.10.25 Office of the Staff Judge Advocate

The Staff Judge Advocate (SJA) performs all the legal functions for Fort Bliss. Through the Environmental Law Attorney, the SJA serves as legal advisor to the Installation Commander, the CRM, and the LEC on cultural resources. The SJA reviews draft cultural resources documents in accordance with AR 200-1, and serves as counsel for the Army in appropriate administrative cases, hearings, and enforcement actions.

2.10.26 Safety Office

The mission of the Fort Bliss Safety Office is to provide Team Bliss commanders and soldiers with quality safety support in accomplishing their missions and to provide a healthy safe working and living environment for soldiers, civilians, and family members of the Team Bliss community.

2.10.27 Army and Air Force Exchange Service

The Army and Air Force Exchange Service (AAFES) maintains a wide variety of retail merchandise, food and service outlets to meet the needs of Soldiers, retirees and their families.

2.10.28 Banking and Credit Union Facilities

Fort Bliss soldiers, families, employees and retired personnel are served by two banking facilities and one credit union located on post. These include First Light Federal Credit Union, Armed Forces Bank, and Wells Fargo Bank.

2.10.29 United States Customs and Border Protection

The priority mission of the Customs and Border Protection is preventing terrorists and terrorist's weapons, including weapons of mass destruction, from entering the United States. Border Patrol Agents patrol nearly 6,000 miles of international land border with Canada and Mexico and nearly 2,000 miles of coastal border. The El Paso sector covers the entire state of New Mexico and the two westernmost counties in Texas, Hudspeth and El Paso.

2.10.30 United States Postal Service

The United States Postal Service operates several post offices on Fort Bliss. These include facilities on the main cantonment, Biggs Army Airfield, McGregor Range and WBAMC.

2.10.31 United State Veteran's Administration

The Veteran's Administration Health Care System (VAHCS) opened its facility in October 1995 adjacent to WBAMC, and consists of nearly 250,000 square feet housed within a four story building. The VAHCS provides primary and specialized ambulatory services to veterans in the El Paso and surrounding counties and also operates a Community Based Outpatient Clinic in Las Cruces, New Mexico. The Veteran's Administration also operates and manages the Fort Bliss National Cemetery.

2.10.32 Federal Prison

The Federal Prison Camp at Fort Bliss is a satellite low security facility to the larger La Tuna Federal Correctional Institution (FCI) in Anthony, Texas. Low threat inmates are frequently seen doing community service on Fort Bliss.

2.10.33 Fort Bliss Museum and Study Center

The Fort Bliss Museum and Study Center identifies, collects, researches, preserves, and interprets historically significant military properties dating from 1848 to the present. These programs provide for scholarly research, enhanced morale, and strengthen the strong relationship that exists between the United States military and surrounding communities. It provides a repository for the history of Fort Bliss and shows the impact of the United States Army on El Paso, the southwest, the nation and the world. The programs and exhibits serve to educate youth and adult alike.

2.10.34 El Paso Independent School District

The El Paso Independent School District (EPISD) has three (3) public schools located on Fort Bliss lands. EPISD leases the land. Three (3) additional public schools, initially constructed on Fort Bliss lands, have been deeded to EPISD. EPISD is responsible for cultural resources management of properties they have on leased Fort Bliss lands.

2.10.35 German Air Force Air Defense School

The core of the German Air Force Air Defense School is training in weapon related systems, tactical and technical training and advanced training of Hawk and Patriot surface to air missile systems. In 1966, the school was relocated from Aachen, Germany to Fort Bliss. (German Air Force Command moved to Holloman Air Force Base in September 2013 and the Air Defense Center will be moving back to Germany by 2017).

The German Air Force (GAF) Command is the superior GAF Headquarters on the North American Continent. The mission of the GAF Command is to represent German interests to the United States military, coordinate between German and United States headquarters, conduct tactical training of operational units and to recommend proposals for the further development and adaptation of training to the needs of the operational units.

2.10.36 Balfour Beatty Military Housing

Balfour Beatty Communities is responsible for the design, development, construction, renovation, operation and management of military housing projects for the DOD. These facilities were privatized, under the Military Privatization Initiative through the Residential Communities Initiative in 2004 however, Fort Bliss retains Section 106 oversight and responsibility.

2.11 Interested Parties

There are a number of organizations, both public and private, that have an expressed interest in cultural resources on Fort Bliss. As interested parties, they may be concerned with the effects of Army undertakings on cultural resources. Under the NHPA, all of these parties are given opportunities to participate in the Section 106 process. Under the American Indian Religious Freedom Act (AIRFA), interested parties are limited to those Federally recognized Tribes that

may have sacred sites on lands managed by Fort Bliss with a responsibility to determine, in consultation with Fort Bliss, appropriate protection and preservation measures of Native American religious cultural rights and practices as they may be affected by Fort Bliss missions. Under the NAGPRA interested parties are those Tribes (1) whose aboriginal lands now fall under Fort Bliss management; (2) that are or are likely to be culturally affiliated with remains uncovered or that may be expected to be encountered during an undertaking; and (3) that have a demonstrated cultural relationship with the remains uncovered or that may be expected to be encountered during an undertaking. If the results of consultation with the appropriate tribes trigger Section 106 of the NHPA, then the appropriate State Historic Preservation Office (SHPO) will become an interested party. These organizations are identified below but should not be considered complete. It is likely that other organizations, not included here, will have interests in cultural resources on the fort.

2.11.1 Advisory Council on Historic Preservation

The Advisory Council on Historic Preservation (ACHP) is an independent Federal agency responsible for reviewing policies and programs of Federal agencies to ensure their consistency with the policies and programs of the NHPA, as amended. The ACHP provides guidance on the application of the procedures in the Section 106 process and generally oversees the operation of the Section 106 process. Although identified in this section as an interested party, the ACHP is a concurring party in the Army's management of historic properties under the NHPA.

2.11.2 Bureau of Land Management

The Bureau of Land Management (BLM) has management responsibility for non-military activities on withdrawn lands on Fort Bliss (McGregor Range). This responsibility is defined by Public Law 99-606, The Military Lands Withdrawal Act of 1986, by the Federal Lands Policy Management Act (FLPMA) of 1976 and by the Memorandum of Understanding between Fort Bliss and BLM (2006). These responsibilities include management of cultural resources in the withdrawal areas.

2.11.3 El Paso County Historical Commission

The El Paso County Historical Commission (EPCHC) has statutory responsibility to initiate and conduct historic preservation programs suggested by El Paso County Commissioners Court and the Texas Historical Commission (THC). In El Paso, the EPCHC works in a dynamic and positive partnership with the THC to preserve El Paso's heritage for the use, education, enjoyment and economic benefit of present and future generations. They have been responsible for the preservation of historic buildings, artifacts, documents and other pieces of Texas history. The EPCHC is also responsible for reviewing all applications for state historical markers, including those at Fort Bliss, before they are sent to the THC. They also serve as advisors to their commissioner's court on matters of historic preservation.

2.11.4 El Paso County Historical Society, Inc.

The mission of the El Paso County Historical Society, Inc. is to study local El Paso and El Paso County history, foster local research, acquire and preserve historical documents and archives,

make collections available to the public for research and information, encourage historical writing and publication, and to maintain and restore the Richard F. Burges House, home of the Society. Fort Bliss is significant in the city's and county's history and development.

2.11.5 El Paso Historical Landmark Commission

The City of El Paso is a Certified Local Government (CLG). This means that the City has a preservation program certified by the SHPO and the National Park Service as meeting the minimum standards to participate as a partner in the NHPA preservation programs and receive grant funds. As a CLG, the City carries out the purposes of the NHPA on the local level. The El Paso Historical Landmark Commission acts on behalf of the City.

2.11.6 El Paso Preservation Alliance

The mission of the El Paso Preservation Alliance is to promote the preservation of El Paso's history as it is manifested in the community's historic buildings.

2.11.7 Comanche Nation of Oklahoma

The Comanche Indian Tribe is a Federally-recognized Tribe that has expressed interest in Fort Bliss' management of cultural resources. Although identified as an interested party under this section, the Comanche Indian Tribe has a government-to-government relationship with Fort Bliss and shall be consulted with at that level.

2.11.8 Fort Sill Apache Tribe of Oklahoma

The Fort Sill Apache tribe is a Federally-recognized Tribe with traditional interests in land managed by Fort Bliss. Although identified as an interested party under this section, the Tribe has a government-to-government relationship with Fort Bliss and shall be consulted with at that level.

2.11.9 Pueblo of Isleta

Isleta Pueblo is a Federally-recognized Tribe that has expressed an interest in cultural resources on Fort Bliss. Although identified as an interested party under this section, the Tribe has a government-to-government relationship with Fort Bliss and shall be consulted with at that level.

2.11.10 Kiowa Tribe of Oklahoma

The Kiowa Tribe of Oklahoma is a Federally-recognized Tribe with traditional interests in land managed by Fort Bliss. Although identified as an interested party under this section, the Tribe has a government-to-government relationship with Fort Bliss and shall be consulted with at that level.

2.11.11 Ysleta del Sur Pueblo (Tigua)

The Ysleta del sur Pueblo (Tigua) is a Federally-recognized Tribe with traditional interests in lands managed by Fort Bliss. Although identified as an interested party under this section, the Tribe has a government-to-government relationship with Fort Bliss and shall be consulted with at that level.

2.11.12 Mescalero Apache Tribe

The Mescalero Apache Tribe is a Federally-recognized Tribe with traditional interests in lands managed by Fort Bliss. Although identified as an interested party under this section, the Tribe has a government-to-government relationship with Fort Bliss and shall be consulted with at that level.

2.11.13 White Mountain Apache Tribe

The White Mountain Apache Tribe is a Federally-recognized Tribe with traditional interests in lands managed by Fort Bliss. Although identified as an interested party under this section, the Tribe has a government-to-government relationship with Fort Bliss and shall be consulted with at that level.

2.11.14 Preservation Texas

Preservation Texas, with offices in Austin, is a statewide non-profit organization dedicated to the preservation of Texas' historic resources through education, promotion, and advocacy.

2.11.15 State Historic Preservation Officer

Pursuant to Section 101 of the NHPA, the State Historic Preservation Officer is responsible for administration of a State Historic Preservation Program as approved by the Secretary of the Interior. Although identified in this section as an interested party, the SHPO officer is a consulting party in the Army's management of historic properties under the NHPA. Additionally, SHPO staff are available to lend technical assistance in cultural resources management issues. Fort Bliss, with lands in both New Mexico and Texas, coordinates with both the New Mexico and Texas State Historic Preservation Officers.

2.11.16 United States Department of Agriculture-Forest Service

The United States Department of Agriculture (USDA) -Forest Service has management responsibility on withdrawn lands from the Lincoln National Forest (approximately 17,000 acres), including management of cultural resources, for any Forest Service activities. Fort Bliss shares this land and has management responsibility for any military activities. This responsibility is defined by Public Law 99-606, the Military Lands Withdrawal Act of 1986, the Federal Lands Policy Management Act (FLPMA) of 1976, and by the Memorandum of Understanding (MOU) between Fort Bliss and Forest Service (1971).

2.11.17 New Mexico Heritage Preservation Alliance

The NM Heritage Preservation Alliance is a state-wide, private non-profit organization that promotes, protects and advocates for New Mexico's heritage.

NOTES

3.0 LEGAL FOUNDATION AND METHODS FOR ICRMP

AR 200-1 requires each installation to prepare and implement an ICRMP. The legal foundation for AR 200-1 is in the body of Federal laws that address cultural resources. This section reviews the preservation laws applicable to Fort Bliss. Following each review is an analysis of the fort's current preservation programs for compliance with each of these laws. Preferred actions for ensuring compliance with these laws are identified in the text as "Action Items." The Action Plan, found in Section 6.0 "Implementing the ICRMP", lists these action items in the order in which they should be carried out.

3.1 Federal Cultural Resources Laws (with Action Items)

3.1.1 National Historic Preservation Act of 1966, as amended.

The NHPA of 1966, as amended in 2014 and codified in Title 54 of the United States Code, establishes a national program for historic preservation. The NHPA directs the Secretary of the Interior to publish regulations and guidelines for a number of preservation policies. These include Federal agency responsibilities under the Act, consideration of the effects of Federal undertakings on cultural resources, curation of Federally-owned and administered artifacts, and documentation of cultural resources by private and public parties. These are discussed in 54 United States Code (U.S.C.) 306101 through 306114 and Section 106 of the NHPA and 36 CFR 79, respectively. At Fort Bliss, Section 106 is addressed by the Programmatic Agreement. Section 110 compliance follows the NHPA.

3.1.1.1 Title 54 U.S.C. (Formerly Section 110) of the National Historic Preservation Act

Title 54 U.S.C. outlines Federal agency responsibilities under the NHPA. The Department of the Army's AR 200-1 addresses agency responsibilities. For a complete understanding of agency responsibilities under NHPA, consult 54 U.S.C. in the NHPA and the National Park Service's (NPS) standards and guidelines implementing Section 110.

3.1.1.2 54 U.S.C. 306101 (Formerly Section 110 (2)(a)(1))

The heads of all Federal agencies shall assume responsibility for preservation of historic properties that are owned or controlled by such agency. Each Federal agency shall use, to the maximum extent feasible, historic properties available to them.

- **ACTION ITEM 1:** Fort Bliss will carry out maintenance, repair, new construction and renovation of historic properties in accordance with "The Secretary of the Interior's Standards for the Treatment of Historic Properties with Guidelines for the Rehabilitating, Preserving, Rehabilitating, Restoring and Reconstructing Historic Buildings."

3.1.1.3 Title 54 U.S.C. 306102 (Formerly Section 110 (2)(a)(2))

Each Federal agency shall establish a preservation program for the identification, evaluation and nomination of historic properties to the NRHP, and protection of historic properties.

- **ACTION ITEM 2:** Fort Bliss, in support of the Department of the Army's responsibilities under Title 54 U.S.C. 306102 (Formerly Section 110 (2)(a)(2)), will survey and inventory lands and real property under its management and evaluate identified properties for NRHP eligibility as required, driven by undertakings proposed by Fort Bliss.
- **ACTION ITEM 3:** Fort Bliss will protect identified historic properties through a series of measures: (1) review undertakings proposed on Fort Bliss for their potential to adversely affect historic properties, (2) seek first to avoid any adverse effect, but if not possible because of the nature of the undertaking, pursue the most effective mitigation measure (3) establish off limits areas of representative archaeological sites

3.1.1.4 Title 54 U.S.C. 306103 (Formerly Section 110 (2)(b))

Prior to demolition or substantial alteration, historic properties will be recorded and those records will be deposited with the agency (or some other appropriate agency) for future use and reference.

- **ACTION ITEM 4:** Fort Bliss will record historic properties as provided for in the Programmatic Agreement for management of cultural resources among Fort Bliss, the Advisory Council, and the New Mexico and Texas State Historic Preservation Officers and store that information in their curatorial facility.

3.1.1.5 Title 54 U.S.C. 306104 (Formerly Section 110(2)(c))

The head of each Federal agency shall designate a preservation officer, who meets Secretary of Interior qualifications for archaeology or historic preservation, who shall be responsible for coordinating that agency's activities under the NHPA. The Fort Bliss CRM is the responsible person on behalf of the GC for meeting the requirements of this ICRMP. Responsibilities may be delegated to appropriate qualified staff to address the cultural resource under consideration.

- **ACTION ITEM 5:** The GC shall designate a CRM until rescinded. During the duration of this ICRMP, the CRM will ensure that appropriate personnel meet the Secretary of the Interior's Professional Qualifications Standards as archaeologists and historic architects or architectural historians.

3.1.1.6 Title 54 U.S.C. 306105 (Formerly Section 110(2)(d))

All Federal agencies shall carry out agency programs and projects in accordance with the purposes of the NHPA.

- **ACTION ITEM 6:** The cultural resources program shall consider the impact of proposed Fort Bliss projects and activities on historic properties to ensure consistency with the requirements of the NHPA.

3.1.1.7 Title 54 U.S.C. 306106 (Formerly Section 110(2)(e))

The Secretary of the Interior shall review and approve plans for transfer of surplus Federally-owned historic properties to ensure that prehistoric, historic, architectural and culturally significant values will be preserved or enhanced.

- **ACTION ITEM 7:** Fort Bliss shall ensure that any transfer of Federally-owned historic property follows the appropriate state and federal regulations (including but not limited to the NPS/GSA Historic Surplus Property Program).

3.1.1.8 Title 54 U.S.C. 306107 (Formerly Section 110(2)(f))

The heads of each Federal agency shall undertake planning and actions to minimize harm to National Historic Landmarks and provide reasonable opportunity for the Advisory Council on Historic Preservation to comment on undertakings that directly and adversely affect National Historic Landmarks.

- **NO ACTION REQUIRED** (No National Historic Landmarks on Fort Bliss)

3.1.1.9 Title 54 U.S.C. 306109 (Formerly Section 110(2)(g))

Each Federal agency may include the costs of preservation activities under this Act as eligible project costs.

- **ACTION ITEM 8:** When applicable, Fort Bliss will include costs and staff time required in proposed projects to adequately address historic property issues.

3.1.1.10 Title 54 U.S.C. 306110 (Formerly Section 110(2)(h))

The Secretary shall establish an annual preservation awards program for recognition of outstanding contributions to historic preservation.

- **NO ACTION REQUIRED**

3.1.1.11 Title 54 U.S.C. 306111 (Formerly Section 110(2)(i))

Nothing in this Act shall be construed to require the preparation of an environmental impact statement where one would not be required under the National Environmental Policy Act, and nothing in this Act shall be construed to provide an exemption from any requirement for the preparation of a statement under such Act.

- NO ACTION REQUIRED

3.1.1.12 Title 54 U.S.C. 306112 (Formerly Section 110(2)(j))

The Secretary of the Interior shall publish regulations under which requirements of this section may be waived in whole or in part in the event of a major natural disaster or an imminent threat to the national security.

- ACTION ITEM 9: Fort Bliss staff will monitor for changes to the Act and 36 CFR Part 800.

3.1.1.13 Title 54 U.S.C. 306113 (Formerly Section 110(2)(k))

Federal agencies shall not grant a loan, loan guarantee, permit, license or other assistance to an applicant with the intent of avoiding Section 106 requirements, unless after consultation with the Council, determines that circumstances justify granting such assistance.

- NO ACTION REQUIRED

3.1.1.14 Title 54 U.S.C. 306114 (Formerly Section 110(2)(l))

With respect to any undertaking subject to Section 106 which adversely affects any historic property, and for which a Federal agency has not entered into an agreement pursuant to regulations issued by the Council, the head of such agency shall document that decision and may not delegate that responsibility.

- NO ACTION REQUIRED (The programmatic agreement outlines the procedures Fort Bliss will follow under Section 106 requirements)

3.1.1.15 Section 106 of the National Historic Preservation Act.

The head of any Federal agency having direct or indirect jurisdiction over a proposed Federal or federally-assisted undertaking in any State and the head of any Federal department or independent agency having authority to license any undertaking shall, prior to the approval of the expenditures of any Federal funds on the undertaking or prior to the issuance of any license, as the case may be, take into account the effect of the undertaking on any district, site, building, structure, or object that is included in or eligible for inclusion in the National Register. The head of any such Federal agency shall afford the Advisory Council on Historic Preservation

established under Title II of the NHPA, a reasonable opportunity to comment with regard to such undertaking.

36 CFR Part 800.14(b) of the NHPA provides the opportunity for Federal agencies to streamline the Section 106 process through the development of a Programmatic Agreement (PA). PAs apply to a particular program, large or complex project, or class of undertakings that would require numerous individual requests for comments. Fort Bliss has elected to address its Section 106 responsibilities under a PA between the Advisory Council on Historic Preservation, the New Mexico and Texas SHPOs, Tribal Historic Preservation Officer, Tribes and other interested parties. This PA will direct Fort Bliss on fulfilling its Section 106 responsibilities. This PA is found in Appendix A of this ICRMP.

Undertakings addressed through a fully executed Fort Bliss PA or other Fort Bliss Program Alternative executed in accordance with 36 CFR Part 800.14 and that are not subject to the stipulations of the PA are:

- 1) PA regarding the Fort Bliss Residential Communities Initiative (RCI). This agreement addresses implementation of the Army's privatization of Army Family Housing, for which the future effects on historic properties can be determined prior to approval of the undertaking.
- 2) In addition to the Fort Bliss PA, there is a nationwide PMOA in effect that addresses World War II Temporary Buildings. This PMOA provides for demolition of this class of historic property with no further consideration under Section 106. See Appendix J for a list of buildings covered by this Program Comment.

Finally, the ACHP and Federal Regulation 36 CFR Part 800.14(e) provides for the opportunity for Federal agencies to develop Program Comments to address a category of undertakings in lieu of conducting individual reviews. There are three (3) Program Comments in effect that address historic property types found on Fort Bliss:

- 1) Program Comment regarding Capehart/Wherry Era Army Family Housing and Associated Structures and Landscapes (1949-1962): Provides for the ongoing operations, maintenance and repair, rehabilitation, renovation, mothballing, cessation of maintenance, new construction, demolition, deconstruction and salvage, remediation activities, and transfer, sale, lease, and closure of Cold War era (1946-1962) family housing without further Section 106 consideration. See Appendix J for a list of buildings covered by this Program Comment.
- 2) Program Comment for Cold War Era Unaccompanied Personnel Housing (1946-1974): Provides for the ongoing operations, maintenance and repair, rehabilitation, renovation, mothballing, cessation of maintenance, new construction, demolition, deconstruction and salvage, remediation activities, and transfer, sale, lease, and closure of Cold War era (1946-1974) barracks without further Section 106 consideration. (Figures 3.1, 3.2, 3.3, 3.4 and 3.5 identify UPH housing on Fort Bliss' Main Cantonment, Briggs Air Field, and Base Camps covered by this PC.) See Appendix J for a list of buildings covered by this Program Comment.

- 3) Program Comment for Cold War Era (1939-1974) Ammunition Storage Facilities. Provides for the ongoing operations, maintenance and repair, rehabilitation, renovation, mothballing, cessation of maintenance, new construction, demolition, deconstruction and salvage, remediation activities, and transfer, sale, lease, and closure of World War II and Cold War era (1939-1974) ammunition storage facilities without further Section 106 consideration. See Appendix J for a list of buildings covered by this Program Comment.
- 4) Program Comment for World War II and Cold War Era (1939-1974) Army Ammunition Production Facilities and Plants for the ongoing operations, maintenance and repair, rehabilitation, renovation, mothballing, cessation of maintenance, new construction, demolition, deconstruction and salvage, remediation activities, and transfer, sale, lease, and closure of World War II and Cold War Era Army Ammunition Production Facilities and Plants without further Section 106 consideration. Currently, there are no facilities at Fort Bliss that are covered by this Program Comment.

- ACTION ITEM 10: Provide appropriate SHPO with listing of properties that are covered by these Program Comments (see Appendix J).

A final tool for streamlining Section 106 for specific undertakings that have a short life is through an MOA. This document is prepared when adverse effects cannot be avoided and defines stipulations that must be met prior to performing the undertaking. These stipulations provide a means of mitigating the adverse effects projects may have on cultural resources as determined through consultation. The PA provides for mitigation and will require no new MOAs to address individual projects.

3.1.2 The Native American Graves Protection and Repatriation Act of 1990

The NAGPRA of 1990 provides for the order of custody and the repatriation of Native American human remains, funerary objects, sacred objects, and objects of cultural patrimony removed from Federal and tribal lands. NAGPRA applies to cultural items in possession or control of Federal agencies, cultural items in possession or control of any institution or State or local government receiving Federal funds, and to cultural items intentionally or unintentionally excavated on Federal or tribal lands. Regulations to carry out NAGPRA are found at 43 CFR Subpart A § 10, "Native American Graves Protection and Repatriation Regulations". The Act requires consultation with Indian tribal officials and traditional religious leaders with respect to these remains and items.

Under the Act, Section 5 requires Federal agencies to complete, in consultation with tribal entities, an inventory of all human remains and associated funerary objects in the possession or under their control. Under Section 6, Federal agencies are required to complete a summary of all unassociated funerary objects, sacred objects, or objects of cultural patrimony in their possession or under their control.

- NO ACTION REQUIRED (Section 5 and Section 6 reports have been completed)

Responsibilities under NAGPRA continue however, after completion of these Section 5 and Section 6 requirements. The intentional excavation of human remains, funerary artifacts, sacred

objects and objects of cultural patrimony during Section 106 review or the inadvertent discovery of these remains or items during an undertaking require that NAGPRA be addressed.

To meet its NAGPRA responsibility, as well as other tribal issues, a Draft Comprehensive Agreement specifically addressing tribal consultation, tribal range access, tribal concerns regarding natural and cultural resources across the installation, and consultation under NAGPRA (including custody and disposition) has been reviewed by IMCOM and the Tribes. As a result of that review, Fort Bliss separated the government-to-government clauses from the NAGPRA clauses and created two separate documents: a Cooperative Agreement covering consultation and NHPA matters, and a Comprehensive Agreement addressing NAGPRA matters. The revised documents have been reviewed by IMCOM and the Tribes.

- ACTION ITEM 11. Fort Bliss will incorporate those documents into this ICRMP and follow the terms of the final reviewed and approved Cooperative Agreement and Comprehensive Agreement.

A final NAGPRA issue remains pending: on April 18, 2012, the Office of the Secretary of the Interior published a proposed rule designed to address “minor inaccuracies or inconsistencies in the regulations.” Of interest is the proposed rule for the Disposition of Culturally Unidentifiable Human Remains (Title 43 Part 10 Subpart C Section 10.11); the final rule was published March 15, 2010.

- ACTION ITEM 12. Fort Bliss will incorporate and follow the guidelines of the final rule regarding transferring control of culturally unidentifiable human remains and associated funerary objects, especially from whose aboriginal lands the human remains and associated funerary objects were removed (as is most applicable on Fort Bliss).

3.1.3 The Archaeological Resources Protection Act of 1979

The ARPA protects archaeological resources and sites on public and Indian lands; violations of ARPA can result in criminal and/or civil penalties. Regulations for ARPA are found in 32 CFR Part 229, Protection of Archaeological Resources: Uniform Regulations. ARPA outlines illegal activities and prescribes civil and criminal penalties for each infraction, establishes a permitting process for removal of archaeological resources from public and Indian lands, and provides for the confidentiality of archaeological site location information. Standard operating procedures for ARPA compliance can be found in Section 4 CRM Standard Operating Procedure #1: Compliance with Archaeological Resources Protection Act of 1979. AR 200-1 specifically identifies the GC to be the Federal agency official with management authority over archaeological collections and associated records, includes a requirement for a permit to search for or collect from archaeological resources, allows for curation of archaeological materials from Army lands in 36 CFR 79-compliant repositories, and upholds the protection from disclosure of the nature and location of archaeological resources.

ARPA prohibits a variety of activities from being conducted on archaeological sites without a permit: excavation, removal of items, damage, alteration, or defacing, or attempts to excavate

remove, damage, alter or deface. Other activities such as selling, purchasing, exchanging, transporting, receiving, or offering to sell, purchase, or exchange archaeological resources are also prohibited.

- **ACTION ITEM 13:** The CRM will coordinate with the SJA to ensure that ARPA is integrated into the missions of applicable military and nonmilitary organizations on Fort Bliss. The CRM will incorporate ARPA into training sponsored by the Environmental Division, including Environmental Compliance Officer training and the Unit Commander Course. ARPA training will be conducted on Fort Bliss during FY15 (funded by the IBWC and conducted by the NPS), and subject to the availability of funding, will host ARPA training for military law enforcement and other applicable units and organizations every three to five years.

3.1.4 36 CFR Part 79 Curation of Federally-Owned and Administered Archaeological Collections

The Federal curation regulation, 36 CFR Part 79, Curation of Federally-Owned and Administered Archaeological Collections establish definitions, standards, procedures and guidelines to be followed by Federal agencies to preserve collections of prehistoric and historic material remains, and associated records. The regulation outlines basic collections management procedures and standards, including access to and use of Federal collections. It presents general criteria for evaluating curatorial services provided by collection repositories and provides sample contract language that may be used by Federal agencies in procuring curation services.

Implementation of the requirements of 36 CFR 79 is left to each Federal agency. The United States Army's service-wide guidance for curation is found in AR 200-1. That regulation specifies that curation of archaeological items is to occur only in 36 CFR 79-compliant repositories and collection of archaeological materials is to be minimized to diagnostic artifacts and other significant and environmentally-sensitive material that will add important information to site interpretations.

Fort Bliss maintains its own specific SOP for collection and curation of archaeological and historical collections and associated records (See SOP #5). Those procedures are also provided to any entity permitted to collect items from archaeological sites on Fort Bliss; their submissions must strictly adhere to those guidelines.

- **ACTION ITEM 14:** Fort Bliss staff will provide long-term management and preservation of preexisting and new collections, as set forth in 36 CFR 79.
- **ACTION ITEM 15:** Fort Bliss will ensure that all associated records (including digital data) are curated and format migrated, as warranted.

NOTES

4.0 STANDARD OPERATING PROCEDURES

The SOPs for meeting sections 106 and 110 of the NHPA of 1966 (as amended) provide a more efficient structure in which Fort Bliss will operate on a day-to-day basis. The Stipulations found in the current PA among Fort Bliss, the Advisory Council on Historic Preservation, and the Texas and New Mexico State Historic Preservation Officers (2015 – 2025) comprise the majority of these procedures. These procedures have been distributed on Fort Bliss as the GC's Policy.

In addition to the Stipulations provided in the PA, the following SOPs addressing other preservation laws are implemented by this ICRMP.

- SOP #1: Compliance with Archaeological Resources Protection Act of 1979
- SOP #2: Compliance with the Native American Graves Protection and Repatriation Act of 1990.
- SOP #3: Native American Consultation under the National Historic Preservation Act
- SOP #4: Identifying Consulting Parties
- SOP #5: Curatorial and Collection Management of Archaeological and Historical Collections and Associated Records

4.1 Standard Operating Procedure #1: Compliance with Archaeological Resources Protection Act of 1979

4.1.1 Applicability

This Standard Operation Procedure (SOP) applies to all organizations, property, and activities under the control of the Department of the Army and located within the boundaries of Fort Bliss or other contiguous land under Fort Bliss control. It also includes activities undertaken on behalf of the Army or with consent of the Army, or as a result of consent of the Army by contract, lease, or inter-service support agreement or other instrument to which Fort Bliss, the United States Army, or the Department of Defense (DOD) is a party, within Fort Bliss or other contiguous land under Fort Bliss control.

4.1.2 Objective

This procedure implements the provisions of the Archaeological Resources Protection Act of 1979 (ARPA), Public Law 9696 (93 Stat. 171; 16 U.S.C. 470aa-mm), and its implementing regulations issued under the Act by the DOD (32 CFR 229). ARPA makes it a Federal felony offense for the unauthorized excavation, removal, damage, alteration, or defacement of any archaeological resource located on Federal lands. The purchase, sale, transport, exchange or receipt of any archaeological resource obtained in violation of this or related laws are also considered a felony offense under ARPA. Archaeological resources include the material remains of past human life or activities which are of archaeological interest and at least 100 years of age. Paleontological materials found in an archaeological context are also covered under ARPA. The nature and location of archaeological resources is also protected under this Act.

4.1.3 Policy

Under AR 200-1, the GC serves as the Federal land manager with responsibility for compliance with ARPA. The GC appoints a Cultural Resource Manager (CRM) to assist in that compliance. Those responsibilities include ensuring that Army law enforcement personnel are trained in conservation law enforcement where appropriate.

4.1.4 Implementing Procedures

4.1.4.1 Training and Awareness

Representatives from the Cultural Resources and Environmental Liaison programs at the Directorate of Public Works - Environmental Division (DPW-E), USACAS Range Riders, Provost Marshals Office (PMO), and the Staff Judge Advocate (SJA) completed Archaeological Law Enforcement Training conducted by Archaeological Resource Investigations (ARI) in 2006. When funds are available, Fort Bliss will provide a refresher course. Fort Bliss DPW-E will continue to train members of the Fort Bliss community on the provisions of ARPA through the following training venues:

- The Environmental Compliance Officer (ECO) course (a primary and alternate ECO is required for every military unit) includes information in the Cultural Resources section explaining ARPA and responsibilities under this Act.
- For in-coming military units, environmental briefings conducted by the Environmental Liaisons will include discussion of ARPA violations and the penalties that can be assessed.
- Units will be issued “Environmental Compliance Field Cards” with a brief discussion of prohibitions and penalties under the Act.
- ARPA briefings are provided once per quarter in the regular Unit Commander Course for incoming unit commanders.

4.1.4.2 ARPA Permit Procedure

Archaeological investigations that result in removal and/or excavation of archaeological resources from Fort Bliss may not proceed without the express written approval of the GC or his or her delegated CRM. All archaeological investigations conducted by individuals or agencies that are under contract are authorized to remove or excavate archaeological materials in accordance with the Statement of Work for that project. In those cases, the contract serves as the ARPA permit and the terms of the scope of work ensure compliance with ARPA. For all archaeological investigations conducted by individuals or agencies that are not under contract to, or otherwise cooperatively assisting the Department of the Army, the agencies or individuals must obtain a permit issued by the Fort Bliss delegated CRM (sample permit follows below).

FOR OFFICIAL USE ONLY

Date received:

Date approved:

United States Army-Fort Bliss Garrison Command
Application for a Federal Permit under
THE ARCHAEOLOGICAL RESOURCES PROTECTION ACT
Approved October 31, 1979
Public Law 9696 (93 Stat. 721; 16 U.S.C. 470aa470MM; 32 CFR 229)
or
THE ANTIQUITIES ACT
Approved June 8, 1906
Public Law 59-209 (34 Stat 225; U.S.C. 431-433; 43 CFR 3)

Instructions: Complete form and submit two copies to the Fort Bliss Directorate of Environment. All information requested must be completed before the application can be processed. Use additional sheets of paper if more space is needed to complete the form.

1. Name of Institution or company:

2. Address:

3. Permit type: (check appropriate box)

a. Surveys and limited testing or limited collections on Fort Bliss lands (Army Fee-Owned)

b. Excavation, intensive testing, major collections of specific sites on Fort Bliss lands (Army Fee-Owned)

4. Specific areas and/or sites for which the permit is requested: (include state and Fort Bliss site numbers, specific training areas, USGS quad names and legal descriptions for the study area. Maps may be attached)

5. Nature and extent of proposed work, including purpose and methodology:

6. Include name, address, and institutional affiliation for persons in "a" and "b" below. Applicants must attach evidence of qualifications (vitae or resume) and meet the qualifications outlined in the Uniform Regulations:

a. Individual(s) proposed to be directly responsible for conducting the work in the field:

b. Individual(s) proposed to be responsible for carrying out the terms and conditions of this permit (in “general charge” of the project if different from “a” above):

7. Proposed date field work will begin:

8. Proposed date for end of field work:

9. Curation: All applicants for ARPA permits on Fort Bliss must agree to curate all materials at the Fort Bliss Curatorial Facility, following the specifications outlined in the current Fort Bliss Curation SOP. All archaeological and paleontological materials removed from Fort Bliss lands are the property of the US government.

10. Proposed outlet and or method of public written dissemination of the results (Note: applicant must agree to provide final copies of all results, reports, articles, etc. to the Fort Bliss Directorate of Environment. Fort Bliss DOE must have an opportunity to review and comment on all drafts before publication)

11. Evidence of applicant’s ability to initiate, conduct and complete the proposed activity including evidence of logistical support, equipment and laboratory facilities:

12. Signature of individual in general charge (item 6b above)

13. Date of application: _____

14. Signature of GC or designated CRM: _____

15. Date of approval: _____

The Fort Bliss CRM and staff will monitor the field investigations and results of activities conducted under ARPA permits to ensure:

- Compliance with the requirements of 32 CFR 229, 43 CFR 10 and the terms and conditions of the permit.
- Any interests that Federally-recognized Tribes have in the permitted activity are addressed in a manner consistent with the requirements of the National Historical Preservation Act (NHPA), Native American Graves Repatriation Act (NAGPRA), and American Indian Religious Freedom Act (AIRFA).
- That permitted activities are performed according to applicable professional standards of the Secretary of the Interior.

4.1.4.3 Jurisdiction for ARPA case investigation

Fort Bliss is responsible for all ARPA compliance on the cantonment and New Mexico and Texas training areas. McGregor Range is withdrawn Bureau of Land Management (BLM) land, used for military training purposes. It is anticipated that during the life of the Integrated Cultural Resource Management Plan (ICRMP) a memorandum of agreement (MOA) between Fort Bliss and the BLM will be signed and will include the following stipulations:

- The BLM will be the lead agency for permits required by the ARPA for survey, research, excavation, data recovery, and other cultural resources projects for which the BLM is the proponent and for all third party activities on withdrawn public lands, to include recreational activities.
- The BLM will be responsible for ARPA violations occurring as the result of non-military personnel, except when those personnel are affiliated with Fort Bliss, such as civilian employees.
- Fort Bliss will be responsible for all ARPA violations occurring as the result of military personnel or civilian personnel affiliation with Fort Bliss.
- In all cases, each agency will work together to support the ARPA compliance on McGregor Range and will share resources and information when available.

Portions of Fort Bliss are on withdrawn Forest Service lands. Fort Bliss and the Forest Service are operating under a 1971 Memorandum of Understanding. In this agreement, Section A, Item 7 states “ The Service [Forest Service] will administer all archaeological and paleontological activities on the Lands in conformance with the Uniform Rules and Regulations prescribed by the Secretaries of the Interior, Agriculture, and Army; and the Antiquities Act (34 Stat. 225; 16 U.S.C. 432-433).” Until such time as this agreement is amended, the Forest Service will assume responsibility for ARPA permitting and ARPA violations on the withdrawn Forest Service lands.

4.1.4.4 Documentation Procedures for ARPA Violations

Investigation of looting or vandalism of an archaeological site requires a systematic examination of the crime scene by both a law enforcement investigator and a professional archaeologist. A law enforcement officer is responsible for investigating violations of law, and therefore, directs the archaeological crime scene investigation process. The archaeologist provides expertise on

archaeological resources for the crime scene investigation and is responsible for archaeological site documentation and completion of a damage assessment report. The archaeologist may be requested to assist in other activities including taking photographs, testifying, helping with crime scene sketches, or providing assistance in collecting the archaeological evidence. In some cases, other experts may be part of an investigative team, to include geoarchaeologist, forensic anthropologists or Tribal representatives.

Investigative goals for an ARPA violation should include:

- Identifying the entire crime scene
- Maintaining the integrity of the crime scene
- Discover all available facts
- Identify and collect all evidence
- Utilize proper forensic standards
- Identify those responsible
- Successfully prosecute

An ARPA investigation begins when an archaeological crime is first suspected or discovered, whether in person or upon receiving a report from a third party. If the violation is reported by a witness, information provided should include a signed narrative statement describing the location of the suspected violation, specific activities and the people and vehicles involved.

Specific investigation steps should be followed, which include:

- Investigative note-taking should contain, at a minimum, the who, what, where, when, why, and how of the incident. All members of the investigative team should keep accurate, detailed notes. Field notes should include the following specific information:
 - Name and title of law enforcement investigator and/or archaeologist
 - Date and time assigned to the case
 - Who reported the crime and how it was reported
 - Location of the crime
 - Date and time of arrival at the crime scene
 - Names of other members of the investigative team
 - Weather and other environmental conditions
 - Witnesses or other persons present
 - Detailed description of the crime scene
 - Specific details concerning the actions taken

Crime Scene Search. The archaeologist should accompany the law enforcement investigator during the initial crime scene survey to assist in locating archaeological site damage and other physical evidence. If the crime scene involves human remains or objects of cultural patrimony, follow the requirements of SOP #2, Compliance with the Native American Graves Protection and Repatriation Act of 1990. The crime scene search should include a systematic strategy to identify both standard physical evidence as well as archaeological evidence. Care should be taken to protect fragile evidence such as fingerprints, shoe prints, tire impression, tool marks, etc.

Crime Scene Photography. Photographic evidence is crucial to a successful ARPA crime scene investigation. Three types of photographs should be taken including overall photos of the crime scene, intermediate photos showing the relationship of physical evidence to the scene, and close-up photos of each specific piece of evidence. Photographs should be done in 35 mm black and white and color film. Additional digital pictures may be collected as well.

The general rules concerning crime scene photography include:

- Photograph the overall scene first
- Take intermediate crime scene photographs second
- Photograph each item of evidence before it is collected or moved
- Maintain an accurate photo log and description of each photograph
- Mark each photograph for identification purposes
- Handle all photographs, slides, and negatives as evidence

Crime Scene Sketch. The purpose of the crime scene sketch is to record the exact location of each item of evidence. The crime scene sketch must be accurate and referenced to a fixed, immovable object. The sketch should also include the case number, date and time of the sketch, name of the individual doing the sketch, location, and name of the person assisting in measurements. Using tools such as survey-grade geographic positioning system (GPS), Total Stations, etc. is highly recommended. If approved by the law enforcement agent in charge, the archaeologist should map the overall site to include the site boundaries, individual features, artifact concentrations, looters holes, any site damage, etc. This map should also include plots of any evidence or other information requested by the law enforcement agent.

Evidence Collection. Generally, handling and collecting of physical evidence at a crime scene will be handled by the law enforcement investigator. The sequence of evidence collection should follow a logical, systematic order. How evidence is handled directly affects its evidentiary value, thus evidence must be properly collected, marked and maintained. Photographs and sketches should be done prior to collection. Fragile evidence should be collected first. In some cases, control samples for lab analysis may need to be collected. All evidence should be handled carefully and packaged separately in the proper containers. Each container should be properly marked with the case number, date and time, person collecting and description of the evidence.

Case Report. Detailed investigative field notes by both law enforcement and archaeological specialists are the basis for preparing an ARPA case report. The report should include:

- Synopsis of the incident
- Individual team member reports
- Damage assessment report, to include archaeological or commercial value and cost of restoration and repair
- Photograph log
- Evidence log
- Laboratory report
- Crime scene sketches, diagrams, and maps

- Witness statements
- List of potential government witnesses
- Letter from land manager concerning lack of ARPA permit issuance
- Chain of Custody log

4.2 Standard Operating Procedure #2: Compliance with the Native American Graves Protection and Repatriation Act of 1990 (this SOP is subject to revision pending completed Comprehensive Agreement)

4.2.1 Applicability and Objective

Fort Bliss is engaged in on-going survey, evaluation, and excavation of cultural resources on Fort Bliss. This standard operating procedure (SOP) applies to all organizations, property, and activities under the control of the Department of the Army located within the boundaries of Fort Bliss and other contiguous land under its control. It also includes activities undertaken on behalf of the Army or with consent of the Army, or as a result of consent of the Army by contract, lease, or inter-service support agreement or other instrument to which Fort Bliss, the Army, or the DOD is a party, within the boundaries of Fort Bliss and other contiguous lands under its control. Portions of Fort Bliss are on withdrawn Bureau of Land Management (BLM) and United States Department of Agriculture (USDA)-Forest Service lands. When Native American Graves Repatriation Act (NAGPRA) applicable discoveries are made as part of non-military activities, such as recreation or grazing activities, etc. then per the MOA between the BLM and Fort Bliss, it will be the BLM's responsibility to comply with the NAGPRA terms in that agreement. The MOA between the USDA and the Department of Army states all archaeological and paleontological activities will be administered by the Forest Service.

The Fort Bliss GC serves as the Federal Agency Official with responsibility for installation compliance with NAGPRA (AR200-4, Section II, 1-9[1]). The GC has delegated this authority to the Cultural Resource Manager (CRM) for the Department of Public Works-Environment Division (DPW-E), Conservation Branch. The CRM is identified as the point-of-contact to be notified immediately if Native American human remains and/or cultural items are inadvertently discovered within the boundaries of Fort Bliss and other contiguous lands under its control.

This SOP replaces SOP #17 of the Fort Bliss *Integrated Cultural Resources Management Plan, 2008-2012*. (ICRMP), an internal planning document guiding cultural resources management on Fort Bliss. The objective of this SOP is to lay out the procedures to be followed to insure Fort Bliss' compliance with the NAGPRA.

4.2.2 Definitions

Reference: NAGPRA 25 U.S.C. 3001, Sec. 2, unless indicated otherwise.

- *Burial site* means “any natural or prepared physical location, whether originally below, on, or above the surface of the earth, into which as a part of the death rite or ceremony of a culture, individual human remains are deposited, and includes rock cairns or pyres which do not fall within the ordinary definition of grave site” [43 CFR 10.2(d)(2)].
- *Cultural affiliation* means “that there is a relationship of shared group identity which can reasonably be traced historically or prehistorically between members of a present-day Indian tribe or Native Hawaiian organization and an identifiable earlier group. Cultural affiliation is established when the preponderance of the

evidence, based on geographical, kinship, biological, archaeological linguistic, folklore, oral tradition, historical evidence, or other information or expert opinion, reasonably leads to such a conclusion” [43 CFR 10.2(e)].

- *Cultural objects* specifically refers to associated funerary objects, sacred objects, and objects of cultural patrimony.
- *Custody* means ownership or control of human remains, funerary objects, sacred objects, or objects of cultural patrimony excavated intentionally or discovered inadvertently in Federal or tribal lands after November 16, 1990 [43 CFR 10.6].
- *Funerary objects* means “items that, as a part of the death rite or ceremony of a culture, are reasonably believed to have been placed intentionally at the time of death or later with or near individual human remains.” [43 CFR 10.2(d)(2)]. *Associated funerary objects* are “those funerary objects for which the human remains with which they were placed intentionally are also in the possession or control of a museum or federal agency” [43 CFR 10.2(d)(2)(i)]. *Unassociated funerary objects* are “those funerary objects for which the human remains with which they were placed intentionally are not in the possession or control of a museum or federal agency” [43 CFR 10.2(d)(2)(ii)].
- *Human remains* means the “physical remains of a human body, including but not limited to bones, teeth, hair, ashes, or mummified or otherwise preserved soft tissues, of a person of Native American ancestry. For the purposes of determining cultural affiliation, human remains incorporated into a funerary object, sacred object, or object of cultural patrimony, as defined below, must be considered as part of that item” [43 CFR 10.2(d)(1)].
- *Inadvertent discovery* means “the unanticipated encounter or detection of human remains, funerary objects, sacred objects, or objects of cultural patrimony found under or on the surface of Federal or tribal lands pursuant to section 3(d)” of NAGPRA [43 CFR 10.2(g)(4)].
- *Indian tribe* (statutory definition to be used, rather than regulatory definition, per August 2014 final action on Interim Rule of July 5, 2011; from Public Law 93-638, The Indian Self-Determination and Education Assistance Act of 1975 as Amended) means “any Indian tribe, band, nation, or other organized group or community, including any Alaska Native village or regional or village corporation as defined in or established pursuant to the Alaska Native Claims Settlement Act (85 Stat. 688), which is recognized as eligible for the special programs and services provided by the United States to Indians because of their status as Indians.”
- *Intentional excavation* means “the planned archaeological removal of human remains, funerary objects, sacred objects, or objects of cultural patrimony found under or on the surface of Federal or tribal lands pursuant to section 3(c)” of NAGPRA [43 CFR 10.2(g)(3)].
- *Objects of cultural patrimony* means “items having ongoing historical, traditional, or cultural importance central to the Indian tribe or Native Hawaiian organization itself, rather than property owned by an individual tribal or organization member. These objects are of such central importance that they may not be alienated, appropriated, or conveyed by any individual tribal or organization member. Such objects must have been considered inalienable by the culturally affiliated Indian

tribe or Native Hawaiian organization at the time the object was separated from the group” [43 CFR 10.2(d)(4)].

- *Sacred objects* means “items that are specific ceremonial objects needed by traditional Native American religious leaders for the practice of traditional Native American religions by their present day adherents. While many items, from ancient pottery sherds to arrowheads, might be imbued with sacredness in the eyes of an individual, these regulations are specifically limited to objects that were devoted to a traditional Native American religious ceremony or ritual and which have religious significance or function in the continued observance or renewal of such ceremony” [43 CFR 10.2(d)(3)].
- *Tribal contacts* means the Indian tribes listed in Appendix B.

4.2.3 Policy

The GC will ensure compliance with the NAGPRA of 1990 [25 U.S.C. 3001-3013, 43 CFR 10]. The GC-appointed CRM will coordinate with the SJA, Criminal Investigation Division (CID), Provost Marshal’s Office (PMO), Directorate of Planning, Training, Mobilization and Security (DPTMS), and Master Planning (Directorate of Public Works, DPW) to ensure that the CRM is:

- Incorporated in the planning of training and construction in order to assess the potential for the discovery of Native American burials and archaeological sites, and
- Identified as the point-of-contact to be notified immediately if a Native American burial or archaeological site is inadvertently discovered on installation property.

4.2.4 Implementing Procedures

4.2.4.1 Inadvertent Discovery or Intentional Excavation of Human Remains and Associated Funerary Objects, Sacred Objects, or Objects of Cultural Patrimony (Reference: NAGPRA 25 U.S.C. 3002 Sec. 3(d), 43 CFR 10)

Upon the discovery of known or suspected human remains or funerary objects on Fort Bliss administered lands, all activity within a 30 meter radius of the remains shall stop, no human remains and/or funerary items shall be moved or removed and the area will be temporarily secured and protected from further disturbance. The individual shall immediately notify the CRM by telephone of the discovery. The individual will follow up with written confirmation to the CRM. The CRM will certify receipt of the notification within three days to the individual that initial notification was received.

When notified of the possible discovery of human remains or cultural objects, the CRM or a qualified professional archaeologist will visit the site within three working days of the notification of discovery. The CRM will make an initial determination whether the remains or objects meet the criteria defined in NAGPRA. The CRM will ensure that the area has been temporarily secured and protected.

If upon examination, the remains appear to be human and associated with a crime scene,

the CRM will ensure that the PMO and the CID are notified. The CID will assume jurisdiction over the area.

If upon examination the remains are identified as non-human, the CRM will determine if archaeological contexts are present that need to be evaluated pursuant to Section 106 of the NHPA [16 U.S.C. 470-470w].

If the human remains are determined to be non-Native American and historic in nature, and not part of a crime scene, then NAGPRA will not apply and the requirements of this SOP will be complete. The CID will assume jurisdiction over the area.

If the human remains are determined to be Native American and not associated with a crime scene, the CRM will prepare a preliminary summary outlining the circumstances of the discovery, description of the site and/or context of the remains, a description of the remains and objects, and an evaluation of their potential temporal affiliation.

If preliminary assessment is inconclusive, the CRM will assume Native American affiliation and proceed as described below.

4.2.4.2 Notification of Native American Tribes

Within three (3) working days after verification the CRM shall notify by telephone (with written confirmation) and initiate consultation with any known lineal descendant and with the Tribes who:

- Are likely to be culturally affiliated with the human remains or other cultural items.
- On whose aboriginal lands the remains and other cultural items objects were discovered.
- Are reasonably known to have cultural relationships to the human remains or other cultural item.

The written notification will be sent to the designated tribal NAGPRA coordinators.

Decisions on which Indian Tribes to notify will be based on the signatories of the Fort Bliss Comprehensive Agreement. Other tribes may come forward at any time and request to be a signatory and Fort Bliss will consult with those tribes accordingly.

4.2.4.3. Native American Consultation

After the notification letter has been sent to the Signatory Tribes for review, the CRM will continue to consult with the Tribes to visit the site containing the human remains and/or funerary objects.

Determining Custody

An Indian Tribe that wishes to make a claim of ownership of human remains or cultural objects must be able to demonstrate an affiliation by a preponderance of evidence according to the criteria for the priority of custody specified in 25 U.S.C. 3002, Sec.3(a) and 43 CFR 10.6.

Priority of ownership or control of Native American human remains and cultural objects is: [For details, see 25 U.S.C. 3002, Sec. 3(a)(1)-(2), 43 CFR 10.6]

- 1) Lineal descendants, as determined pursuant to 43 CFR 10.14(b).
- 2) Indian Tribe land owner.
- 3) Culturally affiliated Indian Tribe, as determined pursuant to 43 CFR 10.14.
- 4) Indian Tribe recognized as the aboriginal owners of the land by a final judgment of the Indian Claims Commission or the United States Court of Claims.
- 5) Indian Tribe aboriginally occupying the land.
- 6) Indian Tribe with the strongest demonstrated cultural relationship.
- 7) Unclaimed.

Per the Fort Bliss Comprehensive Agreement and Disposition Plan, the signatories agree that all the Tribes have aboriginally occupied the Fort Bliss area. The Tribes agree to designate the Mescalero Apache as the lead tribe for the transfer of custody. The attached Disposition Plan outlines the planned disposition of the remains.

Disposition Plan

In consultation with the signatory tribes on the Comprehensive Agreement, Fort Bliss has developed a Disposition Plan that will be used as a written plan of action (43 CFR § 10.5 (e)) for all Inadvertent Discoveries or Intentional Excavations. The Disposition Plan can be found in Appendix B of this SOP.

- 1) Development, review, and signature of the Disposition Plan follows Army protocol specified in AR 200-1, 6-4, d (5).
- 2) The CRM will prepare the details in the correspondence to the Tribes and follow the Disposition Plan for each discovery.
- 3) The GC or his/her official designee will pre-approve and sign the Disposition Plan.
- 4) Correspondence describing the final results of disposition for a discovery will be provided to the consulting Indian Tribes.

Information obtained during consultation and included in the Disposition Plan:

- 1) Kinds of material to be considered as cultural objects pursuant to 43 CFR 10.2(b).
- 2) Specific information used to determine custody pursuant to 43 CFR 10.6.
- 3) Treatment, care, and handling of human remains and cultural objects.
- 4) Archaeological recording of the human remains and cultural objects.
- 5) Kinds of analysis for identification of human remains and cultural objects.

- 6) Kind(s) of traditional treatment(s) to be afforded the human remains or cultural objects.
- 7) Nature of the reports to be prepared.
- 8) Disposition of human remains and cultural objects in accordance with 43 CFR 10.6.
- 9) Steps to be followed to contact Indian Tribe officials if there is a future inadvertent discovery or before any intentional excavation of human remains or cultural objects.

4.2.4.4 Publishing Notice

Following 43 CFR 10.6(c), prior to implementation of the Disposition Plan, Fort Bliss will publish a notice of the proposed disposition in a newspaper of general circulation in the area in which the Native American human remains and/or objects were discovered, and in which the Tribes who aboriginally occupied the land currently reside.

- 1) The notice will provide information as to the nature and affiliation of the human remains, funerary objects, sacred objects, or objects of cultural patrimony and solicit further claims to custody.
- 2) Privileged information will not be included in the notice(s).
- 3) The notice(s) must be published twice, at least a week apart in the Ruidoso News and El Paso Times newspapers.
- 4) A copy of the notice(s) and information on when and in what newspaper(s) the notice(s) were published will be sent to:
Departmental Consulting Archaeologist
National Park Service,
P.O. Box 37127
Washington, D.C 20013-7127
- 5) The disposition of the Native American human remains and/or object will not take place until at least thirty (30) days after the publication of the second notice(s) to allow time for any additional claimants to come forward.

If, during the thirty (30) day period of publication, additional claimants come forward and the CRM is unable to determine which claimant is entitled to custody of the Native American human remains and/or objects, the process outlined in *Dispute Resolution*, of this SOP will be followed.

4.2.4.5 Treatment and Disposition of Native American Human Remains, Associated Funerary Objects, Sacred Objects, and Objects of Cultural Patrimony

- a. The treatment and disposition of Native American human remains and/or objects recovered from Fort Bliss administered lands will follow the plan of Disposition Plan developed through consultation with the Signatory Tribes.
- b. When the remains are in no immediate harm and will not be affected by an undertaking, the Tribes may chose to leave the remains in place after transfer of custody. At this point, the

disposition process is concluded. Fort Bliss would continue to manage and reasonably protect the remains. This course of action will be included in the Disposition Plan.

c. When the remains may be affected by an undertaking, Fort Bliss will transfer custody of the remains to the Mescalero Apache, and in consultation with the Mescalero Apache will re-inter the remains in a nearby location, preferably on the same archaeological site, that is secure and unlikely to be harmed by the undertaking. Fort Bliss will continue to manage and reasonably protect the remains. This course of action will be included in the Disposition Plan.

d. Fort Bliss will notify the Tribes when the 30-day required publication period is up and will initiate consultation to implement the Disposition Plan. If no response is received by the Tribes within 30 days, or if the Tribes are unable to visit the site after the 30-day period, but before the resumption of activities in the area that could put the remains at risk, the Native American human remains and/or objects will be removed from their original burial context and will be temporarily maintained in a safe and secure manner agreeable to the consulting parties as required by 43 CFR 10.6(c) and 10.15 until the Disposition Plan can be concluded.

f. Fort Bliss will provide the Tribes an opportunity for religious ceremonies pursuant to the American Indian Religious Freedom Act (AIRFA) [42 U.S.C. 1996-1996a] and E.O. 13007 at the burial site.

4.2.4.6 Resumption of Activity [43 CFR 10.4(d)(2)]

a. The activity that resulted in the inadvertent discovery of Native American human remains and/or object may resume if otherwise lawful after thirty (30) days of the certification of the receipt of notification by the CRM.

b. Activity may resume before that time (30 days) if approved by Fort Bliss and the Signatory tribes and if steps for stabilization and protection of the site are taken and there is no excavation or removal of human remains and funerary objects in accordance with 43 CFR 10.3, or change in their disposition to lineal descendants or Indian Tribe/s with priority of custody as defined in 25 U.S.C. 3002, Sec. 3(a) and 43 CFR 10.6.

4.2.4.7 Dispute Resolution

a. All disputes regarding the cultural affiliation of inadvertently discovered or intentionally excavated Native American human remains and/or objects shall be resolved in accordance with Sections 3 and 7(e) of NAGPRA and the implementing regulations 43 CFR 10.

b. Should any interested Tribe make a conflicting claim of cultural affiliation or dispute the methods of treatment or disposition of Native American human remains and/or objects as delineated herein, the CRM will notify the GC. The GC may elect to notify and solicit participation from the Army Environmental Command (AEC).

c. Fort Bliss will continue consultation with the disputing parties, suggest that the disputing parties seek resolution among themselves and, if the disputing parties concur, go before the

NAGPRA Review Committee which is given the authority under 25 U.S.C. 3006, Sec. 8(c)(4) and 43 CFR 10.16 and 10.17 to make recommendations on the resolution of disputes.

d. If upon receipt of the recommendations of the NAGPRA Review Committee, the most appropriate claimant still cannot be determined, Fort Bliss shall retain the disputed Native American human remains and/or other cultural items until the question of custody is resolved, as stated in 43 CFR 10.15(a)(2).

4.2.4.8 Additional Parties

a. Interested Tribes claiming lineal descent or cultural affiliation may join these procedures at any time should they express a desire to do so.

b. In accordance with 43 CFR 10.15 (a)(1), if an interested party fails to make a written claim prior to the time the Native American human remains and other cultural items are duly repatriated or disposed of to a claimant in accordance with 43 CFR 10, the interested party is deemed to have irrevocably waived any right to claim such items pursuant to these regulations.

4.2.5 Disposition Plan

Introduction

Inhumation sites of Native Americans may be expected to be located within prehistoric and historic archaeological areas on Fort Bliss and could be at risk of impacts by natural forces such as erosion, and man-made activities such as military training. Such areas may contain both human remains and associated funerary objects (Section 10.2 of NAGPRA).

In consultation with affiliated Indian tribes, and in accordance with Section 3(c) of NAGPRA and its implementing regulations at 43 CFR 10.4 and 10.5(e), the following disposition plan (Plan) establishes conditions and directions for the treatment and disposition of Native American human remains and associated funerary objects on Fort Bliss. Those tribes include: the Comanche Nation of Oklahoma, the Fort Sill Apache Tribe, the Pueblo of Isleta, the Kiowa Tribe of Oklahoma, the Mescalero Apache Tribe, the White Mountain Apache Tribe, and the Ysleta del Sur Pueblo (hereafter the Tribes).

Definitions

The following definitions for terms used in this Plan are taken from NAGPRA.

- *Disposition* means the transfer of control over Native American human remains, funerary objects, sacred objects, and objects of cultural patrimony by a museum or Federal agency.
- *Human Remains* are the physical remains of a person of Native American ancestry. The term does not include remains or portions of remains that may reasonably be determined to have been given or naturally shed by the individual from whose body they were obtained, such as hair made into ropes or nets or individual teeth.

- *Associated Funerary Objects* are objects that, as a part of the death rite or ceremony of a culture, are reasonably believed to have been placed with individual human remains either at the time of death or later; other items made exclusively for burial purposes or to contain human remains can also be considered as associated funerary objects.
- *Unassociated Funerary Objects* means those funerary objects for which the human remains with which they were placed intentionally are not in the possession or control of a museum or Federal agency.
- *Cultural Affiliation* means a relationship of shared group identity that can reasonably be traced historically or prehistorically between a present day Indian tribe and an identifiable earlier group. Cultural affiliation is determined by Fort Bliss based on a review of evidence, including geographical, kinship, biological, archaeological, anthropological, linguistic, folkloric, oral traditional, historical, or other relevant information or expert opinion.
- *Removal* means the intentional and scientific excavation or other method of recovery of identified or discovered human remains and other cultural items from within the area.
- *Inadvertent Discovery* means the unanticipated encounter or detection of human remains and other cultural items under or on the surface of Federal lands.

Types of objects to be considered NAGPRA items: human remains, associated funerary objects, unassociated funerary objects, sacred objects, and objects of cultural patrimony.

Cultural Affiliation

Fort Bliss recognizes the aboriginal occupation of Fort Bliss lands by the Tribes, following 43 CFR 10.2(e) and 10.11 of NAGPRA, and as such recognized as affiliated Tribes for the purposes of repatriation under NAGPRA. The Tribes further identify the Mescalero Apache as the Tribe to receive custody of the human remains/associated funerary objects/sacred objects/objects of cultural patrimony (unless some other claim is accepted).

If NAGPRA items are to be exhumed and reburied, the following procedures shall be followed (if the items are to remain in place, only the partially exposed item(s) will be described and the item(s) will be re-covered):

Planned Treatment, Care, and Handling of NAGPRA Items

Excavation, analysis, documentation, and reporting of Native American human remains and other cultural items will be conducted in a respectful and professional manner, taking all feasible care to prevent their loss or damage, and to avoid unnecessary disturbance, physical modification, or separation of human remains and associated funerary objects. All NAGPRA items will be stored in a canvas cover, unless otherwise denoted by the Tribes.

Recording of NAGPRA Items

NAGPRA items will be recorded at a descriptive, non-invasive level, including measurement, type, and morphology. The location of the site containing NAGPRA items shall be thoroughly described.

Kinds of Analyses Planned

During the discovery and notification period, analysis of discovered NAGPRA items will consist of in-field analysis to determine age and sex of the individual, as well as any obvious trauma, health or forensic issues (for example, arthritis or broken bones/mended bones).

Inadvertent Discovery

Fort Bliss will follow the procedures outlined in the NAGPRA SOP (Appendix A of the Comprehensive Agreement) upon notification of the discovery of human remains. In all cases, the Tribes will be invited to the site for their evaluation and assessment.

- a. The preferred method of disposition will be to leave the remains in place; other security measures, if any, will be decided during consultation.
- b. If the remains are found to be at great risk of disturbance, the second method of Disposition may be the removal of the remains and the re-interment in a more secure location, as close to the original location as possible. Fort Bliss will secure the means for removal and reburial. The Tribes will complete the reburial with a private ceremony.
- c. An alternate method of disposition will be the interim step of removal of the remains and the temporary transfer to a secure location on Fort Bliss; this method will only be used if the Tribes are not able to visit the site before the resumption of activities in the area that would be expected to place the remains at great risk (and not less than 30 days after the publication of the second Notice of Intended Disposition). The disposition process would continue until custody has been transferred.

Reporting

No Native American human remains will be put on public display in any manner; location information will be collected and hand-drawn sketches may be made as part of the descriptive and analytical recordation of human remains and other cultural items and the activities involved in their recovery. Those records will be secured and stored at Fort Bliss as sensitive information and not available to the public. Any and all reports, articles, or other publicly available accounts that may include mention of the discovery of a burial recovered from Fort Bliss shall treat them with respect and concern for the traditional values of the Tribes.

Disposition

The parties have agreed that the Mescalero Apache will act as agent for all the Tribes and will take custody of the NAGPRA items. Disposition will not occur until at least 30 days after publication of the second Notice of Disposition.

Review and Updating

This Plan will be reviewed by Fort Bliss and updated as necessary to ensure that it continues to meet both Fort Bliss and tribal objectives. It will also be updated as necessary to comply with any changes in NAGPRA or its implementing regulations at 43 CFR part 10. Issues and concerns regarding the adequacy and effectiveness of the Plan may be brought to the attention of Fort Bliss by any of the Tribes at any time and will be promptly addressed. Substantive changes will only be made in consultation with all Tribes.

4.2.6 Notice of Disposition

Notice is here given in accordance with the Native American Graves Protection and Repatriation Act (NAGPRA), 43 CFR 10.6 (c) of the intent to transfer custody of Native American human remains and/or associated funerary objects in the control of Fort Bliss.

A detailed assessment of the Native American human remains and/or associated funerary objects was conducted by Fort Bliss Directorate of Public Works, Environmental Division (DPW-E) archaeologists in consultations with representatives of the Comanche Nation of Oklahoma, Fort Sill Apache Tribe, Kiowa Tribe of Oklahoma, Mescalero Apache Tribe, Pueblo of Isleta, New Mexico, White Mountain Apache Tribe, and Ysleta del Sur Pueblo (Tribes). During the assessment it was determined that, pursuant to 43 CFR 10.2 (d)(1), the physical human remains represented a total of _____ [provide total] unknown individual(s) of Native American ancestry.

On _____ [date of discovery], Native American human remains and/or associated funerary objects were discovered at site 41EP_____/LA ____/FB _____ on Fort Bliss, El Paso/Otero/Dona Aña County (circle one), Texas/New Mexico. (circle one)

- 1) If reported by an archaeological contractor: The site is located in Training Area Number _____ and was being surveyed/evaluated/excavated (circle one) by Fort Bliss contractor _____ [provide contractor's name] as part of a cultural resource management project conducted to assist in compliance with Section 106 of the National Historic Preservation Act (NHPA) and the Advisory Council on Historic Preservation's implementing regulations as set forth under 36 CFR Part 800. The site appears to represent a _____

_____ [provide short description of the site], and based on the nature of the archaeological features and artifacts identified there, is believed to be associated with the people of the Jornada Mogollon or _____ (other) culture who prehistorically occupied the land in/and around Fort Bliss. Immediately upon the detection of a potential human burial, Fort Bliss contractor _____ [provide contractor's name] ceased work activity within the area and notified the Fort Bliss Cultural Resource Manager (CRM) by telephone and via email of the discovery.

- 2) If reported by a soldier, civilian or other non-archaeological contractor: The site is located in Training Area Number _____ and was reported by

[Insert who reported the remains, what the circumstances were, etc. Provide any discussion about sites, features etc., same as above if applicable]

In consultation with the Tribes listed above, the Fort Bliss CRM has determined that, pursuant to 43 CFR 10.6 (a), the preponderance of historical and geographical evidence suggests that Fort Bliss land was aboriginally occupied by the Mescalero Apache. As such, the Native American human remains and/or associated funerary objects will be turned over to the custody of the Mescalero Apache, and an agreed upon plan of intended disposition will be executed if no other Federally Recognized Tribe(s) makes a claim for ownership or control of the remains.

Representatives of any other Federally Recognized Tribe that wish to claim ownership or control of the human remains and/or associated funerary objects should contact the Fort Bliss CRM, at the following address:

Cultural Resource Manager
Fort Bliss Directorate of Public Works,
Environmental Division, Conservation Branch
Building 624, Pleasonton Road
Fort Bliss, Texas 79916-6812

Disposition of the Native American human remains and/or associated funerary objects will proceed after _____ [insert date 30 days after publication of second notice] if no additional claimants come forward before that date.

The Fort Bliss CRM will notify the above Tribes that this notice has been published.

4.3 Standard Operating Procedure #3: Native American Consultation Under the National Historic Preservation Act (this SOP is subject to revision pending completion of a Tribal Memorandum of Agreement- in Draft and Consultation at the time of this ICRMP)

4.3.1 Applicability

This standard operating procedure (SOP) applies to all organizations, property and activities under the control of the Department of the Army and located within the boundaries of Fort Bliss or other contiguous land under Fort Bliss control. It also includes activities undertaken on behalf of the Army or with consent of the Army, or as a result of consent of the Army by contract, lease or inter-service support agreement or other instrument to which Fort Bliss, the United States Army, or the DOD is a party, within Fort Bliss or other contiguous land under Fort Bliss control.

4.3.2 Objective

Consultation is communication that emphasizes trust and respect. It is a shared responsibility that allows an open and free exchange of information and opinion among parties that leads to mutual understanding and comprehension. Consultation is integral to a process of mutually satisfying deliberations to result in collaboration and joint decision making. The objective of this SOP is to establish how consultation between Fort Bliss and appropriate Native American Tribes may occur in meeting consultation requirements under the National Historic Preservation Act (NHPA). Consultation specific to the Native American Graves Protection and Repatriation Act (NAGPRA) will be conducted as outlined in SOP #2: Compliance with the Native American Graves Protection and Repatriation Act of 1990.

4.3.3 Policy

It is Fort Bliss policy to initiate consultation and meaningful tribal participation at any time throughout the projects' process. Fort Bliss offers of tribal consultation and participation will be triggered by relevant and significant events, such as discoveries of cultural phenomena, or initiation of projects or processes that have a potential to affect cultural phenomena.

Fort Bliss and each Tribe, according to their internal procedures and protocols, will designate government-to-government representatives for consultation purposes. It is desirable to have consultation occur at appropriate staff levels. Signatories to agreements between the parties will be high-level representative officials from each organization.

The following provide the foundation upon which all Native American consultation will take place:

- Respect the sovereign status of each Native American Tribal government. Fort Bliss must work directly with Federally-recognized Tribes on a government-to-government basis, recognizing the sovereignty of each Tribe. First contact should be made with the Tribal leadership.

- At a minimum, the Indian Tribes with whom consultation should occur are those groups that have tribal or trust lands in proximity to Fort Bliss, those Tribes that occupied the area of Fort Bliss in aboriginal times, those Tribes or groups with which Fort Bliss has previously held consultation proceedings, and those Tribes or groups that identify themselves as having interests on lands managed by Fort Bliss.
- An attempt should be made to identify any non-Federally recognized Native American groups that may eventually be brought into consultation as interested parties under certain Federal laws and regulations.
- Notification to Tribal representatives should be made in letter form signed by the GC to the head of the Tribal government, followed immediately by a confirming telephone call. Written notification should be sent by certified mail or similar device that offers receipt of delivery to the address.
- The consultation timetable should be developed to allow for the greatest opportunity possible for appropriate Tribal representatives and others to participate in consultation.
- The GC should request information concerning Tribal-developed regulations, ordinances, resolutions, and protocols for handling issues covered under specific Federal cultural resources legislation when first establishing a consultation relationship.
- Consultation should identify, as early as possible, all potential issues that may result from a particular procedure or activity, so that resulting consultation meetings will not address these issues in a piecemeal fashion.
- For procedural and planning decisions, consultation should be designed to result in mutually acceptable terms for avoiding or minimizing effects on Native American human remains or cultural resources. Agreement upon mutually acceptable revisions to plans or procedures that take into consideration Tribal concerns may be all that is necessary.
- For proposed construction or land use activities, intentional excavations may be planned to determine whether any Native American cultural resources are present. The scope and procedures used for intentional excavations should be developed in consultation with all interested parties as outlined in the “Programmatic Agreement among the Fort Bliss Garrison Command and the New Mexico State Historic Preservation Officer and the Texas State Historic Preservation Officer and the Advisory Council on Historic Preservation for the Management of Historic Properties on Fort Bliss, Fort Bliss, Texas, under Sections 106 and 110 of the National Historic Preservation Act of 1966 (as amended).”
- If a Tribe, or Tribal representative, does not respond in the requested time frame, follow-up notification should be made and alternative methods of consultation should be considered.
- Any Tribe may request to enter into consultation with the Fort Bliss GC to develop a Memorandum of Agreement (MOA) on how consultation will be conducted between the installation and the requesting Tribe.

4.3.4 Implementing Procedures

The following procedures provide the general guidelines for consultation and identify issues to consider.

4.3.4.1 Consultation

Fort Bliss shall have respectful, meaningful, and effective two-way communication with the Signatory Tribes before Fort Bliss makes its decision or moves forward with its action. Consultation shall occur as early and often as needed or desired by all parties.

At a minimum, Fort Bliss will hold an annual meeting with the Signatory Tribes. During the annual meeting Fort Bliss and the Signatory Tribes will, at a minimum, discuss the Area of Potential Effect (APE) for future projects to identify any areas that the Signatory Tribes might attach religious and/or cultural significance. No consultation will occur on Exempted Actions (Appendix A) other than notice of those activities. Army-wide exemptions include undertakings where there is an imminent threat to human health and safety. Other meetings can be called with the consensus of the Signatory Tribes.

Consultation shall remain meaningful throughout the relevant projects and processes, including ensuring that a reasonable number of parties are present and have sufficient opportunity to express views and concerns, ensuring that Fort Bliss staff in attendance have some degree of decision-making authority for purposes of consultation, ensuring that time, place, and agenda for each meeting are mutually agreed upon, and ensuring that all parties have access to all relevant and necessary information concerning the subject(s) of the consultation.

Fort Bliss and each tribe, according to their internal procedures and protocols (see Attachment A for Ysleta del Sur Pueblo protocol), will designate government-to-government representatives for consultation purposes.

4.3.4.2 Access

Access to the Fort Bliss Training Complex (FBTC) will follow established protocol for visitors, although the Army training mission will take precedence.

The Signatory Tribes are advised to consult with Fort Bliss on the most current procedures. Access to the Fort Bliss training areas must be coordinated with Range Operations and include obtaining a vehicle/recreation pass. The Fort Bliss Cultural Resource Manager (CRM) and staff will assist the Signatory Tribe(s) in obtaining access to the training areas.

4.3.4.3 Natural Resources

Fort Bliss recognizes that activities and undertakings on lands that it manages have the potential to affect natural resources of interest to the Signatory Tribes. Fort Bliss recognizes that natural resources are an integral part of tribal cultural beliefs and practices and are not always separated from cultural resource issues. To insure tribal interests are considered in a timely manner and in

the spirit of cooperation, the signatories to this MOA agree to the following in regard to natural resources.

Fort Bliss will work cooperatively with the Signatory Tribes in developing/revising its Integrated Natural Resources Management Plan (INRMP). Fort Bliss will incorporate tribal interests in the INRMP as developed through consultation.

The Signatory Tribes will provide information on significant resources to Fort Bliss in a timely manner to insure appropriate incorporation in the Fort Bliss INRMP.

Fort Bliss will work cooperatively with the Signatory Tribes to identify what plants located on Fort Bliss have cultural significance to the tribes (Attachment C : Plants of Interest List— Mescalero Apache Tribe, Ysleta del Sur Pueblo, and Comanche Nation of Oklahoma). As plants of interest are identified, Fort Bliss will work towards identifying plant-specific habitat that may sustain harvesting by interested tribes, subject to availability of funds and military mission constraints.

Fort Bliss will work with the Signatory Tribes to identify other natural resources (i.e., rabbits, ochre, etc.) that may be of interest to the tribes. As these resources are identified, and upon request by the tribes, Fort Bliss will work towards identifying areas that may sustain collection, subject to availability of funds and military mission constraints.

4.3.4.4 Cultural Resources

Fort Bliss and the Tribes agree that a variety of cultural resource types can be found on Fort Bliss and that those designations can at times overlap: prehistoric sites, historic sites, sacred sites, Traditional Cultural Properties (TCPs). The parties understand that the National Historic Preservation Act (NHPA) of 1966 (36 CFR, part 800), as amended, and particularly Section 106 of that Act, sets forth the procedures for Federal agencies to follow when proposing an undertaking and any effects that undertaking may have on historic properties. Part 800.2(c)(2) of that Act includes procedures for consultation with Indian tribes and Native Hawaiian organizations. Additionally, the parties understand that a Programmatic Agreement (PA) among Fort Bliss, the Advisory Council on Historic Preservation, and the Texas and New Mexico State Historic Preservation Officers for the management of historic properties on Fort Bliss has been agreed upon as a program alternative to implementation of Section 106. This Stipulation does not alter any of those basic procedures.

Identify and Recording Sites. Fort Bliss will identify and record cultural resources following the methods outlined in the PA, Appendix C, Identifying and Evaluating Properties (Appendix A). It is understood that the identification of properties of traditional religious and cultural importance (including sacred sites and TCPs) is best conducted by those most qualified, the Tribes, in consultation with Fort Bliss, subject to military mission constraints.

Evaluating Sites. Fort Bliss will follow the methods outlined in the *Significance and Research Standards for Prehistoric Archaeological Sites at Fort Bliss: A Design for the Evaluation, Management, and Treatment of Cultural Resources* (Miller et al. 2009) for the evaluation of

prehistoric archaeological sites under the National Register of Historic Places (NRHP) Criteria for Eligibility as consulted on with the Tribes in November 2008. That document has been made available to all Tribes and is also available on the Fort Bliss web site <https://www.bliss.army.mil/DPW/Environmental/EISDocuments2.html>. The *Significance and Research Standards for Prehistoric Archaeological Sites at Fort Bliss: A Design for the Evaluation, Management, and Treatment of Cultural Resources* is currently being reviewed and updated. Per the PA, the Significance Standards revision will be complete by the end of Fiscal Year 2017.

Sharing Data. Fort Bliss will provide compact discs (CDs) of any report(s) produced during survey, evaluation, and mitigation projects when those projects address areas or sites that have been identified as culturally and/or religiously significant to the Signatory Tribes, or upon their request.

4.3.4.5. Properties of Traditional Religious and Cultural Importance

Fort Bliss will consider Properties of Traditional Religious and Cultural Importance (including TCPs and sacred sites) in project planning. The parties agree that the identification, evaluation, and management of Properties of Traditional Religious and Cultural Importance require tribal consultation and participation.

According to the National Park Service National Register Bulletin, *Guidelines for Evaluating and Documenting Traditional Cultural Properties* (1998), a “traditional cultural property...can be defined as one that is eligible for inclusion in the National Register because of its association with cultural practices or beliefs of a living community that (a) are rooted in the community’s history, and (b) are important in maintaining the continuing cultural identity of the community.” Such properties may be determined to be eligible for inclusion on the National Register (National Historic Preservation Act (NHPA) Section 101[d][6][A]) and must meet one or more of the NRHP criteria. A site’s eligibility can be based on traditional knowledge, literature reviews, archaeological work, and archival records. In addition to having to meet at least one of the four Criteria of Eligibility, the property must retain integrity. Although under the NHPA a TCP is considered a “historic property” and Fort Bliss will also follow the procedures as set forth in the PA for assessing effects to historic properties, additional considerations may be given to the properties. For example, a TCP may or may not meet the criteria for a sacred site.

From Executive Order (EO) No. 13007, a sacred site “means any specific, discrete, narrowly delineated location on Federal land that is identified by an Indian tribe, or Indian individual determined to be an appropriately authoritative representative of an Indian religion, as sacred by virtue of its established religious significance to, or ceremonial use by, an Indian religion; provided that the tribe or appropriately authoritative representative of an Indian religion has informed the agency of the existence of such a site.” The parties agree that there is a benefit to both parties to identify, at some level, the existence of such sites. A sacred site may not meet the criteria for a Historic Property under the NHPA. However, even if the site is not considered a historic property and subject to those procedures, EO 13007 goes on to say that Federal agencies shall ensure reasonable notice of proposed actions or land management policies that may restrict future access to or ceremonial use of, or adversely affect the physical integrity of sacred sites.

The goal is to accommodate access to and ceremonial use of sacred sites and to avoid adversely affecting their physical integrity.

In addition to EO 13007, Fort Bliss and the Signatory Tribes also acknowledge the American Indian Religious Freedom Act (AIRFA) (42 U.S.C. 1996) as a federal law that was created to protect and preserve the traditional religious rights and cultural practices of American Indians, Eskimos, Aleuts, and Native Hawaiians. These rights include, but are not limited to, access of sacred sites, repatriation of sacred objects held in museums, freedom to worship through ceremonial and traditional rites, including within prisons, and use and possession of objects considered sacred.

Level of Identification: Tribal consultation will determine the level of effort required to identify Properties of Traditional Religious and Cultural Importance. It should be noted that Properties of Traditional Religious and Cultural Importance may include natural settings and do not necessarily need to contain culturally modified objects/sites to be considered in the planning process. The tribes will identify Properties of Traditional Religious and Cultural Importance significant to them.

Recordation of Properties of Traditional Religious and Cultural Importance: Fort Bliss will develop a GIS-based database for recording Properties of Traditional Religious and Cultural Importance. This will be accomplished in a manner sensitive to tribal sovereignty, religious freedom, and confidentiality concerns. Database access may be restricted to specific staff. When Fort Bliss undertakings are proposed, the CRM or specified staff will check the project location against sites identified in that database; consultation will be initiated when a project has the potential to affect one of those identified properties. For areas that have not been surveyed for Properties of Traditional Religious and Cultural Importance, consultation will be initiated by Fort Bliss with the Signatory Tribes to identify such sites that may exist in the project's APE.

Periodic Monitoring. The Signatory Tribes may conduct periodic monitoring of sites of interest and provide a report of that work to Fort Bliss, subject to military mission constraints.

When any of the Signatory Tribes perform research and work under this stipulation, tribal members are exempt from meeting professional standards as outlined in the Secretary of the Interior's Professional Qualifications Standards unless the work includes:

- Archaeological survey
- Archaeological evaluation under Criteria of the National Register of Historic Places
- Archaeological data collection as part of data recovery effort

Additional Confidentiality: Tribes may determine that sharing information about a Property of Traditional Religious and Cultural Importance is inappropriate. In such circumstances, consideration of adverse effects in the planning process is still possible. Tribes may delineate a boundary around a significant site, which will be large enough to avoid inadvertent discovery of the property. The boundary demarcation will be represented in the Fort Bliss Archaeological GIS database. When an undertaking is proposed within the boundary, consultation with the appropriate tribe(s) will be initiated to discover whether the proposed project will affect the

Property of Traditional Religious and Cultural Importance. If the project may adversely affect the site, avoidance through project relocation will be explored. Where adverse effects cannot be avoided, consultation by Fort Bliss with the Signatory Tribes will determine appropriate mitigation measures. In respect of confidentiality issues, Fort Bliss will only request information necessary to consider adverse effects in the planning process.

Alternatives to a Finding of Effect: For projects that may affect Properties of Traditional Religious and Cultural significance, Fort Bliss will consider the following alternatives in consultation with the Signatory Tribes.

- **Avoidance:** Avoidance of properties of traditional religious and cultural importance is the preferred action. Locating projects in areas not containing significant resources may often be achieved with little adjustment or delay if addressed early in the planning process.
- **Protection:** Sometimes undertakings cannot avoid areas that may contain Properties of Traditional Religious and Cultural Importance. In these instances, it may be possible to protect the property from adverse impacts by physically placing them off-limits. Barriers, markers, SIBER stakes, signs, or fencing may be used to protect sites.
- **Monitoring:** Physical protection of Properties of Traditional Religious and Cultural Importance can include periodic monitoring to assess the effectiveness of the protective measure. If it is suspected that written or verbal instruction is being ignored, or that markers or barriers placed around the site are insufficient, other strategies will be explored in consultation with the Signatory Tribes and implemented to better ensure protection.
- **Mitigation through data recovery:** Fort Bliss acknowledges that the Signatory Tribes are the expert as to the type and extent of adverse effect a particular activity may have on a Property of Traditional Religious and Cultural Importance. Therefore, if a property cannot be avoided and an adverse effect requires mitigation, Fort Bliss will consult with the Signatory Tribes to identify suitable mitigation measures.

Additional Consultation under Properties of Traditional Religious and Cultural Importance:

If the proposed project was not anticipated at the annual meeting, a special meeting will be arranged to consult on the effect, if any, the project might have on Properties of Traditional Religious and Cultural Importance and how, if present, the site(s) might be avoided, protected, monitored, or effects mitigated.

4.3.4.6 Assessing Effects of Undertakings

Within an Area of Potential Effect (APE), if the Fort Bliss CRM finds that no historic property is present, or that no historic property would be affected, or that no historic property would be adversely affected by an undertaking, Fort Bliss will document that decision and notify the Signatory Tribes during the annual meeting. From the NHPA of 1966, as amended (800.16 Definitions), the APE is defined as “the geographic area or areas within which an undertaking

may directly or indirectly cause alterations in the character or use of historic properties, if any such properties exist. The area of potential effects is influenced by the scale and nature of an undertaking and may be different for different kinds of effects caused by the undertaking.”

If the Fort Bliss CRM finds that an undertaking will cause an adverse effect to a historic property of interest to the Signatory Tribes, Fort Bliss will initiate consultation with all Signatory Tribes on the resolution of that adverse effect.

If the Fort Bliss CRM determines that data recovery is the best option for resolution of the adverse effect, then Fort Bliss will submit a research design to the tribes and allow 30 days for review of that plan. If, after 30 days, no comments are received, Fort Bliss will proceed with the proposed mitigation strategy. If changes are recommended, they will be incorporated or consultation will continue.

If the characteristics of the sites at risk for adverse effects fit one of several Historic Contexts outlined in the revised Significance Standards, Fort Bliss may conduct data recovery using an established Programmatic Research Design. The signatory tribes will be advised of that decision and may consult the Significance Standards for the particulars of that plan. As more Programmatic Research Designs are developed, Fort Bliss will consult with the Signatory Tribes for a 30-day review of those proposed plans.

4.4 Standard Operating Procedure #4: Identifying Consulting Parties

4.4.1 Applicability

This standard operating procedure (SOP) applies to all organizations, property, and activities under the control of the Department of the Army and located within the boundaries of Fort Bliss or other contiguous land under Fort Bliss control. It also includes activities undertaken on behalf of the Army or with consent of the Army, or as a result of consent of the Army by contract, lease, or inter-service support agreement or other instrument to which Fort Bliss, the United States Army, or the DOD is a party, within Fort Bliss or other contiguous land under Fort Bliss control.

4.4.2 Objective

The objective of this SOP is to lay out a process for Fort Bliss to follow to identify appropriate consulting parties per 36 CFR Part 800 and the Programmatic Agreement (PA). Under 36 CFR Part 800, State Historic Preservation Officers and Federally recognized Native American Tribes must be consulted on undertakings. The PA and 36 CFR Part 800 also requires additional parties to be given an opportunity to comment and consult on agency undertakings. This SOP does not set out how consultation with these additional parties will take place. Consultation is addressed under the appropriate SOP in the PA. This SOP addresses how additional parties will be identified.

4.4.3 Policy

It is Fort Bliss policy to allow all consulting and interested parties to comment on undertakings that may affect historic properties as outlined in the PA.

4.4.4 Implementing Procedures

The following procedures shall be followed:

- Fort Bliss shall provide all representatives of local governments the opportunity to consult on undertakings that may have the potential to affect cultural resources. At a minimum, these shall include Certified Local Governments (CLG) as identified in Section 2.10 Interested Parties of this ICRMP. As other local governments may become a CLG or upon identification of interest, these will be included. Contact and consultation is accomplished under the National Environmental Policy Act (NEPA) procedures as identified by the appropriate SOP of the PA.
- Fort Bliss shall seek and provide entities that have an interest in historic preservation topics an opportunity to consult on undertakings that may have the potential to affect cultural resources. This may consist of, but not be limited to, El Paso County Historical Society, El Paso Historical Foundation, Preservation Texas and the New Mexico Archaeological Council.

- Fort Bliss shall seek and provide the general public an opportunity to comment on undertakings that may have the potential to affect cultural resources. The general public is used here in terms of individuals expressing individual interests. The following must be provided by the individual in order for him or her to be considered a consulting party.
 - Individual must identify the undertaking that is of interest and establish what their interest is. Fort Bliss will not entertain blanket statements from individuals stating he or she wishes to be consulted on all Fort Bliss undertakings that may affect cultural resources.
 - Individuals must make their request through written communication to the Cultural Resource Manager (CRM). Copies of this request must be furnished to the appropriate State Historic Preservation Officer.
 - If the individual's interest is with undertakings that may affect properties of traditional cultural and religious importance to a Native American Tribe(s), the individual must notify that Tribe(s) of his or her request to be consulted with. If the Tribe(s) request that the individual not be consulted because of the sensitive nature of the resource, the individual will be informed that he or she will not be consulted.

- It is Fort Bliss' responsibility, in consultation with the appropriate State Historic Preservation Officer, to identify appropriate parties to consult. If, through consultation with the appropriate SHPO, it is determined that the requesting individual does not have an interest in the resources potentially affected by an undertaking, that individual will be notified as such.

- It is highly recommended that individuals work through consulting parties (SHPO, ACHP, Tribes) or through established groups (i.e. NMAC) to have their concerns addressed in the consultation process. Individuals will be addressed as interested parties but not as consulting parties (i.e., will not be signatures to agreements that may result in consultation).

4.5 Standard Operating Procedure #5: Curatorial and Collection Management of Archaeological and Historical Collections and Associated Records

4.5.1 Applicability

This standard operating procedure (SOP) applies to all organizations, property and activities under the control of the Department of the Army and located within the boundaries of Fort Bliss or other contiguous land under Fort Bliss control. It also includes activities undertaken on behalf of the Army or with consent of the Army, or as a result of consent of the Army by contract, lease or inter-service support agreement or other instrument to which Fort Bliss, the United States Army, or the DOD is a party, within Fort Bliss or other contiguous land under Fort Bliss control.

4.5.2 Objective

The mission of the Fort Bliss Curatorial Facility is threefold: (1) as a premier facility for the preservation of the archaeological resources of Fort Bliss; (2) as a research center for scholars and professionals who wish to analyze and study the collections and thus further promote the history and heritage of Fort Bliss and the associated prehistoric cultures of the region; (3) as a secure repository facility for the collections of other Federal agencies.

In accordance with this mission, the Curatorial Program at Fort Bliss will ensure that the highest standards of care, organization and preservation are accorded to all historic and prehistoric artifacts, as well as project and site supporting documentation extant on the collections of the Directorate of Public Works - Environmental Division (DPW-E), Conservation Branch, Fort Bliss Military Reservation. The Curatorial Facility, located in Buildings 624 and 645, is required to comply with 36 CFR 79, *Curation of Federally Owned and Administered Archaeological Collections*, and other governing Federal regulations as they relate to Federally-owned and administered collections. These regulations require that artifacts and supporting data be accessioned in accordance with 36 CFR 79 standards, be appropriately curated in a secure climate-controlled facility with an appropriate disaster preparedness and response plan, and be cataloged, inventoried, and preserved in perpetuity. The governing authority initiated by 36 CFR 79 gives retaining agencies the authority to:

Preserve collections of prehistoric and historic material remains and associated records recovered under the authority of the Antiquities Act (16 U.S.C. 431-433), the Reservoir Salvage Act (16 U.S.C. 469-469c), section 110 of the National Historic Preservation Act (16 U.S.C. 470h - 2) or the Archaeological Resources Protection Act (16 U.S.C. 470aa-mm) (36 CFR 79.1; 372).

The constructs of 36 CFR 79 also require that collections and supporting documentation be made available to qualified researchers and institutions. The unique scope of the Fort Bliss archaeological collection lends itself to on-going analysis by qualified professionals. Consequently, it falls under the mission of the Curatorial Facility to encourage independent research using the collection. Facilities exist for visiting scholars and archaeologists to have on-

site access to the collection. Research facilities, the standard operating procedure for on-site analysis and loans of artifacts are treated in Section 4.5.4.6.

4.5.2.1 Research

In accordance with the Fort Bliss Curatorial Facility's Collection Policy (4.5.3 Collection Policy), the facility's manager and staff will endeavor to secure those artifacts and supporting data not currently in the possession of Fort Bliss. Collectors have long surveyed the ground of Fort Bliss, and some of these individuals collected artifacts from the post and ranges. As a repository for the archaeological heritage of Fort Bliss, the Curatorial Facility accepts as part of its mission the task of attempting to retrieve, through donations and deeds of gift (4.5.4.8 Deed of Gift), this property from private collectors.

Fort Bliss contains a number of museums, each with its own focus. The concern here is only with the collections controlled by the DPW-E, Conservation Branch and housed in the Fort Bliss Curatorial Facility. These collections are primarily archaeological in nature and contain culturally significant artifacts from prehistoric and historic contexts, as well as associated documentation in the forms of site files, project files, photographs, slides and contact sheets with negatives, USGS and Defense Mapping Agency maps and aerial photographs.

Additionally, the Curatorial Facility houses collections controlled by the Fort Bliss Historic Architecture Program. These include architectural elements, historic photographs, and plans pertinent to the treatment and maintenance of the historic structures of the post.

The prehistoric landscape of Fort Bliss spans approximately 12,000 years from the end of the Pleistocene until A.D. 1540. Historic periods represented on Fort Bliss range from historic Native American groups who utilized the area through the American rancher period to the end of the Cold War.

4.5.3 Collection Policy

4.5.3.1 Prehistoric and Historic Collections

The Curatorial Facility at Fort Bliss curates artifacts pertinent to the prehistory and history of the land included in the Fort Bliss Military Reservation. The prehistoric collection includes all artifacts from prehistoric contexts, regardless of age or cultural affiliation, provided the artifacts were recovered within the reservation boundaries. Human remains are also covered in this policy, also see SOP #2 (Compliance with NAGPRA). Historic artifacts include but are not limited to objects of civilian or military manufacture from contact period (16th Century) to the present and recovered from the property encompassed by Fort Bliss or pertinent to any historic event involving the military installation. Federal and state guidelines define an archaeological site as a discrete locus or collection of loci of cultural materials of at least 50 years of age. Because some sites and materials on Fort Bliss date from the Cold War Era (1953–1991), this Collection Policy contains latitude for the collection and preservation of artifacts, documents and photographs from this important period in history.

4.5.3.2 Necessity

The Collection Policy for the Fort Bliss Curatorial Facility is necessary due to the scope and diversity of the collection under the care and mission of the Curatorial Program. The Collection Policy ensures the focus of the collection will remain on the history and cultural heritage of the Fort Bliss Military Reservation.

4.5.3.3 Scope of Collections

The diversity of the Fort Bliss collection and the potential for unregulated growth dictate that the Curatorial Program maintains a strict collection policy. The Collection Policy pertains solely to the archaeological and documentary collections of Fort Bliss and the accessions and documentation thereof. This Collection Policy does not however, preclude the use of the Curatorial Facility as storage for collections from other Federal agencies. Acceptance of such collections from other agencies for curatorial services must be accompanied by proper documentation, memoranda of agreement (MOA), and supporting data. The provision of curatorial services is contingent on the status of the Fort Bliss collection and laboratory staffing requirements. All non-Fort Bliss-specific collections will be stored and maintained separately from the main collection. Such collections may be documented through a separate database, but only when this is specified by the affected Federal agency who shall maintain collection ownership.

4.5.4 Implementing Procedures

4.5.4.1 Collection Management

Management of all collections administered by the Fort Bliss Curatorial Facility will be to the highest standards and in full compliance with Federal regulations as set forth in 36 CFR 79. This compliance standard includes the maintenance of associated records and files pertaining to the collection and the fulfillment of all regulatory requirements. All collections received for curation at the Fort Bliss Curatorial Facility must adhere to certain standards of processing (e.g., housing, labeling). Collections not meeting these standards require an advance arrangement with the Fort Bliss Curatorial Facility for standard processing to be completed by the curatorial staff.

4.5.4.2 Artifacts

Artifacts in the Fort Bliss collection encompass a wide variety of types recovered from a variety of environments during different projects. However, all artifacts are processed into the collections in the same manner, regardless of how they have been collected or the material from which they are made.

4.5.4.3 Associated Records

Each archaeological investigation generates associated documentation or records. Even in cases where artifacts are not collected, some kind of record is produced (e.g., letter, report, and site forms). These associated records are represented as mixed media, site and project files, slides

and various sizes of photography. The primary goal of archiving associated records is to stabilize and arrange the records so they are easily accessible.

4.5.4.4 Curatorial Facility

A state-of-the-art Fort Bliss Curatorial Facility is located in Buildings 624 and 645 at the corner of Pleasanton and Taylor. These renovated stable buildings provide more than 35,000 cubic feet of climate-controlled artifact storage space as well as facilities to accommodate visiting researchers and a processing laboratory.

The artifact storage spaces in Building 624 are divided into two rooms, the main artifact storage room and a cold storage room. Both are climate controlled and each maintains ideal conditions for their individual collections. Both rooms are equipped with digital thermal hygrometers to allow laboratory personnel to monitor and track fluctuations in either temperature or relative humidity. Both storage spaces are equipped with sprinklers for fire suppression. Both also contain water-alert sensing systems to protect against water damage due to flash flooding. This section of the facility is secured by a keypad entry security system.

Building 645 has the capacity to store approximately 30,000 linear feet of cultural material. The main artifact storage room is equipped with digital hydrometers to allow laboratory personnel to monitor and track fluctuations in both humidity and temperature. Building 645 is also equipped with sprinklers for fire-suppression and contains water-alert sensing systems to protect against water damage due to flash flooding. This section of the facility is secured by a keypad entry security system. Two additional rooms off the south end of Building 645 are to be finished as research stations for visiting scholars involved in use of the collections.

All efforts by the curatorial staff are made to ensure the integrity and longevity of the collection. While the Curatorial Facility can slow the degradation process, it cannot arrest it, and therefore, a strategy for the preservation and conservation of the collection is necessary. Although the scope of this SOP does not encompass individual preservation and conservation strategies, it does provide for the establishment of an inventory and preservation or conservation policy.

The initial inventory of the Fort Bliss Curatorial Facility will be completed as the collection is accessioned and cataloged. Any necessary preservation or conservation strategies for individual artifacts will be noted, the strategy formulated, and then carried out with all appropriate documentation. The policy of the Curatorial Facility calls for as little intervention as possible, and recommends that any that does occur be as nontoxic and minimal as possible and, beyond all else, completely reversible.

Following completion of the initial inventory, the collections held at the Fort Bliss Curatorial Facility will be subjected to an overall inventory every five years to ensure the integrity of the collection.

4.5.4.5 Research and Collection Use

Section 79.10 of 36 CFR 79 provides for and encourages the use of collections by qualified professionals and institutions. According to the regulations:

The Federal Agency Official shall ensure that the Repository official makes the collection available for scientific, educational, and religious uses, subject to such terms and conditions as are necessary to protect and preserve the condition, research potential, religious or sacred importance, and uniqueness of the collection.

In accordance with 36 CFR 79, the collections stored in the Fort Bliss Curatorial Facility will be made available for analysis and research to qualified professionals and institutions who wish to conduct on-site research with the collections. Research hours are 0800 to 1630 Monday through Friday.

Every effort will be made to encourage and accommodate the use of the collections by qualified researchers. To conduct research with the collections, prior arrangements must be made at least one (1) week in advance with the Curatorial Facility manager. Researchers should telephone, email, or submit a letter detailing the components of the collections they wish to view, a synopsis of the scope of their research, and whether or not they believe they will need photocopying or photo reproduction services. Objects of research will be retrieved from and returned to, the collection by DPW-E staff archaeologists.

The facility in Building 624 includes a research room for individuals to conduct research. Researchers will provide their own materials. Please note that ballpoint and ink pens are not allowed in the research room. When applicable, white cotton gloves will be provided by the archaeology staff. Food and drink are not allowed in any portion of the Curatorial Facility.

Research conducted with the Fort Bliss collections must acknowledge the repository in the appropriate manner. The DPW-E, Conservation Branch requires copies of all publications, dissertations and theses, or documents resulting from such research. In cases where the researcher is known to the DPW-E staff, it may be possible for portions of the collections to be loaned to that individual.

All photographs held by the Fort Bliss Curatorial Facility are public domain. However, the Fort Bliss Curatorial Facility requests that any images used in publications contain a credit line stating: *Courtesy of the Fort Bliss Curatorial Facility* or *Courtesy of the Fort Bliss Historical Photography Collection*. Individual collections held by the facility should be credited accordingly: e.g., *From the P. J. Michaels Collection Courtesy of the Fort Bliss Historical Photography Collection*.

4.5.4.6 Loans

The Fort Bliss Curatorial Facility will enter into short-term loan agreements with qualified researchers and institutions. Loans are made for research, educational, analytical, and

instructional purposes and a standard loan agreement accompanies loans for off-site artifact analysis and evaluation.

Loans to qualified institutions for exhibition or research purposes are subject to short-term loan agreements that specifically state the responsibilities of the collection owner — the United States Government and Fort Bliss — and the borrower. The Fort Bliss lending policy states that artifacts are loaned on a per annum basis, i.e., renewed annually subject to prearranged conditions set forth in the loan agreement. In some cases, particularly with regard to loans to other institutions, the terms of the loans will be set for a five-year term, to be renewed every five (5) years. In either case, it is important to note that the *borrower* is responsible for insuring the material against loss, breakage, contamination and theft. Permission must be obtained from the Curatorial Facility manager before any destructive analysis is performed on objects borrowed from the Fort Bliss collections. Standard loan agreements are herein included.

4.5.4.7 NAGPRA

On December 4, 1995, the Department of the Interior Office of the Secretary published and distributed its final rule on 43 CFR 10, the Native American Grave Protection and Repatriation Act (NAGPRA) regulations. First signed into law on 16 November 1990, NAGPRA addresses the rights of lineal descendants, Indian Tribes, and Native Hawaiian organizations to certain Native American remains, funerary objects, sacred objects, or objects of cultural patrimony with which they are affiliated (*Federal Record*, Vol. 60 Number 232, December 1995, 62134).

In response to a November 1995 Department of the Army, United States Army Environmental Center memorandum, *Results of NAGPRA Compliance Analysis for Fort Bliss and attached report, Collections Summary for Fort Bliss, Texas, U.S. Army NAGPRA Compliance Project*, Technical Report No. 32, the Army Corps of Engineers, St. Louis District, Mandatory Center of Expertise for Curation and Management of Archaeological Collections conducted an inventory and evaluation of NAGPRA-specific artifacts and remains curated in the Fort Bliss collection. Fort Bliss has completed Sections 5 and 6 inventories and contacted the appropriate Tribes and is in compliance with NAGPRA. As the directors of an active ongoing program of site testing and mitigation, DPW-E personnel remain vigilant with regard to human remains and associated grave goods subject to NAGPRA regulations that may be recovered from Fort Bliss property.

Negotiations and consultation among individual Tribes and Tribal councils and Fort Bliss are conducted by the Chief of Conservation Branch of the DPW-E, assisted by other members of the archaeological staff. In no way will Curatorial Facility personnel initiate any repatriation negotiations with any Tribe, Tribal member or Tribal council.

4.5.4.8 Deed of Gift

Deeds of Gift are those legal forms that transfer ownership in perpetuity of an artifact or collection of artifacts from a private owner to a museum or Federal repository. The execution of a Deed of Gift must follow the form shown below or include all ingredients of that form in order for it to be legal, binding, and non-negotiable from that date forward either by the person donating the artifact and/or collection or his or her heirs. A Deed of Gift between an individual

and Fort Bliss entitles both donor and recipient to a number of benefits. The greatest benefit for the donor is a tax deduction. It is imperative that any individual acting on behalf of Fort Bliss explain in full that in order for a donor to claim a tax deduction on donated material, such material must be donated without provision or attached conditions. It is the responsibility of the donor to obtain a fair appraisal of the artifacts or collection to be donated by a disinterested party. It is UNETHICAL for any individual associated with the Deed of Gift process or any employee of Fort Bliss or any personnel associated with the Curatorial Facility to suggest an appraisal value for any artifact.

An example of a Deed of Gift is shown below as it appears in *Appendix A* of 36 CFR 79, with the addition that any Deed of Gift will be for all time, and the donor and his or her heirs will renounce all claim to any donated material.

Donations of historical photography or associated records will follow the same general format for a Deed of Gift as that provided below. Differences will be that the donor holds free and clear title to the images, will allow for the publications and use of such images with appropriate credits as it pertains to collections held in the public domain, and renounces all claims to the images for all time, either from the donor or the donor's heirs. (A sample Deed of Gift form follows below.)

DEED OF GIFT
TO THE FORT BLISS CURATORIAL FACILITY

Whereas, the Fort Bliss Curatorial Facility, hereinafter called the Recipient, is dedicated to the preservation and protection of artifacts, specimens and associated records that are generated in connection with its projects and programs;

Whereas, certain artifacts and specimens listed in Attachment A to this Deed of Gift, were recovered from the <include name of historic or prehistoric resource or site> within the property boundaries of Fort Bliss Military Installation in connection with the Recipient's <name of project> project;

Whereas, the <name of the prehistoric or historic resource or site> is located on lands to which title is held by <name of Donor>, hereinafter called the Donor, and that the Donor holds free and clear title to the artifacts and specimens;

Whereas, the Donor is desirous of donating artifacts and specimens to the Recipient to ensure their continued preservation and protection;

Now therefore, the Donor does hereby unconditionally donate to the Recipient, for unrestricted use for all time, renouncing any further claim as could be made by the Donor and/or his or her heirs, those artifacts and specimens listed in Attachment A to this Deed of Gift;
and

The Recipient hereby gratefully acknowledges the receipt of the artifacts and specimens.

Signed: <Signature of Donor>

Date: <Date>

Signed: <Signature of Federal Agency Official>

Date: <Date>

Attachment A: Inventory of Artifacts and Specimens
[55 FR 37360, Sept. 12, 1990; 55 FR 41639, Oct. 10, 1990]

4.5.4.9 Loan Agreements

All property under the jurisdiction of the United States Government is subject to certain governing laws and regulations. Property held by the United States Government or any agency may not be disposed of without due process through GSA or other governing authority. Artifacts, as well as associated records, photography, and historical photography and documentation, are governed by regulations as set forth in 36 CFR 79. According to these regulations however, provisions are made for the loan of culturally significant collections curated by Federal agencies for research, exhibition or education or instructional purposes. Such loans are subject to a standardized short-term loan agreement as set forth in *Appendix C* of 36 CFR 79. Included herein is a template of a standard short-term agreement that is in compliance with 36 CFR 79. Loan agreements between the Fort Bliss Curatorial Facility and borrowing institutions or qualified professionals will be for a duration not to exceed one (1) year. Loans may be renewed annually subject to provisions for the preservation of the artifact and the condition of the artifact at the end of the short-term loan agreement period.

Following is a standardized version of a short-term loan agreement, followed in turn by a long-term loan agreement:

SHORT-TERM LOAN AGREEMENT

IMBL-PWE, Conservation Branch

Date _____

This is a short-term loan agreement between Fort Bliss DOE-C and the following entity:
Please print name and address

The following items are hereby loaned to the undersigned for a period of time not to exceed one-year, at which time they are to be either returned or this loan is to be renewed for an additional year.

ITEMS (please list):

(use additional paper as needed)

Loan received by: (Print Name) _____ (Signature) _____

Loan released by: (Print Name) _____ (Signature) _____

LONG-TERM LOAN AGREEMENT
BETWEEN THE
Fort Bliss Curatorial Facility
AND THE <Name of Borrower>

The Fort Bliss Curatorial Facility, hereinafter called the Repository, agrees to loan to <Name of Borrower>, hereinafter called the Borrower, certain artifacts, specimens, and associated records, listed in Attachment A, which were collected from the <name of prehistoric or historic resource or site or collection>, which is assigned <list site number and/or accession number>. The collection was recovered in connection with the <name of Federal or Federally authorized project or name of Donor if Deed of Gift> project (or collection), located on the property of the Fort Bliss Military Installation in El Paso, El Paso County, in the state of Texas. The collection is the property of the United States Government either by rights of land ownership in which the artifacts, specimens, or associated records were recovered, or by Deed of Gift between a Donor and Fort Bliss Curatorial Facility as Recipient.

The artifacts, specimens and associated records are being loaned for the purpose of <cite purpose of loan>, beginning on <month, day, year> and ending on <month, day, year>, a period not exceeding five years in duration.

During the term of the loan, the Borrower agrees to handle, package, and ship or transport the Collection in a manner that protects it from breakage, loss, deterioration, and contamination, in conformance with the regulation 36 CFR Part 79 for the curation of Federally owned and administered archaeological collections and the terms and conditions stipulated in Attachment B to this loan agreement.

The Borrower agrees to assume full responsibility for insuring the Collection or for providing funds for the repair or replacement of objects that are damaged or lost during transit and while in the Borrower's possession. Within five (5) days of discovery, the Borrower will notify the Repository of instances and circumstances surrounding any loss of, deterioration and damage to, or destruction of the Collection and will, at the direction of the Repository, take steps to conserve damaged materials.

The Borrower agrees to acknowledge and credit the United States Government and the Repository in any exhibits or publications resulting from the loan. The credit line shall read as follows: "Courtesy of the United States Army Air Defense Artillery Center and the Fort Bliss Curatorial Facility." The Borrower agrees to provide the Repository and the United States Army with copies of any resulting publications.

Upon termination of this agreement, the Borrower agrees to properly package and ship or transport the Collection to the Repository.

Either party may terminate this agreement, effective not less than thirty (30) days after receipt by the other part of written notice, without further liability to either party.

Signed: <Signature of Repository Official>

Date: <Date>

Signed: <Signature of Borrower>

Date: <Date>

Attachment A: Inventory of Objects Being Loaned

Attachment B: Terms and Conditions of the Loan

NOTES

5.0 CULTURAL RESOURCES INVENTORY

To manage a resource successfully, it is necessary to identify that resource. Section 2.5 Historic Overview provides an understanding of what cultural resources might be present on the Fort. This section provides an overview of work that has been done, literature generated by the work, and the inventory of cultural resources identified from the work.

5.1 Literature Review

5.1.1 Summary of Investigations

The earliest written accounts of the region come from the Spanish Entradas, through the journals of explorers and missionaries, including the first official exploratory party lead by Fray Rodriguez-Captain Chamuscado in 1581. Along their route from Santa Barbara, Chihuahua, Mexico, they traveled the Rio Concho and then followed the southern and western edges of the Rio Grande, up to just south of Socorro, New Mexico. Although not entirely clear from the accounts, it appears that in the vicinity of El Paso, Texas, no native groups were observed during this mid-summer visit. The Antonio Espejo expedition of 1582 also originated in Santa Barbara, Chihuahua, Mexico and ended around Socorro, New Mexico. Arriving in the El Paso area during the winter, the Spanish found a group living in and around marshy pools in rancherías and straw houses, mainly dependent on fish.

In 1598, the Don Juan de Oñate expedition traveled cross-country from Santa Barbara, Chihuahua, Mexico. Rather than encountering native groups in the El Paso area, the *sargento mayor* of the group may have had to bring natives to the Spanish camp from a greater distance, suggesting that the group did not reside by the river. Franciscan Fray Alonso de Benavides, writing in the 1630s, described an Apache tribe living in tents and huts, moving from mountain range to mountain range, somewhat to the north of El Paso.

Some of the earliest modern written accounts of the region include W. A. Bryan, in 1929, in a paper entitled, "The recent bone-cavern find at Bishop's Cap, New Mexico", in *Science*, 70; R. P. Conklin, in 1932, wrote, "Conklin Cavern: the discoveries in the bone cave at Bishop's Cap", New Mexico, in the *West Texas Historical and Scientific Society Bulletin*, 44; E. B. Howard, in 1932, published, "Caves along the slopes of the Guadalupe Mountains", in the *Bulletin of the Texas Archeological and Paleontological Society*, 4; E. B. Sayles, in 1935, in "An archaeological survey of Texas", in *Medallion Papers*, No. 17; C. B. Cosgrove, in 1947, in "Caves of the Upper Gila and Hueco areas in New Mexico and Texas", *Papers of the Peabody Museum of Archaeology and Ethnology*, 24; and D. J. Lehmer, in 1948, in "The Jornada Branch of the Mogollon", *University of Arizona Social Science Bulletin No 17*. Most of this work was conducted in cave sites and provided invaluable data rarely preserved in the mostly open-air sites across the post. Lehmer's work continues to be used today as the seminal description of prehistoric lifeways in the region.

5.1.1.2 Archaeology

Under the Directorate of Public Works - Environmental Division and Housing in the 1970s, the Environmental Office hired its first archaeologist. Prior to this, local avocational archaeological groups conducted many salvage and research projects, including excavations and inventories. Soon thereafter large archaeological inventory projects were conducted in Maneuver Areas 1 through 8 and on McGregor Range to develop a baseline of the types of cultural resources on post. These early inventories resulted in the discovery of more than 10,000 archaeological sites ranging from Paleoindian to late prehistoric sites, in addition to numerous historic period properties. The McGregor Range work was in support of the land withdrawal Environmental Impact Statement (EIS) in 1977. This sample survey gathered baseline data that could be used in assembling the withdrawal EIS. Although some re-surveys are now required to meet later, stricter standards for transect width, most of Maneuver Areas 1–8 have been inventoried for archaeological resources. As of 2013, about 80 percent of McGregor Range Training Areas have been inventoried. On Otero Mesa, 30 to 40 percent has been surveyed. All of this information has been incorporated into a GIS database system that allows for efficient management of the resources. More than 20,000 archaeological sites of all periods have been recorded on post, including over 700 historic period sites. The sites occur in all of the varied topographic zones on post, including the desert basin floor, alluvial fans, Otero Mesa, Otero Mesa escarpment and in the Organ, Hueco, and Sacramento mountains. Many of the sites are regionally and nationally famous and include Pendejo Cave, Escondida Pueblo, Hot Well Pueblo, Ceremonial Cave, Twelve Room House Ruin, Wilde Well, Don Lee's Ranch, Mesa Horse Camp, and Picture Cave.

The continuing focus of the archaeological resources program is to identify aspects of the military mission that could adversely affect historic properties. Some of that information comes from activities proposed in major EISs, but is also gathered from ongoing, day-to-day interactions and project reviews, and results in yearly requests for project funding to address those plans. Depending on the type of proposed plans, those archaeological projects might be for a survey, site evaluations, or data recovery.

Fort Bliss manages resources under a Programmatic Agreement (PA) among the Texas and New Mexico State Historic Preservation Officers and the Advisory Council on Historic Preservation that will expire in 2025. The PA guides Fort Bliss in its management of cultural resources and meets its National Historic Preservation Act (NHPA), Section 106 responsibilities. Fort Bliss is also operating under a Research and Significance Standards that guides the determination of National Registry of Historic Places (NRHP) eligibility of archaeological sites across the installation.

5.1.1.3 Architecture

A series of historic monographs of Fort Bliss were produced in 1962 and 1993 (see 5.1.2.2 for listing of publications addressing Fort Bliss history and buildings). The 1962 work focused on the history of the units that served on Fort Bliss without addressing the Fort's development or buildings (McMaster 1967). Two studies (Harris, et al. 1993 and Jamieson 1993) performed in 1993, provide a review of Fort Bliss by developing specific historic contexts consisting of 1) the formative years of New Fort Bliss (1890-1898); 2) Fort Bliss and the Spanish-American War Period (1898-1902); 3) Fort Bliss and the early new Army period (1902-1910); 4) Fort Bliss and

the Mexican Revolution (1910-1920); 5) Fort Bliss and WWI (1917-1919); 6) creation of a permanent cavalry post (1916-1920); 7) Fort Bliss in the 1920s; 8) Fort Bliss in the 1930s, and 9) Fort Bliss in WWII and the early Cold War period. Although these do not address buildings, they do provide appropriate historic context in which to perform building inventories and address eligibility for inclusion in the National Register of Historic Places. A final historic overview addressing the role Fort Bliss played in the early development of the United States missile program was conducted in 1998 (Enscore 1998). This study, however, does not provide information of buildings as they may relate to the context.

The first project to inventory and evaluate buildings on the Cantonment occurred in 1996 and centered on the William Beaumont General Hospital area (Nowlan et al. 1996). The following year, two studies to inventory and evaluate buildings occurred. The first addressed historic buildings and structures on the ranges (Faunce 1997). Although conducted as a historic archaeological project, the study inventoried properties associated with ranching and homesteads, mineral extraction, and railroad contexts and evaluated their eligibility under Criteria A, B and D. The strength of this document is in the history it provides. Determinations of eligibility for Criteria A and B are weak and require further research. The second study conducted in 1997 inventoried the Main Post and evaluated properties based on the following contexts: 1) Initial Construction Period 1891-1899; 2) Interim Period 1900-1912; 3) First Expansion Period 1913-1917; 4) 7th Cavalry Construction Period 1917; 5) Second Expansion Period 1918-1926; 6) Depression Era 1927-1939; and 7) Post WWII Period 1946-1950 (Burt n.d., Burt et al. 1997 and Ellsworth et al. 2000). It is not understood why this study did not follow the earlier historic context and developed periods based on when construction activities occurred or why it ignored the World War II period. This study also established the policy of only addressing buildings at the time of their construction, ignoring the potential for a building to obtain significance under a later historically significant event. It developed a policy of addressing history as static, ending at the time of the buildings construction.

Beginning in 1999 and continuing into the present, a series of projects were centered on inventorying and evaluating Cold War era properties (Enscore, et al. 2005 and 2006; Keenoy et al. 2005; Nichols et al. 2005; and Nowlan 1999a, 1999b and 2005). A few of these inventoried and evaluated buildings dating between 1946 and 1989 were noted for exceptional importance under Criteria Consideration G – for properties less than fifty years old. The majority have conducted inventory and evaluation of buildings in blocks of five years under various Cold War contexts such as the Hawk Missile Program, the Safeguard Missile Program, etc. These have only addressed those building constructed during that time period and have not considered all extant buildings at the time of the period being considered.

The first project to address building conditions and treatment was performed in 1978 with the study on Building 128 (Battle 1978). The purpose of this study was to determine the building's historic value. Other studies focusing on conditions of buildings consisted of a structural report on Building 4 (John Callan Architect, Inc. 2003) in preparation of its rehabilitation; concrete structural assessments of buildings 11-13, 111-118 and 516 (Jester 2004); and a structures report on Building 503 (John Callan Architect, Inc. 2004a). Beginning in 2000, a series of manuals were developed to guide appropriate replacement or rehabilitation of architectural elements of the Fort's historic buildings (Freeman, 2002a, 2002b, 2004a, 2004b, 2004c, 2005, and 2006).

5.1.2 Published Investigations

Appendix D presents the listing of reports produced from studies conducted on Fort Bliss. It has been divided into the subcategories of Archaeology and Historic Buildings. These reports are on file in the Fort Bliss Directorate of Public Works - Environmental Division, Conservation Branch.

There have been numerous publications on the history of El Paso that provide information on the development of historic contexts under which buildings and landscapes found on Fort Bliss can be evaluated for eligibility to the NHRP. The architectural section however, focuses on those publications and studies directed specifically on Fort Bliss. The following are the studies produced primarily under contract to the Fort Bliss Conservation Branch to inventory, evaluate and provide guidance on maintaining the post's historic buildings.

Additional DOD context documents have been instrumental in evaluating properties at Fort Bliss and they include:

- World War II Temporary Military Buildings (1993)
- Thematic Study and Guidelines: Identification and Evaluation of United States Army Cold War Era Military-Industrial Properties (1998)

5.2 Archaeological Sites

As of November of 2015, over 20,600 archaeological sites had been recorded on Fort Bliss. Those sites span all time periods recognized in the Jornada Branch of the Mogollon cultural sequence, and extend into the protohistoric period, the historic period, and finally the Cold War Era. Most of that sequence is display in Table 2.3.

Of the total of 20,565 archaeological sites recorded, 4,570 have been recommended as eligible for the National Register (16.75 percent), 9,788 have been recommended as not eligible (49.1 percent), and the remaining 34.15 percent have not yet been evaluated for National Register eligibility. Fort Bliss has three (3) sites that are listed on the National Register: Hot Well Pueblo, the Sgt. Doyle Site (pueblo), and Fusselman Canyon (rock art).

Based on either absolute dating techniques (radiocarbon, thermoluminescence, etc.), relative dating (type seriation, diagnostic artifacts, etc.), or types of features or structures or even artifact assemblages, archaeological sites are assigned a temporal affiliation. The majority of sites recorded exhibit only a single temporal component; as most of those lack diagnostic artifacts or dateable features, they remain in the category of unknown prehistoric affiliation. The next highest percentage of single-component sites can only be dated to the Formative period (usually through the presence of El Paso brownware ceramics). The remaining sites show components in the following descending order: Archaic, Mesilla, El Paso, Dona Ana, Paleoindian, Historic, Cold War, and Protohistoric.

Only about five percent of all sites have a historic component: the most common historic-era feature recorded across the installation is a trash dump or trash scatter. Water features, such as tanks, dams, cisterns, ditches and pipelines are the second most likely to be recorded. The well-known Butterfield Trail and the Salt Trail are each in a unique category, as is a unique archaeological field camp from the 1920s.

By landform, over half of all sites are recorded in the bolson or basin between the surrounding north-south trending mountain ranges, with much smaller percentages found on alluvial fans, mesas, and mountains.

Fort Bliss holds and preserves a significant number of important sites within the Jornada Branch of the Mogollon culture area. Table 5.1 below provides details on a few of those properties. Figures 5.1 through 5.7 illustrate some of those sites.

TABLE 5.1. SIGNIFICANT ARCHAEOLOGICAL SITES ON FORT BLISS		
SITE NAME	TEMPORAL AFFILIATION	SITE DESCRIPTION
Hot Well Pueblo	Doña Ana/El Paso phases	Excavations beginning in 1929. At least 26 room blocks of puddled adobe (some painted plaster). Wide variety of southwestern ceramic and lithic types, roofing material, jewelry, minerals, palettes, tablitas, shell, corn, squash, beans, acorns, egg shells, animal bones, burials
Sgt. Doyle Pueblo	Mesilla/Doña Ana/El Paso (ceramics and archeomagnetic)	Excavations beginning in 1968. At least 24 rooms of puddle adobe. Wide variety of southwestern ceramic and lithic types, roofing materials, egg shells, burials
Madera Quemada Pueblo	Doña Ana/El Paso phases	Excavations beginning in 2005. 13-room pueblo. Wide variety of southwestern ceramic and lithic types, jewelry, palettes, minerals, animal bone, intact and burned roof beams.
Escondida Pueblo	Doña Ana/El Paso phases	Recorded 1930s and later excavations. Room block mounds (no longer visible on surface); perhaps 4 or 5, middens, hearths. El Paso Bichrome or Polychrome, Three Rivers, Chupadero, Galisteo, Lincoln, Ramos, Tucson, St. Johns, Pecos Glaze, Tularosa ceramics, variety of lithic types, animal bone, shell, corn cob, shell beads, jewelry, roofing materials, burials

Sacramento Pueblo	El Paso phase	Sampled five rooms. Only excavated settlement along Sacramento River. Roof beams harvested from high elevation areas. Abandoned or closed or terminated through dismantlements, burning, and dedication and termination objects. May blur the lines between El Paso phase and Glencoe phase.
Conejo Site	Mesilla phase	Five pithouses (two possible additional), two middens, 40 other features, roof support materials, El Paso Brown and Mimbres Black-on-white Style I and II, variety of lithic types, over 40 lbs. of rabbit bone
Meyer Pithouse Village	Mesilla/Dona Ana/El Paso phase	Pithouses (one 20 sq m), roof fall, other features, El Paso Brown/Bichrome/Polychrome, Mimbres, Chupadero, Three Rivers, Playas, Chihuahuan ceramics, variety of lithic types, animal bone, (almost 100,000 artifacts), burial
Turquoise Ridge	Mesilla phase	Pithouses, middens, hearths (over 40 features), variety of El Paso Polychrome, Chupadero, Mimbres, Lincoln ceramics (counts in the 1000s), variety of lithic types
Cerro Rojo	Protohistoric	Possible Habitation site. Tipi rings, wickiup rings, cairns, rock shelters, thermal features, midden, variety of lithic types, El Paso brownware, Chupadero and Mimbres, Valle Bajo, Cerro Plain, Llano Plain
Pendejo Rock Shelters	Pre-Clovis(?), Paleo Indian-Protohistoric	Rock shelter, hearth features, El Paso brownware, wide variety of lithic types, esp. projectile points, animal bone (extraordinary paleontological sequence), variety of macrobotanical remains
Pintada Rock Shelter	Archaic - Formative	Rock shelter, midden, pictographs, fire-cracked rock, bedrock metate, burned animal bone
Ceremonial Cave	Archaic-Formative	First excavation 1920s. Cave site. Midden, variety of lithic types, El Paso brownware/Polychrome, petroglyphs, animal bone, prayer sticks, >1000 sandals, darts, grass bedding, cordage, textiles, bone awls, corn cob, tablitas, pipes, reed cigarettes, throwing sticks, fur cloth, basketry, burials, jewelry
Picture Cave	Early Archaic – late Formative	Cave site. Midden. Animal bone, chipped stone, over 400 projectile points (35 types--Jay, Bajada, Augustin, Fresno, Chiricahua, San Jose, San Pedro, Washita, Harrel)

Figure 5.1: Entrance to Ceremonial Cave, Fort Bliss, Texas.

Figure 5.2: Pictograph of Stepped Cloud and Mask at Picture Cave, Fort Bliss, Texas.

Figure 5.3: Results of the ground penetrating radar (GPR) and magnetic susceptibility surveys at Escondida Pueblo (from 2006 Lukowski et al., *Ground-truthing Remote Sensing Data at the Escondida Site (LA 458), Otero County, New Mexico*).

Figure 5.4: Cerro Rojo Site (from 2002 Seymour, *Conquest and Concealment*), Fort Bliss, Texas.

Figure 5.3. Hot Well Pueblo, Area 1.

Figure 5.5: Hot Well Pueblo, Area 1 (from 2005 Lowry, Archaeological Investigations of the Hot Well and Sgt. Doyle Sites, Fort Bliss, Texas) Fort Bliss, Texas.

Figure 5.6: Aerial photo of Madera Quemada Pueblo, Doña Ana Range, Fort Bliss, New Mexico.

Figure 5.7: Aerial photo of Sacramento Pueblo, Otero County, Fort Bliss, New Mexico.

5.2.1 Archaeological Site Protection Measures

Fort Bliss implements several measures for the protection of cultural resources against adverse effects from training, construction, and other ground-disturbing activities. Maneuver area training requests are reviewed by staff who meet the Secretary of the Interior’s Standards and Guidelines for Archaeology and Historic Preservation. Using the location information provided in each online training request, staff re-route training activities out of Red Zones and outline authorized activities in Limited Use Areas; they seek to avoid damage to “eligible” and “undetermined” properties through a reroute or change in activity. They also provide NAGPRA cautions. When necessary, staff will personally consult with the requesting unit to help meet the mission and protect the resource; the DPW-E Environmental Liaison staff, trained in all aspects of environmental protection, provide most of the face-to-face interactions with units. Figures 5.8 through 5.10 show the current off-limits and limited use areas on Fort Bliss: Red Zones (off-limits in red) and Green Zones (limited use areas in green). These zones also appear on the standard Fort Bliss map set used by the military. Red Zones are surrounded by SIBER stakes (distinctly colored fiberglass cylinders atop t-posts) and are off limits to all training. These zones are intended for long term preservation of a sampling of significant sites. Roll-through only training is allowed in Green Zones (Limited Use Areas); no bivouac, static emplacements or digging is permitted. These restricted areas represent less than three percent of the total

installation acreage. With FY12-FY17 funding however, Fort Bliss is re-evaluating all Off Limits and Limited Use Areas. In the case of Red Zones, the intent is to either eliminate the status if the sites do not meet the original intent of preservation of a sampling of significant sites, reconfigure the area to better protect the significant site boundaries, or make no change. In the Green Zones, the intent is to either change that designation to a Red Zone (because part or all of that LUA has significant properties that warrant preservation), or eliminate the restriction altogether. Fort Bliss is always using new or updated data to assess areas for possible new off limits zones. These decisions will not be made until all Off Limits Areas and LUAs have been re-evaluated.

All work orders are also screened for potential to adversely affect cultural resources and are reviewed by archaeological and architectural staff. GIS data and/or site visits determine whether or not survey work is required, whether any eligible properties are within the footprint, and if eligible properties do exist, whether they can be avoided or some type of mitigation will be required. The work order review process is completed with either a “no historic properties,” or “no adverse effects” finding or, if adverse effects are anticipated, then mitigation or avoidance measures are proposed. The goal in all cases is to meet the particular mission while protecting the cultural resource.

As an ongoing measure, Fort Bliss program management staff submit projects for funding that anticipate near and long term military activities with the potential to adversely affect cultural resources, as well as meet Section 110 inventory requirements. Currently, DPW-E, Conservation, Archaeology, has task orders under a Corps of Engineer’s five-year, multiple award task order contract (MATOC) awarded to several contractors. Historic Architecture has been awarded two projects that were completed in September 2015 and they include a survey of an additional 148 buildings and an evaluation and standards for treatment for several buildings on the main cantonment. Currently, DPW-E Historic Architecture anticipates project funding requests to include the following over the next five years:

1. Develop guidelines for the historic district and associated view shed.
2. Additional Section 110 inventory and evaluation.
3. Survey 100 public monuments.
4. Compile histories concerning significant place names on Fort Bliss.
5. Identify and obtain historic photographs from local and state depositories.

Figure 5.8: Off Limits and Limited Use Areas Across the Northern Maneuver Areas, Fort Bliss.

Figure 5.9: Off Limits and Limited Use Areas Across the Southern Maneuver Areas, Fort Bliss.

Figure 5.10: Off Limits and Limited Use Areas on McGregor Range, Fort Bliss.

5.3 Historic Sites

Historic properties at Fort Bliss include individual properties, historic districts, and historic landscapes.

Properties: Inventory and evaluation of facilities on Fort Bliss has been completed for a majority of properties constructed before 1965. It should be noted that this list is not static and the Conservation Branch should be consulted when considering an activity on a building or group of buildings.

Districts: Six (6) historic districts have been identified as eligible for listing in the NRHP (one of which is listed).

- Fort Bliss Main Post Historic District

The Fort Bliss Main Post Historic District was listed in the NRHP in 1998 under various historic contexts. See tables in Appendix J for lists of buildings, structures and landscapes that contribute to this historic district as well as the context in which its eligibility is based. The boundaries of the district are indicated in Figure 5.11.

- Discontiguous Districts

There are seven historic districts that are separate and distinct of the Fort Bliss Main Post Historic District.

- 7000 Area Residential Community Historic District at William Beaumont Medical Center: This district consists of ten Craftsman bungalow style residences, two multi-car garages, a pair of tennis courts, residential streets, and landscape elements. The boundaries of the district are indicated in Figure 5.12.
- Early Cold War Guided Missile Instruction Historic Districts – Areas A-E: These districts consist of five discontinuous areas, A-E. Buildings in Area C were mitigated by demolition in 2010. The properties in this district at Fort Bliss are associated with the testing and training aspects of the early Army missile program. The Army's Cold War air and missile defense missions are significant because they convey a sense of the Army's monumental effort to prepare its forces to meet the threats of an era characterized by unprecedented and rapidly advancing weapons technology.

Boundaries of Areas A and B are contingent to the Fort Bliss Historic District; however, portions fall outside these areas. The properties do not gain their significance from the eligibility contexts of the Fort Bliss Historic District and therefore are identified as unique and distinct districts that fall within the boundaries of Fort Bliss Historic District.

Area A consists of buildings in the 700 area. See Figure 5.11

Area B consists of buildings in the 1000 area. See Figure 5.11

Area C no longer exists.

Area D consists of buildings in the 3600 area, north of the Fort Bliss Historic District. See Figure 5.12

Area E consists of buildings in the 3700 area, north of the Fort Bliss Historic District. See Figure 5.12

Additionally, many Cold War era properties pre-dating 1965 have been evaluated for eligibility for inclusion in the NRHP. Those determined eligible for listing are identified in Appendix J.

Historic View Sheds: In an effort to further protect and enhance historic areas surrounding historic eligible districts, view sheds have been established. These view sheds allow for control over the visual properties in the area that could have an adverse impact on historic buildings or districts. The view sheds and how their boundaries are defined are:

- Fort Bliss Historic District View Shed - The view shed for the Fort Bliss Historic District is approximately 500 feet from the district boundaries. See Figure 5.11.
- Cold War Era Properties - This view shed includes the area 150 feet outside the boundary fence that encloses Buildings 3655, 3671, 3672, 3673, and 3674. See Figure 5.12.
- Biggs Army Airfield - This view shed is 500 feet around Building 11108, an airplane hangar constructed in 1955 as part of the USAF Strategic Air Command. See Figure 5.12.
- Hawk Eye Missile Radar Park Historic District - This view shed includes the area 150 feet outside the boundary fence that encloses Buildings 3701 through 3707 and associated hardstands. See Figure 5.12.
- McGregor Range - The view shed at McGregor Range includes the area around building 9480, a 849 square-foot concrete control building with an antenna to support Nike Missile training. See Figure 5.12.

Landscapes: Fort Bliss has twelve (12) historic landscapes. Eleven (11) landscapes are located on the Main Post and one (1) is located at William Beaumont Medical Center. See Figure 5.13 and Appendix J.

Figure 5.11: Fort Bliss Main Post Historic District with Early Cold War Guided Missile Instruction Historic District Area A and Area B and Associated View Sheds

Figure 5.12: Discontinuous Districts and View Sheds

Figure 5.13: Historic Landscapes

NOTES

6.0 IMPLEMENTING THE ICRMP

6.1 The Garrison Commander's Role

AR 200-1, Section 1-24 places responsibility for compliance with historic preservation laws and regulations on the GC. As such, the GC will implement this ICRMP. Prior to implementing this ICRMP the GC must complete the following actions.

- Direct preparation of an Environmental Assessment (EA) to support implementation of the ICRMP and initiate a public review of the ICRMP in accordance with the NEPA and AR 200-1.
- Initiate an IMCOM review of the ICRMP in accordance with AR 200-1.
- Sign the ICRMP after IMCOM and public comments have been addressed.

Implementation of this ICRMP will require the GC to take the following actions:

- Designate a full time professional CRM who meets the *Secretary of the Interior's Professional Qualification Standards* for archaeology or historic preservation, and task the individual to implement and coordinate the ICRMP.
- Ensure that the CRM and his or her staff receive appropriate, on-going training in cultural resources laws, regulations, and practices.
- Establish a process that requires installation staff, tenants, contractors, users and interested parties to coordinate with the CRM early in the planning of projects and activities to ensure compliance with Section 106 of the NHPA and the PA.
- Establish funding priorities and program funds for cultural resources compliance and management activities.
- Provide an annual review of the ICRMP and initiate revision of the ICRMP if the annual review indicates a need for such revision.

6.1.1 Annual Review of the ICRMP

This ICRMP must undergo an annual review to determine its effectiveness, make necessary improvements, and incorporate changes in cultural resources management programs. This review is initiated by the GC and coordinated by the CRM. Participants in the annual review should include signatories to the PA. The product of this review should be a report on the cultural resources management program at Fort Bliss. The report should summarize preservation activities completed and in progress, progress in carrying out the ICRMP Action Plan, difficulties encountered in performing these activities, revisions proposed to the ICRMP, and any historic sites added to the inventory. This report may be made part of the annual report required by the PA.

6.2 Cultural Resources Manager's Role

As the GC's expert on cultural resources, it is expected that the CRM will play the primary role in implementing this ICRMP. The CRM's responsibilities fall into five (5) categories that are detailed below.

6.2.1 NHPA Title 54 U.S.C. 306101 through 306114 (Formerly Section 110)

- Coordinate a review of the Fort Bliss policies and procedures to ensure compliance with NHPA Title 54 U.S.C. 306101 through 306114.
- Ensure that maintenance, repair, renovation of historic properties, and new construction are carried out in accordance with *The Secretary of the Interior's Standards for the Treatment of Historic Properties* and *The Secretary of the Interior's Standards for Treatment of Historic Properties with Guidelines for Preserving, Rehabilitating, Restoring, and Reconstructing Historic Buildings and Fort Bliss Treatment Standards for Adobe, Roofing, Windows, Stucco and Plaster, Wood & Carpentry, Masonry, Waterproofing, Painting, Interiors, Lighting, and Structural Concrete*.
- Organize properties into representative classes and develop historic context themes for their evaluation for future determinations of eligibility to the National Register of Historic Places.
- Coordinate development and implementation of a cultural resources survey plan for Fort Bliss.
- Pursue funding to meet Title 54 U.S.C. 306101 through 306114 requirements.

6.2.2 NHPA Section 106

- Coordinate with installation staff, tenants, users, contractors and interested parties early in the planning of projects and activities to ensure compliance with the PA (Appendix A) to address management of historic properties under Section 106.
- Coordinate NHPA Section 106 review as directed by the PA.
- Coordinate integration of cultural resources review into the NEPA review process in accordance with the PA.
- Pursue funding to meet Section 106 requirements.
- Annually review the PA and ICRMP for compliance with Section 106.

6.2.3 Consultation with Native Americans

- Coordinate consultation with Federally-recognized Native American tribal entities on a government-to-government basis as required by EO 13084 and the DOD's American Indian and Alaska Native Policy.
- Coordinate development of an MOA for consultation with Federally-recognized tribal entities on NAGPRA issues (in progress).
- Coordinate identification of properties that have traditional or religious significance to Federally-recognized Indian Tribes.
- Submit funding requirements of MOA.

6.2.4 Cultural Resources Education Program

- Coordinate with the GC and his or her deputies to provide yearly briefings on cultural resources laws and the progress of the cultural resources program on Fort Bliss.
- Develop and implement cultural resources training programs for unit commanders of military and civilian organizations on Fort Bliss.
- Submit funding requirements for a cultural resources education program.

6.2.5 Management Responsibilities

- Provide an opportunity for CRM staff to participate in historic preservation courses as funding is available.
- Pursuant to the former Section 110 of the NHPA, ensure that individuals performing preservation activities on Fort Bliss meet the Secretary of the Interior's Professional Qualifications Standards.
- Coordinate an annual review of this ICRMP with the PA review.
- Ensure that contractors carrying out maintenance activities on historic properties follow *The Secretary of the Interior's Standards for the Treatment of Historic Properties*.
- Integrate this ICRMP into all tenant agreements to ensure compliance with appropriate preservation laws.
- Pursuant to the Archaeological Resource Protection Act, ensure that individuals performing crime scene investigations and archaeological damage assessments meet the Secretary of the Interior's Professional Qualifications Standards.

6.3 ICRMP Action Plan

6.3.1 ICRMP Goals

During the life of this ICRMP, the following goals will direct the cultural resources program at Fort Bliss:

- Integrate historic preservation compliance requirements with planning and military training, construction, maintenance, real property management, land use decisions, and other undertakings.
- Establish procedures for compliance with Federal laws, regulations, and executive orders requiring the protection and/or management of cultural resources with the least possible effect on military training and mission support activities.
- Maintain the historic fabric and character of buildings and landscapes contributing to the Fort Bliss historic districts, as well as individually eligible properties.
- Minimize and/or mitigate adverse effects on all cultural resources on Fort Bliss meeting criteria for listing or listed on the National Register in concert with the execution of military training and support activities.

- Conduct data recoveries on National Register eligible properties under the attached PA, eliminating the necessity for individual MOAs on each project.
- Continue development of project manuals and handbooks for guiding treatment of historic buildings, structures and landscapes.
- Set priorities based on currently available information for the inventory and evaluation of cultural resources and establish a procedure for revising those priorities: (1) survey and NRHP evaluation of archaeological sites for eligibility to the National Register in all areas where military training will have the greatest impact; (2) evaluation of any site with “undetermined” eligibility; and (3) ongoing data recovery of sites in areas expected to receive the greatest impact. This plan can incorporate the use of remote sensing, geographic information systems data, and predictive modeling.
- Give top priority to management of properties most at risk for adverse effects by the military mission.
- Use a system of internal controls for review of routine and mission-critical undertakings.
- Enforce Federal laws prohibiting the vandalism of cultural resources or illegal collection of archaeological materials on Fort Bliss and strengthen that effort with continued training and additional staff (as funding is available).
- Implement the existing plan to ensure management of archaeological collections relevant to cultural resources at Fort Bliss in compliance with 36 CFR Part 79.
- Make collections available for research by professionals, interested Native Americans, and other members of the public at the Fort Bliss curatorial facility during normal duty hours.
- Establish and implement a management plan for currently endangered paper collections relating to historic structures, archaeology, cultural landscapes, and objects on Fort Bliss.
- Work with both New Mexico and Texas SHPOs to explore and define Fort Bliss’s interested parties. Once identified, define how interested parties will be brought into implementation of this ICRMP.
- Implement and enhance the public awareness program, including maintaining a mailing list and sending out brochures to interested parties detailing the findings of recently completed projects addressing cultural resources.
- Maintain historic preservation training opportunities for military and civilian personnel whose jobs or building occupancies have an influence on cultural resources.
- Establish realistic budgetary goals.
- Ensure staff responsible for cultural resource management meet the Secretary of the Interior’s *Standards and Guidelines for Archeology and Historic Preservation*, (*Federal Register* Vol. 48, No. 190, pp. 44717–44742) and receive continuing training.
- Through the implementation of this ICRMP, develop an innovative program that demonstrates the value of historic preservation programs, and publicize the commitment of Fort Bliss to historic preservation.

6.3.2 Action Plan Schedule

The purpose of this section is to present a schedule for carrying out the cultural resources program for Fort Bliss. These projects were arrived at through analysis of what impacts to historic properties may occur and which properties have the highest probability of adverse effects. The projects are focused on historic properties in areas where military training has the highest likelihood of adversely affecting the archaeological resources, for the effective preservation management of the historic resources that have been identified, and for unevaluated buildings and structures that are scheduled for demolition or renovation.

Fort Bliss will include projects in this schedule in annual environmental requests and will modify each submission to reflect the funding actually received, including an inflation factor, and projected mission changes that could affect cultural properties in ways not anticipated at the time this plan was prepared.

The fiscal year begins on October 1 of the calendar year and ends September 30 of the calendar year indicated. Fort Bliss will have met its obligations under this plan if funds are obligated in amounts estimated to be required for the completion of projects and plans included in the Projected Schedule anytime during the fiscal year in which they are scheduled.

The Projected Schedule will be the basis for determining funding priority requests submitted by Fort Bliss to IMCOM. If Fort Bliss fails to receive funding for any project included in the projected schedule, they will report the failure in the next annual report along with a modified schedule for the continued implementation of the ICRMP. If either SHPO or the Council objects to the modified schedule, Fort Bliss will enter into consultation with all parties to resolve the objection.

- **ACTION ITEM 16:** Fort Bliss will inventory and survey lands and real property under its management for historic properties and evaluate identified properties for NRHP eligibility.

TASK 1.1 - Survey and Evaluate Sites to Support Home Stationing Training and Proposed Mission Construction in Training Area 2C: This project will conduct archaeological survey and site evaluation in Training Area 2C, Southern Maneuver Area.

TASK 1.2 - Survey and Evaluate Sites to Support Home Stationing Training and Proposed Mission Construction Outside the Infantry Brigade Combat Team (IBCT): This project will conduct archaeological survey and site evaluation outside the IBCT in the Southern Training Area.

TASK 1.3 - Survey and Evaluate in the Southern Maneuver Areas in Support of Increased Use by Home-Stationed Units: This project will conduct archaeological survey and site evaluation of 7,923 acres in Training Area 1A.

TASK 1.4 - Survey and Evaluate in Red Zones in the Northern Maneuver Areas, for Possible Reconfiguration or Elimination: This project will survey and evaluate sites in 2,441.2 acres in Red Zones in the Northern Maneuver Areas.

TASK 1.5 - Survey and Evaluate in Red Zones, Dona Ana Range, for Possible Reconfiguration or Elimination: This project will survey and evaluate sites in 2,349.2 acres in Red Zones on Dona Ana Range.

TASK 1.6 - Survey and Evaluate in Red Zones, Dona Ana Range, for Possible Reconfiguration or Elimination: This project will survey and evaluate sites in 2,001.6 acres in Red Zone 7 on Dona Ana Range.

TASK 1.7 - Survey and Evaluate in Red Zones, Southern Maneuver Areas, for Possible Reconfiguration or Elimination: This project will survey and evaluate sites in 3,021 acres in Off Limits Areas in the Southern Maneuver Areas and evaluate their possible elimination as a Red Zone or reconfiguration.

TASK 1.8 - Evaluate Eligibility of Properties in the Northern Maneuver Areas in Support of New Artillery Firing Boxes: This project will survey and evaluate sites in artillery firing boxes in the Northern Maneuver Areas.

TASK 1.9 - Survey and Evaluate on McGregor Range in Support of Heavy Maneuver Training and Static Positions: This project will survey and evaluate sites in 6,522.6 acres on McGregor Range.

TASK 1.10 - Survey and Evaluate on Otero Mesa (Survey of Unsurveyed Lands in TA 17, 20, and 21): This project will survey and evaluate sites on Otero Mesa.

TASK 1.11 - Survey Buildings Turning 50 Years of Age (to include Buildings Overlooked on Previous Surveys): There are approximately 141 buildings constructed between 1921 and 1972 that need evaluation to determine if they are eligible for listing on the NRHP. The bulk of these buildings were constructed from 1953 through 1972. Included in this evaluation process should be a thematic review of all historic buildings for their roles in various historic time periods.

TASK 1.12 - Survey on Dona Ana Range, TA4B and 5C: This project will survey and evaluate sites in 4,495 acres in Training Area 4B and 5C, Dona Ana Range.

TASK 1.13 - Survey for a Proposed Route for Route Green: This project will survey and evaluate sites in 850 acres along a proposed Route Green extension on McGregor Range.

TASK 1.14 - Survey for a Proposed Route to the Digital Air/Ground Integration Radar (DAGIR): This project will survey and evaluate sites in 1,660 acres along a proposed route to the DAGIR.

TASK 1.15 - Survey in Training Area 2D: This project will survey and evaluate sites in 2,800 acres in TA2D.

TASK 1.16 - Survey and Evaluate 2,440 Acres around Red Zone 19 in the Northern Maneuver Areas: This project will survey and evaluate sites around Red Zone 19.

TASK 1.17 - Survey 5,490 Acres and Evaluate in Military Training Lands With a Focus on the Southern Maneuver Areas in Support of Increased Use by Home-Stationed Units: This project will survey and evaluate sites in the southern maneuver areas.

TASK 1.18 - Survey and Evaluate 3,025 Acres around Red Zones 25 and 28 in the Southern Maneuver Areas: This project will survey and evaluate sites around Red Zones 25 and 28.

TASK 1.19 - Survey 8,230 Acres and Evaluate in the Northern Maneuver Areas in Support of Increased Use by Home-Stationed Units: This project will survey and evaluate sites in the Northern Maneuver Areas.

TASK 1.20 - Evaluate in 935 Acres in Maneuver Areas 30 and 32 in Support of Heavy Maneuver Training on McGregor Range: This project will survey and evaluate sites in Maneuver Areas 30 and 32.

TASK 1.21 - View Shed Guidelines: Develop guidelines to regulate and standardize evaluations of demolitions, new constructions, additions that would have a major impact on a building, group of buildings, or area in the historic district or view shed.

TASK 1.22 - Survey Historic Monuments, Statuary, Memorials, Marker and Other Public Appurtenances: Survey and evaluate components for eligibility.

TASK 1.23 - Place Naming Survey and Publication of Fort Bliss: This project will provide a comprehensive guide that illuminates the history and culture of Fort Bliss embedded in the names of areas, airfields, roads, buildings, and other geographical features.

TASK 1.24 - Design and Produce Poster Standard for Historic Buildings: This project will provide design for a standard poster template that will be used for presenting relevant information on historic buildings.

TASK 1.25 - Collect Digital Historic Photographs: This project will identify and acquire or duplicate historic photographs of Fort Bliss buildings from a variety of sources.

TASK 1.26 - Survey Around Route Red/training Villages: This project will survey and evaluate sites around Route Red/training villages, Dona Ana Range.

TASK 1.27 - Data Recovery in Support of the Battle Area Complex (BAX): This project will conduct data recovery of sites at risk in the BAX area.

TASK 1.28 - Update Fort Bliss Significance Standards: This project will update the Fort Bliss research and significance standards for prehistoric sites.

TASK 1.29 - Survey and Evaluate 1,297 Acres in Support of Dismounted Operations During Table X and Table XII Validation on McGregor: This project will survey 1,297 acres along Hay Meadow.

TASK 1.30 - Survey for a Proposed BAX: This project will survey and evaluate sites on McGregor Range for a proposed BAX.

TASK 1.31 - Survey for Proposed Artillery Firing Boxes on McGregor Range: This project will survey and evaluate sites on McGregor Range for proposed firing boxes.

TASK 1.32 - Survey on Dona Ana Range for New Firing Boxes: This project will conduct survey on Dona Ana Range for proposed new firing boxes.

TASK 1.33 - Survey on McGregor in Support of Home-Stationing: The project will conduct survey on McGregor Range.

TASK 1.34 - Von Ripper Mural Mitigation/Conservation: This project will repair and stabilize an existing eligible wall mural.

TASK 1.35 - High Altitude Mountain Environmental Training (HAMET) Survey in Southern Sacramento Mountains: This project will conduct a survey in the southern Sacramento Mountains for possible use during HAMET.

TASK 1.36 - Monitoring Rock Art Across Installation: This project will conduct periodic monitoring of rock art sites across the installation.

TASK 1.37 - Evaluate Rock Art: This project will conduct an evaluation of rock art sites in a possible land acquisition.

TASK 1.38 - Survey and Context of Drone Facilities: Early drone activities have been identified at Fort Bliss in the 1960s. Survey will identify and evaluate for eligibility these resources and provide a context.

TASK 1.39 - Spartan Missile Survey: Assess, clean, paint, and preserve Spartan Missile. Install at Fort Bliss Missile Park.

TASK 1.40 - Concrete Study: Concrete Investigations/Rehabilitations of Historic Concrete Porch Deterioration for Buildings 11, 13, 111, 112, and 114-117.

TASK 1.41 - Surveys and Evaluations: In Support of the Fort Bliss Facility Reduction Program

TABLE 6.1 ACTION ITEM 16, PROJECTED COSTS FOR INVENTORY/SURVEY/EVALUATE, 2016-2020 (IN \$1000)					
Project	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Task 1.1 Survey in Training Area 2C	371.0	0	0	0	0
Task 1.2 Survey outside IBCT	226.0	0	0	0	0
Task 1.3 Survey Southern	361.4	310.6	189.7	200.0	200.0
Task 1.4 Survey Northern Red Zones	202.0	202.0 *	202.0 *	0	0
Task 1.5 Survey in Dona Ana Red Zone	324.0	0	0	0	0
Task 1.6 Survey Red Zone 7, Northern	248.0	248.0 *	248.0 *	0	0
Task 1.7 Survey Red Zones, Southern	286.0	286.0 *	286.0 *	0	0
Task 1.8 Evaluate Firing Boxes	203.0	0	164.1	0	0
Task 1.9 Survey McGregor	323.0	203.8	142.9	200.0	200.0
Task 1.10 Survey Otero Mesa	252.0	194.2	270.3	250.0	250.0
Task 1.11 Survey Buildings	170	170	170	170	170
Task 1.12 Survey on Dona Ana, 4B and 5C	0	281.3	0	0	0
Task 1.13 Survey for Route Green	0	55.1	0	0	0
Task 1.14 Survey to DAGIR	0	128.5	0	0	0
Task 1.15 Survey in TA2D	0	227.9	0	0	0
Task 1.16 Survey around Red Zone 19	0	201.5	0	0	0
Task 1.17 Survey in Southern MA	0	310.5	0	0	0

TABLE 6.1 ACTION ITEM 16, PROJECTED COSTS FOR INVENTORY/SURVEY/EVALUATE, 2016-2020 (IN \$1000) (CONTINUED)					
Task 1.18 Survey around RZ 25, 28	0	286.1	0	0	0
Task 1.19 Survey Northern	0	419.7	0	0	0
Task 1.20 Evaluate on McGregor	0	203.7	0	0	0
Task 1.21 View Shed Guidelines	0	80	0	0	0
Task 1.22 Survey Monuments	0	200	0	200	0
Task 1.23 Place Naming Survey	0	80	0	0	0
Task 1.24 Design Poster Standard	0	60	0	0	0
Task 1.25 Collect Digital Photos	0	90	50	50	50
Task 1.26 Survey around Route Red/training villages	0	0	270.8	0	0
Task 1.27 Data Recovery at the BAX	0	0	185.3	0	0
Task 1.28 Update Significance Standards	0	0	200.4	0	0
Task 1.29 Survey Haymeadow	0	0	60	0	0
Task 1.30 Survey for the BAX	0	0	125.9	0	0
Task 1.31 Survey for McGregor Firing Boxes	0	0	103.2	0	0
Task 1.32 Survey Firing Boxes, DA	0	0	164.1	0	0
Task 1.33 Survey McGregor	0	0	103.2	0	0

TABLE 6.1 ACTION ITEM 16, PROJECTED COSTS FOR INVENTORY/SURVEY/EVALUATE, 2016-2020 (IN \$1000) (CONCLUDED)					
Task 1.34 Repair and Stabilize Mural	0	0	100.0	100.0	0
Task 1.35 HAMET Survey	0	0	0	215	0
Task 1.36 Monitor Rock Art	0	0	0	213.6	0
Task 1.37 Evaluate Rock Art	0	0	0	174.9	0
Task 1.38 Survey of Drone Facilities	0	0	0	100	0
Task 1.39 Spartan Missile Survey, Preservation and Installation	0	0	50	100	25
Task 1.40 Concrete Repair Survey	63	0	0	0	0
Task 1.41 Facility Reduction Support	0	0	50	50	50
Yearly Total	3029.4	3750.9	2933.9	2023.5	945
NOTE: Does not address staffing requirements *Will re-submit if not funded					

- ACTION ITEM 17: Fort Bliss will monitor maintenance, repair, new construction, and renovation of historic properties in accordance with “The Secretary of the Interior’s Standards for the Treatment of Historic Properties with Guidelines for the Treatment of Historic Properties.”

TASK 2.1 - Section 106 Compliance Monitor: This project provides for a qualified monitor to inspect CRM approved renovation, restoration, or rehabilitation work on Fort Bliss historic properties to ensure work meets standards set by the historic architects and the *Secretary of the Interior’s Standards for the Treatment of Historic Properties*. Due to the number of historic buildings and taking into consideration that there are over 2,400 work orders and service orders received a year for these buildings, outside staff is

required to adequately protect Fort Bliss historic properties. Monitoring also covers the correction of inappropriate repairs to avoid permanent adverse effects.

TASK 2.2 - Historic Properties Rehabilitation: Fort Bliss will procure architectural and engineering services to revise and update the materials maintenance, repair, and installation specific treatment plans that will be used programmatically throughout the post. The project will develop user-friendly manuals for the repair and maintenance of historic buildings on Fort Bliss.

TASK 2.4 - Eligibility Surveys: Fort Bliss will systematically complete eligibility surveys and assessments of buildings older than 50 years old and those buildings that were overlooked on previous studies. Eligibility surveys for monuments, landscapes, and surveys will be systematically completed.

TABLE 6.2 ACTION ITEM 17, PROJECTED PROJECT COSTS FOR MAINTENANCE, REPAIR, NEW CONSTRUCTION, AND RENOVATION OF HISTORIC PROPERTIES, 2016-2020 (IN \$1000)					
Project	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Task 2.1 Section 106 Monitor	60.0	61.8	63.6	65.5	67.5
Task 2.2 Historic Properties Rehabilitation	65.0	65.0	70.0	70.0	70.0
Task 2.3 Eligibility Survey	0.0	75.0	26.4	90.0	102.5
Yearly Total	125.0	201.8	160.0	225.5	240.0

- **ACTION ITEM 18:** Fort Bliss will implement this ICRMP to provide guidance in meeting its legal obligations.

TASK 3.1 - Monitor both the ICRMP and PA for amendments and begin revision of ICRMP and PA in the 4th year of each document.

TASK 3.2 - As part of implementing this ICRMP, staff will provide educational materials for the Fort Bliss community and general public on historic properties found on the fort.

TABLE 6.3 ACTION ITEM 18, PROJECTED PROJECT COSTS FOR MONITORING/EDITING ICRMP/PA, 2016-2020 (IN \$1000)					
Project	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Monitor ICRMP	2.0	2.1	2.2	2.3	2.4
Monitor PA or Annual Reports	4.0	2.1	2.2	2.3	2.4
Revise or Update ICRMP	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0	45.0
Revise PA	0.0	5.0	5.0	5.0	45.0
Education	1.0	1.1	1.1	1.2	1.2
Yearly Total	9.0	12.3	12.5	12.8	96.0
Does not address staffing requirements					

- **ACTION ITEM 19:** Fort Bliss will record cultural resources, mitigate adverse effects on historic properties that cannot be avoided as provided for in the PA, and monitor the condition of important sites.

TASK 4.1 - State Site Number Fees: The states of New Mexico and Texas charge a fee for obtaining state site numbers and filing state site forms. This project will pay those fees.

TASK 4.2 - Mitigate Sites in Firing Boxes in Support of New Mission: This project will mitigate sites at risk for adverse effects from field artillery training in Firing Boxes.

TASK 4.3 - Mitigate Sites at Risk for Adverse Effects from Increased Home-Stationing Training around Orogrande Range Complex: This project will mitigate sites at risk for adverse effects from increased training around the Orogrande Range Complex.

TASK 4.4 - Mitigate Sites at Risk for Adverse Effects from Proposed Projects (Training and/or Military Construction): This project will mitigate sites at risk for adverse effects from proposed future projects that by their design and purpose cannot avoid adverse effects to historic properties.

TASK 4.5 - Monitor Condition of Historic Properties: This project will conduct monitoring of the condition of historic properties across the installation relative to the ongoing military mission. This work involves the periodic inspection of facilities for conditions. This is beyond the task for 106 Compliance.

TASK 4.6 - Monitor Condition of Sites of Traditional Cultural and Religious Importance: This project will conduct monitoring of the condition of TCRIs across the installation relative to the ongoing military mission.

TASK 4.7 - Mitigate Any Proposed Adverse Effects to Historic Structures With Required Documentation as Specified by Consultation Process and the PA: Currently, no proposed building projects have been identified. However, a set of abandoned railroad tracks are likely to be removed in an effort to make adjacent historic warehouses more useable.

TABLE 6.4 ACTION ITEM 19, PROJECTED PROJECT COSTS FOR MITIGATION OF HISTORIC PROPERTIES, 2016-2020 (IN \$1000)					
Project	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Task 4.1 Pay Site Fees	25.0	25.0	25.0	30.0	30.0
Task 4.2 Mitigate Firing Boxes	429.0	0	0	0	0
Task 4.3 Mitigate around Orogrande Complex	200.0	200.0	200.0	200.0	200.0
Task 4.4 Mitigate Sites at Risk	0	0	156.9	150.0	150.0
Task 4.5 Monitor Historic Properties	0	110.0	113.0	116.0	119.0
Task 4.6 Monitor TCRIs	42.0	43.0	44.0	45.0	46.0
Task 4.7 Mitigate Adverse Effects to Historic Buildings	0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
Yearly Total	696.0	478	638.9	641	645
Does not address staffing requirements					

- ACTION ITEM 20: The GC shall designate a CRM until rescinded, or their tenure at Fort Bliss ends. During the duration of this ICRMP, the CRM will ensure appropriate staff meet the Secretary of the Interior’s Professional Qualifications Standards as archaeologists and historic architects or architectural historians.

TASK 5.1 - Designation of CRM: Upon enactment of this ICRMP, the GC shall provide in writing his or her designated CRM. The CRM designee shall continue until the appointment is rescinded, or the individual’s tenure at Fort Bliss ends. No cost associated with action item.

TASK 5.2 - Staff Training: The CRM will ensure that appropriate staff has access to training in their fields to ensure continued growth and knowledge in the fields responsible.

TABLE 6.5 ACTION ITEM 20, PROJECTED TRAINING COSTS FOR CULTURAL RESOURCES STAFF, 2016-2020 (IN \$1000)					
Training	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Archaeological Staff (3)	18.0	19	19.5	20	21.2
Curation Staff (1)	3.0	3.2	3.3	3.5	3.7
Historical Architects (1)	6.0	6.3	6.6	6.9	7.3
Yearly Total	26.0	28.5	29.4	30.4	32.2

- **ACTION ITEM 21:** Initiate a review of the policies and procedures of Fort Bliss to ensure consistency with requirements of Section 110 of the NHPA.

TASK 6.1 - Review Policies and Procedures: Throughout the course of this ICRMP, the CRM and staff will review policies and procedures that may be developed by Fort Bliss for consistency with requirements of the ICRMP, the PA and CFR 651 (AR 200-2) Part 651.33 Actions normally requiring an EA. (h). No cost associated with this action.

- **ACTION ITEM 22:** Presently there are no National Historic Landmarks designated on Fort Bliss. Fort Bliss will monitor the NPS for any notification that it proposes to designate such on the post.

TASK 7.1 - Monitor for National Historic Landmark (NHL) Designation: The CRM and staff will monitor legislation that may be proposed for directing NPS to conduct historic studies for the intent of identifying those sites that may qualify as an NHL, specifically in the Cold War Historic Context era that may lead to designation of a NHL on Fort Bliss. No cost associated with this action.

- **ACTION ITEM 23:** Fort Bliss will include costs in proposed projects

TASK 8.1 - Project Cost: The CRM will work with directorates to include costs in project cost estimates and funding to address appropriate historic issues costs such as mitigation costs. No cost associated with this action.

- **ACTION ITEM 24:** Fort Bliss staff will monitor for changes to preservation acts and implementing regulations.

TASK 9.1 - Monitor for Changes: The CRM and staff will monitor the Advisory Council on Historic Preservation and the Army Environmental Command's websites for proposed changes to laws and regulations that may affect how historic properties are managed. No cost associated with this action.

- **ACTION ITEM 25:** As new Program Comments (PCs) are developed, provide appropriate SHPO with listing of properties that are covered by new PCs.

TASK 10.1 - Alternative Procedures: Notify the SHPOs whenever any alternative procedures, other than PCs, such as Standard Treatments, are implemented along with a list of properties under Fort Bliss management that are affected by the alternative. No cost associated with this action.

- **ACTION ITEM 26:** Ensure active MOAs are completed prior to expirations or request extensions.

TASK 11.1 - MOA Monitoring: Staff will ensure MOAs under their management are met and closed out. No new MOAs are required under the PA. No cost associated with this action beyond costs associated with meeting individual MOA stipulations.

- **ACTION ITEM 27:** Review past MOAs when considering projects that have findings of Historic Properties Adversely Affected to insure mitigation duplications is not occurring.

TASK 12.1 - Review Past MOAs: Staff will review past MOAs when addressing mitigating adverse effects to historic properties to insure non-duplication of mitigation measures. No cost associated with this action.

- **ACTION ITEM 28:** Review Fort Bliss compliance with the provisions of the NAGPRA and any revisions made to that law.

TASK 13.1 - Final regulations published in the Federal Register March 2007 (effective April 20) outlines procedures for the future applicability of the law to museums and Federal Agencies. To date, Fort Bliss has completed Section 5 Inventory and Section 6 Summary reports. Any new collections or holdings since completion of these summaries need to be reported by October 20, 2007. A proposed rule was published April 18, 2012. Fort Bliss will continue to monitor the progress of that proposed rule and implement any changes required. No cost associated with this action.

- **ACTION ITEM 29:** Develop an MOA with the interested tribes to streamline consultation required by NAGPRA and other issues of interest and conduct government-to-government consultation.

TASK 14.1 - Consultation to Comply with NAGPRA and Other Issues of Interest to the Tribes: A draft MOA has been reviewed by the interested tribes and as of August 2012 is being reviewed by IMCOM. That MOA will be incorporated into this ICRMP upon completion. No costs are associated with this action.

TASK 14.2 - Tribal Meetings: This project will fund travel expenses of interested tribes to attend meetings at Fort Bliss for government-to-government consultation.

TASK 14.3 - NAGPRA and Other Tribal Notices: This project will fund publications fees for NAGPRA and other tribal notices.

TABLE 6.6 ACTION ITEM 29, PROJECTED PROJECT COSTS FOR TRIBAL CONSULTATION, 2016-2020 (IN \$1000)					
Project	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018
Task 14.2 Tribal Meetings	25.0	25.0	25.0	25.0	25.0
Task 14.3 NAGPRA notices	4.0	4.0	4.0	4.0	4.0
Yearly Total	29.0	29.0	29.0	29.0	29.0
Does not address staffing requirements					

- **ACTION ITEM 30:** CRM must coordinate with the Staff Judge Advocate to ensure that ARPA is integrated into the missions of applicable military and nonmilitary organizations on Fort Bliss.

TASK 15.1 - CRM will pursue funding to have ARPA training performed at Fort Bliss, at a minimum of every three years.

TASK 15.2 - The GC will assign the CRM the responsibility for issuing ARPA permits on lands controlled by Fort Bliss. No cost associated with this action.

- **ACTION ITEM 31:** Review Fort Bliss permitting process and coordinate with the Army COE and BLM.

TASK 16.1 - BLM and Forest Service Permitting: The CRM will coordinate with the BLM to update the MOA addressing ARPA permitting responsibilities on withdrawn lands. No cost associated with this action.

- **ACTION ITEM 32:** Fort Bliss staff will provide long-term management and preservation of preexisting and new collections, as set forth in 36 CFR 79.

TASK 17.1 - Establish Written Policies and Procedures for Curation of Archaeological Material and Associated Documentation 36 CFR 79.9 (a): Fort Bliss has a Curation SOP, updated in 06/08/2015 and disseminated to all parties preparing collections for curation at Fort Bliss, as well as used by in-house staff. Fort Bliss will conduct periodic reviews and revisions of these policies to stay current with museum practices. No cost associated with action item.

TASK 17.2 - Manage and Preserve New and Pre-Existing Collections on a Long Term Basis 36 CFR 79.5: Fort Bliss has an on-going program to insure the longevity of artifacts and associated records. Staff time includes management and preservation of new collections and purchase of curatorial supplies, and project work includes rehabilitation of backlog.

TASK 17.2a - Rehabilitate 35,250 Artifacts From Backlog: This project will complete the re-housing of approximately 35,250 artifacts backlogged from previous projects.

TASK 17.2b - Rehabilitate 6,500 Artifacts From Backlog: This project will complete the re-housing of approximately 6,500 artifacts backlogged from previous projects.

TASK 17.2c - Rehabilitate 43,800 Artifacts From backlog: This project will complete the re-housing of approximately 43,800 artifacts backlogged from previous projects.

TASK 17.2d - Rehabilitate 45,000 Artifacts From Backlog: This project will complete the re-housing of approximately 45,000 artifacts backlogged from previous projects.

TASK 17.2e - Rehabilitate 25,000 Artifacts From Backlog: This project will complete the re-housing of approximately 25,000 artifacts backlogged from previous projects.

TASK 17.2f - Rehabilitate 50,000 Artifacts From Backlog: This project will complete the re-housing of approximately 50,000 artifacts backlogged from previous projects.

TASK 17.2g - Rehabilitate Project Data Maps: This project will re-house and inventory maps associated with previous projects.

TASK 17.2h - Rehouse Artifacts for Permanent Storage: This project will rehabilitate all accessioned artifacts by moving to permanent shelving and producing an index for proper archive. First year will be spent creating main index and moving all completed accessioned projects to permanent designated storage, while subsequent years will include new completed rehabilitated artifact projects or incoming collections.

TASK 17.2i - Rehabilitate Associated Records From Project 96-28: This project will rehabilitate all associated records from Project 96-28, McGregor Survey.

TASK 17.2j - Rehabilitate Associated Records From Project 97-08: This project will rehabilitate all associated records from Project 97-08, McGregor Survey.

TASK 17.2k - Rehabilitate Special Collections: This project will rehabilitate rare, unique, monetarily valuable, museum quality and/or diagnostic artifacts in the Fort Bliss collection.

TASK 17.2l - Rehabilitate Associated Records From Project 95-02: This project will rehabilitate all associated records from Project 95-02, Texas Green Zone Survey.

TASK 17.2m - Rehabilitate Site Files: This project will rehabilitate incomplete records associated with our site file records

TASK 17.2n - Rehabilitate Project Files: This project will rehabilitate incomplete records associated with our project records.

TASK 17.3 - Curation Supplies: This project will purchase archival supplies associated with the long term care of archaeological collections and associated documents.

TASK 17.4 - Employ Conservation Methods 36 CFR 79.11: Conduct conditions assessments on incoming collections and conserve as condition warrants with appropriate treatment records, on "as needed basis". This may require consultation with a conservator.

TASK 17.5 - Maintain Complete and Accurate Records 36 CFR 79.9(b)(1): Maintain complete and accurate records by conducting data quality control and completeness analysis. No cost associated with action item.

TASK 17.6 - Inspection and Inventories 36 CFR 79.7 and 79.8: Conduct yearly inspections on collections in permanent storage area to monitor physical security, environmental control and to assess condition of collections, providing document of findings. Inspection and quality control is also implemented during artifact accessioning in the form of box inventory. Permanent storage is yet to be implemented in the form of SAF project.

TASK 17.7 - Maintain Physical Plant to Properly Store, Study, and Conserve the Collections 36 CFR 79.9: Recommend purchasing, construction, renovation, expanding to the repository to meet the basic standards for storage. Restrict and monitor security by keeping collections under physical secure conditions and limiting accession to area. Provide additional security for valuable objects such as locking the items in a safe, vault or museum specimen cabinet. Maintain climate control and fire suppression. Use an Integrated Pest Management (IPM) program to monitor collections for signs of infestation.

TASK 17.8 - Make Collection Available for Scientific, Educational, and Religious Use
36 CFR 79.10(a): The collections stored at the Fort Bliss Curatorial Facility will be available for analysis and research to qualified professionals and institutions. Oversee loan and access to collections. Validate professional qualifications of people who are requesting use of collections or of students that are under the directions of a qualified professional. Recommend that Fort Bliss Curatorial Facility be credited for the use of the collections and that copies of any resulting publications are submitted to the facility. No cost associated with action item.

TASK 17.9 - Maintain Automated Catalogue System: Develop associated database files for the management of archaeological collections and associated records (e.g., artifact catalogues, inventories, accession records, finding aids, tracking loans, condition reporting, analysis and site reports). Costs included in Curation Projects.

TASK 17.10 - Update Archaeological Site Database: To comply with the NHPA, including Section 106, the Fort Bliss Site File Database becomes the source for all accumulated site information on the more than 20,000 sites so far recorded on Fort Bliss. This database is a crucial source of information in the PA effort and a key tool for obtaining historical information, doing data analysis, and formulating survey, testing, and mitigation strategies; in-house staff, outside contractors, and outside researchers use the database. Cost for GIS contractor or staff.

TASK 17.11 - Compliance support: Provide accurate and timely advice and guidance on an “as needed bases” to collection managers and researchers. No cost associated with action item.

TASK 17.12 - Architectural Collections Curation: Prepare short term and long-term curatorial projects associated with the archiving and curation of historic architectural materials. Copy paper documents prior to archiving, completion of an on-site inventory of all historical and potentially historic paper documents located on Fort Bliss, treat damaged documents, provide ongoing Historic Resources (Architectural) program support, develop curatorial policy in collection and curation of architectural elements, identify architectural elements for curatorial purposes and inventory and archive architectural building material.

TASK 17.12 - Update Architectural Electronic Files: Scanning work and organization of files is completed by contract staff. Substantial work has been completed, with many extant historic resource information such as original building drawings, historic aerials, historic photographs, and other documents presented and cataloged in a logical and accessible method. The Historical Resources staff scans demolished buildings construction documents, historic photographs and useful historic documents relating to the Fort Bliss built environment.

TASK 17.13 - Architectural Database and GIS Layer: Previous projects have been centered on the development of an inclusive electronic architectural spreadsheet. This project would see the developed spreadsheet populated in a database and used by staff

and contractors. The database would be connected to a GIS layer and installed as part of the CRM overall GIS management system.

TABLE 6.7 ACTION ITEM 32, PROJECTED PROJECT COSTS FOR CURATION, 2016-2020 (IN \$1000)					
Project	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Task 17.2a Rehab 35,250 artifacts	105.9	0	0	0	0
Task 17.2b Rehab 6,500 artifacts	62.8	0	0	0	0
Task 17.2c Rehab 43,800 artifacts	128.4	0	0	0	0
Task 17.2d Rehab 45,000 artifacts	137.8	0	0	0	0
Task 17.2e Rehab 25,000 artifacts	0	82.7	94.8	99	104
Task 17.2f Rehab 50,000 artifacts	0	154.5	150	150	150
Task 17.2g Rehab Project Data Maps	0	54.1	54.1	0	0
Task 17.2h Rehouse Artifacts to Permanent Storage	0	135.9	135.9	100.0	100.0
Task 17.2i Rehab 96-28 records	0	0	188.2	0	0
Task 17.2j Rehab 97-08 records	0	0	145.7	0	0
Task 17.2k Rehab Special Collections	0	0	107.6	0	0

TABLE 6.7 ACTION ITEM 32, PROJECTED PROJECT COSTS FOR CURATION, 2016-2020 (IN \$1000) (CONCLUDED)					
Task 17.2l Rehab 95-02 records	0	0	49.8	0	0
Task 17.2m Rehab Site File records	0	0	153	160.7	168.7
Task 17.2n Rehab Project files	0	0	153	160.7	168.7
Task 17.3 Curation Supplies	15.0	15.0	19.0	20.0	21.0
Task 17.6 Maintain Physical Plant	0	0	0	0	0
Task 17.11 Architectural Curation	112.8	116.1	119.6	123.2	126.9
Task 17.12 Architectural File Management	50.0	50.0	50.0	50	50
Task 17.13 Architectural/ GIS database	0	0	100	100	25
Yearly Total	612.70	608.30	1520.70	963.60	914.30

NOTES

7.0 REFERENCES CITED

- Amick Daniel S.
1991 Folsom Land Use Patterns in the Southern Tularosa Basin. *Current Research in the Pleistocene* 8: 3-5
1994 *Folsom Diet Breadth and Land Use in the American Southwest*, Doctoral Dissertation. Department of Anthropology, University of New Mexico, Albuquerque.
- Battle, David. Historic Structures Report: Building 128—Water Pumping Station. Santa Fe, NM: Southwest Cultural Resources Center, National Park Service. 1978
- Baugh, Timothy and Mark Sechrist. *Protohistoric Apachean Adaptations within the Basin and Range Province of South-central New Mexico and West Texas: A Perspective from the Fort Bliss Reservation*. El Paso, Texas: TRC Mariah Associates Inc. 2001
- Burt, Geoffrey. Historic Landscape Inventory and Assessment for the Main Cantonment of Fort Bliss, Texas. Champaign, IL: Construction Engineering Research Laboratory n.d.
- Burt, Geoffrey, Susan Enscoe, Sheila Ellsworth, and Patrick Nowlan. Inventory and Evaluation of Historic Structures and Landscapes at Fort Bliss, Texas. Champaign, IL: Construction Engineering Research Laboratory 1997
- Chrisman, D., R.S. MacNeish, J. Mavalwala, and H. Savage. Late Pleistocene Human Friction Skin Prints from Pendejo Cave, New Mexico. *American Antiquity* 61(2):357–376. 1996
- Cultural and Natural Resources Branch. Standard Specifications for Historic Building Repair. 1995
- Ellsworth, Sheila, Susan Enscoe, Patrick Nowlan and Amy Woods. *National Register of Historic Places Registration Form: Fort Bliss Main Post Historic District, Fort Bliss, El Paso, Texas*. Champaign, IL: Construction Engineering Research Laboratory. 2000
- Enscoe, Susan. *Operation Paperclip at Fort Bliss:1945-1950*. Champaign, IL: Construction Engineering Research Laboratory. 1998
- Enscoe, Susan, Adam Smith, Sunny Stone, and Patrick Nowlan. Inventory and Evaluation of Cold War Era BASOPS Building on the New Mexico Ranges at Fort Bliss, 1956-1961. Champaign, IL: Construction Engineering Research Laboratory. 2005
- Faunce, Kenneth.
1997 *The Fort Bliss Preacquisition Project: A History of the Southern Tularosa Basin*. Fort Bliss, Texas: Directorate of Environment.
2005 Railroads and ranches: A Fort Bliss Testing Project. Miratek Corporation, Fort Bliss Cultural Resource Report No. 95-04
- Freeman, Joe.
2002a Historic Roofing Manual. El Paso, Texas: TRC Mariah Associates, Inc.
2002b The Historic Windows Manual. El Paso, Texas: TRC Mariah Associates, Inc.
2004a The Masonry Manual. El Paso, Texas: TRC Mariah Associates, Inc.

- 2004b The Waterproofing Manual. El Paso, Texas: TRC Mariah Associates, Inc.
- 2004c The Adobe Manual. El Paso, Texas: TRC Mariah Associates, Inc.
- 2005 The Wood & Carpentry Manual. El Paso, Texas: TRC Mariah Associates, Inc.
- 2006 The Stucco & Plaster Manual. El Paso, Texas: TRC Mariah Associates, Inc.
- Gerald, Rex E. "A History of the Tigua Indians of Ysleta del Sur, Texas." In, *Ysleta del Sur Pueblo Archives, Volume 1*. El Paso: Sundance Press, Inc. 2000 pp.19-41
- Harris, Arthur H. *The Vertebrate Fauna from Pendejo Cave, Otero County, New Mexico*. Directorate of Environment, Cultural Resources Branch, United States Army Air Defense Artillery Center, Fort Bliss, TX. 1995
- Harris, Charles and Louis Sadler. *Bastion on the Border: Fort Bliss 1854-1943*. 1993.
- Jamieson, Perry. *A Survey History of Fort Bliss 1890-1940*. Fort Bliss, Texas: Directorate of Environment 1993
- Jester, Gary. Concrete Preservation and Treatment Report: Structural Condition Assessment Report. El Paso, Texas: TRC Mariah Associates, Inc. 2004
- John Callan Architect, Inc.
- 2003 Building 4, Hospital Isolation Ward: Historic Structures Report. El Paso, Texas: TRC Mariah Associates, Inc.
- 2004a Building 503 Two Company Barracks Historic Structures Report. El Paso, Texas: TRC Mariah Associates, Inc.
- 2004b Fort Bliss National Historic District Exterior Paint Analysis. El Paso, Texas: TRC Mariah Associates, Inc.
- Keenoy, Ruth and Jeffery Holland. Early Cold War Era Base Operation Properties, Fort Bliss, Texas and New Mexico Constructed 1951-1955. 2005
- Keenoy, Ruth, Elia Perez, and Jennifer Thomas. *Live or Die: 27 Homesteads/Ranch Sites Identified in the Tularosa Basin and Hueco Bolson within the Fort Bliss Military Installation*. El Paso, Texas: TRC Mariah Associates, Inc. 2006
- Knight, B. and M. Miller. "Archaeological Survey and National Register of Historic Places Evaluation of Sites Identified in the Proposed Timberon Fire Break, McGregor Range, Fort Bliss Military Reservation, Otero County, New Mexico." Directorate of Environment Historic and Natural Resources Report No. 02-15. United States Army Air Defense Artillery Center and Fort Bliss, Texas. 2003.
- Komulainen-Dillenburg, Nancy and Elia Perez. *The NRHP Evaluation, Under Criterion D, of Eight Historic Properties: Development and Implementation of a New Historic Context, Fort Bliss Military Installation, Otero county, New Mexico*, Fort Bliss Cultural Resource Report No. 1221. 2013
- Krieger, Alex D.
- 1962 The Earliest Cultures in the Western United States. *American Antiquity* 28:138-143.
- 1964 Early Man in the New World. In *Prehistoric Man in the New World*, edited by J.D. Jennings and E. Norbeck, pp. 23-84. The University of Chicago Press.

MacNeish, Richard S. (editor)

1993a *The 1992 Excavations of Pendejo and Pintada Caves near Orogrande, New Mexico: AFAR and Fort Bliss Archaeological Project. The 1992 Annual Report and 1993 Briefing Booklet.* Andover Foundation for Archaeological Research, Andover, Massachusetts.

MacNeish, R. S., G. Cunnar, G. Jessop, and P. Wilner

1993b *A Summary of the Paleo-Indian Discoveries in Pendejo Cave near Orogrande, New Mexico.* Andover Foundation for Archaeological Research, Andover, Massachusetts.

McCarthy, Sheila, and Susan Enscore.

2001a A "Home Town" for Fort Bliss: The Van Horne Park Wherry Housing Project. Champaign, IL: Construction Engineering Research Laboratory.

2001b Dwellings for Officers and Airmen: The Aero Vista Wherry Housing Project at Biggs Army Airfield/Fort Bliss, Texas. Champaign, IL: Construction Engineering Research Laboratory.

McMaster, Richard. *Musket, Saber, and Missile: A History of Fort Bliss.* 1962

Metz, Leon.

1988 *Desert Army: Fort Bliss on the Texas Border.* El Paso: Mangan Books

1993 *El Paso Chronicles: A Record of Historical Events in El Paso, Texas.* El Paso: Mangan Books

Morrow, Herbert. *Women's Army Corps Buildings: William Beaumont Army Medical Center, Fort Bliss, El Paso County, Texas.* 1995

Nichols, Ruth and Jeffrey Holland. *Cold War Building Technologies and Landscape Assessment, Fort Bliss, Texas and New Mexico.* 2005

Nowlan, Patrick.

1999a Identification and Evaluation of Cold War Properties at Fort Bliss, Texas. Champaign, IL: Construction Engineering Research Laboratory.

1999b *National Register of Historic Places Multiple Property Documentation Form: Historic Cold War Properties at Fort Bliss, Texas.* Champaign, IL: Construction Engineering Research Laboratory.

Nowlan, Patrick, Sheila McCarthy, Andy Bohnert, and Roy McCullogh. *Inventory and Evaluation of the Historic William Beaumont General Hospital Area at Fort Bliss, Texas.* Champaign, IL: Construction Engineering Research Laboratory. 1996

Timmons, W.H. *El Paso: A Borderlands History.* El Paso: Texas Western Press. 1990

United States Army Corps of Engineers. *Fort Bliss Mission and Master Plan Programmatic Environmental Impact Statement, Volume I.* Texas: Fort Worth District 1998

NOTES

APPENDIX A: PROGRAMMATIC AGREEMENT

Programmatic Agreement among the Fort Bliss Garrison Command and the New Mexico State Historic Preservation Officer and the Texas Historic Preservation Officer and the Advisory Council on Historic Preservation for the Management of Historic Properties on Fort Bliss, Fort Bliss, Texas, under Sections 106 and 110 of the National Historic Preservation Act of 1966 (as amended)

**PROGRAMMATIC AGREEMENT
AMONG
THE UNITED STATES ARMY GARRISON, FORT BLISS AND
THE NEW MEXICO STATE HISTORIC PRESERVATION OFFICER AND
THE TEXAS STATE HISTORIC PRESERVATION OFFICER AND
THE ADVISORY COUNCIL ON HISTORIC PRESERVATION
FOR THE MANAGEMENT, OPERATION, AND DEVELOPMENT OF HISTORIC
PROPERTIES ON FORT BLISS
UNDER SECTION 106 OF THE NATIONAL HISTORIC PRESERVATION ACT OF
1966 (AS AMENDED)
FORT BLISS, TEXAS AND NEW MEXICO
2015-2025**

WHEREAS, Fort Bliss Garrison Command (Fort Bliss) proposes to continue to coordinate and administer ongoing programs of operation, maintenance and development as part of its mission to provide support to Soldiers and their Families, while operating, maintaining, and utilizing installation lands, facilities, training areas, and ranges in support of Army Readiness on Fort Bliss (Projects); and

WHEREAS, Fort Bliss, a federally owned and operated facility, plans to carry out Projects pursuant to Army Regulation, thereby making the Projects undertakings subject to review under Section 106 of the National Historic Preservation Act (NHPA), 16 U.S.C. Section 470f and its implementing regulations, 36 CFR Part 800; and

WHEREAS, Fort Bliss has determined that the development of a Programmatic Agreement (PA), in accordance with 36 CFR § 800.14(b)(2), is warranted because specific details on some Projects are unknown and the effects on historic properties cannot be fully determined prior to their approval, and for the routine nature of many actions that are part of the ongoing management and operation of Fort Bliss; and

WHEREAS, the Garrison Commander (GC), under Army Regulation (AR) 200-1, *Environmental Protection and Enhancement*, is responsible for compliance with legally applicable and appropriate Federal, state, and local environmental regulations; and

WHEREAS, Fort Bliss has defined, for this PA, the area of potential effect (APE) as the Fort Bliss Installation (as shown in Appendix E), so as to include the potential for impacts to visual, auditory and sociocultural factors, as well as natural resources; and

WHEREAS, Fort Bliss has determined that undertakings may have an adverse effect on historic properties (to include as yet unidentified properties), all of which are eligible (or upon evaluation could become eligible) for listing in the National Register of Historic Places (NRHP) and has consulted with the New Mexico State Historic Preservation Officer (NMSHPO) and the Texas State Historic Preservation Officer (TXSHPO) pursuant to 36 CFR Part 800; and

WHEREAS, Fort Bliss executed the *Programmatic Agreement Among the Fort Bliss Garrison Command and the New Mexico State Historic Preservation Officer and the Texas State Historic*

Preservation Officer and the Advisory Council on Historic Preservation for the Management of Historic Properties on Fort Bliss, Fort Bliss, Texas, Under Sections 106 and 110 of the National Historic Preservation Act of 1966 (As Amended) in 2006 (2006 PA), amended in 2007, 2008, and 2011, for the Army Campaign Plan implementing Army Transformation resulting in the change in military mission from an Air Defense Artillery training mission to the stationing and training of an Armored Division (plus additional units) and specifically the changing land use to open up an additional 700,000 acres of potential off road maneuver area; and

WHEREAS, from 2006 to 2013, Fort Bliss conducted archaeological survey of over 300,000 acres in response to the 2006 PA, evaluated 8,472 archaeological sites, completed data recovery mitigation on 443 archaeological sites and standard treatment measures on 60 buildings to mitigate potential adverse effects resulting from military construction and training, and established Off Limits Areas (aka Red Zones); and

WHEREAS, Fort Bliss, using the National Park Service (NPS) Native American Graves Protection and Repatriation Act (NAGPRA) online database, the Department of Housing and Urban Development Tribal Directory Tool, as well as past consultation experience and known interest, has identified and consulted with the following federally-recognized Indian tribes: the Comanche Nation, the Fort Sill Apache, the Kiowa Tribe of Oklahoma, the Mescalero Apache, the White Mountain Apache, and the Ysleta Del Sur Pueblo (Tigua), for which some sites at Fort Bliss have religious and cultural significance and has invited the Tribes to participate in the development of this PA; and

WHEREAS, Fort Bliss, consulting with the above-referenced tribes, has identified 32 unnamed properties as having religious and cultural significance; and

WHEREAS, Fort Bliss has invited the El Paso Historic Landmark Commission, El Paso Preservation Alliance, Preservation Texas, City of Socorro, Texas, and the El Paso County Historic Society, Inc. to comment and participate on this PA via email; and

WHEREAS, Fort Bliss has invited the public to comment through notice in local newspapers and has made the draft PA available on the Fort Bliss Directorate of Public Works (DPW), Environmental Division's (DPW-E) webpage (<https://www.bliss.army.mil/dpw/Environmental/EISDocuments2.html>) and has considered all recommendations, if any, into this PA; and

WHEREAS, in accordance with 36 CFR § 800.6(a)(1), Fort Bliss has notified the Advisory Council on Historic Preservation (ACHP) of its adverse effect determination providing the specified documentation, and the ACHP has chosen to participate in the consultation pursuant to 36 CFR § 800.6(a)(1)(iii); and

WHEREAS, the management of certain historic properties and day-to-day operations are covered by the *Programmatic Memorandum of Agreement Among the United States Department of Defense, the Advisory Council on Historic Preservation, and the National Conference of State Historic Preservation Officers Regarding the Demolition of World War II Temporary Buildings (as amended)*; the *Program Comment for Capehart and Wherry Era Army Family Housing and*

Associated Structures and Landscape Features (1949-1962); the Program Comment for Cold War Era Unaccompanied Personnel Housing (1946-1947); the Program Comment for World War II and Cold War Era (1939-1974) Ammunition Storage Facilities; and Programmatic Agreement regarding the Fort Bliss Residential Communities Initiative (RCI) and therefore are not part of this PA; and

WHEREAS, Fort Bliss has developed, in consultation with the NMSHPO, TXSHPO, and the Tribes the *Significance and Research Standards for Prehistoric Archaeological Sites at Fort Bliss: A design for the Evaluation, Management, and Treatment of Cultural Resources* (Miller et al. 2009) (Significance Standards) in order to provide an innovative program for assessing NRHP eligibility for prehistoric sites, and the NMSHPO and the TXSHPO concurred on the Significance Standards in 2009 for Fort Bliss to implement the Significance Standards and update by December 30, 2016; and

WHEREAS, in 2008 Fort Bliss completed the *Reevaluation of Selecting Ranching Sites on Fort Bliss* (Victor, et. al., 2008) that includes two historical contexts: *Agricultural Development in South Central NM 1870-1955* and *Irrigation and the Engineering of Water Resources in South Central NM 1870-1955* and is currently developing a historic context for historic railroads on Fort Bliss, and these contexts help provide Fort Bliss with tools to define site eligibility criteria, levels of adequate inventory, and site documentation requirements to guide the evaluation of historic sites, buildings, structures, objects and districts that may be eligible for listing in the NRHP; and

NOW, THEREFORE, Fort Bliss, the NMSHPO, the TXSHPO, and the ACHP agree that the management of historic properties shall be implemented in accordance with the following stipulations in order to take into account the effect of undertakings on historic properties.

STIPULATIONS

Fort Bliss shall ensure that the following measures are carried out:

PROJECT REVIEW

Policy: Fort Bliss shall avoid adverse effects to historic properties under its management, to the extent possible, while meeting mission needs, and coordinating Section 106 responsibilities with the National Environmental Policy Act (NEPA).

Procedure

Qualifications

- All work required to meet the Stipulations of this PA will be carried out under the supervision of a person who meets the minimum standards as identified in the Secretary of the Interior's "Archaeology and Historic Preservation: Secretary of the Interior's Standards and Guidelines (as amended and annotated)" (Professional Qualifications) as appropriate for the historic property being addressed.

- Fort Bliss staff
 - Cultural Resources Manager (CRM): the CRM is the person responsible, on behalf of the GC, for meeting the Stipulations of this PA. The CRM will meet the *Secretary of Interior's Professional Qualifications* for archaeology or historic preservation. Fort Bliss will notify the signatories of the name of staff fulfilling CRM responsibilities.
 - CRM Staff: the CRM Staff shall include qualified staff implementing the Integrated Cultural Resources Management Plan (ICRMP) for Garrison Command, supervised by the CRM.

Determine the Undertaking

- The CRM or CRM Staff shall determine if the proposed project is an undertaking as defined in 36 CFR § 800.16(y) and subject to this PA.
- If the CRM or CRM Staff determines the proposed project is not an undertaking as defined in 36 CFR § 800.16(y), or subject to this PA, Fort Bliss has no further obligations under this Stipulation.
- If the CRM or CRM Staff determine that the proposed project is an exempted undertaking as listed in Appendix B, the CRM shall document this determination for inclusion in the official Fort Bliss, and Fort Bliss has no further obligations under this Stipulation.
- If the CRM or CRM Staff determines the proposed project is not listed in Appendix B and is an undertaking, the CRM or CRM Staff shall document this determination for inclusion in the Record of Historic Properties Consideration (RHPC), see Appendix D for an example, for the undertaking and continue the Project Review process.

Define the Area of Potential Effects and Identify Historic Properties

- The CRM or CRM Staff shall determine and document the project APE for each specific undertaking, appropriate to the scope and scale of the undertaking, and considering direct, indirect, and cumulative effects in the RHPC.
 - The CRM or CRM Staff shall determine whether previous identification and evaluation work has been conducted in the APE, if historic properties have been identified, the standard under which the inventory and evaluations were conducted, the types of historic properties are likely to be found, and whether an existing historic context applies.

- Any survey, in which standards in Appendix C apply or Fort Bliss consulted on with the appropriate SHPO, is adequate enough not to require Fort Bliss to undertake a new cultural resource survey.
- The CRM or CRM Staff shall determine if new cultural resource surveys (to include determinations of eligibility) are needed and shall use one of the following two processes to complete new surveys.
 - The CRM or CRM Staff shall use a process as outlined in Appendix C, to make a reasonable and good faith effort to identify and evaluate historic properties in the APE.
 - The CRM shall consult with the appropriate SHPO, Tribal Historic Preservation Officer (THPO), Tribe, and/or other Consulting Party (as appropriate) to determine the process as needed to complete a reasonable and good faith effort to identify and evaluate historic properties in the APE.
- If the CRM or CRM Staff does not identify historic properties within the APE, and there is no need for a new cultural resource survey, the CRM and/or CRM Staff shall document this determination for inclusion in the official Fort Bliss database, and Fort Bliss has no further obligations under this Stipulation.
- If there are properties requiring evaluation present in the APE, the CRM and/or CRM Staff will evaluate the property for eligibility to the NRHP and will forward documentation supporting the evaluations to the appropriate SHPO for review and concurrence.
 - The SHPO shall be afforded 30 days, upon receipt of all pertinent information, to respond to the determinations of eligibility.
 - If the CRM and the SHPO agree that the cultural resources in the APE are or are not eligible for inclusion on the NRHP, the CRM or CRM Staff may proceed to Stipulation I(B)(4)(b).
 - If the CRM and the SHPO do not agree on determinations of eligibility, the CRM can attempt to resolve the disagreement through further consultation, with SHPO responding no longer than 15 days upon receipt of all pertinent information (or as appropriate in consultation with the appropriate SHPO) or the CRM can consult the Keeper of the National Register pursuant to 36 CFR Part 63 if needed.

Evaluate Effects of the Undertaking

- The CRM or CRM Staff shall work with the appropriate project proponent to discuss best management practices to avoid or minimize effects to historic properties.
 - The CRM may consult with the appropriate SHPO and/or Tribe to discuss best management practices to avoid or minimize effects to historic properties.
 - The best management practice(s) identified by the CRM or CRM Staff and discussed with the appropriate project proponent shall be documented in the RHPC.
 - If any contributing resource within the boundary of an eligible or listed historic district is proposed for demolition, the CRM or CRM Staff shall consider the demolition in accordance with 36 CFR §§ 800.5 through 800.7 and not in accordance with this PA.

- The CRM or CRM Staff shall assess the effects of the proposed undertaking on historic properties, including direct, indirect, and cumulative effects, using the criteria of adverse effects (36 CFR § 800.5(a)(1)) and shall make one of the following determinations:
 - “No Effect to Historic Properties”: if the CRM or CRM Staff determines that there are no historic properties or that historic properties present in the APE will not be affected by the undertaking, the CRM or CRM Staff shall document this determination in the RHPC, and Fort Bliss has no further obligations under this Stipulation.
 - “No Adverse Effect to Historic Properties”: if the CRM or CRM Staff determines that historic properties present in the APE will not be adversely affected by the undertaking, the CRM or CRM Staff shall document this determination in the RHPC, and Fort Bliss has no further obligations under this Stipulation.
 - “Adverse Effect to Historic Properties”: if the CRM or CRM Staff determines that historic properties present in the APE will be adversely affected by the undertaking, the CRM or CRM Staff shall document this determination in the RHPC and proceed in the Project Review process.

Resolution of Adverse Effect to Historic Properties

- For those undertakings with a finding of “Adverse Effect to Historic Properties” the CRM shall provide the appropriate SHPO and Tribe(s) with the RHPC including, but not limited to, the following:
 - Project description, to include but is not limited to depth and amount of ground disturbance anticipated and a summary of best management practices and/or alternatives to avoid or minimize effects to historic properties considered but ultimately rejected;
 - APE map showing the location of the project and of any identified historic properties;
 - description of the historic properties affected;
 - any photos as necessary;
 - standard mitigation measure to be used (see Appendix G) and/or;
 - an alternative mitigation measure as appropriate.
- The Tribes are under no obligation to provide comments on the effect determination or mitigation measure selected; however, if they wish Fort Bliss to consider their comments regarding the effect determination, Tribes should submit comments in writing within 30 days of receipt. If no comments are received within that time, the CRM or CRM Staff shall make a second attempt to ensure that the original notification was received, if comments will be submitted, and if they wish to participate in the resolution of adverse effects before concluding consultation. Fort Bliss shall take any tribal comments received into consideration before concluding the consultation and will notify the SHPO of any tribal concerns, respecting the Tribal request for confidentiality, and the Fort Bliss response to those concerns.
- SHPO shall provide any comments to the Fort Bliss effect determination and mitigation measure within 30 days of receipt of all pertinent documentation.
- The CRM or CRM Staff shall notify appropriate Consulting Parties, and the public, within 10 days of notifying the appropriate SHPO and Tribes of an adverse effect finding and mitigation measure for an undertaking using the following process:
 - The CRM or CRM Staff shall prepare and send the RHPC to the appropriate Consulting Parties including a description of the undertaking, an illustration of the APE, a list of identified historic properties within the APE, the explanation for the finding of adverse

effects, steps taken or considered by Fort Bliss to avoid or minimize the adverse effects, and any appropriate SHPO comments received by Fort Bliss regarding the undertaking.

- When the Adverse Effect is part of an action being analyzed through an Environmental Assessment (EA) or Environmental Impact Statement (EIS) in accordance with NEPA, then Fort Bliss will solicit public participation following Stipulation IV.
- Appropriate Consulting Parties are under no obligation to provide comments on the effect determination or proposed mitigation measure; however, if they wish Fort Bliss to consider their comments, Consulting Parties should submit comments in writing within 30 days of receipt. If no comments are received within that time, the CRM or CRM Staff shall make a second attempt to ensure that the original notification was received, if comments will be submitted, and if they wish to participate in the resolution of adverse effects before concluding consultation. If comments are received, Fort Bliss shall take those comments into consideration before concluding the consultation and shall notify the appropriate SHPO of any concerns and the Fort Bliss response to those concerns.
- The CRM or CRM Staff shall organize a consultation meeting if appropriate, to include the appropriate SHPO, 45 days after notifying appropriate Consulting Parties, to discuss standard or alternative mitigation measures if necessary. Additional meetings shall be scheduled as needed.
- If through consultation with the appropriate SHPO and Consulting Parties the adverse effects are minimized or mitigated, then the measures agreed to by Fort Bliss, the appropriate SHPO, and Consulting Parties shall be documented in the RHPC or a Memorandum of Agreement as appropriate.
- The ACHP will only participate in the resolution of adverse effects for individual undertakings if a written request is received from Fort Bliss, a SHPO, or a Tribe.

UPDATES TO THE SIGNIFICANCE STANDARDS

Policy: Fort Bliss relies on the Significance Standards to guide the evaluation of historic properties, particularly prehistoric/protohistoric archaeological sites.

Procedure

- Fort Bliss shall update the 2009 Significance Standards within two years after execution of this PA in consultation with SHPOs and Tribes.
- Fort Bliss shall update the Significance Standards every five years in conjunction with major ICRMP updates, with new archaeological and ethnographic data as appropriate.

REPORTING DAMAGE TO CULTURAL RESOURCES

Policy: Fort Bliss recognizes that routine Army activities (i.e., training, operation, and maintenance) pose some risk of damage to historic properties. Through the project review process, project monitoring, and cultural resources awareness training of Garrison staff, military units, and contractors by the CRM or CRM Staff, Fort Bliss attempts to minimize that risk.

Procedure

- When the CRM or CRM Staff are made aware of damage to a historic property (or an unevaluated cultural resource that may be eligible for inclusion in the NRHP), either from unintentional or intentional causes (and may or may not be associated with an ongoing project or training exercise), the CRM or CRM Staff shall review the site records, visit the property, and assess the damage to the property. Activity in and around the site (or portion of site) will cease until the procedures applicable to the level of damage in this Stipulation are completed.
- If the damage proves to be intentional, Fort Bliss will follow the guidelines in Archaeological Resources Protection Act.
- If the cultural resource is unevaluated, the CRM or CRM Staff will follow the procedures for documentation and evaluation of that property type and consult on the determination of eligibility with the appropriate SHPO and the CRM or CRM Staff will follow the procedures found in this Stipulation if the property is determined to be eligible for inclusion in the NRHP.
- If the damage is so slight as to have no effect on the site, or does not affect the characteristics that qualify the property for inclusion in the NRHP in a manner that would diminish the integrity of the property's location, design, setting, materials, workmanship, feeling, or association (36 CFR § 800.5(a)(1)), the CRM or CRM Staff shall make a finding of No Adverse Effect, complete the RHPC, and report the incident in the Annual Report.
- If the damage rises to the level of an Adverse Effect, the CRM or CRM Staff shall notify the appropriate SHPO via email, phone, or fax within 48 hours of the initial damage. Within 30 working days, Fort Bliss shall update or prepare a RHPC and the appropriate supporting documents (e.g., site form updates) with a letter signed by the GC.
 - The RHPC will document the circumstances of the damage, its extent and effect, along with potential mitigation measures, as appropriate.
 - The appropriate SHPO shall have 30 days to comment on that submission.

- If mitigation is proposed, and there are no objections to the methods, those measures shall be completed after that 30-day review period and thereafter be reported to the appropriate SHPO.
- If some other treatment is agreed to by the parties that treatment will be completed after the 30-day review period and thereafter are reported to the appropriate SHPO.
- If the parties are in dispute over proposed mitigation or treatment measures, the parties will follow the procedures in Stipulation VII.
- If the damage is to a property of traditional religious and cultural importance to the Tribes, the CRM or CRM Staff shall review the incident, prepare a report for the GC, make recommendations for treatment, if any, and recommend procedures that avoid future effects. The GC will begin consultation with the Tribes within 30 working days of notice of the damage, on the nature of the damage, any proposed treatment, and procedures proposed to avoid future effects.
- If the damage is to a property that is known to have or is discovered to have human remains or other NAGPRA objects, Fort Bliss will follow the process outlined in NAGPRA.

NOTIFICATION AND INVOLVEMENT OF INSTITUTIONS AND INTERESTED MEMBERS OF THE PUBLIC

Policy: Fort Bliss shall notify and invite public comment on planned projects within the implementation of this PA.

Procedures:

- Through the NEPA process, the public is invited to comment on planned projects when an EA or an EIS is the appropriate document for a given project as well as the Section 106 review.
- Mailing Lists of institutions and interested members of the public shall be maintained by the CRM or CRM Staff by area of interest and/or research concern. The institution or interested individual may then contact the CRM or CRM Staff to request an electronic version of a report of interest.

BROADER FORT BLISS OUTREACH

Policy: When Fort Bliss determines studies produced will have a wider range of interest, they may be published in scholarly journals, periodicals, books, or given as papers at learned and historical societies.

Procedure:

- All studies prepared by the CRM or CRM staff shall be submitted through channels to the Fort Bliss Public Affairs Officer (PAO) to ensure compliance with AR 360-5, *Public Information Policies*.
- Release of studies prepared under contract will be approved as specified in the contract.
- The CRM or CRM Staff shall ensure that a process that meets the standards of AR 360-5 is included in the scope of work for contracts approved by Fort Bliss.
- Exact location(s) of historic properties or other information that, in the opinion of the CRM or CRM Staff, might endanger the resources or are administrative in nature and have neither research value nor public interest will be released consistent with Section 304 of the NHPA.
- The CRM or CRM Staff shall provide copies of published articles to the SHPOs.
- The CRM or CRM Staff may attend meetings of local and state organizations concerned with cultural resources management issues at county and state historical societies, and archaeological societies.
 - The CRM or CRM Staff may speak on the status of Fort Bliss cultural resources management program. Informal presentations, including slide presentations, may be presented without prior approval of the PAO.
 - The CRM or CRM Staff shall notify the PAO in advance of anticipated formal presentations and coordinate further if the PAO so requests. If a formal paper is given and copies are distributed, the text will be submitted to the PAO prior to the presentation to ensure the requirements of AR 360-5.
 - The CRM will inform the PAO and appropriate members of the command group of any potentially controversial issues raised during formal or informal presentations.
- The CRM or CRM staff may include the development of popular publications as companions to technical reports when project budgets allow. Fort Bliss will provide Portable Document Files (PDF) of popular publications to individuals and organizations upon request.
- The CRM or CRM Staff may develop an Internet web page that can be used to disseminate information to a broader audience on cultural resource materials and program.

INADVERTENT DISCOVERY OF ARCHAEOLOGICAL SITES

Policy: It is the policy of Fort Bliss to handle the inadvertent discovery of archaeological sites during its day-to-day activities, both expeditiously and with respect for the resource. It is specified in all applicable Fort Bliss work orders, service orders, training requests, other proposed project work, and any cultural resource training that the CRM or CRM Staff is to be immediately notified in the event of an inadvertent discovery of cultural materials.

Procedure

- Fort Bliss shall follow the procedures in NAGPRA for the inadvertent discovery of human remains, funerary objects, sacred objects, or objects of cultural patrimony; all other finds will be addressed in this stipulation.
- If damage has been done to a historic property, Fort Bliss will also follow Stipulation III.
- Fort Bliss shall first ensure that all activity ceases in and around the find; activity may resume when all applicable procedures in this stipulation have been completed.
- The CRM or CRM Staff shall use the flowchart in Appendix F.
- The CRM or CRM Staff shall inspect the location as soon as practical and document the find, first determining whether or not the materials constitute a site (either new or previously recorded), and, secondly, if the site is eligible, and thirdly, if any adverse effects are observable can occur if the activity were to continue.
 - Isolated Occurrence: If the cultural materials are found to be an isolated occurrence (IO), activity can resume as soon as the CRM or CRM Staff make that determination; no additional reporting will be required.
 - If the materials are found to be part of a previously recorded site determined Not Eligible for the NRHP, and the discovery does not change that recommendation, activity can resume as soon as the CRM or CRM staff make that determination.
 - If, however, the discovery appears to change that recommendation to eligible, or if the property is eligible or listed on the NRHP, the CRM will consult with the Tribes and the appropriate SHPO on NRHP eligibility, determination of what type of effect (no adverse/adverse) the activity would have on that site, and if adverse, propose a treatment plan by email, phone, or fax within 48 hours of the find.

- The SHPO and the Tribes shall then have 48 hours upon notification in which to review the documentation and any proposed treatment and provide comment back to Fort Bliss.
 - Fort Bliss shall take into account comments provided and shall move forward with the treatment plan. Activities can resume upon completion. If no treatment is required, work can resume.
- If any consulting party fails to comment by the end of any review period, Fort Bliss will assume that that party concurs with the proposal and proceed to the next step as appropriate.

DISPUTE RESOLUTION

- Should any signatory to this PA object at any time to any actions proposed, or the manner in which the terms of this PA are implemented, Fort Bliss shall consult with such party to resolve the objection. If Fort Bliss determines that such objection cannot be resolved, Fort Bliss will:
 - Forward all documentation relevant to the dispute, including the Fort Bliss proposed resolution, to the ACHP. The ACHP shall provide Fort Bliss with its advice on the resolution of the objection within 30 days of receiving adequate documentation. Fort Bliss shall prepare a written response that takes into account any timely advice or comments regarding the dispute from the ACHP, signatories, and concurring parties, and provide them with a copy of this written response. Fort Bliss will then proceed according to its final decision.
 - If the ACHP does not provide its advice regarding the dispute within the 30 day time period, Fort Bliss shall prepare a written response that takes into account any timely comments regarding the dispute from the signatories and concurring parties to the PA, and provide them and the ACHP with a copy of such written response.
- Fort Bliss shall carry out all other actions that are not the subject of the dispute, subject to the terms of this PA.

ANNUAL REPORT

- Fort Bliss shall provide an annual report of activities conducted under this PA to all consulting parties and interested members of the public that includes the following:
 - A summary of 25 sample reviews of exempted undertakings for the first two years of annual reporting.
 - A summary of all projects that proceeded under the procedures in this PA with the following sections:

- Determination of Eligibility (Texas and New Mexico)
 - State
 - Date
 - RPHC #
 - NEPA #
 - Project #
 - Building #
 - Project Description
 - Determination of Eligibility
 - SHPO Determination of Eligibility

- No Historic Properties Affected
 - State
 - Date
 - RHPC #
 - NEPA #
 - Project #
 - Building #
 - Project Description
 - Project Analysis
 - No Historic Properties Affected
 - Comment

- No Historic Properties Adversely Affected
 - State
 - Date
 - RHPC #
 - NEPA #
 - Project #
 - Building #
 - Project Description
 - Project Analysis
 - Not Adversely Affected
 - Comment

- Adverse Effect
 - State
 - Date
 - RHPC #
 - NEPA #
 - Project #
 - Building #
 - Project Description
 - Analysis

- Adverse Effect
- Comment
- SHPO Date
- Mitigation Comment
- Damage Report
 - State
 - Date
 - RHPC #
 - NEPA #
 - Project #
 - Building #
 - Project Description
 - Analysis
- A random stratified sample of five complete RHPCs for undertakings within the appropriate state for the appropriate SHPO with a finding of “no historic properties affected” and “no adverse effect” for the first two years of annual reporting.
- All projects proposed for the coming year.
- Recommendations for amending the PA, if any.
- Upon request, the CRM shall include a list of Fort Bliss professionals who participated in implementation of this PA during the previous and current fiscal years in each PA annual report. The list will include a description of each professional’s current responsibilities.
- Fort Bliss shall prepare the final report and submit it, through command channels, for approval, reproduction, and release on 15 November each year the PA is in effect.
- Consulting parties will submit to Fort Bliss within 60 days of their receipt of the annual report any comments or any requests for specific RHPCs. If there is no response within this time, it will be assumed that the annual report is acceptable.
- Fort Bliss shall hold an annual review and monitoring meeting as appropriate and/or upon request of a signatory party.
- Fort Bliss shall retain the original documentation of each project undertaken without formal review of the appropriate SHPO for a period of three years. Original documentation shall be made available to consulting parties or interested members of the public upon written request.
- The ACHP shall only receive a copy of the annual report if an amendment is proposed by Fort Bliss.

FISCAL REQUIREMENTS AND SOURCES

The Stipulations of this PA are subject to the provisions of the Anti-Deficiency Act (31 U.S.C. Section 1341) and availability of funds. If compliance with the Anti-Deficiency Act alters or impairs the ability of Fort Bliss to implement the Stipulations of this PA, Fort Bliss will consult pursuant to Stipulations X and XI.

AMENDMENT

This PA may be amended when such an amendment is agreed to in writing by all signatories. The amendment will be effective on the date a copy signed by all of the signatories is filed with the ACHP.

TERMINATION

- If any signatory to this PA determines that its terms will not or cannot be carried out, that party shall immediately consult with the other parties to attempt to develop an amendment per Stipulation X. If within 60 days (or another time period agreed to by all signatories) an amendment cannot be reached, any signatory may terminate the PA upon written notification to the other signatories.
- Once the PA is terminated, and prior to work continuing on the undertaking, Fort Bliss shall either 1) execute a Memorandum of Agreement pursuant to 36 CFR § 800.6 or 2) request, take into account, and respond to the comments of the ACHP under 36 CFR § 800.7. Fort Bliss shall notify the signatories as to the course of action it will pursue.

DURATION OF THIS PA

- This PA takes effect upon last signature date and will remain in effect thereafter for 10 years. Upon consultation with, and agreement by, other parties of this PA, it may be extended, amended, or terminated at 10 years.
- This PA shall be reviewed periodically, not less than three years from the execution of the PA. Fort Bliss shall consult with the Signatories to determine whether the PA needs to be extended, amended, or terminated and take such actions as appropriate one year to the date this PA would otherwise expire.

Execution of this PA by Fort Bliss, the NMSHPO, the TXSHPO, and the ACHP and implementation of its terms evidence that Fort Bliss has taken into account the effects of this undertaking on historic properties and afforded the ACHP an opportunity to comment.

APPENDIX B: ACRONYMS AND DEFINITIONS

ACHP	Advisory Council on Historic Preservation
APE	Area of Potential Effect
AR	Army Regulation
ARPA	Archaeological Resources Protection Act
CATEX	Categorical Exclusion
CRM	Cultural Resources Manager
DOE	Determination of Eligibility
DPW	Directorate of Public Works
DPW-E	Directorate of Public Work, Environmental Division, Conservation Branch
EA	Environmental Assessment
EIS	Environmental Impact Statement
GC	Garrison Commander
GIS	Geographic Information System
GPS	Global Positioning System
HABS	Historic American Building Survey
HAER	Historic American Engineering Record
HALS	Historic American Landscape Survey
HCPI	Historic Cultural Properties Inventory
HP	Historic Property
ICRMP	Integrated Cultural Resource Management Plan
IO	Isolated Occurrence
LA	Laboratory of Anthropology
MOA	Memorandum of Agreement
NAGPRA	Native American Graves Protection and Repatriation Act
NEPA	National Environmental Policy Act
NHPA	National Historic Preservation Act of 1966
NMCRIS	New Mexico Cultural Resources Information System
NMSHPO	New Mexico State Historic Preservation Officer
NPS	National Park Service
NRHP	National Register of Historic Places
PA	Programmatic Agreement
PAO	Public Affairs Office
PRD	Programmatic Research Design
REC	Record of Environmental Consideration
RHPC	Record of Historic Properties Consideration
SDZ	Surface Danger Zone
SHPO	State Historic Preservation Officer
TARL	Texas Archaeological Research Laboratory
TCP	Traditional Cultural Property
THPO	Tribal Historic Preservation Officer
TRU	Transect Recording Unit
TXSHPO	Texas State Historic Preservation Officer
UTM	Universal Transverse Mercator

36 CFR Part 800. The Codified Federal Regulation implementing Section 106 of the NHPA.

Aboveground properties. Properties or portions of properties, typically buildings, structures, and landscapes that are not archaeology.

Adverse effect. Includes but is not limited to the physical destruction, damage, or alteration of part or all of a property's characteristics that contribute to the property's eligibility for inclusion in the NRHP. Adverse effects can also include alteration of a property that is not consistent with the Secretary of the Interior's Standards for Treatment of Historic Properties. Examples include the introduction of elements that are out of character with the property or affect its setting, neglect resulting in deterioration or destruction of the property, and transfer, lease or sale of the property.

Advisory Council on Historic Preservation. Established under Title 11 of the NHPA, as amended. The ACHP is to be afforded a reasonable opportunity to comment with regard to proposed federal, federally licensed, federally permitted, or federally assisted undertakings that may affect properties included in or eligible for inclusion in the NRHP.

Anti-Deficiency Act. Legislation enacted by the United States Congress (September 13, 1982) to prevent the incurring of obligations or the making of expenditures in excess of amounts available in appropriations or funds. Prohibits the Federal Government from entering into a contract that is not "fully funded."

Area of potential effect. Geographic area or areas within which an undertaking may cause changes in the character or use of historic properties, if any such properties exist there. The APE always includes the actual site of the undertaking, and may include other areas where the undertaking will cause changes in land use, traffic patterns, or other aspects that could affect historic properties.

Artifact. An object made or modified by human beings.

Assessment of Effect. Fort Bliss shall apply the criteria of adverse effect to historic properties within the APE. Fort Bliss shall consider any previous or known views concerning effects which have been provided by consulting parties and the public. An adverse effect is found when an undertaking may alter, directly or indirectly, any of the characteristics of a historic property that qualify the property for inclusion in the NRHP in a manner that would diminish the historic property's integrity.

Association. The link of a historic property with a historic event, activity, or person, also, the quality of integrity through which a historic property is associated with a particular past time and place.

Building. A historic property type that represents a resource, such as a house, created principally to shelter any form of human activity.

Consulting Parties. Those individuals and organizations concerned with the effects of a particular undertaking on historic properties. May include, but not limited to SHPO, ACHP, tribes, preservation groups, etc.

Criteria. The general standard by which the significance of a historic property is judged.

Cultural Resources Manager. The CRM is the federal government employee that meets qualifications as outlined by the Professional Qualifications for Archaeology or Historic Preservation and designated by the GC. The CRM is the expert in cultural resources and the administrator of the ICRMP and this PA. The CRM acts on behalf of the GC to coordinate compliance with this PA.

Days. In all instances of time periods for actions, “days” is intended to mean “calendar days” unless otherwise noted.

Design. A quality of integrity applied to the elements that create the physical form, plan, space, structure, and style of a property.

Determination of eligibility. The process of ascertaining a property’s eligibility for listing on the NRHP. A property eligible for the NRHP but not actually listed or formally determined eligible by the Secretary of the Interior is afforded the same protection under Section 106 as a listed historic property.

Dig Permit. Form used by Army to request digging or excavation, for construction or training.

District. A historic property type that represents a significant concentration, linkage, or continuity of sites, buildings, structures, or objects united historically or aesthetically by plan or physical development.

Evaluation. Process by which the significance and integrity of a historic property are judged for eligibility for the NRHP.

Feature. A feature can include any evidence of human activity and is usually non-portable: trash middens, storage areas, houses, hearths, windmills, corrals, and fences, etc. A hearth feature, at a minimum, is defined as 10 or more fire-cracked rocks in a one sq meter area.

Feeling. Quality of integrity through which a historic property evokes the aesthetic or historic sense of past time and place.

Geographic Information System. A computer system capable of capturing, storing, analyzing, and displaying geographically referenced information; that is, data identified according to location. Practitioners also define a Geographic Information System (GIS) as including the procedures, operating personnel, and spatial data that go into the system (from US Geological Survey web site).

Ground-disturbing activities. Any action that disturbs soil either temporarily or permanently accomplished by any method including but not limited to hand or machine excavation, grading and removal of vegetation, rocks, or other ground cover.

Historic American Buildings Survey. A program administered by the NPS to record in detail historic buildings through architectural rendering, large format photography, and written documentation.

Historic American Engineering Record. A program administered by the NPS to record in detail historic structures through engineering drawings, large format photography, and written documentation.

Historic American Landscape Survey. A program administered by the NPS to record in detail historic landscapes through rendering, large format photography, and written documentation.

Historic context. An organizing structure for interpreting history that groups information about historic properties that share a common theme, common geographical location, and common time period. The development of historic contexts is a foundation for decisions about the planning, identification, evaluation, registration, and treatment of historic properties, based upon comparative significance.

Historic Cultural Properties Inventory. A form used by the State of New Mexico to record historic properties.

Historic property. Any prehistoric or historic district, site, building, structure, object, or traditional cultural property included in, or eligible for inclusion in the NRHP. The term includes artifacts, records, and remains related to and located in such properties.

Impact Areas. (Department of the Army Training Circular No. 25-1). *Impact Area- Dudded* – an area having designated boundaries within which all dud-producing ordnance will detonate or impact. This area may include vehicle bodies that serve as targets for artillery/mortar direct and indirect fire. Impact areas containing unexploded ordnance may not be used for maneuver. *Impact Area – Non-Dudded* – an area having designated boundaries within which ordnance that does not produce duds will impact. This area is composed mostly of the safety fans for small arms ranges. These impact areas may be used for maneuver, at the cost of curtailing use of weapons ranges.

Integrated Cultural Resources Management Plan. A required DOD planning tool for compliance with statutory management requirements.

Integrity. Authenticity of a property's historic identity, evidenced by the survival of physical characteristic(s) that existed during the property's historic or prehistoric period. Integrity consists of seven elements: location, design, setting, materials, workmanship, feeling, and association.

Isolated Occurrence. Any cultural material recorded in a survey that does not fit the criteria for a site and is not close enough in proximity to other cultural materials to be added to a site boundary.

Keeper: NPS employ responsible for the NRHP program.

Location. A quality of integrity retained by a historic property existing in the same place as it did during its period of significance.

Material. A quality of integrity applying to the physical elements that were combined or deposited in a particular pattern or configuration to form a historic property.

Memorandum of Agreement. A formal Section 106 document that outlines an agreement made among individuals, groups, or entities, used to cooperatively work together on an agreed purpose or meet an agreed objective.

Mitigate. Reduce harm to historic properties.

Native American Graves Protection and Repatriation Act. Federal Act that describes the rights of Native American lineal descendants, Indian tribes, and Native Hawaiian organization with respect to the treatment, repatriation, and disposition of Native American human remains, funerary objects and sacred objects, and objects of cultural patrimony; also provides greater protection for Native American burial sites and more careful control over removal of Native American human remains, funerary objects and sacred objects, and objects of cultural patrimony.

National Register of Historic Places. A list of districts, sites, buildings, structures, and objects significant in American history, architecture, archaeology, engineering, and culture.

National Environmental Policy Act. A United States environmental law establishing a national policy promoting the enhancement of the environment and setting up procedures for all federal agencies in which to consider the effects of their proposed actions on the environment.

Object: A historic property type that represents a construction primarily artistic in nature or relatively small in scale and simply constructed, such as a statue or milepost.

Period of significance. Span of time in which a property attained the significance for which it meets the NRHP.

Programmatic Agreement. A Section 106 agreement document that records the terms and conditions agreed upon to resolve potential adverse effects, typically developed for a large or complex project or a class of undertakings that would otherwise require numerous individual requests for ACHP comments under the NHPA.

Programmatic Research Design. A strategic, systematic, and reusable program of identifying research goals and methods to address data recovery of a class of site types or time periods or some other unifying characteristic(s).

Proponent. The organization with technical and administrative control over the execution of a project or training exercise; e.g., the DPW acts as the user's agent for construction activity and is the implementing organization for those projects.

Red Zones. Restricted areas on Fort Bliss in which no activity is allowed.

Record of Historic Properties Consideration. Fort Bliss documentation of the Section 106 review process followed by the CRM or CRM Staff to document compliance under Section 106. Information included on the form includes: initiation date of review, associated Work Order number or Archaeological Project number, name of Proponent, project description, APE, project analysis, documentation of determinations of eligibility and findings of effect, treatments of adverse effects, and date review closed.

Section 106 process. A review process established under NHPA Section 106 and administered by the ACHP under its regulations. During this process, agencies afford the ACHP an opportunity to comment on any agency activity or undertaking that may affect historic properties, and must take such comments into account.

Section 110. The section of the NHPA that defines federal agencies' responsibilities to preserve and use historic buildings and to establish a program to identify, evaluate and nominate historic properties to the NRHP.

Service Order. Request for work that can be completed for under \$1,200 or under 40 man-hours of time.

Setting. A quality of integrity applying to the physical environment of a historic property.

Site. A historic property type representing a location of a significant event, a prehistoric or historic occupation or activity, or a building or structure, whether standing, ruined, or vanished, where the location itself possesses historic, cultural, or archaeological value regardless of the value of any existing structure.

State Historic Preservation Officer. A position created under the NHPA. The SHPO is appointed by the governor and charged with the administration of the NHPA and to ensure that the state's interests are considered.

Structure. A historic property type representing a functional construction made for purposes other than creating shelter, such as a bridge.

Surface Danger Zone. (Department of the Army Pamphlet 385-63) The ground and airspace designated within the training complex (to include associated safety areas) for vertical and lateral containment of projectiles, fragments, debris, and components resulting from the firing, launching, or detonation of weapon systems to include explosives and demolitions. The SDZ is a depiction of the mathematically predicted area a projectile will return to earth either by direct fire or ricochet. (Exempted from project review only when active.)

Tenant. A person who occupies real property owned by another based upon an agreement between the person and the landlord/owner, almost always for rental payments.

Traditional Cultural Property. Properties associated with the traditional cultural practices of a living community that (a) are rooted in that community's history or (b) are important in

maintaining the continuing cultural identity of the community. A Traditional Cultural Property (TCP) is the terminology used by the NRHP program.

Transect Recording Unit. A 15 m by 15 m unit or “cell”, part of a larger, virtual grid placed over an archaeological survey area, in which all cultural materials are recorded, usually by means of a hand-held computer, for later projection and use in a GIS.

Tribal Contacts. Under this ICRMP, Tribal Contacts refers to the seven Native American Tribes Fort Bliss consults with on a regular basis. They include; Comanche Nation of Oklahoma, Fort Sill Apache Tribe of Oklahoma, Pueblo of Isleta, Kiowa Tribe of Oklahoma, Ysleta del Sur Pueblo, Mescalero Apache Tribe, and White Mountain Apache Tribe

Undertaking. Under this ICRMP, an undertaking is defined as a project, activity, or program funded in whole or in part under the direct or indirect jurisdiction of a Federal agency including those carried out by or on behalf of the Army; those carried out in whole or in part with Army funds, and those requiring Army approval--from 36 CFR § 800.16(y).

Universal Transverse Mercator. Geographic coordinate system developed by the United States Army Corps of Engineers, to give locations on the surface of the earth. The system divides the earth into 60 zones, each a 6-degree band of longitude, and uses a secant transverse Mercator projection in each zone.

View shed. Areas under the direct or indirect jurisdiction of a federal agency that can be seen from historic properties, typically from the perimeter of a historic district or historic property.

Workmanship. A quality of integrity applying to the physical evidence of the crafts of a particular culture during any given period or prehistory.

Work Order. Requested on Department of the Army Form 4283, a request for maintenance, repair, or new work over \$1,200 or 40 man-hours.

APPENDIX C: EXEMPTED UNDERTAKINGS

The categories of undertakings listed below have been determined by Fort Bliss, the SHPOs, and the ACHP to meet the criteria for exemption; i.e., they qualify as undertakings, but will have no effect on historic properties, or their potential effects will not be adverse. An undertaking of one or more of the types listed below will not require further Section 106 review with the appropriate SHPO, so long as the undertaking is limited to the types listed below, and is not a part of another undertaking. Additionally, if at any time in the course of the undertaking information becomes available that would make this procedure inapplicable, including but not limited to the discovery of historic properties or human remains, Section 106 review or NAGPRA protocol shall be initiated by Fort Bliss.

A. 32 CFR § 651.9 (b)(1) Emergencies. Immediate actions to promote national defense or security and actions necessary for the protection of life or property, including but not limited to the following:

- In-place disposal of unexploded ordnance
- Disposal of ordnance in existing open burning/open detonation units
- Emergency response to releases of hazardous substances, pollutants, and contaminants (no cultural resources work would be conducted, unless and until the danger to human health and safety has been cleared).
- Military activities in existing designated Surface Danger Zones (SDZ). The exemption will apply to designated impact (duded) areas, or areas with unexploded ordnance. SDZ are exempted only when active; areas within an SDZ that become contaminated with unexploded ordnance are then exempted, unless and until the unexploded ordnance is cleared).

B. Fort Bliss will proceed with undertakings required to support mobilization and training required due to unanticipated deployment, mobilization, or armed conflict. The CRM or CRM staff with appropriate security clearance will conduct an internal review. In all cases, however, the CRM or CRM staff will ensure that the effects of these undertakings on historic properties will be considered and a reasonable effort will be made to avoid damage to the historic property. The CRM or CRM staff will include a summary of the undertaking in the Annual Report, provided no information is classified or would have the potential to affect classified actions.

C. Activities on other areas across Fort Bliss shall be exempted from project review because of the limited (or no) potential for cultural resources sites:

- Steep slopes (greater than 30 percent)
- Active arroyos
- Active floodplains
- Areas disturbed to a depth below the proposed undertaking

D. Decisions made through government-to-government consultation with tribes concerning management options for Sacred Sites.

E. Site Work

Replace in kind existing damaged landscaping and plant material with native and/or regional landscaping material. New replacement plantings, xeriscaping and ground cover shall meet the following Fort Bliss Landscape: A Landscape Handbook for Historic Properties (2009) and shall maintain overall character of adjacent historic properties and historic view shed;

Repair or replace in kind existing streets, driveways, sidewalks and curbing. Undertaking includes stripping of pavement, spreading of new gravel on existing roads, and concrete formwork and curing;

Repair or replace existing water, sewer, natural gas, and communications lines in their present configuration, alignments and depth with no impact to character defining features;

Traffic signs as required by law;

Repair or replace in kind existing building signs. Signs should be mounted in a way as to minimize physical damage to historic building materials. New sign installation shall maintain character of historic properties and not alter character defining features;

Temporary buildings or structures that will not have a life longer than five years;

Undertakings that impact areas less than one square meter of ground disturbance;

Repair or replace in kind existing fencing and fence screens. Installation of perimeter security fencing and gates are acceptable provided surveys have not identified historic properties and character defining features are not altered; or

No, or minimal, ground disturbance, and ground disturbance within previously disturbed areas as long as new disturbance does not exceed dimensions of previous disturbance.

F. Roofs

Repair in kind existing roof. If roof is deteriorated beyond repair, a compatible replacement roof is acceptable. Replacement roof(s) shall not alter overall appearance of exterior or diminish character defining features.

All exempted work shall follow Fort Bliss Standards for the Treatment of Historic Buildings: Chapter 7 Maintenance Guide for Roofing (2008) and/or Project Manual – Rehabilitation and Replacement of Historic Roofing (2002).

Installation of new roofing, including white roofs or cool roofs, on a flat-roofed building with a parapet, such that the roofing material is not visible from any public right-of-way.

G. Exterior

Repair or replace in kind existing materials that maintain character defining features: stucco, concrete, masonry, wood siding, trim, porch decking, porch rails, joists, columns, and stairs.

Installation of materials such as netting, bird spikes or sonar equipment for the deterring of bird habitat and does not alter character defining features. Installation should be reversible and not result in physical damage.

All exempted work shall follow the following Fort Bliss published material specific guidance documents: Fort Bliss Standards for the Treatment of Historic Buildings, all chapters as applicable (2008); The Adobe Manual (2004); The Stucco & Plaster Manual (2006); The Wood & Carpentry Manual (2005); The Waterproofing Manual (2004).

H. Doors

Repair in kind existing historic door(s). If door is deteriorated beyond repair, a compatible replacement door is acceptable. Replacement door(s) shall match original design/configuration and shall not alter overall appearance of facade or diminish character defining features. Doors will typically be the same materials unless force protection or safety protocols require otherwise;

Installation of hardware to include dead bolts, door latches and locks, window latches, locks, hinges, and door peepholes, provided historic materials are not removed. New hardware shall be of a plain, contemporary design and made of the same material as existing historic hardware;

Repair in kind door screen(s). Door screen(s) shall be repaired in-kind prior to consideration of replacement. If replacement is necessary, screen shall be replaced in-kind with same material and thickness as existing screen.

All exempted work shall follow the Fort Bliss Standards for the Treatment of Historic Buildings, Chapter 8 Maintenance Guide for Doors (2008).

I. Windows

Repair in kind existing damaged window components. If window components are deteriorated beyond repair, individual window component shall be replaced in-kind. Complete window replacement requires SHPO review;

Paint window components in-kind. Unpainted surfaces shall remain unpainted;

Adjustments of window counterweights including associated disassembly and reassembly;

Replace in kind existing broken window glazing. Replacement shall be clear glass with same thickness as broken glass;

Repair or replace in kind existing damaged window screens and storm windows;

Installation of hardware to include window latches, locks, hinges, provided character defining features are not removed. New hardware shall be of a plain contemporary design and made of the same material finish as remaining existing historic hardware;

All exempted work shall follow these guidance documents: Project Manual – Construction Documents and Specifications for Rehabilitation and Replacement of Historic Windows (2002) and/or Fort Bliss Standards for the Treatment of Historic Buildings: Chapter 9 Maintenance Guide for Windows (2008).

J. Interiors

Repair or replacement of existing non-historic flooring, carpets, and blinds that does not alter character defining features;

Replacement or placement of window treatment such as mini-blinds and curtains;

Repair in kind damaged historic flooring. If flooring components are deteriorated beyond repair, individual flooring component shall be replaced in-kind. Replacement flooring shall match original design, color and material and shall not alter character defining features;

Removal of paint coating through hand scraping or sanding that does not alter character defining features. Removal shall follow Project Manual – Construction Documents and Specification: Preservation & Rehabilitation of Historic Interior Finishes (2007);

Installation of fire, smoke and security detectors;

Installation of new interior furniture/furnishing and information technology systems and equipment that does not alter or diminish character defining features;

Repair of structural and mechanical systems that are not visible and does not alter structural integrity or character defining features;

Repaint or refinish historic surfaces in kind. New paint color/finish shall match existing color and texture and does not alter character defining features;

Removal and replacement of non-historic asbestos flooring and mastic and does not alter character defining features.

All exempted interiors work shall follow Fort Bliss Standards for the Treatment of Historic Buildings (2008), Sections as applicable and/or Project Manual – Construction

Documents and Specification: Preservation & Rehabilitation of Historic Interior Finishes (2007).

K. Electrical/Plumbing/HVAC

Repair or replacement of existing electrical, plumbing fixtures, wiring, lines and pipes and does not alter character defining features;

Repair or replacement of existing heating and cooling systems, ductwork and ventilation systems that are not considered character defining features and do not alter character defining features;

Repair or replacement of existing electrical, power, lighting and communication lines in their present configuration and alignments and depth and do not alter character defining features;

Upgrading existing electrical and plumbing components such as hot water heaters, existing wiring, lines and pipes that do not alter character defining features;

All exempted mechanical and electrical work shall follow Fort Bliss Standards for the Treatment of Historic Buildings (2008).

L. Conservation

Repair or installation of insulation in roofs, crawl spaces, ceiling, attics, walls, floors and around pipes and ducts that do not alter character defining features;

Repair and installation of weather stripping and caulking that does not alter character defining features. Undertaking shall follow Project Manual – Construction Documents and Specifications for Rehabilitation and Replacement of Historic Windows (2002) and Fort Bliss Standards for the Treatment of Historic Buildings: Preservation & Rehabilitation of Historic Windows;

Repair or replacement of existing non-historic lighting systems that do not alter character defining features;

Installation of environmental monitoring units, such as those for water, air quality and electrical usage;

All exempted undertakings that affect windows shall follow these guidance documents: Project Manual – Construction Documents and Specifications for Rehabilitation and Replacement of Historic Windows (2002) and/or Fort Bliss Standards for the Treatment of Historic Buildings: Chapter 9 Maintenance Guide for Windows (2008).

Energy audits and feasibility studies.

Water conservation measures, such as installation of low-flow faucets, toilets, showerheads, urinals, or distribution device controls, provided that plumbing fixtures to be replaced are not original to the building;

Upgrading existing facility and infrastructure-related pumps and motors, including those water/wastewater facilities, to variable-speed or premium efficiency standards;

Hot water tank replacement that does not require a visible new supply or venting; and

Repairing plumbing systems in a manner that does not affect the interior or exterior of the building.

M. Maintenance

Maintenance and routine housekeeping that does not alter character defining features;

Removal of animals, birds, insects and their associated debris.

N. New Construction

New construction in areas that do not include historic properties or with the view shed of a historic district. New construction in or near a historic district and associated view shed shall be reviewed and approved by the CRM and/or CRM Staff.

APPENDIX D: IDENTIFYING AND EVALUATING PROPERTIES

The following procedures are applicable to all survey and/or evaluation work plans conducted under a Section 106/NEPA Review--or a general Section 110 project as appropriate, and will be applicable throughout the term of the PA. Work plans will describe the scope of work (including the boundaries of the survey area, acreage or numbers of buildings and structures to be inventoried), the methods to be used, and the expected output (or deliverables). All work will be conducted by or under the supervision of a professional who meets the minimum standards as identified in the Professional Qualifications as appropriate for the historic property being addressed and must be consistent with the Secretary of the Interior's Standards and Guidelines for Archaeology and Historic Preservation (48 FR 44716).

I. Archaeological Survey

A. Policy: Fort Bliss shall obtain accurate, descriptive field data of all observed cultural materials in consultation with the appropriate SHPOs and Tribes.

B. Procedure

1. Transect Recording Unit (TRU) Survey

- a) The survey area is gridded into 15 m x 15 m units using GIS software.
- b) Each TRU is identified by the WGS 84 UTM coordinate of its southwest corner. Each crewmember walks a 15 m x 15 m line of units, until all units within the survey area have been observed.
- c) Each crewmember uses a handheld electronic data gathering unit to record all observed cultural materials within each 15 m x 15 m "cell."
- d) The electronic data gathering unit usually includes a GPS application that displays the TRU coordinates, with a correctible accuracy of less than or equal to one meter, linked to a menu driven database for recording the artifact and feature types, and other pre-programmed data field.

2. Recording methods

a) Features

- (1) Features are recorded within each 15 m x 15 m unit.
- (2) Data to be gathered when recording a feature include: the type and quantity of materials, the size and shape of the feature, any construction details, probable function, and any relationship to nearby cultural materials.

- (3) Digital photos are taken of each feature.
 - (4) If the feature is tested for subsurface depth/content of materials, then plan and/or profile views are drawn.
- b) Artifacts
- (1) Artifacts are recorded within each 15 m x 15 m unit.
 - (2) Data to be collected can include: type of artifact, size, shape, color, material type (lithic type, ceramic type, glass type), count, maker's mark or other identifiable markings or stamps.
 - (3) Crewmembers may estimate the number of artifacts for TRUs where large numbers of artifacts are observed.
3. Defining archaeological sites
- a) Minimum standards
- (1) Ten or more artifacts of any class or type (except for fire-cracked rock) within a 15 sq meter area (except when all pieces appear to originate from a single source—a ceramic pot, a broken glass bottle, deteriorated sheet of metal, etc.). An exception might be made for a single knapping area which could be considered an activity area, and thus a site; or
 - (2) One or more dateable features (that is, chronometric dating) with or without associated artifacts (associated within a 15-meter radius of the feature); or
 - (3) Two or more undateable features within 30 meters of one another; or
 - (4) One or more undateable features with any associated artifacts.
- b) In general, 30 meters of no cultural materials is the maximum distance allowed between two 15 m x 15 m units containing cultural materials (or “positive” cells) to still be considered part of the same site. Field supervisors will be allowed to assign site status as appropriate to other situations outside of these criteria provided a logical and reasonable justification is made.

- c) Prehistoric Site, Historic Site, or Multi-Component Site
 - (1) Archaeological sites may be historic, or include historic components.
 - (2) A historic component is identified when the feature and/or artifacts can be shown to be 50 years of age or older, but not extending into prehistory.
 - (3) At Fort Bliss that earliest date is 1659 A.D. (or the establishment of the first Spanish missions).
 - (4) Relevant historic records searches will be conducted and in New Mexico, the appropriate state forms are completed when historic buildings or structures are present on the site. Appropriate state forms shall be completed by an individual meeting the Professional Standards.
- d) Isolated Occurrences
 - (1) IOs are recorded when there is a positive TRU that contains cultural materials that do not fit the criteria for a site.
 - (2) Data to be gathered when recording an IO include: the type and quantity of materials, the size and shape of the feature, any construction details, probable function, and any relationship to nearby cultural materials.

4. Conducting Geomorphic Studies

- a) Each investigation shall assess the potential for subsurface deposits and the integrity of those deposits at each site through subsurface testing, although natural cuts into the landscape (road cuts, arroyos, and rills) and other previously collected geomorphic/geologic data can be used.
- b) Testing shall include trowel tests, auger tests, shovel tests or backhoe tests; testing shall be proportional to the size of the site, but otherwise have a minimal impact.
- c) The investigation shall record the soil profile and any other distinguishing characteristics (such as pieces of charcoal or buried artifacts) to identify post-depositional activities that have affected the site (wind or water erosion, man-made impacts, and bioturbation), to estimate the extent of those activities, and to

finally arrive at an estimate of the percentage of the site remaining intact.

- d) When appropriate for a given project, a geomorphologist shall conduct geomorphological studies.

5. Assessing Chronological and Chronometric Potential

- a) Each investigation shall assess the potential for chronological and/or chronometric dating.
- b) Chronological or relative dating potential includes the presence of diagnostic ceramics or stone tool types or features; chronometric dating potential includes the presence of charcoal pieces or carbon-stained soil for AMS dating techniques.
- c) The potential for other types of chronometric dating methods such as dendrochronological (tree ring) or thermoluminescence (time elapsed since last firing) can also be used.
- d) Actual collection and testing shall be based on the availability of funding.

6. Processing Survey Data

- a) Survey data is downloaded to one unit and/or computer and/or server for later Quality Assurance/Quality Control and further processing.
- b) Those files shall be saved in the ESRI .shp file extension for use in one of the ESRI geographic information system (GIS) products such as ArcMap.
- c) Data collection and summary descriptions shall include:
 - (1) general physical environment;
 - (2) horizontal boundary of the site;
 - (3) quantities and types of artifacts;
 - (4) number, size, and types of features;
 - (5) site integrity based on observation and subsurface testing and;

- (6) potential for yielding chronometric and/or paleo climatological samples.
- d) In general, a physical site datum shall be established for each site and a site tag included as appropriate, unless otherwise directed by the CRM or CRM Staff.
 - (1) The datum is usually a piece of rebar with an attached aluminum tag.
 - (2) The tag includes the name of the investigator, date of placement, Fort Bliss project number, and Fort Bliss and appropriate state site numbers.

7. Creating Site Maps

- a) An overall map of the project area and individual site maps shall be created for each survey and included in any report or other written record.
- b) Individual site maps include
 - (1) the site boundary;
 - (2) nearby physiographic features and landmarks;
 - (3) locations of features, site datum, test units, and collections;
 - (4) a “north” arrow, a scale and a legend or key;
 - (5) source graphics and;
 - (6) both Fort Bliss and appropriate state numbers.

8. Completing State Site Forms

- a) Appropriate state forms shall be completed for each recorded site, following the appropriate state guidance.
- b) Fort Bliss numbers are assigned by the CRM or CRM Staff.
- c) The primary number for any site on Fort Bliss is the “Fort Bliss” or “FB” number; the appropriate state number is the required secondary number.

- d) Site maps attached to state site forms shall conform to the requirements of the appropriate state.

II. Historic Buildings, Objects, Structures, and District Surveys

- A. Policy: Fort Bliss shall obtain accurate, descriptive field data of all buildings, objects, structures, and districts, not previously surveyed, in consultation with the appropriate SHPOs and Tribes.

- B. Procedure

- 1. At a minimum the following information shall be collected in a survey of the built environment:

- a) Building Number;
 - b) Year Built;
 - c) Historic Function;
 - d) Evaluator/Date of evaluation;
 - e) Historic code;
 - f) Historic context;
 - g) Architectural description; and
 - h) Photo of the primary façade

- 2. Completing State Forms

- a) Appropriate state forms shall be completed for each recorded building, object, or structure following the appropriate state guidance.
 - b) Fort Bliss numbers are assigned by the CRM or CRM Staff.
 - c) The primary number for any historic property on Fort Bliss is the "Fort Bliss" or "FB" number; the appropriate state number is the required secondary number.
 - d) Maps attached to state forms shall conform to the requirements of the appropriate state.

APPENDIX E: RECORD OF HISTORIC PROPERTIES CONSIDERATION

RECORD OF HISTORIC PROPERTIES CONSIDERATION

Date: 11/3/2010 State: TX Archeology
RHPC No.: 1 Architecture
RHPC Preparer: Sitton Archeology and Architecture
 Dig Permit

NEPA Number: 99-999 Project Number: 9999
Work Order No.: XXX999 Bldg. Number: 2420

Proponent: Proponent(s) Name
Project Name: Project Name
Project Description:
Describe project particulars, location, timelines, etc.

Area of Potential Effect: Describe area at risk for effects

Project Analysis:
Describe process followed to complete review--nature of project, possible issues, research materials used, previous projects and results, any work required or already completed, etc.

Damage Report Acceptable Loss Interior or Exterior: Exterior In District or Viewshed

Criteria for Evaluation

Historic Context: Summarize applicable Historic Context(s)

Criterion A: How site(s) meets the requirements under the criterion

Criterion B: How site(s) meets the requirements under the criterion

Criterion C: How site(s) meets the requirements under the criterion

Criterion D: How site(s) meets the requirements under the criterion

Criteria Considerations Apply to Property

Criterion Considered: test record

Determination of Eligibility

THIS IS A DETERMINATION OF ELIGIBILITY SHPO Consultation Date: 03-Nov-10

Comments: Log Number or Tracking Number, how any comments were addressed, report title and author

Assessing Effects

THIS IS AN ASSESSMENT OF EFFECT

No Historic Properties Affected
Comments: Any comments to better explain findings.

Historic Properties Not Adversely Affected
Comments: Any comments to better explain findings.

Historic Properties Adversely Affected
Comments: Any comments to better explain findings.

Treatment of Adverse Effect

SHPO Consultation Date: 11/3/2010
Comments: How any comments were addressed; other consultation conducted, timelines, or other information.

Attachment List: maps, reports, figures, etc.

Signatures For Findings of Adverse Effect

Preparer: _____ Date: _____

APPENDIX F: AREA OF POTENTIAL EFFECT

**APPENDIX G: FLOWCHART – INADVERTENT DISCOVERY
PROCEDURES**

Cultural Materials Found and Work Stops
 ↓
 CRM or CRM Staff Notified
 (within 48 Hours SHPO and tribes contacted if appropriate)
 ↓
 CRM or CRM Staff Inspect Location

Inside a Known Site?

YES		NO		
Eligible		Not Eligible		
Adverse Effect?		Remains Not Eligible?		
Yes	No	Yes	No	
↓	↓	↓	Consult DOE, Effect, and/or Treatment	
Consult Effect/Treatment	Consult Effect	WORK RESUMES	Concur	Non-concur
↓	↓		↓	↓
Concur	Non-Concur		Proceed as agreed	Consult/Dispute Resolution
↓	↓		↓	↓
Proceed as Agreed	Consult/Dispute Resolution		WORK RESUMES	Proceed as Agreed
↓	↓			↓
WORK RESUMES	Proceed as agreed			WORK RESUMES
	↓			
	WORK RESUMES			

APPENDIX H: STANDARD MITIGATION MEASURES

If the CRM and/or CRM Staff make a finding of Adverse Effect, Fort Bliss will identify consulting parties, including Tribes, and consider all comments on this plan to mitigate those adverse effects. Options for mitigating those effects include avoiding the site or sites by design, data recovery, or some other creative mitigation plan (trade-offs, preservation of another site, development of a new historic context in lieu of data recovery, etc.), or other plans as may be developed during consultation.

I. Recordation

A. Digital Photography Package: Prior to project implementation, the CRM and/or CRM staff shall oversee the successful delivery of a digital photography package prepared by staff or contractors meeting the Professional Qualifications for Architectural History, History, Architecture, or Historic Architecture, as appropriate. The digital photography package will meet the standards cited in the NPS' *National Register of Historic Places Photographic Policy March 2010 or subsequent revisions* (<http://www.nps.gov/nr/publications/bulletins/photopolicy/index.htm>).

The package shall include a comprehensive collection of photographs of both interior and exterior views showing representative spaces and details of significant architectural features and typical building materials. Exterior photographs shall include full oblique and contextual images of each elevation. Exterior views shall be keyed to a site plan while interior views shall be keyed to a floor plan of the building/structure. The photographs shall be indexed according to the date photographed, site number, site name, site address, direction, frame number, subject matter and photographer's name recorded on the reverse side in pencil.

The package shall include printed color copies of the digital photographs (on appropriate paper, per NPS Photographic Policy), a CD/DVD of the digital photographs (per NPS Photographic Policy), the completed appropriate state inventory form, select existing drawings, where available, and a written site history of the historic property.

The CRM shall submit the package to the appropriate SHPO for review and approval. Once approved by the appropriate SHPO, the CRM and/or CRM Staff shall submit a copy of the approved documentation to a state or local historical society, archive, and/or library for permanent retention.

B. 35mm Black and White Photography Package: Prior to project implementation, the CRM and/or CRM Staff shall oversee the successful delivery of a 35 mm black and white film photography package prepared by staff or contractors meeting the Professional Qualifications for Architectural History, History, Architecture, or Historic Architecture, as appropriate.

The package shall include a comprehensive collection of photographs of both interior and exterior views showing representative spaces and details of significant architectural features and typical building materials. Exterior photographs shall include full oblique and contextual images of each elevation. Exterior views shall be keyed to a site plan

while interior views shall be keyed to a floor plan of the building/structure. The photographs shall be indexed according to the date photographed, site number, site name, site address, direction, frame number, subject matter and photographer's name recorded on the reverse side in pencil.

The package shall include one full set of 35mm black and white photographs printed on fiber-based paper, the corresponding 35mm film negatives in acid free sleeves, the completed appropriate state inventory form, select existing drawings, where available, and a written site history of the historic property.

The CRM shall submit the package to the appropriate SHPO for review and approval. Once approved by the appropriate SHPO, the CRM and/or CRM staff shall submit a copy of the approved documentation to a state or local historical society, archive, and/or library for permanent retention.

C. Large Format Photography Package: Prior to project implementation, the CRM and/or CRM staff shall oversee the successful delivery of a large format photography package prepared by staff or contractors meeting the Professional Qualifications for Architectural History, History, Architecture, or Historic Architecture, as appropriate.

The package shall include a comprehensive collection of photographs of both interior and exterior views showing representative spaces and details of significant architectural features and typical building materials. Exterior photographs shall include full oblique and contextual images of each elevation. Exterior views shall be keyed to a site plan while interior views shall be keyed to a floor plan of the building/structure. The photographs shall be indexed according to the date photographed, site number, site name, site address, direction, frame number, subject matter and photographer's name recorded on the reverse side in pencil.

The package shall include one full set of 4x5 or 5x7-inch photographs printed on fiber-based paper, the corresponding 4x5 or 5x7-inch negatives in acid free sleeves, the completed appropriate state inventory form, select existing drawings, where available, and a written site history of the historic property.

The CRM shall submit the package to the appropriate SHPO for review and approval. Once approved by the appropriate SHPO, the CRM and/or CRM staff shall submit copies of the approved documentation to a local historical society, archive, and/or local library for permanent retention.

D. Data Recovery: Prior to project implementation, the CRM and/or CRM Staff shall oversee the successful completion of data recovery undertaken by staff or contractors meeting the Professional Qualifications for Archaeology.

1. If data recovery for an archaeological site is the chosen mitigation method, a Data Recovery Plan will be developed in accordance with the ACHP's

Recommended Approach for Consultation on Recovery of Significant Information from Archaeological Sites (1999), and consultations under this PA.

- a. The plan will be submitted to the appropriate SHPO and the Tribes for a 30 day review and comment period. If no comments are received, Fort Bliss will assume there are no objections and proceed with the Plan; if comments are received, the CRM and/or CRM staff will continue consultation until that Plan is acceptable.
 - b. A copy of the finalized plan will be provided to the appropriate SHPO and the Tribes.
 - c. Upon request of any party, the plan may be submitted to the ACHP for review and comment, also with a 30 day review and comment period.
 - d. The final report of the execution of any plan will be submitted to the appropriate SHPO and the Tribes.
2. Fort Bliss may propose to use a previously accepted Programmatic Research Design (PRD) to implement the mitigation.
- a. The appropriate SHPO and the Tribes will continue to be given a 30 day review and comment period, the PRD may still be sent to the ACHP if requested, and the final report of the execution of the Plan will be submitted to the appropriate SHPO and the Tribes.

II. Public Interpretation

- A. Prior to project implementation, the CRM and/or CRM staff shall work with the appropriate SHPO to design an educational interpretive plan.
- B. The plan may include signs, displays, educational pamphlets, websites, workshops and other similar mechanisms to educate the public on historic properties within the local community, state, or region.
- C. Once an interpretive plan has been agreed to by the parties, the appropriate SHPO and the CRM and/or CRM staff shall continue to consult throughout implementation of the plan until all agreed upon actions have been completed by Fort Bliss.

III. Historical Context Statements and Narratives

- A. Prior to project implementation, the CRM and/or CRM staff shall work with the appropriate SHPO to determine the topic and framework of a historic context statement or narrative Fort Bliss shall be responsible for completing.
- B. The statement or narrative may focus on an individual historic property type, a set of related properties, or relevant themes as identified in the statewide preservation plan.

- C. Once the topic of the historic context statement or narrative has been agreed to, the CRM shall continue to coordinate with the SHPO through the drafting of the document and delivery of a final product.
- D. The appropriate SHPO shall have final approval over the end product.
- E. Fort Bliss shall use staff or contractors that meet the Secretary's Professional Qualifications for the appropriate discipline.

IV. Oral History Documentation

- A. Prior to project implementation, the CRM and/or CRM staff shall work with the appropriate SHPO to identify oral history documentation needs and agree upon a topic and list of interview candidates.
- B. Once the parameters of the oral history project have been agreed upon, the CRM and/or CRM staff shall continue to coordinate with the appropriate SHPO through the data collection, drafting of the document, and delivery of a final product.
- C. The SHPO shall have final approval over the end product.
- D. Fort Bliss shall use staff or contractors that meet the Secretary's Professional Qualifications for the appropriate discipline.

V. Historic Property Inventory

- A. Prior to project implementation, the CRM and/or CRM staff shall work with the SHPO to establish the appropriate level of effort to accomplish a historic property inventory.
- B. Efforts may be directed toward the resurvey of previously designated historic properties and/or districts which have undergone change or lack sufficient documentation, or the survey of new historic properties and/or districts that lack formal designation.
- C. Once the boundaries of the survey area have been agreed upon, the designated responsible party shall continue to coordinate with the appropriate SHPO through the data collection process.
- D. The designated responsible party shall use appropriate SHPO standards for the survey of historic properties and appropriate SHPO forms as appropriate.
- E. The CRM and/or CRM staff shall prepare a draft inventory report, according to appropriate SHPO templates and guidelines, and work with the appropriate SHPO until a final property inventory is approved.

- F. Fort Bliss shall use staff or contractors that meet the Secretary's Professional Qualifications for the appropriate discipline.

VI. Geo-References of Historic Maps and Aerial Photographs

- A. Prior to project implementation, the CRM and/or CRM staff shall work with the SHPO to identify the historic maps and/or aerial photographs for scanning and geo-referencing.
- B. Once a list of maps and/or aerial photographs have been agreed upon, the designated responsible party shall continue to coordinate with the appropriate SHPO through the scanning and geo-referencing process and shall submit drafts of paper maps and electronic files to the appropriate SHPO for review.
- C. The appropriate SHPO shall have final approval on the quality of the documentation provided by Fort Bliss.
- D. The final deliverable shall include a paper copy of each scanned image, a geo-referenced copy of each scanned image, and the metadata relating to both the original creation of the paper maps and the digitization process.

APPENDIX I: ARCHAEOLOGICAL REPORT LISTING

APPENDIX J: HISTORIC PROPERTIES: TABLES AND MAPS

Properties Covered by World War II Program Comment
Properties Covered by UPH Program Comment (1946-1974)
Properties Covered by Ammo Program Comment
Fort Bliss Main Post Historic District Historic Properties
Cold War Era Historic Properties
Properties located at William Beaumont Medical Center

World War II PROPERTIES COVERED BY PROGRAM COMMENT		
Building No.	Construction Date	Historic Building Function/Name
1288	1941	ENG/HOUSING MNT
2031	1941	LAUNDRY/DRY CLEAN
2033	1941	HEAT PLT BLDG
5095	1940	CONSOL OPEN DINING
5312	1941	CHAPEL
5358	1941	GEN INST BLDG
8102	1944	COMM. CENTER
8103	1944	VEH. MAINTENANCE
8251	1944	RANGE OPNS BLDG
8309	1944	STORAGE
11116	1943	ORG STORAGE
11275	1943	CHAPEL
11633	1941	TRAINING CENTER
• 11641	1992	INMATE SERVICE BLDG
11642	1943	CONFINEMENT
11643	1943	CONFINEMENT
11644	1940	CONFINEMENT
11645	1941	CONFINEMENT

PROPERTIES COVERED BY UPH PROGRAM COMMENT (1946-1974)			
TEXAS PROPERTIES			
Building No.	Construction Date	Historic Building Function/Name	CAT CODES
1002-1014	1956	Hammerhead Barracks	72XXX
2410-2414	1956	Hammerhead Barracks	72XXX
2416-2418	1956	Hammerhead Barracks	72XXX
2420-2421	1956	Hammerhead Barracks	72XXX
2442	1956	Hammerhead Barracks	72XXX
2444-2450	1956	Hammerhead Barracks	72XXX
2452	1956	Hammerhead Barracks	72XXX
2471-2480	1956	Hammerhead Barracks	72XXX
2901-2905	1956	Hammerhead Barracks	72XXX
5015-5020	1956	Apartment Type BOQ	72XXX
5023	1956	Apartment Type BOQ	72XXX
5039-5045	1956	Apartment Type BOQ	72XXX
11141-11142	1967	Semi-Permanent H-Shaped Barracks	72XXX
11144	1967	Semi-Permanent H-Shaped Barracks	72XXX
11147	1967	Semi-Permanent H-Shaped Barracks	72XXX
11149-11153	1967	Semi-Permanent H-Shaped Barracks	72XXX
11285	1967	Semi-Permanent H-Shaped Barracks	72XXX
NEW MEXICO PROPERTIES			
Dona Ana Base Camp			
8107-8149	1966	C-Hut	72XXX
8153	1966	Mobilization Dining Hall	72XXX
8155	1966	Mobilization Dining Hall	72XXX
8157	1966	Mobilization Dining Hall	72XXX
8159	1966	Mobilization Dining Hall	72XXX
8160	1966	Mobilization Dining Hall	72XXX
8162-8164	1966	Mobilization Dining Hall	72XXX
8203-8239	1966	C-Hut	72XXX
McGregor Base Camp			
9402-9432	1957	Semi-Permanent H-Shaped Barracks	72XXX
9441	1951	Semi-Permanent Dining Hall	72XXX
9504-9506	1959	Semi-Permanent U-Shaped Barracks	72XXX
9510	1957	Semi-Permanent Dining Hall	72XXX
9517-9518	1959	Semi-Permanent U-Shaped Barracks	72XXX
Orogrande Base Camp			
8609-8610	1961	Semi-Permanent 16-Man BOQ	72XXX
8614-8615	1959	Straight-sided Quonset Hut	72XXX
8620-8637	1959	Straight-sided Quonset Hut	72XXX
8644-8656	1959	Straight-sided Quonset Hut	72XXX
8680-8682	1961	Semi-Permanent H-Shaped Barracks	72XXX
8879	1958	Quonset Hut Dining Hall	72XXX

PROPERTIES COVERED BY AMMO PROGRAM COMMENT			
NEW MEXICO PROPERTIES			
Building No.	Construction Date	Historic Building Function/Name	CAT CODES
8347	1972	GM MAG INST	42XXX
8697	1944	GM MAG INST	42XXX
9542	1959	FUSE/DET MAG IN	42XXX
9543	1959	LIQ PROP STR	42XXX
9544	1959	FUSE/DET MAG IN	42XXX
9545	1959	LIQ PROP STR	42XXX
9550	1959	GM MAG INST	42XXX
9557	1959	GM MAG INST	42XXX
9566	1957	PAD	42XXX
9567	1957	FUSE/DET MAG	42XXX
9910-9913	1961	IGLOO STORAGE INST	42XXX
9915-9917	1961	IGLOO STORAGE	42XXX
9935	1969	IGLOO STORAGE	42XXX
TEXAS PROPERTIES			
Building No.	Construction Date	Historic Building Function/Name	CAT CODES
3664	1957	MAG GP BLDG	42XXX
11500	1952	IGLOO STR INST	42XXX
11505	1956	IGLOO STR INST	42XXX
11507	1956	IGLOO STR INST	42XXX
11509	1952	IGLOO STR INST	42XXX
11511-11514	1956	IGLOO STR INST	42XXX
11530	1949	AMMO HUT	42XXX
11540	1943	IGLOO STR INST	42XXX
11550	1943	IGLOO	42XXX

FORT BLISS MAIN POST HISTORIC DISTRICT BUILDINGS - CONTINUE			
Building	Year	Historic Function	Context
221	1893	Captain's Quarters	Initial Construction Period
222	1893	Lieutenant's Quarters	Initial Construction Period
223	1893	Lieutenant's Quarters	Initial Construction Period
224	1893	Captain's Quarters	Initial Construction Period
225	1914	Captain's Quarters	First Expansion Period
226	1914	Captain's Quarters	First Expansion Period
227	1893	Lieutenant's Quarters	Initial Construction Period
228	1910	Commanding Officer's Quarters	Interim Period Group
229	1893	Lieutenant's Quarters	Initial Construction Period
230	1893	Captain's Quarters	Initial Construction Period
231	1893	Lieutenant's Quarters	Initial Construction Period
232	1893	Lieutenant's Quarters	Initial Construction Period
233	1893	Captain's Quarters	Initial Construction Period
234	1893	Lieutenant's Quarters	Initial Construction Period
235	1893	Captain's Quarters	Initial Construction Period
236	1914	Captain's Quarters	First Expansion Period
237	1914	Captain's Quarters	First Expansion Period
238	1914	Captain's Quarters	First Expansion Period
239	1914	Captain's Quarters	First Expansion Period
240	1914	Captain's Quarters	First Expansion Period
241	1893	Guardhouse	Initial Construction Period
242	1917	Post Electrical Substation	First Expansion Period
243	1939	Bachelors Officer's Quarters	Depression Era
244	1936	Officer's Garage	Depression Era
246	1936	Garage	Depression Era
247	1936	Garage	Depression Era
248	1937	Post Officers's Club Servant's Quarters	Depression Era
250	1919	Officer's Open Mess	Second Expansion Period
251	1934	Girl Scout House	Depression Era
265	1936	Garage	Depression Era
266	1936	Garage	Depression Era
267	1936	Garage	Depression Era
268	1936	Garage	Depression Era
269	1936	Garage	Depression Era
270	1936	Garage	Depression Era
271	1936	Garage	Depression Era
272	1936	Garage	Depression Era
273	1921	Recruiting Office	Second Expansion Period
275	1912	Arms Storage Magazine	Interim Period Group
300	1944	Pershing Gate Stone Monuments	World War II
301	1934	Officer's Quarters	Depression Era
302	1934	Commanding Officer's Quarters	Depression Era
303	1934	Officer's Quarters	Depression Era
304	1934	Officer's Quarters	Depression Era
305	1934	Servant's Quarters	Depression Era
306	1934	Officer's Garage	Depression Era
311	1938	War Department Theater	Depression Era
315	1924	7 th Cavalry Service Club	Second Expansion Period

FORT BLISS MAIN POST HISTORIC DISTRICT BUILDINGS - CONTINUE			
Building	Year	Historic Function	Context
317	1930	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
318	1930	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
319	1930	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
320	1930	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
321	1930	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
322	1930	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
323	1930	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
324	1930	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
325	1930	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
326	1930	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
327	1930	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
328	1930	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
329	1930	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
330	1930	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
331	1930	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
332	1930	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
333	1930	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
334	1930	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
335	1930	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
336	1930	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
337	1930	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
338	1930	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
339	1930	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
340	1930	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
341	1930	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
342	1930	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
343	1930	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
344	1939	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
345	1939	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
346	1939	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
347	1939	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
348	1939	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
349	1934	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
350	1934	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
351	1934	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
353	1934	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
354	1934	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
355	1934	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
356	1934	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
357	1934	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
400	1934	Officer's Quarters	Depression Era
401	1934	Officer's Quarters	Depression Era
402	1934	Officer's Quarters	Depression Era
403	1934	Officer's Quarters	Depression Era
404	1934	Officer's Quarters	Depression Era
405	1934	Officer's Quarters	Depression Era
406	1934	Officer's Quarters	Depression Era
407	1934	Officer's Quarters	Depression Era
408	1934	Officer's Quarters	Depression Era
409	1934	Officer's Quarters	Depression Era
410	1934	Officer's Quarters	Depression Era
411	1934	Officer's Quarters	Depression Era

FORT BLISS MAIN POST HISTORIC DISTRICT BUILDINGS - CONTINUE			
Building	Year	Historic Function	Context
412	1934	Officer's Quarters	Depression Era
413	1934	Officer's Quarters	Depression Era
414	1934	Officer's Garage	Depression Era
415	1934	Officer's Garage	Depression Era
425	1934	Officer's Garage	Depression Era
426	1934	Officer's Quarters	Depression Era
427	1934	Officer's Quarters	Depression Era
428	1934	Officer's Quarters	Depression Era
429	1934	Officer's Quarters	Depression Era
440	1919	Mess Hall	7 th Cavalry Construction Period
442	1919	Mess Hall	7 th Cavalry Construction Period
443	1919	Mess Hall	7 th Cavalry Construction Period
444	1919	Mess Hall	7 th Cavalry Construction Period
448	1919	Enlisted Men's Barracks	7 th Cavalry Construction Period
449	1919	Enlisted Men's Barracks	7 th Cavalry Construction Period
450	1919	Enlisted Men's Barracks	7 th Cavalry Construction Period
451	1919	Enlisted Men's Barracks	7 th Cavalry Construction Period
452	1919	Enlisted Men's Barracks	7 th Cavalry Construction Period
500	1934	Enlisted Men's Barracks	Depression Era
501	1934	Noel Field	Depression Era
503	1934	Enlisted Men's Barracks	Depression Era
504	1934	Enlisted Men's Barracks	Depression Era
512	1934	Enlisted Men's Barracks	Depression Era
515	1934	Enlisted Men's Barracks	Depression Era
516	1934	Enlisted Men's Barracks	Depression Era
522	1934	Officer's Quarters	Depression Era
523	1934	Officer's Quarters	Depression Era
524	1934	Officer's Garage	Depression Era
525	1934	Officer's Quarters	Depression Era
526	1934	Officer's Quarters	Depression Era
527	1934	Officer's Quarters	Depression Era
528	1934	Officer's Quarters	Depression Era
529	1934	Officer's Quarters	Depression Era
530	1934	Officer's Quarters	Depression Era
531	1934	Officer's Quarters	Depression Era
532	1934	Officer's Garage	Depression Ear
533	1934	Officer's Garage	Depression Ear
534	1934	Officer's Garage	Depression Ear
535	1934	Officer's Garage	Depression Ear
536	1934	Officer's Quarters	Depression Era
537	1934	Officer's Quarters	Depression Era
538	1934	Officer's Quarters	Depression Era
539	1934	Officer's Quarters	Depression Era
540	1934	Officer's Quarters	Depression Era
541	1934	Officer's Quarters	Depression Era
542	1934	Officer's Quarters	Depression Era
543	1934	Officer's Quarters	Depression Era
544	1934	Officer's Quarters	Depression Era
545	1948	Officer's Quarters	Post World War II (1946-1950)
546	1948	Officer's Quarters	Post World War II (1946-1950)
547	1948	Officer's Quarters	Post World War II (1946-1950)

FORT BLISS MAIN POST HISTORIC DISTRICT BUILDINGS - CONTINUE			
Building	Year	Historic Function	Context
548	1948	Officer's Quarters	Post World War II (1946-1950)
549	1948	Officer's Quarters	Post World War II (1946-1950)
550	1948	Officer's Quarters	Post World War II (1946-1950)
551	1948	Officer's Quarters	Post World War II (1946-1950)
552	1948	Officer's Quarters	Post World War II (1946-1950)
553	1948	Officer's Quarters	Post World War II (1946-1950)
554	1948	Officer's Quarters	Post World War II (1946-1950)
565	1948	Officer's Quarters	Post World War II (1946-1950)
611	1934	Blacksmith and Saddle Shop	Depression Era
612	1934	Blacksmith and Saddle Shop	Depression Era
613	1934	Blacksmith and Saddle Shop	Depression Era
614	1934	Cavalry Stables	Depression Era
616	1934	Cavalry Stables	Depression Era
618	1934	Cavalry Stables	Depression Era
620	1934	Cavalry Stables	Depression Era
622	1939	Cavalry Stables	Depression Era
624	1939	Cavalry Stables	Depression Era
627	1934	Stable Guard Quarters	Depression Era
628	1934	Stable Guard Quarters	Depression Era
629	1934	Stable Guard Quarters	Depression Era
631	1939	Stable Guard Quarters	Depression Era
632	1939	Stable Guard Quarters	Depression Era
633	1939	Stable Guard Quarters	Depression Era
635	1939	Cavalry Stables	Depression Era
639	1939	Cavalry Stables	Depression Era
641	1939	Cavalry Stables	Depression Era
643	1939	Cavalry Stables	Depression Era
645	1939	Cavalry Stables	Depression Era
649	1939	Blacksmith and Saddle Shop	Depression Era
650	1939	Blacksmith and Saddle Shop	Depression Era
651	1939	Blacksmith and Saddle Shop	Depression Era
730	1936	Garage	Depression Era
762	1939	Organization Garage	Depression Era
769	1939	Organization Garage	Depression Era
801	1939	Organization Garage	Depression Era
888	1916	Ammunition Warehouse	First Expansion Period
889	1916	Ammunition Warehouse	First Expansion Period
890	1916	Ammunition Warehouse	First Expansion Period
1101	1921	Ordnance Office and Warehouse	Second Expansion Period
1102	1921	Warehouse	Second Expansion Period
1103	1921	Warehouse	Second Expansion Period
1104	1921	Warehouse	Second Expansion Period
1105	1921	Warehouse	Second Expansion Period
1106	1921	Warehouse	Second Expansion Period
1107	1921	Warehouse	Second Expansion Period

FORT BLISS MAIN POST HISTORIC DISTRICT BUILDINGS - CONTINUE			
Building	Year	Historic Function	Context
1108	1921	Warehouse	Second Expansion Period
1109	1921	Warehouse	Second Expansion Period
1110	1921	Warehouse	Second Expansion Period
1111	1921	Warehouse	Second Expansion Period
1112	1921	Warehouse	Second Expansion Period
1113	1921	Warehouse	Second Expansion Period
1114	1921	Warehouse	Second Expansion Period
1115	1921	Warehouse	Second Expansion Period
1116	1921	Warehouse	Second Expansion Period
1117	1921	Warehouse	Second Expansion Period
1118	1921	Warehouse	Second Expansion Period
1119	1921	Warehouse	Second Expansion Period
1120	1921	Warehouse	Second Expansion Period
1121	1921	Warehouse	Second Expansion Period
1122	1921	Warehouse	Second Expansion Period
1123	1921	Warehouse	Second Expansion Period
1124	1921	Warehouse	Second Expansion Period
1125	1921	Latrine	Second Expansion Period
1126	1921	Latrine	Second Expansion Period
1127	1921	Latrine	Second Expansion Period
1128	1921	Latrine	Second Expansion Period
1318	1917	Post Pumping Plant	First Expansion Period
1334	1921	Motor Vehicle Repair Garage	Second Expansion Period
1336	1921	Riding Hall	Second Expansion Period
1361	1919	Quartermaster Granary	Second Expansion Period
1372	1918-1941	Scalehouse and Scaleways	Second Expansion Period
1400	1933	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
1401	1933	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
1402	1933	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
1403	1933	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
1404	1933	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
1405	1933	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
1406	1933	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
1407	1934	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
1408	1934	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
1409	1934	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
1410	1939	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
1411	1939	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
1412	1939	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
1413	1939	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
1441	1915	Post Bakery	First Expansion Period
1442	1930	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
1443	1930	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
1444	1930	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
1445	1930	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
1446	1930	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
1447	1930	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
1448	1930	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
1449	1930	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
1450	1930	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
1451	1930	NCO Quarters	Depression Era

FORT BLISS MAIN POST HISTORIC DISTRICT BUILDINGS - CONTINUE			
Building	Year	Historic Function	Context
1452	1930	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
1453	1930	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
1454	1930	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
1456	1920	Tailor Shop	Second Expansion Period
1457	1930	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
1458	1930	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
1459	1930	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
1460	1930	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
1461	1930	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
1462	1930	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
1463	1930	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
1464	1930	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
1465	1930	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
1466	1930	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
1467	1930	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
1468	1930	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
1469	1930	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
1470	1930	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
1471	1930	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
1472	1930	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
1473	1930	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
1474	1930	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
1475	1930	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
1476	1939	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
1477	1939	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
1478	1939	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
1479	1939	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
1480	1923	Medical Dispensary	Second Expansion Period
1481	1930	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
1482	1930	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
1483	1930	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
1484	1930	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
1485	1930	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
1486	1930	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
1487	1930	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
1488	1930	NCO Quarters	Depression Era
1655	1952	VEH Maintenance	Cold War BASOPS
1656	1952	Lab/Tst Building	Cold War BASOPS
1660	1955	Admin Gen Purpose	Cold War BASOPS
2004	1926	Clothing Store	Second Expansion Period
2009	1895	Wagon and Wheelwright Shop	Initial Construction Period
2010	1908	Horseshoeing Shop	Interim Period Group
2011	1893	Quartermaster Stables	Initial Construction Period
2014	1917	Veterinary	First Expansion Period
2019	1895	Forge Shed	Initial Construction Period
2020	1917	Administration Building	First Expansion Period
2021	1893	Quartermaster Storehouse	Initial Construction Period
2022	1897	Storehouse	Initial Construction Period
2032	1920	Loading Dock	Second Expansion Period
5051	1948	Museum Building	Post World War II (1946-1950)
5052	1948	Museum Building	Post World War II (1946-1950)

FORT BLISS MAIN POST HISTORIC DISTRICT BUILDINGS - CONTINUE			
Building	Year	Historic Function	Context
5053	1948	Museum Building	Post World War II (1946-1950)
5053A	1948	Museum Building	Post World War II (1946-1950)
5054	1948	Museum Building	Post World War II (1946-1950)

COLD WAR ERA PROPERTIES		
Building No.	Construction Date	Historic Building Function/Name
2	1954	Hinman Hall
59	1953	Access Control Facility
60	1953	Ben Hq/Org Classrooms
720	1953	Gen Rep Inst
721	1953	Org Storage
722	1954	Veh Maint Inst
723	1954	Gen Inst Bldg
724	1954	Tng Aids Center
725	1954	Gen Rep Inst
738	1960	Gen Rep Inst
739	1960	Veh Maint Inst
740	1960	Veh Maint Inst
741	1960	Veh Maint Inst
743	1960	Veh Maint Inst
744	1960	Access Cnt Fac
745	1960	Veh Maint Inst
746	1960	Gen Rep Inst
747	1960	Gen Rep Inst
751	1960	Access Cnt Fac
754	1958	Gen Rep Inst
756	1960	Veh Maint Inst
762	1939	Organization Garage
769	1939	Organization Garage
772	1958	Storage
1080	1959	Gen Rep Inst
1081	1959	Gen Rep Inst
1082	1959	Gen Rep Inst
1084	1959	Veh Maint Shp
1085	1959	Veh Maint Shp
1089	1959	Veh Maint Shp
1090	1959	Veh Maint Shp
1091	1960	Access Cnt Fac
1092	1959	Veh Maint Inst
1093	1959	Comp Rep Inst
1094	1959	Gen Rep Inst
1095	1959	Access Cnt Fac
1655	1952	Veh Maintenance
1656	1952	Lab/TST Bldg
1658	1963	Admin Gen Purpose
1660	1955	Admin Gen Purpose
2445	1953	CO HQ/Enl UPH
2446	1953	BDE HQ Bldg
3672	1960	WPN QA/CAL Dep
3674	1960	Storage
3701	1960	Org Storage
3702	1961	Org Storage
3703	1961	Org Storage
3704	1961	Org Storage
3705	1961	Org Storage
3706	1961	Org Storage
3707	1961	Org Storage
5867	1968	Nav Bldg Air
8771	1966	HIPAR Building/Classroom

COLD WAR ERA PROPERTIES CONTINUE		
Building No.	Construction Date	Historic Building Function/Name
8772	1966	Flag Pole
8773	1966	Target Drone Storage
8774	1966	Alignment Building
8777	1966	JATO Storage
8778	1966	Launch Control
9402	1959	Org Classroom
9480	1961	Nav Bldg Air
9505	1959	Administration
11108	1955	Hangar

WILLIAM BEAUMONT ELIGIBLE PROPERTIES		
Building No.	Construction Date	Historic Building Function/Name
7010	1937	Garage Family Housing
7011	1930	Garage Family Housing
7014	1921	Family Housing LTC/Maj
7015	1912	Family Housing LTC/Maj
7016	1921	Family Housing LTC/Maj
7017	1921	Family Housing LTC/Maj
7018	1921	Family Housing LTC/Maj
7019	1922	Family Housing LTC/Maj
7020	1923	Family Housing LTC/Maj
7022	1923	Family Housing LTC/Maj
7023	1923	Family Housing LTC/Maj
7024	1923	Family Housing LTC/Maj
7115	1942	Nursing School (Historicall Psych Ward)
7167	1921	Laboratory/Blood Bank (mural)